

From Fringes to Centre: A Case Study of *The Taming of Women, The Roof Beneath their Feet, Felanee, Fence and Hangwoman*

**A
Thesis**

Submitted to Himachal Pradesh University Shimla

For the Award of Degree

of

Doctor of Philosophy

in

English

Supervised by:

Dr. Ashwani Rana

Submitted by:

Munish Kumar Thakur

**Department of English
Himachal Pradesh University
(NAAC Accredited 'A' Grade University)
Summer Hill Shimla-171005
2023**

Himachal Pradesh University Shimla
(NAAC Accredited 'A' Grade University)
Department of English
Summer Hill Shimla – 171005

Dr. Ashwani Rana
Associate Professor

Certificate

It is hereby certified that the thesis entitled “**From Fringes to Centre: A Case Study of *The Taming of Women, The Roof Beneath their Feet, Felanee, Fence and Hangwoman***” is an original work of **Mr. Munish Kumar Thakur**, completed under my supervision and guidance in the Department of English, Himachal Pradesh University, Summer Hill Shimla. This work in my opinion is fit to be considered for the award of the degree of **Doctor of Philosophy** in English. It has not been submitted in part or full for any diploma or degree of any university.

(Dr. Ashwani Rana)

The Report is Generated by DrillBit Plagiarism Detection Software

Submission Information

Author Name	Munish
Title	From Fringes to Centre: A Case Study of The Taming of Women, The Roof Beneath their Feet,...
Paper/Submission ID	1195418
Submitted by	himanshu@hpuniv.ac.in
Submission Date	2023-12-11 12:40:03
Total Pages	234
Document type	Thesis

Result Information

Similarity **6 %**

Exclude Information

Quotes	Excluded
References/Bibliography	Not Excluded
Sources: Less than 14 Words %	Not Excluded
Excluded Source	0 %
Excluded Phrases	Not Excluded

Database Selection

Language	English
Student Papers	Yes
Journals & publishers	Yes
Internet or Web	Yes
Institution Repository	Yes

A Unique QR Code use to View/Download/Share Pdf File

Declaration

I hereby declare that the research work entitled “**From Fringes to Centre: A Case Study of *The Taming of Women, The Roof Beneath their Feet, Felanee, Fence and Hangwoman***” embodies my original work and has not been submitted in part or in full for any other degree or diploma. All sources of information used in the writing of this work have been duly acknowledged. This work represents my own ideas and findings and has been completed under the guidance of my supervisor.

(Munish Kumar Thakur)

[Research Scholar]

Acknowledgements

I would like to take this opportunity to express my deepest gratitude and appreciation to all those who have supported me throughout my journey in completing this PhD thesis.

*First and foremost, I am immensely grateful to my supervisor, **Dr. Ashwani Rana**, Associate Professor, Department of English, ICDEOL, Himachal Pradesh University, for providing me with constant guidance and motivation throughout the research process. Your invaluable insights, constructive feedback, and unwavering support have been instrumental in shaping this thesis.*

I would also like to extend my sincere thanks to Dr. Himanshu Parmar, The Chairperson, Department of English, Himachal Pradesh University, for his support and encouragement. I would also like to thank Ms. Savitri, Senior Assistant, Department of English for all her kind help. Their expertise and resources have been indispensable in my research journey.

My heartfelt appreciation also goes out to my parents (Mr. Vijay and Mrs. Indra Thakur), my brother, Dr. Rishi Thakur and especially my wife, Veena who have been a constant source of love, encouragement, and motivation. Thank you for always believing in me and for being my pillars of strength.

Above all, I thank the Almighty for bestowing me with the strength and determination to accomplish my research work. Moreover, my profound thanks to Goddess Lakshmi for blessing me with my cute loving daughters Jiyanshi and Arika Thakur.

Once again, thank you to everyone who has played a part in making this thesis a reality.

(Munish Kumar Thakur)

Abbreviations Used

1. *RBTF* *The Roof Beneath their Feet*
2. *SOF* *The Story of Felanee*
3. *TOW* *The Taming of Women*

➤ MLA 9th Edition has been followed for purpose of the in-text citations and bibliography.

Contents

Chapters	Title	Page No.
I	Introduction	1-72
II	Role of Gender Inequalities in Select Narratives	73-138
III	Role of Caste and Religion in Women's Subjugation	139-190
IV	Representation of Women's Identity in Select Narratives	191-250
V	Conclusion	251-264
	Bibliography	265-309
	Publications	

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Literature has experienced the characters of women developing through the ages. The portrayal of women was, without doubt, prejudiced as the society was ruled by Men and most of the published writers were men until modern times. Therefore, the journey of women being neglected and dominated has been occurring historically throughout in Literature.

(Singh, Portrayal of Women in Literature – Through the Ages 40)

Indian women writers have realistically portrayed women's issues, both physically and emotionally, in their works. Their narratives are compelling and thought-provoking, giving voice to marginalized women. They have also shattered the false representation of women in the past and have conducted extensive research on the characters, projecting various perspectives on women, their experiences, and their role in society. Literature is a written expression of a society which depicts the realities of one's life as affected by socio-political, economic and cultural circumstances. It is a medium that shapes a culture's perspective and as a consequence, literature forces one to think carefully about society's problems, and occasionally it also offers a remedy. All writers—poets, playwrights, novelists, and essayists—reflect culture in their writings. Creative writers transform real incidents and happenings of daily life into literary works. Through literature, a writer targets oddities in society, attempts to raise certain issues and hints at some resolution/s. Today's youth is profoundly influenced by literature, and it will aid them in understanding the mistakes made by past generations as well as how to make amends for them. Literature has also changed political institutions and shaped cultures (Keerthika 471-72).

Literature articulates many social problems and deformities prevalent in societies. Discrimination against women is one such social issue that has been repeatedly depicted by many writers to eradicate injustice against women. The present study investigates the position and status of women in Indian rural societies as depicted by the select regional women writers from different locales of India. It is therefore befitting to locate these works and authors in the larger backdrop of regional writing in India, Indian writing in English, and Indian writing in translation.

Indian English literature has become a phenomenon which cannot be overlooked and in the last few years, it has attracted great attention both in India and abroad. By juxtaposing early Indian works with newer entries in Indian literature, one might get a sense of the full possibility of this form of writing in India. Furthermore, in today's literary landscape, Indian writing in English has equal standing with works of literature from other nations. Women writers from India also have made their voices heard around the world by articulating themselves creatively. Therefore, in recent years, Indian women authors have been able to achieve worldwide recognition. Indian women writers have expressed the position and standing of women, illuminating literature with episodes from their lived experiences. India is a vibrant place, with its various languages, faiths, ethnicities, and traditions, so Indian writers can conceptualize a wide range of issues. The voices of Indian women authors have successfully negotiated social, historical, philosophical, and cultural aspects, centred on humanism.

In comparison to male writers, Indian women have now made substantial contributions to world literature. However, India's influence in literary circles is generally recounted through its writing in English, especially by male writers. Many modern Indian English writers have hailed Indian English writing as a distinctive force

in global literature, expressing their artistic desires in no other tongue but English. It incorporates not only India's past but also the present world's complicated challenges and freshly encountered realities. The new Indian English novel is confident in its ability to respond to contemporary subjects and methods, as well as new ways to cope with such issues.

The essence of the times must be more pervasively and efficiently portrayed in fiction than in other art forms like poetry and drama. As a result, it is no surprise that Indian women's writing in English has made the most important contribution of the period in fiction. Modern Indian women authors including Anita Desai, Nayantara Sehgal, Arundhati Roy, Gita Mehta, Shashi Deshpande, Bharathi Mukherjee, as well as Jhumpa Lahiri led to a literary rebirth as that of the 3rd generation of Indian writers through their works published throughout the 1980s and 1990s. These are the major women writers of the third generation, and they are pivotal figures in the modern literary landscape. They have left an indelible mark on the international literary landscape due to their ability to manage expression. They have received national and international acclaim, as well as handsome earnings and prestigious prizes.

The present study primarily focuses on examining discrimination and the status of Indian rural women living in different regions of India as depicted by various regional women authors. The selected works for a detailed analysis are *The Taming of Women* translated in 2011 by Pritham K. Chakravarthy originally written as *Anandhayi* (1992) by P. Sivakami who is a Tamil writer; *The Roof Beneath their Feet* translated in 2013 by Rahul Soni originally written as *Tirohit* (2001) by Geetanjali (Pandey) Shree who writes in Hindi hails from Mainpuri, Uttar Pradesh; *The Story of Felanee* translated in 2011 by Deepika Phukan originally written as *Felanee* (2003) by Arupa

Pathangia Kalita, is an Assamese writer; *Fence* translated in 2015 by Rita Kothari originally written as *Vaad* (2011) by Ila Arab Mehta who is a Gujarati writer and *Hangwoman* translated in 2016 by J. Devika originally written as *Aarachaar* (2012) is written by K. R. Meera who writes in Malayalam.

In order to locate these works in the literary history of Indian Literature and its development, it is only appropriate to trace a brief history of the representation of women in Indian writing in English first and later, in the context of Indian regional writings and their translation in English.

The backdrop of the Study

a. Indian Literature in English

At first glance, Indian literature in English may be traced back in time. The first link to consider is the adoption of English as a means of teaching in India and the subsequent adoption of English literature as a part of the core curriculum in various institutions. Two prerequisites had to be fulfilled before Indians could compose poetry in English. First, the English language needed to be adequately Indianized to convey the realities of the Indian context. Furthermore, Indians needed to be adequately anglicised to communicate in English. James Augustus Hicky produced the first newspaper in India, *Hicky's Bengal Gazette*, in English in 1780. In the year 1817, the Hindu College, which subsequently turned out to be Presidency College, was established as Bengal's foremost academic institution (De 30).

The adoption of English as the language of teaching was mandated by Macaulay's approach to Indian Education, which claimed that the English language would be the most beneficial for our native topics. At the same time as delivering his

legendary speech, Macaulay acknowledged openly that he had not studied some of the Sanskrit or Arabic works but continued to proclaim: “I have never found one among them who could deny that a single shelf of a good European library was worth the whole native literature of India and Arabia” (qtd. in Makdisi 61). Therefore, he is of the view that the entire historical data gathered in the Sanskrit language is less than what can be discovered in the pitiful carefulness employed in English preparatory schools.

As a result, India served as a sort of test platform for introducing English literature into the classroom at a period when English institutions were still immersed in Latin and Greek classics. Consequently, English was brought into academic institutions, courts, and even workplaces, displacing Arabic and Sanskrit as a method of interaction and recording. In the year 1835, Lord William Bentinck said that the administration would prefer “those who follow the courses of Education in European Science and in the English Language” (Hilliker 44). Jyoti Yadav points out that the creation of institutions in Bombay, Madras, and Calcutta was announced in the year 1854 by the Wood Dispatch, which made the English language available to students, professors, and government officials (82).

To begin with, the adoption of English at some of these levels has some intriguing consequences. The first child of the unhappy union between the British English language and the hesitant Babu was what is sarcastically referred to as ‘Babu English.’ The creativity they employed in the offices, as well as their difficulty with the terminology, became a source of ridicule (Bashir 31). English started to establish itself in literary theory as well. In 1864, Bankim Chandra Chatterjee published *Rajmohan's Wife* (1864), the first Indian book in English. Vinay Dharwadker expresses that in the last three or four decades of the nineteenth century, Indian writers imitated romanticism

and British romantic poets such as Wordsworth, Shelley, Keats, Byron, and Scott were the main sources of motivation. During the early decades of the twentieth century, Indian poets attempted to integrate the romanticism of early nineteenth-century British poets as well as the late romantics of the indulgent time frame to express the awareness of the Indian revival between patriotism and political shifts, which eventually led to the achieving of political rights in the mid of twentieth century (219).

The time of literary revival in India was the very first stage of Indian poetry. Derozio's poetry, Kasiprasad Ghose's "The Shair or Minstrel and Other Poems", Michael Madhusudan Dutt's "The Captive Lady," and Manmohan Ghose's "Love Songs and Elegies," all bear witness to the artistic explosion sparked by the romantic passion reawakened by the literary renaissance. Toru Dutt, the only romantic poet of the very first stage, emphasises India as well as her history by setting a significant number of Indian tales to poetry (Dharwadker 221). Sarojini Naidu, Tagore, Aurobindo Ghose, and Harindranath Chattopadhyaya were the poets, who were still romantic in mood and wrote a great deal of poetry.

Romesh Chandra Dutt was a well-known writer at the time. Before retirement as the Diwan of the Royal Baroda State, he held significant government positions. In Bengali, he penned six novels, two of which he translated into English: *The Lake of Palms* and *The Slave Girl of Agra* (Rathod 26). Rabindranath Tagore's name, on the other hand, stands out among this group. It would be impolite to refer to him as an English writer since he penned in Bengali with similar felicity as well as elegance. Rakesh Rathod opines *Gitanjali* elevated Tagore to the status of a global literary giant, winning him the Nobel Prize in Literature in the year 1913 and more significantly, served as a major spiritual bridge between East and West. It was written in 1913 and cemented Tagore's literary greatness (26).

The years that followed witnessed a slew of triumph stories in the area of Indian writing in English. The English critic, William Walsh, chose three of the most well-known authors on the literary arena. Mulk Raj Anand, R. K. Narayan, and Raja Rao have been dubbed the Trinity of Indian English Writing. Nevertheless, since they were among the first to use the English language to describe an Indian perspective, their efforts were fraught with difficulty. The novel's continuous structure further contributed to the difficulty of portraying Indian life in English. Furthermore, since the novel is fundamentally a Western form, it imposes certain constraints and, as a result, modifies the Indian perspective (Carver 499–500).

Mulk Raj Anand's first novel, *The Untouchable*, started his career as a writer. *The Untouchable* provided a remedy to Indian casteism that was in line with Gandhi's concept of dignity for the lower castes. *The Village* (1939), *Across the Black Waters* (1940), and *The Sword and the Sickle* (1942) are three of his other books with a reformist bent (Rathod 27). Unlike the flamboyant Anand, who was influenced by Western culture, R. K. Narayan, whose debut novel was *Swami and Friends*, was modest and humble (1935). He made up the fictional area of Malgudi, a tiny South Indian village that he described as 'a mix of oriental and pre-1914.' Except for *Waiting for Mahatma*, which depicts the 1942 Quit India Movement, he does not address contemporary political issues in his works. In *The Dark Room* (1938), Savitri is married to the cruel spouse Ramani. One of his most well-known masterpieces written in 1958 was *The Guide* (Narayan 6-7).

Literature written in Indian English is no longer ignorable and over the last few decades, it has garnered considerable attention in India and beyond. What began as a small plant has now developed into a beautiful subdivision with many branches. The

full potential of this sort of writing in India might be gauged by comparing the first books written by Indians to those written more recently. Furthermore, in the contemporary literary landscape, Indian writing in English has an equal rank with other national literature. Particularly, Indian women writers have made their voices known over the globe in an overly creative manner. In addition, Indian women authors have excelled in all fields of English literature in recent years and garnered worldwide acclaim.

Through their English works, Indian women writers expressed the role and status of the woman, illuminating literature with its importance and vibrancy. They have elaborately portrayed the culture and history, and “there are many Indian women writers both novelists and poets, based in the USA and Britain. Some like Jhabvala and Anita Desai are late immigrants while others, like Jhumpa Lahiri, belong to the second generation of Indians abroad” (Margaret 32). Even though the texts deal with regionalism extensively, universal themes transcend the natural bounds. India is a place of variety due to its diverse languages, religions, ethnicities, and civilizations. This diversity affords writers the chance to explore a variety of issues. In addition to discussing historical, social, as well as philosophical topics, Indian women writers centre their ideas on humanity. They focus on social, diasporic, feminine, scientific, and technological subjects, among others (Margaret 32).

b. Portrayal of Women in Indian Male-Dominated Literature

Roles of women in literature have evolved throughout the period, but until recently, most recognised authors are males, and the depiction of women in writing was unquestionably skewed. Much of it may be attributed to the reality that education was severely restricted in classical civilizations, and the bulk of those who could write were

men. The contributions of women to oral folklore, including traditional songs, tales, literature, and poetry in general, cannot be overstated.

Here's a glance at how women have been depicted in literature for ages in the male-dominated culture in India. The great Indian epics like *Mahabharata* and *Ramayana* depict, “various noble women, there seemed to be a trace of dichotomy inherent in Indian thought. This dualism portrayed woman either as a sensual, secular creature like Surpanaka or as a devoted wife and mother like Sita” (Kishore 3). As Sima Singh points out:

Some depicted women as symbols of strength and unity and some used them as an object of pleasure. The characters were curated and modified to suit the prerequisites of a patriarchal society. Example of these is the epic *Ramayana* and *Mahabharata*—women characters and the contrasting characteristics of Sita being submissive, sacrificing yet unacceptable in the society who had to go through all the agonies for no fault of hers, whereas Draupadi has been known for her sharp eloquence and interpretations and has been represented as the central power and the reason or the cause of the *Mahabharata*. (39)

When it comes to the depiction of women in Indian poetry, Mahadevi Verma, a liberation warrior, educator, as well as campaigner, has become the figurehead of Hindi poetry on women's problems. She also argued for women's liberation plus feminine sexuality, which she believed occurred outside of the wedding. The traditional literature of Hindus, which discussed freeing imagery, provided motivation for the renowned poetess's themes.

Jai Shankar Prasad, who was known for his powerful depiction of women, turned out to be renowned for praising women. Amrita Pritam, a poetess, was one of

the most prominent figures in the local poetry of India in the twentieth century. Kamala Das made the path for a soul attire of admirable womanly poems, in which a recurring factor was the investigation of the male-women connection, with her Punjabi passages, which spoke about the after-effects of the separation of India and Pakistan in the province of Punjab as well as the victimized women, achieving cult status among poetry admirers. Several women poets, like Gauri Deshpande and Chitra Narendran, have also adopted this approach.

Mridula Garg in her best-selling novel *Chittacobra* asserts if we reach the peak of civilization, all our faults will be performed in combination with a collective accord to the tune of popular approbation, and she feels this is still true of women's representation in literature today. More crucial than establishing oneself on the correct side of the feminist discussion is a compassionate portrayal of both men and women who choose to disagree with the mainstream opinion. On the surface, there is a franker portrayal of women's sexuality as well as overall freedom. Women's sexuality, on the other hand, has been limited to body autonomy, which includes the vocal but insignificant portrayal of bodily processes like periods, sexual urges, and sexual abuse. The true freedom that comes from making choices without regard to religious, societal, patriarchal, or feminist canons is absent (Rajan 205-06).

There was no shame felt by women who did not adhere to ethical constraints in the writings of Mirabai, and subsequently Amrita Pritam and Krishna Sobti, where even men were regarded with the same compassion as women. There is a lot more conflict today, as well as open and outspoken affirmation of feminists. However, there are certain advantages to this. Chetan Bhagat and Anita Nair, two contemporary Indian fantasy fiction authors, have recently included modern women characters in their

works. Chetan portrays his women protagonists as agents of societal transformation and fairness in his novel *One Night @ the Call Center*, in which men and women are treated equally and work overnights. Characters in Nair's novels experience anguish and grief, yet they triumph above it all, as shown by her best-selling novel, *Ladies Coupe* (Chitra 16).

A woman who could live a fulfilled life on her terms was a concept the writer seemed unable to conceive or unwilling to explore. Women in literature have thrown off some stereotypes, but if a women character decides to live a solitary life, readers get upset. In Anita Nair's works, characters like Akhila (*Ladies Coupe*), Radha (*Mistress*), and Lena (*Alphabet Soup for Lovers*) have been chastised for deviating from the norm (Sangeetha 456). Shobhaa De's frank depiction of women in her books has also been unavoidable. The women of De vary from traditional, oppressed, and disadvantaged to ultramodern and free. De's works draw from urban living and genuinely depict an emotional aspect of urban women's existence and their suffering in today's civilization. Also noteworthy is how she emphasizes a woman's involvement in the tyranny and misery of other women, a theme that De explores in *Starry Nights*.

The women in De's writings resurrect their fortunes, appear gorgeous, behave unconventionally, defy social conventions, and are sexually free as well as free intellectuals (Mishra 16). As Deepanjali Mishra asserts, "Sexual expressions and physical intimacy have been maintained as befitting background for an in-depth analysis of the modern Indian society in which a woman always finds herself at the receiving end. Sometimes men seek pleasure from a prostitute where a woman is commercialized" (19). As the present study is about the condition of women in the different locales of India and based on the texts written by women on the socio-

economic conditions of women, therefore, it is pertinent to succinct feminism in the Indian context. The poor representation of women in literature is also one of the reasons for the rise of feminism against patriarchy. This section discusses feminism in India with special relevance to regional women and their oppression based on their gender, class, caste, religion and their quest for identity.

c. Feminism in India

In “The Upsurge of Women's Activism in India” Jana Everett traces the historical and social context of women activism in India. She finds the roots of the ‘jati (sub-castes)’ system in the Hindu religion where it is divided into a hierarchy of Brahmins, Kshatriyas, Vaishyas and Shudras respectively (19). She further expresses the traditional Indian customs where she finds that the women of the upper class have to face many restrictions at the hands of their male counterparts because they are totally dependent on them and don’t work whereas the lower caste women have some freedom in this context because they go out for earning their livelihood. But lower caste women are physically exploited by the males of the upper caste (19). There were no improvements in the conditions of women even during the colonial period till 1947. However, some of the social reformers worked for the abolition of ‘sati paratha’ and the remarriage act for women was legalized. “The social reform movement provided a secular space for women in other areas by looking at various issues which were culturally imposed on women by society and making them crippled” (Pande 5).

Religious customs have adverse effects on the suppressed women as Uma Chakravarti asserts, “The general subordination of women assumed a particularly severe form in India through the powerful instrument of religious traditions which have shaped social practices. A marked feature of Hindu society is its legal sanction for an

extreme expression of social stratification in which women and the lower castes have been subjected to humiliating conditions of existence” (579). It is only after the liberation of India “a small women's movement developed among the urban educated upper castes, and through its lobbying efforts and participation in the nationalist movement, equal rights for women were guaranteed in the Indian Constitution (1950) and in a reformed Hindu Law (1954-56)” (Everett 19). Thereafter when the capitalist movement was in force the upper caste/class males became powerful and there arose a division of the upper and lower class. However, the upper-class population was scant as compared to the lower class, therefore, there arose a difference in the economy and there was an upsurge of mass poverty. So all the lower-class people had to work under the upper class and they were exploiting them. Everett further opines:

While in the past lower-caste/class families were bound to local landlords, now many families have been ‘freed’ and, as a result, have lost the guarantee of a subsistence livelihood. Employers- capitalist farmers, factory owners, foreign aid dispensers- consider men to be more suitable workers and so lower-caste/class women are displaced. Unable to find wage employment, many women eke out a living in the ‘informal sector.’ (19)

Capitalism in India introduces education to women hence forming working middle-class women who are educated and supporting their families economically. However, this results ambiguously for the women residing in India as on the one hand urban middle-class women abolished ‘purdah’ and on the other, the well-off families in rural areas restricted their women from going out to work so that they may not mix up with those urban women.

The reason for this is, as Uma Chakravarti points out, “The safeguarding of the caste structure is achieved through the highly restricted movement of women or even through female seclusion. The lower caste male whose sexuality is a threat to upper caste purity has to be institutionally prevented from having sexual access to women of the higher castes so women must be carefully guarded” (579). Patriarchy has taken a new face in the form of ‘dowry’ which affects both classes of women equally (Everett 19). Crimes become more often against the lower caste women due to the non-fulfilment of the dowry demands. Therefore, “The impact of modernization on women was that it invariably concentrated on the role-conflict of the middle-class working women” who “remained encapsulated in their roles, while critiques of the family were sidelined as the sexual division of labour was naturalized. The studies of mediations of relations of production and reproduction . . . have led to a wider understanding and critique of capitalist development in India” (Rege 227).

During the nineteenth century, several women's issues were brought to light, and changes were implemented. Initially, the feminist movement in India was led by males, who were subsequently supported in their endeavours by their sisters, daughters, spouses, as well as other women. “Feminism as a women-led movement began independently in Maharashtra a few years later, with pioneering advocates for women’s rights and education such as Savitribai Phule, who founded India’s first girls’ school” (“Women Movement in India”).

During the nineteenth century, their educational opportunities grew exponentially, giving them the tools, they needed to further their careers. Several women in India have been transformed as a result of the development of market economies, urbanization, and life expectancy, and they have had to adapt to new social

demands. As a result, several women became more aware of their enforced social, legal, and political inequity. Furthermore, numerous women-led social change organisations, including spiritual reformation, antislavery, temperance, and suffrage, provided a background, a public, and a venue for women authors to voice their ideas. Although most scholars believe that several women authors implicitly acknowledged the completely separate realm of domestic life that the era expected of them, they also contend that as the century progressed; a rising percentage of women began conveying their discontent with gender roles as well as the sufferings of women generally in their texts (Howell 23-25).

R. K. Gupta opines, “Feminism became visible in Indian literature as early as in the 1920s and 1930s. It is, however, perhaps only in the post-Independence period, and especially since the 1960s, that the traditional literary interpretation of women's role and status in society began to be seriously questioned” (181). Education for women has promoted a sense of individuality and a greater understanding of their rights as individuals. Women started to battle against the twin benchmarks of the obsolete social law and the feminist wave in Indian writings throughout this period. Women began to pursue schools and make a name for themselves in writing, primarily as a result of the rise of feminism.

The number of women writers in the nineteenth century was greater than in any previous century. Even before that many male writers have also contributed towards the cause of feminism. “Both Bankimchandra Chatterji and Rabindranath Tagore had depicted women who showed rare courage and strength in critical situations and played a pivotal role in their sphere of operation. Sarat Chandra Chatterji, who created perhaps the most memorable portraits of women in Indian literature” (Gupta 180-81). R. K.

Gupta further asserts feminism isn't just confined to the representation of women by men in literature but also relates to the other areas of their perception and experiences in society. So "a feminist approach has usually meant either, or both, of two things: one, a re-examination through creative literature of the role and status of woman in society and a new way of portraying woman in creative literature which does justice to her identity as an individual; two, a re-interpretation and revaluation of literary texts . . . from a woman-centred point of view" (180).

Therefore, many Indian writers in English and regional literatures in India started to portray women in their works to challenge the traditional stereotypes of women in literature. Many prominent Indian writers in English like R. K. Narayan, Mulk Raj Anand, Raja Rao, Arun Joshi, Anita Desai, Kamala Markandaya, Ruth Praver Jhabvala, Bharti Mukherjee, Shobha De, and Nayantara Sahagal fight against the ill-treatment of women in literature and portrayed some strong real life-like women protagonists (Kadu 115). Similarly, many Indian regional writers also take the initiative to correct the image of women by portraying some remarkable women characters in their respective works. Amrita Pritam in Punjabi, Sarat Chandra, Nabaneeta Deb Sen, Ashapurna, Bani Basu in Bengali, Jainendra Kumar, Mahadevi Verma, Geetanjali Shree in Hindi, Ismat Chugati in Urdu, P. Sivakami, C. S. Lakshmi, Meena Kandasamy in Tamil, Vasuben Bhatt, Meenal Dikshit, Anjali Khandwala, Arupa Pathangia Kalita in Gujarati etc. fight against the patriarchal discrimination against women through their writings in their respective regional language.

Since the 1960s, there has been a change in women's problems like traditional responsibilities and accomplishments, political and social rights, and gender inequalities. In their works, contemporary and postmodern women writers promote a

feminist perspective. Western liberalism, in general, and feminist thinking, in particular, have resulted in feminist writing in English. Indian women, trapped between modernity and tradition and burdened by the past, abandon their ambitions, and this is the core of feminism in Indian literature (Chitra 17-18). As a result, feminism is actively rooted in India as a philosophy that opposes patriarchal tyranny and women's oppression. The primary goal of feminism is to achieve and maintain political, financial, and cultural equality for women, as well as equal treatment. And now, "The Constitution of India mandates that women must be treated as equals and prohibits any discrimination against women in all areas, including education, vocational training, skill development and employment" (Majlis 52). Mridula Garg is of the view:

Feminism has come to India, not so much as an ideology or body of thought representing a worldview of women distinct from the accepted worldview of men, but in the form of a movement emphasizing the need for freeing women from the tyranny of men. More pragmatic than theoretical in approach, it focuses on the emancipation of women rather than the development of a philosophy of political thought. (414)

Feminists were chastised by the patriarchal community in the early phases of the feminist movement for tainting women's thoughts with liberation from their oppressed condition and pushing them to reject their mindless obedience to existing standards. In a short time, the campaign had taken on a global scale in many nations. The feminists' explanatory and innovative works have significantly assisted in their fight to empower women as well as assisted them in rising above their disadvantaged position. They promoted and supported issues relating to women's subjugation, which helped to alter the social climate. While feminists, including feminist authors, have

been able to obtain constitutional rights for women, much work can be done on a cultural level. The suffering of modern women, their difficulties and disagreements, and their attempts to achieve self-identity and autonomy have different stories to tell in different countries with different faiths and social traditions. Modern authors are still working to free women from the oppressive socio-cultural constraints and restrictive beliefs that exist in various nations.

With the increased use of social media platforms among the people of every nation, there is an uprise of the fourth wave of feminism. To quote Shruti Jain, “Cyberfeminism goes beyond previous feminist waves that conceived women as a homogenous group, whose interests could be represented by a singular agenda. To avoid replicating the damaging universalism of old-style feminism, it is essential that cyberfeminism becomes more diverse, decentralized and democratic” (10).

Since the present study is based on Indian regional women writers and to contextualize these writers, it would be appropriate to review women's writing in English and Indian literature translated into English. Further, in the context of the present study, it is necessary to discuss the importance of translation studies in a diverse country like India where a large number of languages are spoken and several writers write in their respective languages.

d. Evolution, Growth and Developments in Women's Writing in English

Indian literary history shows that Toru Lata Dutt was the first woman writer who portrayed many women mythical characters in her works. There are a few other notable women writers like Rajlakshmi Debi, Swarna Kumari Ghosal, Cornelia Sorabji and Sarojini Naidu who fought against social deformities of society. The writings of

Pandita Ramabhai Saraswati laid the foundation of feminism in India. However, most of the earlier women characters portrayed by women writers are mostly the same as portrayed by most of the male writers, for example, the characters who are filled with feminine qualities of love, sacrifice and submissive nature.

Indian women writers have made important contributions to the realm of English novels. The diversity and maturity of the Indian novel have expanded significantly. It is not difficult to trace the progressive evolution of the Indian novel from its imitative period to its rational phase to its psychological stage to its investigative phase. The 1980s have a special place in the emergence and evolution of women's writing of the Indian English novel. During this period, several gifted women authors wrote their first novels and garnered unprecedented honours and accolades both in India and abroad. These Indian women's works, like those of the third generation of women novelists, testify eloquently of their individuality and unmatched creativity.

Indian women have made substantial contributions to world literature on par with male writers. The majority of India's contribution consisted of Indian writing in English, with novelists taking the lead in this respect. A lot of contemporary women writers have communicated their creative impulses only in English and have cited Indian English fiction as a distinctive force in international literature. It incorporates the freshly encountered situations and complex issues of the contemporary world. The new English novel demonstrates confidence in tackling new topics and employs unique tactics and ways to do it. Attributed to the reason that their own language is globalized, it may have been simpler for these women authors to portray the new problems and developments in Indian writing. Once, the majority of the new fiction authors were members of the Indian diaspora. Living in the West, they were heavily exposed to

important contemporary Western literary movements including post-modernism and diverse narrative approaches like magic realism. It allowed them to approach literature with a new perspective (Kishore 4).

Therefore, it should not come as a surprise that the most important contribution of the moment is Indian women's fiction. The voice of contemporary Indian women authors since the 1980s led to a literary rebirth of the third generation of Indian women writers including Anita Desai, Nayantara Sehgal, Shashi Deshpande, Arundhati Roy, Bharati Mukherjee, Gita Mehta, and Jhumpa Lahiri. These are the most prominent women authors of the third generation, and they are crucial to the modern literary scene. They have created an indelible mark on the international literary landscape due to their command of language. They have received national and worldwide acclaim, substantial revenues, and significant honours (Kishore 4). Gita Hariharan and Bharathi Mukherjee point out the moral problems that women experience. Accurate sociological research and truthful descriptions are hallmarks of Rama Mehta and Meena Alexander's work.

Shobha De is renowned for her candid account of events, emphasising India's affluent women. Arundhati Roy connects the group as mentioned above by providing a realistic representation of women's struggles for 'identification' in a patriarchal culture. Therefore, earlier women were also portraying women as done by most of the male writers in traditional stereotypical images, but with the upsurge of feminism in India most of the women writers started to write about women's issues in their works. Even some of the bold writers go beyond that and start to portray rebellious characters in their works who are capable enough to fight for their equal rights as provided in the constitution of India.

Apart from these mainstream women writers, there are a number of women writers who remain confined to their particular region/language until they are not being translated into English 'the universal language.' In order to make the works of such women authors and to know how they are depicting the issues of women in their regional areas, the role and importance of translation studies increases. A brief history of women's writing in Indian literatures shows that even during the ancient and medieval times there were only a few women writers and the bulk of the literature was in the form of folk songs and poetry. Therigatha (600 BC) is a collection of songs sung in the glory of nuns in pali language.

The Sangam Literature (100 B.C.-A.D. 250) in Tamil shows "A total of 154 of the 2,381 poems carry women's signatures, and it is possible that some of the 102 poems that have not yet been attributed to specific composers were also written by women. Anonymous, we know from other cultures, was often a woman" (Tharu and Lalita 70). Till the nineteenth century there were some prominent women writers like Akkamahadevi, Sule Sankavva and Sanciya Honnamma in Kannada; Atukuri Molla, Muddupalani and Tarigonda Venkamamba in Telugu; Rami and Chandrabati in Bengali; Gangasati, Ratanbai and Mirabai in Gujrati; Janabai and Bahinabai in Marathi; and Mahlaqa Bai Chanda in Urdu literature (Tharu and Lalita viii-ix).

During the nineteenth century, in Bengali literature there were women writers like Jogeswari, Bhabani, Rassundari Devi, Hannah Catherine Mullens, Mokshodayani Mukhopadhyay, Swarnakumari Devi, Sarat Kumari Chaudhurani, Binodini Dasi, Nirupama Devi and Ashapura Debi; in Marathi literature, India has Savithribai Phule, Muktabai, Tarabai Shinde, Kashibai Kanitkar and Ramabai Ranade; in Hindi, there are Sudha Chauhan, Subhadra Kumari Chauhan, Homvati Devi and Mahadevi Varma;

Sughra Humayun Mirza, Janaki Bai and Nazar Sajjad Hyder in Urdu (Tharu and Lalita x-xiv); and many more in different languages. Since then, there has been a large number of women writers who are writing quite effectively and actively in different Indian Vernacular literatures. To name a few are Ismat Chughtai, Amrita Pritam, Rajam Krishnan, Dudala Salamma, Mahasweta Devi, Kamal Desai, Saroj Pathak, Mannu Bhandari, and last but not least Kamala Das. Most of these women writers in contemporary times are taking up all the societal issues in their writings and they are trying their hands quite effectively in all forms of Indian regional literatures.

The main objective of the present study is to explore the discrimination against women in the rural parts of India and to observe any differences or similarities in the position and experiences of women in the different regional parts of India or not through the close analysis of women characters as portrayed by select regional women writers. As the present study is based on translated works written by women writers, who belong to different interior regions of India, it is relevant here to discuss the need and relevance of translation studies in a multilingual/multicultural nation like India. The regional writers can only acclaim the global publicity if they are being translated into English from their respective regional languages. Further, the present study focuses on the translated novels of Indian regional women writers, therefore, it is quite felicitous to present a compendious review of translation theories and their relevance in the act of translation.

Translation Studies in India

a. The Role and Scope of Translation Studies

As an academic discipline, 'Translation Studies' explores the process of translation or interpretation in a systematic and theoretical manner. Holems in "The Name and Nature

of Translation Studies” coined the term in 1972. It has “two main objectives: (i) to describe the phenomena of translating and translation(s) as they manifest themselves in the world of our experience, and (ii) to establish general principles by means of which these phenomena can be explained and predicted” (El-dali 30). Reeta Agnihotri opines, “Translation studies aim to extend the methodologies, areas of interest and Conceptual frameworks inside the discipline while testing the traditional boundaries of the notion of translation and offering a forum for debate focusing to historical, social, institutional and cultural facts of translation” (320).

The translation process is defined by H.M. El-dali as, “the transformation of a text originally in one language into an equivalent text in a different language retaining, as far as is possible, the content of the message and the formal features and functional roles of the original text” (31). In a reply to what is translation, Anisha opines, “Translation is not just a process; it is communion between two minds – the translator and the author... It is really difficult to comprehend ‘translation’... the term ‘translate’ means ‘to express in another language, while systematically retaining the original sense’” (340). Subhas Dasgupta reviews Rabindranath Tagore on translation and points out that as per Tagore, translation is a creative process that originates from the unconscious or the subconscious mind of the translator (140). With the growth and rise of Indian literature in English, there is no scarcity of writers writing in their particular regional language. Therefore, the role of translation in a nation like India is vital and the introduction of the English language in India has increased the reach of Indian regional literature at the global level.

In a multilingual nation like India, where the law recognizes twenty-two languages, fifteen distinct scripts, hundreds of native languages and thousands of

languages, the importance of translation cannot be overstated. One might argue that the people of India have a translational tenet and that the sheer circumstances of their daily situations and interactions have made Indians bilingual, if not multilingual. Without exaggerating, India would not have become a country if it had not been for translation. Indians continue to translate, practically subconsciously, from their mother tongues when conversing with individuals who speak in a different language (Yadav 573).

Translation helps in knowing the culture and people residing in different locales as Kirti Kapur asserts, “In the 21st century the role of translation has become even more significant. It is one of the most effective ways of building cross-cultural bridges, . . . that brings us closer to alien cultures and societies not only through their literatures but also their films and other electronic media through subtitling and dubbing” (46). Newspapers, magazines, radio, television, cinema, and other print, electronic, visual, and aural media all need many translators from one dialect to another. In addition, several media companies publish articles and periodicals in multiple languages or broadcast television channels in multiple languages simultaneously, necessitating fast yet accurate translations of information, serials, movie screenplays, and programmes.

Other methods include dubbing and subtitling. All these methods help in sharing the cultural information however, “A pooling and sharing of knowledge is indeed possible only when special efforts are made to cross language boundaries. The best tool employed for this purpose is translation which seeks special attention in our multilingual context” (Kapur 47). While discussing the connection between translation and multilingualism, Hephzibah Israel quotes Meylaerts who opines, “At the heart of multilingualism, we find translation. The translation is not taking place in between monolingual realities but rather within multilingual realities” (125), therefore, “rather

than considering multilingualism as an exceptional feature of some regions of the world where it challenges the demand for translation, scholars have been increasingly identifying multilingual contexts as ubiquitous, and translation as integral to all multilingual realities” (Israel 125).

Translation also helps to broaden the reach of language and reframe the limits of what may be spoken. The creation of new terminology and coinages as a result of translating contributes to the increased expressibility of any writer. One acquires the ability to comprehend international philosophy and literature in the home tongue and talk about contemporary understanding in the local languages, ranging from quantum physics to nanotechnology, computer science, to molecular biology. In contemporary times, even the publishers cannot deny publishing your good translation of any regional writing as Subhasnata Mohanta asserts:

Translation became an equally important part of the publishing vision as you can't run your business in the publishing industry in a country like India, with is a multicultural as well as multilingual nation without publishing translation. The media exposure and prizes that regional authors are receiving have greatly aided in bringing these wonderful, captivating literary works to the attention of the people.

Further, as Kirti Kapur expresses, “Multilingualism is increasingly becoming a significant phenomenon all over the world. Knowing more than one language increases the scope for wider communication. At the same time, the growing interest in the maintenance and revival of many languages among their speakers provides an additional impetus for the development of multilingualism” (49). Therefore, this multilingual and multicultural aspect of India can only be celebrated well with the

increased role and scope of translation. The sharing of cultural information from any particular region would also be possible only due to the translation of the literature and knowledge of that into the reader's native/universal language. Sometimes the translator may not be able to understand the cultural aspects of any particular region so in his translation, he may represent that cultural representation of that particular region in a negative sense to the reader of the target text. The upcoming section explores the difficulties or problems of translation in India.

b. Difficulties/Problems in Translation

The work of any author remains confined to his regional area/language only until it is translated into English or any other popular language. Therefore, "by removing linguistic restrictions, writers and publishing houses will have a better opportunity to showcase their creativity, perception, and insights" (Mohanta) to a larger number of readers globally and, "Translation, especially into English, becomes perhaps the sole means of knowing about the classical and native Indian literature, mapping the literary history of India and encouraging literary dialogue and criticism" (Valiyamattam 26).

Due to widespread education to all and English as the main medium of instruction, the importance of English as a language has increased in contemporary times. Moreover, English is a link language in India, therefore, regional work's translation into English is considered the most feasible and economically viable form of translation. However, "Translations in the English language have been critiqued on two grounds, viz. (a) that there are limits to how much a European language can convey the meaning of the matter in any of the languages of the subcontinent and (b) that the success of the translations in the English language endangers translations in other languages of the region" (Baruah 77). Hindi is considered the most common language

of India, and it has attained a drag in southern regions such as Kerala and Tamil Nadu, where people take pleasure in exclaiming their tongues. How many good literary works produced in other Indian languages, much less English, are transcribed into Hindi? At the same time, scripting in English (as well as producing a gem), one can only imagine what lesser mortals suffer when it comes to releasing their writings transcribed from local dialects into Hindi or English (Cowley 28).

Translation is the only method to connect India's many cultures and offer her writings to global readers. A translator may be fluent in both the source words and the language they are transcribing into yet something always gets lost in the act of translation as Daisy Rockwell asserts, "What of the original is truly lost in translation? Everything. All of it. Translation is what happens next." To this Geetanjali Shree also agrees, "Yes, rhetorically or philosophically speaking, everything is lost. Every articulation is a new translation. And where am I in all of this? Constantly needing to inhabit new shapes emerging in the text, constantly becoming another voice and being, another character in the novel" (Shree and Rockwell). Similarly, Shahane is of the view while translating Hindi works into English, "The trochaic lilt of Hindi and its carry forward melodies seemed very difficult to put across into English translation . . . the process of word-order, emphasis or repetition in a line and the exploration of the latent power in sound and word" (16).

Therefore, "this is indeed a very complex issue of the problem of translation of Indian or Hindi poetry into English. It makes translation a truly great art" (Shahane 18). Daisy Rockwell, the translator, of the Booker Prize-winning novel *Tomb of Sand* mentions the problem of translation when she enquires, "Does 'tomb' belong in the title? How can you bury the complexity and depth of the Hindi word 'samadhi' within

the text?” even after the publication of the novel. Therefore, translation is a never-ending process that can never be perfect. According to Ajeesh and Pranesh Kumar, translation may result in the loss of feelings of the original as happens with the title of K. R. Meera’s *Aarachar* in Malayalam translated by J. Devika as *Hangwoman*. They opine:

Hangwoman, a feminine word, even though in Malayalam it remains a gender-neutral word usually referring to a man since it was uncommon for a woman to occupy the post of a hangman. The translator refrained from using a gender-neutral word like ‘Executioner’ as an equivalent alternative to refer to the female protagonist of the novel. . . . The title in Malayalam evokes an elusive and powerful image of an executioner even though the novel has almost nothing to do with it whereas the title of the translated text though it evokes none of those feelings, remains true to the content of the text. This further helps a foreign reader to understand the idea even before reading it. The title can also be considered as having cultural implications for translation. (4073)

Nonetheless, notwithstanding such flaws and difficulties, it is encouraging to see the Indian translation effort has gradually increased to a decisive gathering. More skilled translators are needed today to enable India’s great local literature to escape from its cocoon and reach a worldwide audience, not simply a significant number of Indian readers. Regional writers, like translators, benefit greatly.

The translator must be acquainted with the subject area as well as the setting for which the research instruments were created to successfully translate them. This was evident in this project since the original translators misinterpreted the queries or used language that did not match the theme and/or was too complex for the intended

audience. The wellness, activity, and program-specific assessment forms looked to be the most troublesome. Depending on the target language, the quality of a bilingual's translations might vary greatly. Translations to English are less troublesome than translations to any other language. According to Rositta Joseph Valiyamattam:

As far as the translation of native Indian literatures into English is concerned, the translator faces three major issues. The first is grasping the meaning of the original text which requires a deep understanding of its linguistic structure and idiom, subtle cultural nuances and varied interpretations of the same word or phrase. . . . The second issue pertains to transferring the exact meaning of the original text. . . . The third issue involves communicating the meaning of the original text. (14)

Therefore, the process of translation is not as easy as it seems. There are lots of difficulties and problems that occur during the act of translation as discussed. There are many lexical and cultural differences in the literature of the vernacular in India. So in order to give any sort of uniformity in the act of translation, there is a strong need for some unified Indian translation theories. The next section discusses the relevance of translation theories in the Indian context.

c. The Relevance of Translation Theories

No one can master all the languages to imbibe knowledge from different literatures/cultures. Only translation has made it possible to share the knowledge of a particular religion/culture worldwide. For instance, many Western ancient philosophers like Dante, Horace and Homer come to Indian readers through translation only and likewise, Indian spiritual knowledge from Vedas and other scriptures which were originally written in Sanskrit would not have spread to the Western nations without

translation. Improving Indian translation is the best method to break down linguistic boundaries and promote literary tradition. Translation broadens the scope of our work and allows it to reach a wider audience. Linguistic knowledge may help people communicate more effectively all around the world. The most fascinating thing that has been found is that translation aids in the establishment of cultural equality. It not only makes it easier for individuals to study Indian literature, but it also educates them about the cultural Diasporas.

A writer gains greater fame and has the opportunity to learn from writers from a variety of literary and ethnic backgrounds. The importance of translation in Indian literature cannot be overstated. With the law recognizing 22 languages and the necessity for high-quality education, it is hard not to be drawn to transcription. Caste, province, dialect, and faith are all obstacles that translation breaks through. “In post-independent India then, translation has figured as a significant “nation-building” exercise, encouraging participatory citizenship in the new multilingual, democratic, republic at best, and a somewhat utopian rhetoric at worst” (Israel 128). This is because of the different power politics in language persist there as Hephzibah Israel opines:

Despite repeated efforts to declare more languages as legally equal through the Indian constitution, many further languages (including oral and written dialects and language registers) have remained marginalized. Such paradoxical pulls between an apparently multilingual nation, made up of monolingual nationals, each valorizing their own “mother tongue”, continue to obfuscate attitudes to and understandings of translation in India. (128)

The sacred texts are also available in all scripts. This allows us to understand more about different cultures while also broadening our viewpoint on problems. In a nation

like India, where people are becoming increasingly bilingual, if not multilingual, each hour of each day, translation has aided in making people multilingual. The requirement to understand more than a single language and the availability of books or scriptures in several languages has enhanced the nation's educational situation. The majority of translation firms in India concentrate on translating all documents into as many dialects as possible (Chandras 39).

The idea of translation varies differently in different regions/ages, therefore, “the practice of translation without a theoretical background tends toward a purely subjective exercise” (El-dali 33). He further quotes Manfredi who opines, “When dealing with translation, we firmly believe that this need is even stronger. Proficiency in two languages, the source one and the target one, is obviously not sufficient to become a competent translator” (qtd. in El-dali 33). For example, “In the East (particularly in India) translation has always been regarded as ‘New writing’ but in the West, the theory of translation has developed from the purely linguistic approach of the 1960s through the textual focus of the late 1970s to the culturally based interpretation of the present time” (qtd. in Anisha 341). Till British rule, there was no particular theory of translation recorded in India.

So the process and the purpose of translations as G. N. Devy opines, “In the Indian context...can be divided into three types: (i) those interested in preserving the ancient literary heritage, (ii) those interested in ‘Westernising’ Indian languages and literature, and (iii) those interested in ‘nationalising’ literature in modern Indian languages” (qtd. in Anisha 341). Therefore, as per the purpose and need the way of doing translation differs in India. From the ancient to pre-colonial period, translations from Sanskrit to different languages were done to preserve the religious and cultural

heritage of different parts of India and the translations were regarded as a mere shadow of the original text. During the colonial period, many Indian scriptures were translated into English and vice-versa in order to exchange the knowledge and customs of different cultures. Anisha points out, “In the post-colonial era, the situation has been totally changed. With the origination of the modern Indian languages, translation activity became intensified and the concept of ‘translation as a shadow of original text’ was not strictly followed” (343).

The value of translation in a multilingual nation like India is far greater than one realizes. Due to increase in the translation activities, a good translation theory is the need of the hour. As Anisha asserts, “In recent years, the contacts with Western languages like English, French, Spanish, etc. and culture also have influenced the theoretical standpoint of the translators of India. As a result of these historical changes, new translation theories have emerged with the developments in the socio-cultural situations and the changing tastes of the new generation” (343). The evolution of translation theories in India, as discussed by various critics, is as follows:

1. **Transcreation:** It is used as a way to translate Sanskrit texts into many other Indian languages to make the content available to those who aren’t acquainted with Sanskrit. Many Indian texts like the Ramayana, Mahabharata and other such religious texts are translated into various languages using this method. Even during the “20th century, poets like Rabindra Nath Tagore, Sri Aurobindo, A.K. Ramanujan, Girish Karnad also used . . . global marketing and advertising campaigns because advertisers seek to transcend the boundaries of culture and language” (Anisha 344).

2. **Psycho-spiritual:** In her article “History and Theories of Translation: India” Jayasree says, “Sri Aurobindo, philosopher, poet and translator has recorded the

theoretical framework of his own translations in several of his articles, drawing from the psycho-spiritual interpretations of the Upanishads” (4). Dr. Anisha also points out, “After translating a number of texts, he developed these theories with the cognition of philosophy and psychology as he was influenced by the cognitive philosophy and tradition especially pre-Buddhist and Buddhist period of India” (344).

3. Rabindranath Tagore’s Theory of Creative Translation: Tagore discusses the act of translation to defend his own translation of *Gitanjali* into English. Subhas Dasgupta opines, “His theory and practice of translation are often so inextricably interwoven that while speaking of his self-translation, he is found enunciating, perhaps unconsciously, a theory of translation, or, to be precise, discussing a particular aspect of the translation problem” (136). Rabindranath Tagore was a strong advocate of creative translation, therefore:

Firstly, he makes a comparative discussion on the literal or word-for-word translation and what may be called 'rewriting' or creative translation. He speaks of the aesthetic joy that he derives from 'rewriting' or creative translation, a joy that literal or word-for-word translation cannot provide. . . . Secondly, Tagore has no hesitation in accepting translation as ‘a form of original creative writing on a par... with the poem of which it is a translation’ . . . Thirdly, he feels that his poems [read his 'translations'] need to be 'divested' of their native 'adornments' so that foreigners can understand and appreciate his poems...Fourthly, he would like to use the English language creatively while rewriting his poems so that they might be a 'reincarnation', or acquire a new life of their own in the target language. (Dasgupta 136-38)

Tagore feels that translation is an act of rewriting from the original to the target text to match some of the ideologies and power poetics of the same. However, for him, it is a pure creative process without any sort of intentional manipulation and “the objective of rewriting is, then, creative 'reincarnation or 'rebirth' of the original” (Dasgupta 139).

4. Indian Poetic Theories: According to this theory, the meaning of any word is always multiple and suggestive as per the Indian tradition of translation. Therefore, it is very crucial to focus on the suggestive meaning in the translation of any Indian Language. Anisha asserts that “the suggestive meaning depends mainly on three factors: (i) it depends on the peculiar expression of the word (ii) different shades of the meaning of the word (iii) and the socio-cultural context.” She further points out:

(i) The technique of transcreation was in vogue even in ancient India which is now popular in Western culture (ii) Indian translators tried to enrich the regional languages through translation (iii) the psycho-spiritual theories of Sri Aurobindo have significance in translation studies (iv) theory of suggestive meaning is the important factor to considerate while translating any text. (345)

Indra Nath Choudhuri points to Ayyappa Panikar’s views on Indian medieval translation of Sanskrit classics which uses these concepts:

i) Anukriti is imitation of the original. One can imitate only what one is not. The product of imitation is not the same text, but a similar text; ii) Arthakriya is putting emphasis on the manifold ways in which meanings are enacted in different texts. It emphasizes the creation of meaning or addition, omission, displacement and expansion; iii) Vyaktivivekam is rendering of the meaning inferred by the reader or invoking interpretation based on anumana or inference potential of a given passage; iv) Ullurai is a Dravidian term primarily means the

inner speech, not the heard melody but the one unheard or the speech within.
(118)

Theorists in ancient India understand that the meaning of speech is not limited to its literal interpretation. Focusing only on the literal meaning may cause one to miss the deeper or symbolic significance of the message. Instead, they place greater importance on discovering the true essence or hidden meaning behind the words (Choudhuri 117).

In contemporary times, the importance and the need for translation are increasing due to the increase in the number of regional language literary pieces in Indian Literature. As Indra Nath Chaudhary further points out:

In the present-day India plurilingual writers, writing in the language of the ex-colonizer or in Indian bhashas are challenging and redefining many accepted notions in translation theory. We can no longer merely concern ourselves with the conventional notion of linguistic equivalence or ideas as loss and gain, which have long been a consideration in translation theory. The reason is the extensive use of different upabhashas by Indian writers like Kambar, Debesh Roy, Krishna Sobti and others, or the creation of a new language by Dalit writers or the use of tribal languages in multilingual contexts. (122)

Therefore, the discussion shows that Indian linguistics and poetics may participate significantly towards the growth of translation theories in India. For Indian regional literature to remain unified in such diversity, a profound theoretical framework is very much required in translation studies. Therefore, translation is not an easy task and the role of a translator is way more difficult than that of a language teacher. Translation is a very careful exercise and needs to be done quite consciously. While translation a translator has to take care of the cultural aspects of not only the source text

along with the linguistic but also the target language as well. A translator needs to keep the feelings and sense of the original text when converting it into any target language.

d. Role of Translator

Zhang Qun-xing quotes Lawrence Venuti who asserts, “The voice that the reader hears in any translation made on the basis of *simpatico* is always recognized as the author’s, never as a translator’s, nor even as some hybrid of the two” (178). Therefore, there is a need for “nonfluent, nonstandard, and heterogeneous language by producing foreignized rather than domesticated texts so that translators could make themselves visible and their voice detectable” (Qun-xing 178). In “Role of Translation: The Translator : His Triple Role” Lila Ray opines that a translator has a triple role in the act of the translation. At first, he needs to be an eager receiver of the original text which he selects to translate. He must try to understand completely the need and purpose of the author behind writing that text. Secondly, the translator becomes the Trans-placer who not only carries the text from one language to another but carries it along with the cultural context of the source to the target language because “Translation is a dual process: it takes place both on the level of language and the level of culture” (149).

The cultural aspect is a must for any translator as Hassan S. Kashoob opines, “Cultural translation is considered to be one of the most essential and, complicated translations. If the translator does not have any cultural background of the source language then he will face difficulties conveying the whole meaning of the cultural patterns that, are included in the original text” (91). “Language and culture may thus be seen as being closely related and both aspects must be considered for translation. . . . The cultural implications for translation require a full understanding of the notion rather than an emphasis on the original SL reference” (James). So a translator “must

identify the situations where there is cultural overlap and try to bridge the gap caused by the cultural distance between the two languages” (Kashoob 91).

While discussing the third role of the translator, Lila Ray asserts that after completing the first two steps very closely with proper encoding of the message of the source text and extensive understanding of author’s choice of every inflexion, grammatical or structural expression, the translator now has to adapt his third role of originator who needs to decipher the text into the target language by “producing a work that sounds as natural to the second audience as it did to the first and evokes the same response” (124). Although a translator is regarded as an originator but he only acts as a ‘secondary originator’ who doesn’t have his own freedom to alter the original text while translating it into any target language. As Steven Rendall opines, “While fidelity and freedom in translation have long been seen as conflicting tendencies, it also seems that this deeper interpretation of one of them does not reconcile the two, but on the contrary, denies the other any justification” (162).

So “we must remember that the role of the translator is different from that of the ‘normal communicator’: the translator is a bilingual mediating agent between monolingual communication participants in two different language communities” (El-dali 30). However, “literary translation is interwoven with more cultural and social elements, the translator has to make a choice between loyalty and violation, getting freedom and being restricted when he or she confronts with all the clashes and conflicts between the source language culture and the target language culture” (Chen-qing 294). Therefore, “He has to work thrice as hard, know much more and be three times as skilful as the original author” (Lila 124).

Honesty and respect for others, as someone has for oneself, is the prime requirement from a translator. A translator needs to feel for the target language as he/she feels for his/her own/source language. As Gayatri Spivak asserts, “The task of the translator is to facilitate this love between the original and its shadow, a love that permits fraying, holds the agency of the translator and the demands of her imagined or actual audience at bay. . . . Translation is the most intimate act of reading. I surrender to the text when I translate” (181). She further comments on ethical translation:

The presupposition that women have natural or narrative-historical solidarity, that there is something in a woman or an undifferentiated women's story that speaks to another woman without the benefit of language-learning, might stand against the translator's task of surrender. Paradoxically, it is not possible for us as ethical agents to imagine otherness or alterity maximally. We have to turn the other into something like the self in order to be ethical. To surrender in translation is more erotic than ethical. In that situation, the good-willing attitude ‘she is just like me’ is not very helpful. . . . In order to earn that right of friendship or surrender of identity, of knowing that the rhetoric of the text indicates the limits of language for you as long as you are with the text, you have to be in a different relationship with the language, not even only with the specific text. (Spivak 183)

Spivak wants the translator to set aside his/her own identity to be ethical towards the task of translation. It is by that only a translator can set a rapport with the mindset of the original texts and its cultural context which is utterly needed to incorporate the same feelings into the translated version. “Being polyglots, we use more than one language while speaking or even thinking. But the big question is why isn't there a

single critical text specifying the art or science of translation parallel to Panini's *Ashtadhyayi* or Bharata's *Natyashastra*" (Choudhuri 113). He further opines that in India, "the exclusivist attitude of the speakers of the master narrative is responsible for this kind of dismal situation" (Choudhuri 113).

After all, it is not just about translating; it is also about retaining the precise feelings, emotions, and meanings of words as well as idioms, and so forth, across all dialects and nations. As Vasant A. Sahane asserts, "Meaning is an important goal in translation, especially if it is a total, and not a partial . . . The search for the right word is central to the process because the meaning of the original has to be retained in the other language as much as possible" (6-7). Certain translation companies in India have succeeded in providing excellent translations of Indian literature, while others have not.

Therefore, the above discussion shows that translation isn't a mere exercise of converting anything written in one language into any other by the mere use of words. A translator needs to be very careful while performing the act of translation. First of all, the translator has to decipher the meaning and purpose of the original text with a complete focus on its lexical and cultural context. Then accordingly while converting from the source language to the target language, the translator has to keep in mind the lexical and cultural context of the target language so that it may arouse the same feelings in the reader's mind as done by the original text. Translation is a process through which the cultural aspects of any nation/region may also be transmitted to other areas. The authority enjoyed by those who exercise it in a specific culture might be made to appear legitimate through translation. It's not a new idea to employ translation as a tool of hegemony or a dictatorial policy. The next section discusses the role of politics in translation especially in India.

e. Politics of Translation

In the process of translation also there is politics of giving importance to certain aspects as beneficial to the colonizers and the issues which highlight the problems of the colonized are not given space. “The politics of translation is located in struggles for meaning, in rendering encounters and interactions tangible and legible. For instance, in processes of translation, some actors are given voice and others silenced, and hierarchies are established and dismantled” (Capan et al 398). Jamil Asghar opines about the dominating role of the socio-political institutions in propagating certain things which in turn shapes them into an established ideology. Such ideologies become the core reality for the outside translators which prejudice the true meaning of the original works being translated by them. “The discourses based upon such themes as racism, gender inequality, minority rights or unipolarism become a mouthpiece for entire social institutions . . . by virtue of their power, exercises huge influence” (34) on the minds of the translators.

He further asserts, “The act of rewriting operates on the politics of inclusions/exclusions as well. Which readers/writers, systems of values and sets of beliefs are to be privileged and which ones are to be deprived? This is a fundamental question and plays a critical role in the politics of inclusions/exclusions” (Asghar 35). All these power politics restrict the translation of some works/aspects that they don't want readers outside the language to know about that particular culture/region or they may force the readers to know them in a particular way which is not the way it actually is. “The Anglo-American translation tradition is particularly noted for its tendency to practice these exclusions/inclusions. This is usually done through selectively adopting such apparently apolitical and innocent-sounding strategies as gisting, free translation, compensation, heavy glossing, or ennoblement” (Asghar 35).

This is how powerful institutions play a negative role in the process of translation and due to which only half knowledge inscribed in the original text is conveyed to readers by the translator. “This politics is evident right from the early practices of oriental translations including that of Edward Fitzgerald’s translation of Omar Khayyam’s *Rubaiyat*, William Jones’s translation of *Sakuntala*, Charles Wilkin’s translation of *Bhagavad Gita*, Jones and Wilkin’s *Menu’s Institutes* and H.H. Wilson’s *Kalidasa*” (Stenza). Translation is a method whereby foreign ideas can enter a native society, confront it, and sometimes corrupt it instead of simply opening a door to a different world. The control vested in those who exercise it within a particular civilization can be made to appear legitimate through translation.

A false value system developed in India due to the emergence of British power there and the dissemination of English learning. The political context of translation furthered the implementation of this value structure, which held that whatever British was essentially good. For example, C. Vimala Rao asserts, “The act of translation in colonial times especially had a racial, political agenda, as we have seen. When Edward Lane published his popular translation of *The Thousand and One Nights* in 1859 he went on to say in the Introduction to the book that the Arabs were more gullible and did not distinguish between reality and fiction” (139). Likewise, “Edward Fitzgerald . . . spoke in disparaging terms of Persian poetry and said in his Introduction that the *Rubaiyyat* of Omar Khayyam was beautiful poetry because he had embellished it with his superior craft in the English Translation!” (Rao 139). Language is a strong tool with which one can convey to the world the manipulated reality of the original version.

Therefore, “the politics of translation takes on a massive life of its own if you see language as the process of meaning-construction” (Weissbort and Eysteinnsson).

Publishers also play an important role in promoting the translations of a certain regional language/author in English depending upon their personal liking as Arunava Sinha points out, “By a strange quirk of publishing history, many of the first set of editors in India were Bengali-speaking. Not surprisingly, this was the language that was represented the most in the first wave of published translations.” So they try to promote only their own regional language without being bothered that there may be much better works written in other regional languages that are worth publishing and translating into English.

Translators as well as interpreters are traditionally thought of as impartial intermediates that help persons who don't speak the same language communicate. Since cultural awareness is ingrained in language, translation, as well as interpretation, are political activities that may establish, influence, and reject values and norms in both the source and destination cultures. Despite being the closest to the culture depicted in the vernaculars' works, one doesn't get enough space among readers worldwide. Their fame is short-lived and remains confined to their culture and space (Das and Som 172). As Makarand Paranjape asserts, “vernacular texts that are not translated remain a part of what is pejoratively termed ‘regional’ literature. More often than not, neither are they read by a pan-Indian or international audience nor are they read in a manner that makes them a part of the kind of larger discourse” (91). To find the required fame and space worldwide is also one of the main reasons for the so-called Indian regional literature in English translation. As Jayasree points out:

Niranjana elaborates upon the politics of translation and the use of translation as a tool by the colonizers. She examines how the colonizers used translation socially, politically and culturally to continue their domination. She says that by

giving English audiences a ‘fixed’ picture of the colonised people through the translation of Indian texts, the translators created a people without history. The colonisers translated the Indian texts in such a way as to justify their ideology of domination. (5-6)

Sometimes translators deliberately avoid to translate some important aspects of an original text as Onur Köksal and Nurcihan Yürük point out, “One of the most recent translation problems is not related to translation error itself; it is interpreter’s “preference not to translate”. Sometimes interpreters either soften or skip the whole subject while interpreting to avoid damaging diplomatic relations or inclining cultural and social misunderstandings” (335).

Therefore, the discussions in the section show that there can be a lot of politics in the act of translation as a translator while converting the text into English or any other power language may change the inherent meaning of the original text that the writer intended to convey to the readers. In this way, the translated version of the converted text will not solve the purpose of the writer or may even worsen his cause of writing that particular text. Several regional writers are writing in their respective languages so the role of translation studies increases to increase the number of readers at the global level.

Indian Literature in English Translation

India, due to its multilingualism, has the finest and most varied literature in the world. It is not a new occurrence. It has been this way for years—far before the written language. The clan of Indian authors who only write in English is growing by the day, but this is not the focus of the present study. So what matters here are the tens of thousands of other people who write in a range of various tongues. The nation

possesses 20 formally approved tongues, such as Hindi, Bengali, Urdu, Tamil, Gujarati, and Marathi, without even considering the varieties spoken in the different states of India. Good English translations of Indian regional literature would enhance India's national literature and make a significant contribution to global literature. As Vinay Dharwadker points out, "Indian-English literature by itself is inadequate to represent who we are to the rest of the world. Only a broad representation of the full range of Indian literature, translated into a world language such as English, can do what is needed" (134). However, excellent translations of writings from India's vast diversity of local dialects into Hindi and English are shockingly rare. As a result, India's literary gold mine remains virtually untapped.

Translation promotes democracy by creating equality among dialects and calling into question the predominance of some over others, demonstrating certain thoughts, including feelings, can be conveyed in all dialects and are interchangeable despite their differences. It also allows the poorer members of society to be recognised since they may communicate in their own languages or tongues, which are subsequently transcribed into more commonly spoken and recognised dialects. As a result, translation aims to inspire marginalised or disadvantaged groups such as the impoverished, women, dalits, tribals, minorities, the handicapped, and many others. Dr. Anisha says, "Translation has now emerged as a major discipline both as a field of study as well as a process of recreating the world of one language into another" (346).

It is not easy being a translator as they must be able to imagine and have an intimate relationship with both tongues. As Vasant A. Shahane points out, "translation is as much an act of creativity as the original writing in literature is acknowledged to be...An imaginative translation has been defined as transcreation" (5). The uniqueness

of the writer's subject, as well as the presentation, is among the most significant aspects anyone considers before going for its translation. The second aspect is to think about how well the work will perform with audiences outside of the specific literary environment in which the writer created it. Reading as well as publishing translations becomes an interesting and gratifying undertaking as a result.

In contemporary India, translated works have achieved great success as Harish Trivedi writes, “Of all the literary happenings in India in 2022, the most newsworthy clearly was the award of the International Booker Prize to *Tomb of Sand*, the English translation by Daisy Rockwell of Geetanjali Shree’s Hindi novel *Ret Samadhi*.” Therefore, it won't be wrong to assert good translations are bridging the literary gap between regional languages in India to Indian writing in English. Moreover, with the increased result of well-translated books talented regional writers from India gain a wide range of readers when their works are transcribed into English, the global language.

There are a number of writers in Indian Literature who have penned a lot of masterpieces in various languages and whose work has been appreciated and translated into some other languages as well. The majority of male writers depict women as a figure of selflessness, unconditionally caring mothers, devoted wives or obeying daughters. But none of the male writers have ever depicted women as independent human beings like their male characters. As Sangeeta Dutta points out, “With Sita and Savitri as predominant models of reference, Indian women are expected to be pure and faithful as wives and self-effacing, loving and giving as mothers” (84).

Such is the depiction of women in the male-dominated literature. On the other hand, women writers tried to put forth the self-identity of a woman by defying these

traditional roles which are being imposed on women by patriarchal customs. Geetanjali Shree, a prominent Hindi writer has presented through the depiction of one of her characters, Lalna, in her *The Roof Beneath their Feet* (2003). The present study focuses on women's position in male-dominated Indian rural societies as depicted in the translated novels of regional women writers residing in the different regions of India. Therefore, it is required here to dwell on prominent writers whose works have been translated into English.

Notable Women Writers in Translation

A number of women writers write in their respective regional languages and their works get translated into English later on. Most of them are depicting the discrimination against women in male-dominated societies in rural India. Among Tamil writers there is C.S. Lakshmi (Ambai) who is known for her feminist storylines and her collection of short stories inspired by folklore, feminism, as well as everyday women's lives entitled *In a Forest* and *A Deer* (2006) was translated by Lakshmi Holmstrom. The next is Bama Faustina Soosairaj, her autobiographical book *Karukku* (1992) is regarded as a significant work of dalit writing because it is courageous, freeing, and therapeutic which was again translated by Lakshmi Holmstrom.

Bama depicts the cruel life of dalit women in Indian societies; her works show the pathetic living conditions of dalit women and show how they are discriminated against at many levels. Salma is another important poet and fiction writer whose novel *Irandaam Jaamathin Kadai* was also translated by Lakshmi Holmstrom as *The Hour Past Midnight* (2009). P. Sivakami is also a Tamil writer and a prominent feminist whose novel *The Taming of Women* (2011) is selected for close textual analysis in the present study.

Sangeeta Bandyopadhyay, a Bengali writer, explores femininity in an unusual way. Her recent work, *The Yogini* (2019), was chosen as one of the finalists for the PEN Translate Grant. It was transcribed into English by Arunava Sinha. The other famous writer from Bengal is Mahasweta Devi. Her short story, *Rudali* (1993) depicts the pathetic condition of low-caste women and their intense sufferings in rural India. *Rudali* is one of the most important feminist texts in regional literature in India.

Gogu Shyamala has written *Father May Be an Elephant and Mother Only a Small Basket* (2012) in Telugu which explores the narrations of discrimination against dalit women. Besides her Yaddanapudi Sulochana Rani, Ranganayakamma, and Tenneti Hemalata are some of the prominent Telugu women writers.

In Punjabi and Hindi literature, there are other renowned women authors like Amrita Pritam, Krishna Sobti and Geetanjali Shree. Amrita Pritam's *Pinjar* (1950) is one of her famous novels translated by Khushwant Singh into English. Krishna Sobti has written a number of novels in Hindi and one of the most famous is *Mitro Marjani* (1967) translated by Gita Rajan. Geetanjali Shree is also one of the renowned names of contemporary Hindi Writers in India. Her novel *Ret Samadhi* (2018) translated into English by Daisy Rockwell as *Tomb of Sand* (2021) has become the first Hindi novel to be awarded the prestigious International Booker Prize in 2022. *Tirohit* (2003) by Geetanjali Shree depicts the life of two females who are struggling for freedom and equality in the patriarchal society.

Lalitambika Antharjanam, in Malayalam, is known for her depiction of women's struggle for social and political struggle, her novel *Agnisakshi* (1976) presents the critique of social customs of India which restricts women from their freedom and curtail their self-identity. Another famous Malayalam writer Kamala Das is known for

her interrogation of patriarchal stereotypes of women in Indian societies as depicted in her works. *Ente Katha* (1973) translated as *My Story* (1976) depicts her own story of discrimination in the male-dominated society.

Among Assamese women writers, there are famous names like Indira Goswami and Arupa Pathangia Kalita. Indira Goswami, in her novel *Neel Kanthi Braja* (1986), has depicted the condition of widows in India and other social discriminations against women in Indian rural societies. In *Tej Aru Dhulire Dhushorito Prishtha* (1998) she has portrayed the conditions of women during communal frenzy, violence and riots. Likewise, Arupa Pathangia Kalita in her novel *Felanee* (2003), which is one of the novels selected for the present study, depicts the suffering of women during ethnic riots and an outbreak of violence in rural Assam.

The present study explores the depiction of women in select novels of P. Sivakami (*The Taming of Women* in 2011 originally in Tamil in 1992), Geetanjali Shree (*The Roof Beneath their Feet* in 2013 originally in Hindi in 2003), Arupa Pathangia Kalita (*The Story of Felanee* (2011) originally in Assamese in 2003), Ila Arab Mehta (*Fence* (2015) originally in Gujarati in 2011), and K.R. Meera (*Hangwoman* in 2016 originally in Malayalam in 2012). A famous Tamil writer, P. Sivakami, is a prolific dalit feminist from South India. She was born in 1957 and has written around six novels and a number of short stories. Some of her prominent works include *Pazhayana Kazhidalum* (1988), *Nalum Thodarum* (1989), *Kadaisi Mandhar* (1995) and *Kurruku Vettu* (1999). She translated her first novel *Pazhayana Kazhidalum* into English in 2006 entitled *The Grip of Change*. The novel is a strong revolt against the patriarchal plight of dalit women at multiple levels in rural parts of India. Her next novel *Anandhayi* (1992) was translated into English entitled *The Taming of Women* (2011) by Pritham K Chakravarthy.

Geetnajali Shree, a famous name in Hindi literature, was born in 1957 in Mainpuri, Uttar Pradesh and resides in New Delhi. She has written around five novels in Hindi, a number of short stories and a few works on Munshi Premchand including her PhD thesis. Her latest novel *Ret Samadhi* (written in 2018) got her Booker Prize in 2022 when translated into English by Daisy Rockwell entitled *Tomb of Sand*. Her famous novel *Mai* (2000) was also shortlisted for the Crossword Book Award (2001). Her novel *Tirohit* (2001) was translated in 2013 by Rahul Soni entitled *The Roof Beneath their Feet*.

In modern Assamese writing, Arupa Patangla Kalilta is a well-known feminist and award-winning writer. In addition to the many articles in vernacular publications, many of which were traduced into other Indian and English languages, she has written more than ten novels (notably *Dawn*, which was released in English by Zubaan) as well as short story anthologies (*Memories* and *The Plum Tree* translated into English by Deepika Phukan). She is a resident of Guwahati and works as an English teacher at Tangla College in Assam. She has won many awards like Bhartiya Bhasa Parishad Award (in 1995 for *Shatya*), the Assam Valley Literary Award, 2009 the Sahitya Sanskriti Award, the Lekhika Samaroh Sahitya Award (2011) and she won Sahitya Akademi Award (2014) for her collection of stories entitled *Mariam Austin Othoba Hira Barua* later translated in English by Ranjita Biswas as *The Loneliness of Hira Baru* (2020). One of Arupa's famous novels *The Story of Felanee* (2011) translated by Deepika Phukan has been selected for the present study. This novel was shortlisted for the Crossword Book Award.

A famous Gujarati Writer, Ila Arab Mehta, was born in 1938. She has written a number of novels and a collection of short stories. Her major works include *Trikonni*

Tran Rekha (1966), *Radha* (1972), *Ek Hata Diwan Bahadur* (1976), *Batris Laksho* (1976), *Varasdar* (1978), *Avati Kalno Sooraj* (1979), *Batris Putalini Vedana* (1982), *Ane Mrityu* (1982), *Shabne Naam Hotu Nathi* (1981) and her latest work *Vaad* (written in 2011) got translated into English as *Fence* by Rita Kothari in 2015.

Malayalamwriter, K. R. Meera, from Kerala was born in 1970. She has written some short stories, novellas and around five novels. Her works include: *Ormayude Njarambu* (2002), *Mohamanja* (2004) translated as *Yellow is the Colour of Longing* by J. Devika in 2011, *Ave Maria* (2008) for which she got Kerala Sahitya Akademi Award, and her masterpiece and widely recognized novel, *Aarachaar* (2012), translated by J. Devika as *Hangwoman* in 2016 and got shortlisted for DSC Prize for South Asian Literature.

The in-depth literature review in the next section points out that only a few scholars/critics have commented on the works of select women novelists for the present study. Only a few articles or reviews have appeared in magazines or newspapers and there is no detailed research has been done so far on one or two select authors and their works. Therefore, the present study has assimilated as many reviews as accessible on various resources.

Review of Literature

a. P. Sivakami

Anandhayi (1992) was originally written in Tamil by P. Sivakami and translated into English as *The Taming of Women* (2011) by Pritham K. Chakravarthy. The prolific author and dalit campaigner, P. Sivakami, has written five novels, four collections of short stories, five essays and two volumes of poetry. Most of her writings have been

translated into English and other languages. “The first Dalit (lower caste) woman to become a novelist, the titles of Palanimuthu Sivakami’s books reveal her life and times. After her first novel *The Grip of Change*, the recently released *The Taming of Women*, is all set to create waves” (Pathak). Deepa Nair and N. Nila, in “Docile Bodies and Dividing Practices in P. Sivakami’s *The Taming of Women* and Nawalel Saadawi’s *Woman at Point Zero*” written in 2020, are of the view, “P. Sivakami . . . chronicles the lives of women trapped in patriarchy. . . . Anandhayi is a woman who struggles to perform several roles as a mother, wife and even as an agricultural labourer in her own fields . . . Anandhayi has been reduced to what Foucault calls ‘docile bodies’” (856-57). They further opine:

Periyannan . . . beats her, abuses her and holds her responsible for the problems he encounters. He also maintains a mistress, Lakshmi within his family home. Thus he devalues the importance of his wife by using “dividing practices” that position his mistress at a higher level than his wife. But there are also occasions when he lures Anandhayi to have sex with him. Anandhayi loves and needs Periyannan. It is this dependence that is exploited by Periyannan to reduce Anandhayi to a docile body. (857)

About P. Sivakami’s *The Taming of Women* Yash Raj and others in “Raising the Voice against the Atrocities: A Critical Study of P Sivakami’s *Taming of Women*” (2020) point out that dalits have been oppressed and ruled by higher caste people from the beginning of existence. They are deprived of all fundamental necessities, and they are denied the equitable footing in society that they deserve. Since they belong to the lowest social strata, they are shunned and driven to the outside of society.

The plight of dalit women is even worse, and special attention should be paid to how they survive and live in these appalling conditions, “*Taming of Women* by P. Sivakami unleashes the horrific condition of Anandhayi who suffers at the hands of her husband Periyannan. There are many incidents in the texts which inform us about the trauma and pain of Anandhayi” (Raj et al. 654). They further observe that the novel is an example “of those courageous efforts and protests where Dalit women have started to question the norms of the society and especially have tried to challenge the set rules of the patriarchal society. Dalit Literature off late has tried to give confidence and boost to the voice of women” (Raj et al. 655)

Supriya in “Sivakami’s *The Grip of Change: Revisited*” (2017) points out issues like politics based on gender and class in the main protagonist’s life. Thangam, the main protagonist, has to face a lot of struggles due to her low class and being a woman. Supriya asserts “The author of *The Grip of Change* had criticized the leadership of Dalits when the Dalit movement was gaining ground. Novels had to be read against the background of their times” (73). Shanmathi in “Ceaseless Sadism against Women in P. Sivakami’s *The Taming of Women*” (2017) is of the view that P. Sivakami is one of India's top Dalit novelists. She wrote about sexism and the Dalit struggle before anybody else. Her debut work was translated as *The Grip of Change (Pazhaidalum)*. She abandoned her job as a secretary-level bureaucrat and started her own political party. Sivakami’s writings address women’s and Dalit’s oppression. Both the novels “deals with the concept of male chauvinism, suppression, sexual abuse, incest, rural lifestyle” (320).

Shanmathi further asserts, “Sivakami teaches the readers, how a woman is being treated in the society and how she should be treated. . . . As a good writer, Sivakami

brings out the truth of men ill-treating women, instead, men should give women love and care, and provide them the space they need to be free and happy” (326). Pratibha Somkuwar in “Unjustified Justice in *The Grip of Change*” (2014) points out, “[The novel] is a unanimous expression of the youth of the oppressed community who is eagerly asking questions to patriarchal dominance . . . The author directly relates Thangam’s body with fertility, letting her to face the triple marginalized status by the hands of social structure, power relations and patriarchy” (19).

She further asserts, “*The Grip of Change* creates the impression that . . . a subaltern Dalit third world woman goes on facing . . . violence in the form of physical, emotional, psychological, and religious ways . . . Since centuries, women, are being dominated by . . . patriarchy” (22). Shalini in a book review opines, “Sivakami has presented the sufferings of a Dalit which becomes more pathetic when a Dalit is a woman. Moreover, this book makes its readers understand the human-made discriminations and their results, how Dalits have been subjugated by upper caste people for centuries, and they feel like the ‘other’ in their own land.”

In a book review written in 2012, Sandhya Renukamba expresses, “We are often led to believe in the myth of innocence and simplicity in rural life. Our movies and popular literature often perpetuate this myth, but P. Sivakami debunks it in *The Taming of Women*.” In an article published (2012) in the *Deccan Herald*, Shinnie Anthony discusses the realistic aspects of the novel *The Taming of Women*. She writes, “As a sad commentary on real life, the book works like a documentary; there are no false echoes even if somewhat overstuffed with dialogue . . . As two of the tamed women from the title, Anandhayi and Lakshmi are more statistics than path-breaking heroines. Fiction gives them a voice but they fail to tame fiction to break through.”

It emerges from the above reviews that P. Sivakami's works centre on discrimination of Dalit women as the writer of the novel herself is a Dalit. The present study explores the elements of multi-layered discrimination of a Dalit female; at first by virtue of being a woman born in a patriarchal society and oppression in myriad ways in Indian society, second, as a Dalit woman exploited by Dalit men, and third as a Dalit woman exploited by upper caste men. Most of the female characters in the novel suffer from such oppression at a variety of levels. For instance, Periyannan, who is a Dalit male and the main antagonist of the novel, treats every woman as his slave and gives inhuman treatment to all female characters. He ill-treats not only his wife, daughter, and mistresses but even also his mother. It further points out how Sivakami herself being a Dalit exposes the patriarchal dominance of some male Dalit leaders who exploit not only the women of their own caste but also some poor high-caste women like Lakshmi which is mostly ignored by the critics so far. It further highlights the elements of dowry and the patriarchal notion of marriage as an institution as depicted by Sivakami through her main protagonist, Anandhayi and her daughter Dhannam who is tortured by her husband for dowry.

b. Geetanjali Shree

Tirohit (2001) by Geetanjali Shree in Hindi was translated in 2013 by Rahul Soni entitled *The Roof Beneath their Feet*. Her other works include *Mai*, *Tirohit*, *Hamara Sheher*, *Us Baras*, *Khali Jagah* and *Between Two Extremes: An Intellectual Biography of Premchand*. Her novel *Khali Jagah* was translated into Urdu in Pakistan and then into English. *Mai* was nominated for the "Hutch-Crossword Translation Award" in 2000 for its English translation. For her contribution to Hindi literature, she has won the "Indu Sharma Katha Sammaan", the "Hindi Akademi Sahityakar Sammaan", and

the “Dwijdev Sammaan”. Geetanjali Shree has also received attention from scholars and critics for her works.

In the essay “Geetanjali Shree and Daisy Rockwell on Translation” published in *The New York Times* on June 18, 2023, Geetanjali Shree asserts a writer and a translator are equal as “Every writer is necessarily a translator. She articulates — translates into words — that inchoate, amorphous pre-word which jostles within her for expression. The translator, similarly, is also a writer.” She further adds, “At times our two identities merged in some kind of erosion of egos, but not fully — never fully! We always made it somewhere worthwhile. The writer, a translator, and the translator, a writer.” In the same essay, Daisy Rockwell also opines, “We think of translation as a set of binaries — a journey between two texts, two languages, two writers, two places — but in actuality, it is a continuum between these points. Loss is the immediate outcome, and discovery occurs over the long term. Where does Geetanjali stop, and where do I begin? Are we one author, or two?”

Kamle Balika Ramrao in her PhD thesis *Geetanjali Shri Ke Kathasahitya Ka Anushilan* (2020) points out the feministic approach of Geetanjali Shree and asserts her novels boldly shows the struggle women have to face in the male-dominated culture prevailing in the interior middle-class societies of India (213). Vibha Purohit in her PhD thesis *Geetanjali Shree Ke Katha Sahitya Ka Vivechanatmak Adhyayan* (2019) finds out that Geetanjali Shree is an independent woman and she always advocates self-identity for every woman. Therefore, her literature also represents women as carving for freedom and thus struggling against the age-old patriarchal tradition. Women are just hanging in between their traditional binding to the patriarchal customs and on the other hand, they are in search of respect and equality in the male-dominated society. A similar struggle is also prevalent in Shree’s *The Roof Beneath their Feet* (253).

Arunava Sinha in his book review (2013) of Geetanjali's *The Roof Beneath their Feet* expresses, “[Her] characters demolish external expectations to stake a claim to life on their own terms” as, “the relationship between Chachcho and Lalna takes them into a story they build for themselves, empowering them to get away from their respective tyrannies into something that makes life a little more colourful.” He also praises the translation of Geetanjali Shree's *Tirohit* by Rahul Soni and asserts, “These are novels in translation, a fact sometimes easy to forget because of the facility of the English versions. Rahul Soni in Shree's case and Vasudha Dalmia in Sobti remain unobtrusive and faithful to the watercolour words in the originals, happily avoiding the earthiness that English often injects into prose.”

Mridula Garg in “Intervention of Women's Writing in Making of Literature” (2013) has just listed Geetanjali Shree among the Hindi writers who are still writing on the theme of motherhood in Hindi literature in India. In this article, Garg differentiates between the Indian Feminist writers and western feminists. She asserts, “The concept of *dwitya* had a far-reaching influence on the attitude of Indian women writers to motherhood. Unlike feminists in France, most Hindi women novelists did not seriously reject motherhood for a significant time” (185). She further opines, “A large part of feminist writing saw motherhood as an essential part of womanhood. But there was a dissenting factor within it. It lay in recognizing that the uniqueness of motherhood lay in its empowering a woman with the capacity to nourish and keep alive another human being, without external material support” (185).

In an interview published in, *The Caravan* (2011), Geetanjali Shree gives valuable insights about her novel and asserts, “*Tirohit* (2001), owed its inspiration to something as pedestrian...The walls of the houses below kept respectable, conservative

middle-class life contained within them, but once you escaped to the top—having only the sky above and the roof beneath you—what rules could not be broken? What barriers remained?” *Tirohit* is a story of love between two women and their flight into freedom from class and gender exploitation, from the tyranny of societal expectations and obligations, and from various inherited and enforced inhibitions.

Kuhu Chanana in “Plurality of Lesbian Existence in Modern Indian Writers: Manju Kapur, Rajkamal Chaudhary and Geetanjali Shree” (2010) questions the patriarchal objection of the lesbian relationship between Chachcho and Lalna in her novel *Tirohit*. The novel “reveals the complicated layers of patriarchal oppression regarding lesbian invisibility, compulsive heterosexuality, lesbian motherhood, sexual oppression within marriage and class dynamics in homoerotic passion. The novel is remarkable for its depiction of the system of patriarchal domination buttressed by the subjugation of women through heterosexuality” (Chanana 192). She further asserts that Geetanjali Shree uses the theme of lesbianism to challenge the patriarchal subjugation of women in society. Therefore, she has portrayed such characters to rebel openly against the biased patriarchal treatment of women.

It emerges from the above reviews that only a few critics/scholars have commented upon the works of Geetanjali Shree. There are two PhD theses based on her works but only in Hindi literature. So there is no extensive research available on this Booker prize-winning author whose works deserve some detailed exploration. The harmonious relationship between Chachcho and Lalna is central to this novel that needs to dwell in detail. Women suffocating in the clutches of patriarchy and carving for freedom are also some of the underlying themes of this novel. Therefore, the present study explores lesbian relationship between Chachcho and Lalna; the suffering of a

middle-class woman and her desire to live freely in a male-dominated society and the rebelliousness of an exploited woman in detail. The role of class in a patriarchal society also needs to traverse in the context of the select novel.

c. Arupa Patangia Kalita

Felanee (2003) was originally written by Arupa Patangia Kalita in Assamese and translated by Deepika Phukan in English as *The Story of Felanee* (2011). Arupa Patangia Kalita, a scholar, author, and short story writer, finds inspiration in her homeland. Patangia is a passionate recorder of socio-political happenings in her homeland, having spent most of her life teaching English in Assam. Assam is a constantly changing site for Patangia due to complex human and material links. In her research, Savi Khera (2021) opines, “The relegation and confinement of women to the domestic sphere in the Northeast has the sanction of age-old traditions and customs prevalent among the different communities. The assumption that the burden of patriarchy is perhaps less oppressive in the Northeastern region is debunked as...the region too is rooted in a patriarchal social structure” (170).

Dr. Jayanta Madhab Tamuly in “The Insane Women- A Trauma Reading of *Felanee*,” (2021) analyses trauma in Arupa Patangia Kalita's *The Story of Felanee*. It investigates how trauma defines and develops specific literary characters. Trauma isn't the main focus of *Felanee*, but it has a big influence on the tale and the characters, especially women. He points out that all women are typically victims of abuse and trauma. This article examines the traumas that shaped the novel's protagonists. Dr Jayant Tamuly points out, “In *Felanee*, the novelist portrays a moving picture of traumatized characters borne out of physical, psychological and structural violence. Felanee, the central character of the novel, is a perfect example of post-traumatic stress

disorder” (2). He further says, “In a wider perspective, such reading can also be used to illustrate how violence and trauma engender a new trajectory in the field of fictional production by Assamese writers” (4).

In an article, Shiva Prasad Sharma points out the struggle and issues faced by females for survival during ethnic violence as depicted by Arupa Pathangia Kalita in her *Felanee* (2003) and *Written in Tears* (2015). About *Felanee*, Sharma in an article written in 2020 opines:

The novel . . . raises the rather vexed problem of the definition of insider/outsider, is space/location exclusive to the majority. Who speaks? For whom? About what? Can someone be really inside and outside, observer and participant of events unfolding in a contentious space at the same time? . . . The Assam movement therefore for *Felanee* as well as others living in the refugee camp is not a step towards fulfilment of the illusion of ‘golden Assam’ but an exercise into self-destruction. (11020)

He further asserts, “Violence and its impact on the lives of common individuals ends with the image of . . . women who have lost not only their families but also a part of their existence which resuscitates the river bank points towards an appropriation of the physical space marred by violence with their strong zeal for survival” (Sharma 11024). Sharma in his book review (2020) on *Written in Tears* opines, “In the space called Assam, the term secret-killing symbolizes the dark periods of its political history. The term terrorized and tormented the people of Assam for four years between 1998 and 2001 . . . Women became widows, parents lost their sons, sons their fathers and many sisters and brothers could never see their siblings again” (11026).

Basumatary and Rao in “The Days of Trial: Textualization of Conflicts in Arupa Patangia Kalita’s *–The Story of Felanee*” (2020) point out the political and ethnic conflicts in Assam during the 1970s. They also highlight the struggle of Felanee to sustain herself and her son amid such bloodshed after losing her loving husband and home (16-18). Deepshika asserts, “Since identity concerns both self-identity and social identity, the marginalized women in the novels *Ayananta (Dawn)* and *Felanee*, attempt to bring changes in their gender roles and identities, resisting and challenging patriarchal domination and victimization; thus establishing gender values in the society” (188).

Sultana in “Writing Conflict, Writing Gender: Looking at Two Assamese Novels” (2017) expresses that the callousness and utter disregard for human life, the ugly play for power, for electoral gain, the sham and petty hypocrisies, and the bloody horror of ethnic violence all lie exposed in this powerful novel written by one of Assam’s leading fiction writers. Hemjyoti Medhi in “Gender and Identity Politics: Arupa Patangia Kalita's *Felanee (The Story of Felanee)* and Rita Chowdhury's *Ei Samay Sei Samay*” (2016) points out how a woman has to struggle for identity and to sustain her family during the ethnic moments in Assam when women and children, in particular, were at the receiving end due to socio-political outbreak of riots in the state. “Women’s collective survival remains central to the *Felanee* story; how women sustained themselves and their families, taking care to feed and fight if necessary” (51). He also observes Felanee’s dilemma over her identity and survival as she introspects, “What shall she wear? What would she take? Baishya had asked her to remove the shakha-pola if she wanted to be alive. Bulen says she must wear the dokhna if she wants to live. The young men with guns have warned her against mixing with outsiders. How shall she live?” (50).

Mompi Choudhury in “Violence and Marginalization of Women in Arupa Patangia Kalita’s *The Story of Felanee*” (2014) expresses her concerns over violence and marginalization of women in Indian societies. She opines that the novel is based on real-life events. It is a story of courage, survival, ethnic conflict and violence that tears people and communities apart in the most brutal, savage way. Set in Assam, which has seen two major agitations that have crippled the economy, this is a story that will shock the reader with its sheer passion and brutal honesty. Mompi opines, “During the emergency, the entire state became a conflict region with making no distinctions between private and public. Homes raided and people were killed, some became homeless or were traumatized with fear which caused a great loss of livelihoods and less economic prosperity” (570). She further asserts:

Keeping violence and conflicts in the background, Arupa Patangia Kalita in her novel documents the life, experiences and personal loss of her protagonist ‘Felanee’ meaning trash or “to be thrown away”. Throughout the novel, the writer involves the fortune of a group of displaced women who are directed from fear, violence and marginalization to an atmosphere of empathy, sisterhood and self-discovery that comfort, provide security, stability of mind as well as healing. (570-71)

It emerges from the above reviews that Kalita’s works demonstrate trauma suffered by a woman due to the violence during war and ethnic riots as her novel *Felanee* is based on the incidents of ‘The Assam Movement’ during the late 1970s and early 80s. This movement in Assam was evoked due to the illegal immigration of people from West Bengal and Bangladesh in Assam which resulted in ethnic agitation, cultural conflicts and revolt against Bengalis. The main protagonist’s multi-ethnic

identity is the root cause of her sufferings in the novel which needs to be dwelling in detail. The novel tries to problematize the 'Assamese Movement' by posing a challenge through the character of Felanee who happens to be a part of Assam by virtue of her marriage to an Assamese husband. Such characters become victims of a movement which is the cause of ethnic boundaries. Not only was the class of the individuals but also the varied cultural lineages of people living in Assam were the root cause of the riots. The novel negotiates the problem of extremist's clash between the so-called Assamese people and the Bengali immigrants. Tribal politics, emotional displacement and homelessness are also some of the prominent aspects of the novel which need to be traversed at length. Therefore, the identity issue for Felanee is the main theme of the novel which needs to be explored in detail through the various incidents depicted in the novel.

d. Ila Arab Mehta

Vaad (2011) was originally written in Gujarati and translated into English as *Fence* by Rita Kothari in 2015. Ila Arab Mehta has received a number of awards and is one of Gujarat's most famous writers. She has numerous collections of short stories and many novels. Her most famous works of feminist thought in the literary world of Gujarat are *Batris Putlini Vedano* and *Paanch Pagla Prithvi Par*. At the Indian Institute of Engineering in Gandhinagar Rita Kothari is an author, translator and professor affiliated with the Department of Humanities. She has written *The Burden of Refuge* (2009) which is a study of the Sindhi partition experience and translated many works of Gujarati into English,. In a book review on *Feminism in India* (2016), Poulomi Pal highlights the views of Mehta when she asserts:

No matter how much the situation might have changed (or not) in terms of women's property holding rights, nothing takes away the fact of deprivation and marginalization women still face across the world. Even today, renting a house if you are a single woman and trying to have an independent life is difficult, unless of course you can negotiate with your financial prowess. . . . And imagine if you are a woman who belongs to a minority or marginalized community, who wants to stay in a cosmopolitan, believing in the same democratic and constitutional rights of equality and equity? Will it be easy?

Mehta further adds, "Fence seems so real to me. It is something I can understand and relate to very well and so can anyone else; be it the women leading the "Pinjra Tod" Campaign, where they believe that no one has the right to dictate a moral code to them" (qtd. in Pal).

In a book review (2016), Sudhagee points out, "The underlying theme of *Fence* is Fateema's search for a place to call her own. It is also a search for her identity and her wish to be a part of larger society by breaking barriers or fences that exist between communities without losing her own identity." Nilanjana S Roy in "Translations: Ila Arab Mehta, Ismat Chughtai, Arupa Patangia Kalita" (2015) opines, "The saddest part of *Fence* is not that the prejudices Mehta sketches so expertly are true; it is that the compassion, trust and practical assistance Fateema receives from strangers, friends and even the police ring slightly hollow." Nipam Chauhan in a comparative study of Afro-American and Gujrati novelists (2015) asserts, "Being a feminist writer Ila Arab Mehta, advocates for women emancipation. She believes in equal nurturing of sons and daughters and believes that man and woman should have equal rights and respect in society, as both are human beings" (138).

Rita Kothari in “*Fence*, Translated From Gujarati” (2014) observes, “Ila Arab Mehta’s moving and sharply observed novel follows one woman’s struggle to find her way in a world torn by communal violence, to reconcile her conflicting loyalties to her family and friends, to find a place that she can ultimately call ‘home.’” The reader wishes he or she could read *Fence*, Rita Kothari's English translation of Ila Arab Mehta's Gujarati novel *Vaad* (2011), in one sitting because of the influence of recommendation as well as the economy of phrases, a compassionate depiction of a brave central character, an informative enunciation of Islam, and the taut framework of the storyline.

It emerges from the above reviews that Mehta's works are seen as a woman’s struggle for freedom, equal rights and self-identity in a male-dominated society. But there are also other aspects like discrimination of women in Muslim religion and the same has been depicted by Mehta in her novel *Fence*. Most of the critics have ignored this aspect of the novel which is the main aspect of the main protagonist’s sufferings in the novel. Especially her brother and his friend who are the main instruments of Islamic dominance try to suppress Fateema and keep her under their control. Further, the novel is trying to dismantle the barriers, which the writer has named as ‘Vaad,’ created by societies on the basis of religion. Other than these issues, the present study explores the aspects like a woman’s struggle to be self-reliant, her self-belief and the role of education in her empowerment in detail. The present study also probes an inquiry that most of the reviewers have missed pointing out that Illa Arab Mehta being a Hindu has chosen to write about a Muslim girl and her life. The question here is whether is it appropriate for an outsider, in this instance a Hindu writer, to comment upon the cultural practices of Muslim religion which Muslims regard as a part of their cultural identity. For example, in this novel through her character Fateema, Mehta tries to oppose the compulsion of wearing ‘burkha’ for all women in Muslim culture.

e. K. R. Meera

Aarachaar (2012) was originally written in Malayalam by K. R. Meera and translated by J. Devika as *Hangwoman* in 2016. K. R. Meera is a famous Malayalam writer and English essayist who have written four novels, five novellas, six collections, two children's books and two essay series. She has received all major literary prizes in Malayalam such as the Kendra Sahitya Akademi award, the Kerala Sahitya Akademi award, the Vayalar award and the Odakuzhal award. Her translation works include *Hangwoman*, *The Poison of Love*, *The Unseeming Idol of Light*, *Yellow* and *The Gospel of Yudas*. K. R. Meera's works, especially her novel *Hangwoman* are praised by many scholars and critics.

K. R. Meera, in her interview with Akshaya Pillai in 2022, opines, “They say a woman isn't born, she is made. I feel the same way about feminists. And I don't want to write for feminists. I write with the hope that my book will convert readers into feminists.” Similar assertiveness comes out of her characters as Febi Abraham in “Paradigm of Perseverance: Trauma Theory and Feminism in K. R. Meera's ‘Arachaar’ in Comparison with the Malayalam Movie ‘KannezhuthiPottumThottu’” (2022) points out, “how the binary oppositions and the patriarchal clutches are broken by the protagonists Chetna and Bhadra to gratify their revenge and to prove themselves by emerging as a phoenix out of the traumatic experiences that they had to endure” (453).

Dr. K. Mini highlights the negative face of media in contemporary times and in “Influence of Media in *Hangwoman*” (2021) he asserts, “It's not the duty of the media to look with closed eyes at what needs to be exposed and give more importance to what is triflin . . . The media in the novel focuses on the collection of news in order to upsurge ratings rather than social issues. Readers glimpse the corporate-minded

channel media and journalists like Sanjeev Kumar Mitra” (299). Nistha Pandey in “Reading K.R. Meera’s *Hangwoman* as a Critique of Biopolitical Control” (2020) opines, “The roles of women in Meera’s novel are intimately tied to the terrible reality of the brothels in Sonagachi as well as . . . examines *Hangwoman* as a critique of the patriarchal homo-social economy of exchange in India which does not allow women to embody non-gestational, non-objectified forms of power” (54).

Hareesh K. G. and Sreenath Muraleedharan K. in “Evolved Femininity: An analysis on K R Meera’s Novel *Aarachar*” (2019) expresses, “The challenging quest starts with the title *Aarachar* itself, denotes the ‘hangman’ in Malayalam which did not even have a feminine counter word” (197). Reshma Jose in “Noose around the Noose Maker - A Study of Media-Cannibalism in K R Meera’s *Hangwoman*” (2019) points out the selfishness of media and its insensitivity towards social issues when she exposes, “the exploitative sensationalism of present day Indian media, which thoughtlessly perceives personal experience as a mere subject of news value. In a disturbing age of hyper-reality and manipulative commercialism of the postmodern visual media, the seemingly terrifying expression ‘media cannibalism’ would not be an overstatement” (980).

V. P. Prasaga in “Traversing the Feminine: A Postmodern Feminist Reading of *Hangwoman*” (2019) opines, “The novel can be grouped under the rubric of postmodern feminism, where the novelist questions the notion of gender and attacks the dichotomy of femininity and masculinity” (143). A. K. Ajeesh and R. Pranesh Kumar Hari (2019) in “Translation, Culture and the Loss of Meaning in K. R. Meera’s *Aarachar*” are of the view that the language used by Meera in this novel is not the same as it is used in the cultural context of Bengal. As the novelist belongs to Kerala, therefore, there are cultural issues while writing the story in Malayalam (4072).

Athira Radhakrishnan in “Countering Power: The Politics of Realignment in *The Hangwoman*” (2018) asserts, “The novel arranges the inspired counter discourses through the play of binaries. . . . One of the strange combinations is the manner in which she connects love and death. . . . The structure thus evolved gains its co-existence with power through its relation to inadvertently opposing images” (9). M. G. Hari in “Negotiation of Identity in K. R. Meera’s *Hangwoman*” published in *Rupkatha* (2017) expresses that “the trajectory of the evolution of Chetna’s character with a lot of psychological insight. She moves from a woman who is not very different from a gendered subject in India to an authentic human being who is resourceful enough to act and speak without the fetters of her highly controlled social identity” (248).

Similarly, Harsha in his book review (2015) of *Hangwoman* observes, “The novel reads like a legend, with the narrative constantly switching between past and present, recounting tales from the centuries-long history and myths surrounding the Mallick family. It is also the story of the sheer power and defiance of a woman in a man’s world and in front of his pride.” Shruti Rao in her book review (2014) praises Meera’s technique of narration in *Hangwoman* and opines, “The intensity of this book is sometimes overwhelming. But even when you feel you cannot bear to read another word, you just cannot set the book aside. Borrowing a metaphor from the novel, reading the book felt like I’d been subjected to the hangman’s noose myself. . . . I was breathless, and felt like the life was sucked out of me. Yet, it was deeply satisfying.”

Similarly, Zafar Anjum in his book review (2014) also comments upon Meera’s storytelling style and points out, “the continued influence of the past in present-day events; of fate and heritage, and the individual’s capability to rise above circumstances and make one’s unique impact; the conflicting facets of man-woman relationships; the

author examines all this and more in the course of a fascinating narrative.” About the plot structure of *Hangwoman*, Abhirami Sriram in a book review in *India Today* in 2014 is of the view, “For all its complex twists and turns of plot, the true genius of *Hangwoman* lies in its denouement and the swift insouciance with which K. R. Meera . . . conspire to pull the lever on the reader on the very last page.” In a review article published in *The Indian Express* in 2014, Samantak Das is of the view, “K. R. Meera borrows liberally from the myth and mystique of the Dhananjoy hanging, the last in West Bengal, to frame the narrative of her *Hangwoman*, set in a contemporary Kolkata, where her protagonists carry the surname Grddha Mullick and where ‘Ma, mati, manush’ is a readily recognisable slogan.” However, *Hangwoman* is not just a fictional retelling of a sensational death sentence from a decade ago. It is a powerful and thought-provoking work that goes beyond the surface-level story and delves into deeper themes and issues.

It emerges from the above reviews that K. R. Meera’s *Hangwoman* is very popular among readers and commented upon by several critics. Some of the critics have explored translation issues, power politics, women's power and strength, and the insensitivity of media, while others have scrutinized historical angles to women's issues, binary opposition of trauma and feminism, biopolitical control etc. Postmodern feminism and the new identity of women which is the central theme of this novel have not so far been explored in detail. Therefore, the present study will explore at length the new woman identity in which Meera tries to excel through the depiction of her character Chetna who dismantles the barriers between masculinity and the stereotypical feminine the ‘weak’ tag imposed on women by patriarchal culture and society. Further, Chetna’s quest to be the ‘new woman’ in the male-dominated society where women are stereotyped as weak sex is taken up in detail.

Research Methodology

In view of the nature of the present study takes eclectic approach which is a combination of different methods and techniques. The select narratives belong to different cultures/states/languages and depict different aspects of women's discrimination in Indian rural areas, therefore, it would not be appropriate to follow any single approach. As the study focuses on the socio-cultural dynamics of women's oppression and their struggle against it, therefore, it adopts various methods like the qualitative method which is based on the close textual analysis of the five select translated novels and other secondary data available in the form of books, book chapters, scholarly articles and any other writings available on various websites, journals, libraries (online and offline) and academic research carried out by various research scholars in the field.

The research methodology further relies on theories advanced by feminism/gender studies, further supplemented by studies in cultural studies. As the present study is based on translated texts, therefore, it also dwells briefly on translation studies to explore the relevance of translation theories. It examines the role and need of translating Indian regional texts into English, the problems and solutions in the process of translation. Apart from translation studies, the role of cultural studies is also important since the proposed study compares and contrasts the struggle of women residing in different societies/cultures in India. Therefore, due to the varied nature and scope of the present study, the eclectic approach is more suitable to bring out various dimensions in the study of women characters.

CHAPTERIZATION

The present study is divided into five chapters. A brief overview is as follows:

Chapter I Introduction

The introductory chapter gives an overview of Indian literature concerning the portrayal of women in the male-dominated literature of India. The chapter gives a brief history of feminism and its impact on Indian writers with a special focus on Indian regional writers. The chapter focuses on the evolution, growth and developments in women's writing in India and the growth and evolution of Indian regional literatures. Further, the translation theories, their relevance, the role of politics in translation and difficulties in translation are also discussed. A detailed review of literature on select authors has been carried out in a chronological manner to establish research gap followed by giving chapterization.

Chapter II Role of Gender Inequalities in Select Narratives

The chapter entitled “Role of Gender Inequalities in Select Narratives” scrutinizes different aspects of gender inequality like gender discrimination, social stereotypes, mental and physical harassment, and patriarchal objectification of women as portrayed by select women writers. The chapter also discusses marriage as an institution, the problem of the dowry system in rural India as demonstrated in P. Sivakami's *The Taming of Women*, and the issues of inter-State/ inter-culture marriage as it happens in *Felanee* by Arupa Pathangia Kalita. Further, the chapter explores K. R. Meera's *Hangwoman* to see how she dismantles the masculine-feminine barriers as it is the root cause of gender inequality. The chapter also compares select novels to observe any similarities or differences in the experiences of women based on their language and culture.

Chapter III Role of Caste and Religion in Women's Subjugation

Chapter three dwells on how caste and religion contribute towards women's subjugation as depicted in the works of select women authors. P. Sivakami in *The Taming of Women* shows how the lower caste women are tortured physically and mentally. The writer exposes the power politics of some male Dalit leaders who misuses their power and money to oppress not only the women of their own caste but also the poor women of upper caste as well. Religion of an individual also plays a major role in women's sufferings as depicted in Ila Arab Mehta's *Fence*. The chapter further explores whether Mehta, being a Hindu, is right in appropriating the sufferings of a Muslim girl and how religion can operate as a socio-political weapon in a volatile State like Gujarat.

Chapter IV Representation of Women's Identity in Select Narratives

The fourth chapter titled "Representation of Women's Identity in Select Narratives" explores problem of women's identity in rural parts of India as depicted by select regional women writers. The chapter focuses on Anandhayi's identity as an oppressed Dalit woman under patriarchy. Geetanjali Shree portrays Chachcho and Lalna as lesbians in the story of *The Roof Beneath their Feet*. This aspect is discussed in detail to examine how Chachcho and Lalna oppose male-dominated society through their sexuality. The chapter dwells on the problem of a multi-ethnic identity of Felanee as depicted by Arupa in her novel. Felanee's struggle in her quest for identity in the multi-ethnic space is discussed in the light of the 'Assam Movement' which took place during the late 1970s and early 1980s. Further, the chapter discusses Ila Arab Mehta's *Fence* to show how a single Muslim woman struggles to own an independent house of her own to become a self-reliant woman in her quest for identity. The chapter also

discusses Chetna's struggle for identity to become 'a new woman' as portrayed by K. R. Meera in *Hangwoman*. It explores how Chetna dismantles/challenges the barriers between the masculine and the feminine.

Chapter V Conclusion

The concluding chapter recapitulates the issues raised in the chapters and identifies any differences/similarities in the experiences of women residing in different parts of rural India. Also, it collates whether the women in contemporary times still face similar problems or is there any positive change in their lived-experience in Indian regional societies.

CHAPTER II

ROLE OF GENDER INEQUALITIES IN SELECT NARRATIVES

The present chapter explores gender-based inequalities which are deeply rooted in Indian societies and the authors of select translated novels have described these inequalities through the female characters of their novels. The chapter's primary goal is to discuss the notions related to gender disparity at work in the Indian regional literature. It further explores the theme and the condition of women in Indian rural societies for the last few decades as depicted in select novels. For that matter, the selection of the novels has been confined to the last two decades only. The first in the selection, *The Taming of Women*, originally comes from Tamil Nadu and was written in 1992 (translated into English in 2006). The last in the selection, *Hangwoman*, is originally from Kerala and was written in 2012 (translated into English in 2016). *The Roof Beneath Their Feet* (2013) by Geetanjali Shree (originally in Hindi in 2001), *The Story of Felanee* (2011) by Arupa Patangia Kalita (originally in Assamese in 2003) and *Fence* (2015) by Ila Arab Mehta (originally written in Gujarati in 2011) also explores similar issues.

The chapter dwells on the various aspects of gender inequality like gender discrimination, patriarchal objectification, social stereotyping of sexes, physical and psychological trauma, marriage as an institution, restricted education to girls, etc. as portrayed by the select novelists in their respective works. The present chapter examines the progress in the condition of women residing in different states/cultures/regions in Indian rural societies over the last two decades through a scrutiny of women protagonists portrayed by the select women writers in their respective works.

The Taming of Women and *The Roof Beneath their Feet* explore gender discrimination, stereotypes, and marriage as an institution. Gender discrimination and the restricted education for Muslim girls are discussed in *Fence*. In *The Story of Felanee*, Kalita points out the gender discrimination and physical and psychological trauma faced by women. K. R. Meera discusses gender discrimination, patriarchal stereotyping of sexes, objectification and psychological trauma of women in *Hangwoman*.

Gender inequality is a deeply rooted issue in Indian society. Women have long been subjected to discrimination and stereotyping, and have been denied access to education and other opportunities. However, there have also been efforts to address these issues and promote gender equality. The Indian government has implemented policies and programs to empower women and promote their rights. Additionally, many organizations and activists are working to raise awareness about gender-based discrimination and advocate change. While there is still much work to be done, there has been progress in recent years towards achieving gender equality in India.

Both feminism and gender studies are important in addressing the issue of gender inequality and promoting gender equity. While feminism focuses more on activism and social change, gender studies provide a theoretical framework for understanding the complex ways in which gender operates in society. Together, these fields can help promote a more just and equitable world for all individuals, regardless of their gender identity or expression. The present chapter focuses on the complexities of gender in Indian rural societies as portrayed by the select female authors in their respective works, therefore, it is important here to evaluate the differences between feminism and gender studies.

Distinction between Feminism and Gender Studies

Feminism is a social, political, and cultural movement that seeks to achieve gender equality and dismantle systems of oppression based on gender. It aims to challenge and change traditional gender roles, stereotypes, and power dynamics that have historically disadvantaged women and other marginalized genders. Feminism advocates for equal opportunities, rights, and protections for women and other genders, and seeks to address issues such as reproductive rights, workplace discrimination, gender-based violence, and access to education and healthcare. The world's unfair treatment of women, as well as the later feminist movement, prepared the ground for the development of feminism. This philosophy aimed to strengthen women to the point where they could compete with males.

Feminism began as a reaction to violent male dominance and unfair subordination of women characters. It passionately advocates for similar gender, political, and constitutional issues, as well as economic issues for both men and women. Women's attempts to gain independence and self-identity sparked a worldwide movement, which critics and observers called 'liberalism.' Contemporary authors are still working to free the feminine world from the repressive socio-cultural restrictions and illusions in their various nations. This revolution has crossed the globe, bringing about a significant shift in the position of women everywhere.

The feminist movement began with Mary Wollstonecraft's 1792 publication of *A Vindication of the Rights of Woman*, which advocated equivalent privileges for women in the fields of learning, commerce, and politics. In his book *The Subjection of Women*, John Stuart Mill, a staunch male advocate of women's emancipation, expressed significant worry about women's subjugation (1869). He recognised the need for better

women's education and referred to women's subjugation as 'household enslavement' (Myles 1-2). Rekha Pande opines:

Any basic definition of Feminism or Feminisms can start with the assertion that at the centre of feminism is the concerns for women's subordinate status in society and with the discrimination encountered by women because of their sex. Furthermore, feminists call for changes in the social, economic, political or cultural order to reduce and eventually overcome this discrimination against women and creation of an equitable society in which gender justice is achieved. (2)

Therefore, many social, ethnic, and democratic organisations, ideologies, and ethical convictions that address gender inequality and egalitarian privileges for women are collectively referred to as feminism.

Gender studies, on the other hand, is an academic field that focuses on the social and cultural construction of gender and its intersections with other identity categories such as race, class, and sexuality. It examines how gender shapes people's experiences and identities, and how it intersects with other social structures to produce inequality and oppression. Gender studies draws on a range of disciplines, including sociology, psychology, anthropology, and literature, to explore the complex ways in which gender operates in society. It aims to deepen our understanding of gender and to use this knowledge to promote social justice and equality. "The early 1990s . . . saw the emergence of gender studies as an academic discipline" (Filipowicz 9) "that examines gender inequality, women's lived experience, sexuality, masculinity, and the interaction of gendered social processes with race, class, and other systems of inequality . . . in a range of fields including, anthropology, literature, history, geography, political science, and sociology" (Scarborough and Risman) at various institutions in India.

The extensive area of research known as gender studies looks at how physiological sexuality and gender preconceptions affect societal, cultural, and political perspectives towards females and males. Halina Filipowicz opines, “Because gender studies recognizes that men have historically held themselves to ideas of masculinity as unrealistic and coercive as anything they have imposed on women . . . is indispensable to the efforts to understand more completely how and why gender continues to be constructed in ways that perpetuate patriarchy and homophobia” (9). Gender studies offer a significant glimpse of the conceptual relevance in a context that makes one consider how studies of gender in this always-expanding population support the very centralised manner whereby males and females are examined in this cosmos. Since both men and women are important for the study of discourse, gender studies have traditionally been given priority. Whereas gender studies focuses on male's actions during women's history, women studies explores the history of women. Feminism begins to examine women's literature, whereas gender studies concentrates on how males shape and at times create women's literature.

“Feminist and queer theories have, if nothing else, taught us to be suspicious of the deterministic connections between the author's biological sex or sexual orientation and the constructions of gender in texts” (Filipowicz 14). However, “Gender studies asks what it means to make gender salient, bringing a critical eye to everything from labour conditions to healthcare access to popular culture. Gender is never isolated from other factors that determine someone's position in the world, such as sexuality, race, class, ability, religion, region of origin, citizenship status, life experiences, and access to resources” (Zaborskis). Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate the participant's interactions with the study's researchers from male and female perspectives to establish the theoretical foundation for gender, which is a distinct concept.

Gender studies cannot just rely on cultural differences but also take into account the social and political concepts which are also a basis of distinction between males and females in any region/society. As Brooke Ackerly and Jacqui True assert, “Studying politics and gender without feminism is akin to institutionalising democracy without women. We argue that it is not possible to understand the gender dynamics of politics without feminism” (259). However, gender studies can’t stand alone without the existence of the discipline of feminism. Gender studies is, therefore, one of the approaches to discover the discrimination against women in a multi-approach, political and theoretical discourse termed feminism. The next section gives a brief account of the conceptual framework of gender inequality in the context of Indian regional works of literature.

The Issue of Gender Inequality in Indian Women’s Narratives

One of the topics frequently covered by Indian mainstream and vernacular women writers to demonstrate their inventiveness is gender injustice. Gender is present in every aspect of our life. As Meenakshi Thapan says, “How gender is inscribed on the subject in everyday life both socially as well as through her own perceptions, desires and fantasies. It is in this sense that gender identity is truly, as Moore tells us, ‘both constructed and lived’” (32). It shows up in the way one acts and behaves, the clothing one wears, and the rules and beliefs one follows because “one is not born, but rather becomes, a woman” (Beauvoir 301). Gender is expressed in a variety of ways, including restrictions on women's productivity, childbearing, sexuality, and movement. Gender is intertwined with other socially selected populations that influence males' as well as women’s results.

The societal formation of masculinity and femininity sexuality is inextricably linked to women's roles in amusement and leisure. Gender disparity in men's and

women's sexual relationships reflects and sustains subjugation. Gender has a major impact on class and caste, as well as on ethnicity and tribe. In order to comprehend gender, one must consider its relationship to each of these factors, as they influence one another. Sangeeta Sharma points out that in her novels, "Deshpande proves that in the Indian Patriarchal system, a woman can survive only by negating her own personality. And this negation of her own personality makes her completely powerless in the patriarchal order" (169). Only a "few of the Indian contemporary writers, such as Arundhati Roy, Kamala Das, Sivakami, Bama, and Meena Kandasamy, state their anxieties pertinent with sexual orientation and politics in their writings" (Sinsinwar and Upadhyay 213).

Apart from the regional women writers, there are a number of renowned women writers from India who have written on the subject of gender discrimination in Indian societies. Anita Desai's *Cry, the Peacock*, Bharati Mukherjee's *Wife* (1975) and *The Tiger's Daughter* (1971), and Shashi Deshpande's *That Long Silence* (1989) etc. represent women's consciousness and discrimination at the hands of male-dominated Indian society. Rita Joshi's *The Awakening* written in 1992, Srividya Natarajan's *No Onions Nor Garlic* written in 2006, and Soma Das' *Sumthing of a Mocktale* written in 2007 are just a few examples of Indian Campus fiction in English authored by female writers that prominently shed light on the important aspect of the involvement of female's education in India in preserving/enforcing gender parity and enhancing the social status of women, in the context of their family, society and nation. Puja Chakraborty and Krishanu Adhikari assert:

Amulya Malladi's *The Mango Season* (2003), and Kavita Daswani's *The Village Bride of Beverly Hills* (2005) present such neoliberal and (trans)

national/cultural female subjects within the ever-dynamic contexts of a postcolonial nation, and also tend to analyze the perpetual ambivalence in patriarchy in acknowledging the individual choices/decisions of women in the purview of their marriage, evident enough in the post-liberal urban spaces of new India” (4).-

However, most of the mainstream English women writers have ignored the basic issues in their writings as faced by the rural women which have been depicted truly by the regional women writers in their language and culture. “As a reaction against mainstream Indian feminism that tended to ignore the problems of caste, Dalit women and those who advocate their cause have been making a valid case for Dalit feminism” (Sen 38). Chitra Mudgal, in her short stories like ‘Bhookh,’ ‘Lane’ etc., portrays women as social beings from the slums in Mumbai. Her women are struggling for social and economic equality in the male-dominated system.

Likewise, Manjul Bhagat in her novel *Anaro* depicts the issues of sexual harassment of women from slum areas in Mumbai. “Sexism, discrimination, a lack of opportunities afforded to women writers at the hands of male gatekeepers, who wield much power, are still very real issues that plague the world of Indian writing. . . . Before Simone de Beauvoir, we had Tarabai Shinde who fought against a male-dominated society through her work” (Deodhar). Mridula Garg is of the view that the portrayal of women by women is also sometimes seen as quite ironic and asserts, “When the women writers want to portray the complexities, intricacies, inequities, and incongruities of the socioeconomic or the value system, they choose men as their protagonists. They choose women protagonists only when they want to portray the complexities, inequities, or intricacies of personal relationships, family life, or sexual exploitation, both within and outside marriage (417).

This is also may be due to the psychological conditioning of the minds of the women writers in the patriarchy which confines men to outside household tasks and women in relations with men inside their home. As Kamalesh Kumar Mourya points out about the characters of the famous Hindi writer, Krishna Sobti:

Although she has audacious and daring women characters like Mitro, Balo and Ratti, she has largely depicted traditional, stereotypical, typically rural, husband and father obeying women characters in her novels. Unsteadily hovering on the threshold of conventionality and modernity, she successfully represents a whole generation of early women novelists and short-story writers of India. (110)

In the Vedic literature of India, women are depicted as the 'shakti' or the power source of the whole universe. They are given the status of Goddess Durga as the saviour of humanity from many demons like Mahishasura and Chand Munda. People worship Goddess Lakshmi and Saraswati as Goddesses of wealth and knowledge. Even in Indian epics like Ramayana and Mahabharata also women were treated with dignity. As Preeti Jha and Niti Nagar point out, "An Indian woman was in the position of high esteem and was pronounced by the word of maata (mother) or Devi (goddess) in the *Vedas* and *Upanishads*. Same as *Manu Smriti*, a woman was considered as a precious being and in the early Vedic age, girls were looked after with care" (48).

Women were also vested with freedom of choice and treated with respect. "Rigvedic verses suggest that the women married at a mature age and were probably free to select their husbands. Scriptures such as *Rigveda* and *Upanishads* mention several women sages and seers, notably Gargi and Maitery" (Rana 5). But the woman's condition has degraded so much in modern India. Their status was respectable during the Vedic period and "began to decline with *Smrities* (esp. *Manusmriti*) and with the

Islamic invasion of Babur and Mughal empire and later Christianity curtailing women's freedom and rights. The position of women in Indian society further deteriorated during the Medieval period” (Rana 6).

The people who worship Goddess Lakshmi and Saraswati ill-treat and exploit other women. As Sailen Das and Rubul Patgiri say, “In India women idols are worshipped as goddesses in temples and at home women in flesh and blood are beaten up by their husbands. While we have had a woman as the President of India, common women are struggling for a place in their family in decision making” (113). The highly ingrained patriarchal structure in Indian society is the main contributor to gender disparity. Mridula Garg opines, “Women revolutionaries, when portrayed by male writers, such as the great Bengali writers Rabindra Nath Tagore or Sarat Chandra Chatterji, were cast not as thinking leaders but as fighters under the leadership of men” (411).

Even *Anand Math* (1984) by Bankim Chandra Chatterjee also has males as chief protagonists. “Woman did retain her participatory character as a representative of her class, suffering class exploitation in the same manner as men in Premchand’s writing. . . . She was not the chief protagonist in novels such as *Godan*, *Premashram* or *Rangbhoomi*, which dealt with the ramifications of . . . exploitation in the rural-urban society” (Garg 411). Charu Gupta is of the view, “The paucity literature on women, however, still remains grave, especially in the context of modern Indian history. . . . The pattern of woman’s lives, their expectations and ideals, their orientation to social reality . . . considerably shaped by the models of womanly conduct set out in stories, legends” (88). There are “four images of women, emerging in Premchand’s stories: the ideal woman, the counter-model of woman, the suffering woman and one who protests” (Gupta 90).

Leela, in Premchand's short-story *Swarg Ki Devi*, is depicted as "the epitome of patience, sacrifice and forgiveness. She has an uneducated husband, a cheat for a father-in-law and a dominating mother-in-law . . . [and her] children die due to cholera. In this atmosphere, she accepts her fate without complaining . . . [and] preserves family by her unquestioning love" (Gupta 90). The purpose of such portrayal of women in literature is to restrict them only to such roles as Karuna Chanana in her essay argues that patriarchy in India wants to confine women only to domestic life and she further asserts, "Notwithstanding the accent on women's education, the gender role expectation of and about women continues to be that of a homemaker. This role definition has been internalized by even those women who have had access to modern education and to career opportunities" (76).

The condition of gender disparity is more adverse in rural India where women are not even allowed to do anything without the consent of their male counterparts. Moreover, females are not even allowed to go for higher education and the patriarchal thinkers force them into early premature marriages. Women are depicted in similar roles in the male-dominated literature in India. Therefore, Mridula Garg rightly asserts, "Generally, women play a secondary role in the male-dominated novels. They may be educated, enlightened, independent, . . . but they appear only in relationship to men" (418).

This traditional approach of stereotyping women in literature is challenged by feminist writers and they are portraying strong female characters who are fighting against gender inequality and presenting the issues faced by women in Indian regional societies. So about women's writing, she opines, "If by feminist writing we mean texts that project a unique world view different from the historically accepted world view of

men, then most writing by women in India cannot be called feminist” (Garg 418). In their novels, Indian women writers also depict women's issues but due to “the difference in the socio-cultural environment, the Indian women writers express themselves in different ways” (Rana 10).

With regard to concerns around what they should write, what is necessary, and what she accurately depicts on the topics of gender disparity and caste prejudice, Kandasamy adopts a distinctive stance that sets her apart from other regional authors in India who are also affected by otherness. A popular Hindi writer, Shivani, portrays her characters from the traditional higher-caste families who oppose discrimination in a lighter manner and there are no radical fights against it. Whereas Mannu Bhandari (Hindi) and R. Chudamani (Tamil) “candidly portray female characters who possess the same desires for freedom of sexual expression, economic independence, and human equality as their male partners” (Mani 21). Anuradha Sharma also opines, “Mannu Bhandari has contributed in providing a distinct dimension to the social and cultural picture of women in family and society. These discriminating socio-cultural values, attitudes and practices which cripple the personalities of the female psyche are highlighted in her stories” (574).

Amrita Pritam, a renowned Punjabi writer, has raised the issue of discrimination against women in Indian societies and she was mainly concerned with the economic dependence of women on men which she feels is the main cause of their problems. Therefore, “collective resistance to patriarchal domination, followed by the active re-assertion of female subjectivities through their claims of equality in terms of the financial, performative and other socio-cultural rights of women” (Chakraborty and Adhikari 3) is required from all women writers.

Various aspects of gender inequality prevail in Indian rural societies and act as a dominant theme for a number of women writers. Gender parity and other social issues “continue to be a major source of literary inspiration for writers of fiction in various Indian languages. In fact, it . . . is perhaps the most persistent theme in modern Indian fiction,” opines R. K. Gupta (302). Therefore, one can notice that the stereotypical images of women were being portrayed by most of the male writers who were ignoring the real issues faced by women residing in Indian rural societies. This is due to the dominance of patriarchal conditioning of the sexes in Indian societies which never let anyone see a male or female behave/live in a manner other than already coded for them by their culture and society.

It emerges from the discussion above that gender inequality in Indian rural societies is quite prevalent as depicted in literature by many Indian male writers. However, in most of the male-dominated Indian literature, a woman is depicted as a motherly figure who is selfless, caring, soft, piteous and emotional; as a devoted wife; and as a timid, caring and helping sister. They never highlight the real issues faced by women and always depict them as charming characters who are living happily under the control of men without questioning their dominance. They never question the socially constructed roles for men and women in society and always portrayed males and females as stated by the patriarchal power structure. Whereas, most of the female writers portray women as a victim of patriarchal culture, social stereotyping, gender discrimination and domestic violence. Moreover, in contemporary times, they portray such characters who do not only oppose male-dominated patriarchal notions but battle against discrimination quite courageously.

The present chapter explores various aspects of gender inequality like gender discrimination, social stereotypes, patriarchal objectification, marriage as an institution

etc. The purpose of the present chapter is to examine these gender disparities in the select novels written by Indian regional women writers and to investigate the status of women in Indian rural societies in the last two decades. It would be relevant here to discuss how various scholars and critics in the field have commented upon these aspects in the works of select authors in order to identify gaps in the research done so far.

R. Jayakumar and T. Deivasigamani observe the discrimination against women in Indian rural societies as depicted by Sivakami in *The Grip of Change* and *The Taming of Women*. They explore that the main protagonists of both novels undergo physical and sexual assault at the hands of a tyrannical man. They assert, “The men prefer to ‘possess’ a concubine or two to assert their ‘masculinity’ to teach a ‘lesson’ to their legally wedded wife, or simply because they lust after women, whether in the rural, agrarian milieu of *The Taming of Women* or the urban township bustling with political activism as in *The Grip of Change*” (6681)—likewise, Shanmathi. S., Raj and others in their articles observe gender discrimination in *The Taming of Women*.

Kamle Balika Ramrao and Vibha Purohit have explored feministic aspects in Geetanjali Shree’s short stories. Jayanta Madhab Tamuly analyses trauma in *The Story of Felanee*, Hemjyoti Medhi, Mompi Choudhury, Basumatary and Rao explore gender politics and ethnic violence in the novel. Arupa Pathangia Kalita’s short stories portray women in the socio-political and economic conditions in Assam. Kalita has depicted the social status of women in “*Chikar* from the collections of Moruyatra Aru Anyanya (1992) and *Prastavana* from the collection Morubhumit Menoka Aru Anyanya (1995). She has presented many aspects of problems of women, the social position of women in a patriarchal society and the struggles of women in society” (Handique 43). Some book reviews on *Fence* points out the gender discrimination in Islam.

Febi Abraham points out the psychological trauma and female objectification faced by the main protagonist Chetna in *Aarachar* by K. R. Meera. He explores “how the tormenting memories of the past actually break into giving a revelation of the power of the mind, by dissociating the thoughts from the consciousness and thereby gaining a willpower and determination to execute the vengeance” (c459). Hareesh K. G. and Sreenath Muraleedharan opine, “K. R. Meera’s novel *Aarachar* questions the basic distinction of men and women drawn by the codes and conventions of the society. By creating, a quantified table for analysing the features of society perceived male and female, it is easy to illustrate how much K. R. Meera has moved to break the rigid system” (197). A number of book reviews on *Hangwoman* by Meera also point out the issue of gender inequality in Indian rural societies.

The review of literature on select authors and their respective works shows that no exhaustive study has been taken up so far on these aspects of gender inequality by any critic/scholar. In a multilingual and multicultural country like India, such comparative research in the field of regional literature written by regional women writers in their respective regional languages exploring the real lived first-hand experiences of rural women would play a great role in the discourse of Indian feminism. Hence, the present study explores the status of women in Indian rural societies as depicted by regional women authors in their local languages over the last two decades.

Discrimination on the basis of Gender

Many Indian women regional writers highlight in their writings, women’s struggle to protect their dignity as well as how they are subjugated by patriarchal societies. Everywhere in the world, women’s dignity is always under question. Women are never

treated equal to men. Such discrimination is depicted by P. Sivakami in her novel *The Taming of Women*, which shows how the antagonist, who is the face of brutal patriarchy, discriminates against all women he deals with in his life whether it is his mother, his wife, his daughters or his mistresses.

In *The Taming of Women*, the issue of gender discrimination is explored through the female characters of the novel. The author portrays the patriarchal objectification of women and the social stereotypes of sexes in Indian rural societies. The female protagonist is subjected to physical and psychological trauma, and her agency is restricted due to her gender. The novel highlights the struggle of Dalit women in Indian societies to overcome the gender-based inequalities imposed upon them. The author's portrayal of gender discrimination in the novel provides insights into the complexities of gender in Indian rural societies.

The Taming of Women, a novel from Tamil Nadu, explores the theme of gender discrimination and the challenges faced by women in patriarchal societies. Gender discrimination is a pervasive issue in Tamil Nadu. Women are often subjected to social, economic, and political inequalities due to their gender. Despite various efforts to address this issue, discrimination against women continues to persist in many areas of Tamil Nadu. Women are often denied equal access to education, healthcare, and job opportunities. In addition, they are subjected to violence, harassment, and exploitation in both public and private spheres. Gita Wolf opines, "In Tamil Nadu, this connection of misogynistic popular culture with politics effectively reduces any alternative space for women" (71).

P. Sivakami depicts the hardships and sufferings of women and how they are oppressed by males in patriarchal Indian culture. The differences in upbringing

between the boys and girls in the novel are remarkable. Mani and Anbu have an overwhelming sense of belonging as they mature and are never held accountable for anything. They correct their sisters' behaviour even as teenage boys. Mani responds, "If I am not strict with her now, she will regret it in the future" (*TOW* 82). The youngest, Anbu, loses his temper quickly and is comforted by the remark that "his temper is just like his father's" (*TOW* 153) as if this were a positive thing. However, Arul, Dhanam, and Kala are raised with a feeling of enslavement and are taught that they are to blame for all things. Days after Kala reaches adulthood, Periyannan discovers her riding a bike. She is then thwacked by her father quite brutally. The female protagonists are treated as mere sexual objects by the tyrannical men. At the beginning of the novel, Anandhayi discovers the infidelity of her husband Periyannan who brings his mistress with him while she is in labour pains.

Periyannan even assaults her at that moment when she goes into labour to give birth to their baby. This demonstrates his inhuman treatment of his wife and he doesn't even care about her being pregnant. He doesn't even "come down at his newborn's cry, Anandhayi shut her tear-filled eyes" (*TOW* 5). Anandhayi's mind is cluttered with regrets, and she has lost her sense of calm. Anandhayi's mother-in-law interrogates her with empathy, "Why should a woman who's just given birth starve? So the husband went to a whore, uh! Still, why should you go hungry? Is he all that you have in your life? Don't you have your children, enough wealth? Acres of fields and cattle of your own? . . . After all, there are five children; can't she just wash her hands off him forever? (*TOW* 17).

The conversation shows that Periyannan treats Anandhayi just as a sexual tool to give birth to his children only and like many patriarchally conditioned males he feels

that she has no identity without him in society. Even if women are being treated like Anandhayi they cannot go away to live alone with their children as most of them are economically dependent upon men. “At least in India, a woman still needs the anchor of a husband and a family. Their dominating nature has led women to walk with their heads down” (Jha and Nagar 48). This is one of the reasons why Anandhayi is silently bearing the inhuman treatment of her husband towards her and further, the situation illustrates the patriarchal domination of males over females in Indian rural societies.

Geetanjali Shree, a novelist from Delhi, in *The Roof Beneath Their Feet* presents women as a thing that must always be kept inside the four walls of one’s home. They must not be given any freedom or privilege to go outside like men. If they do so then everyone looks at them with suspicious eyes as is the case of Lalna. Lalna herself asserts, ““Even if I’m in my bed, sleeping, they’ll say they saw me in someone’s lap or embracing someone else. Then why shouldn’t I do as I please?”” (*RBTF* 38). No one will ever raise a single question about a man but indulge in vulgar speculations if it were a woman. As Paresh says, “We’re men, we can do anything” (*RBTF* 62). Due to the old-fashioned traditional thinking of the people, they can’t digest if a woman does something that is always being done by a man.

Therefore, “When Lalna started driving Uncle’s scooter, no one was happy except Chachcho. Even I couldn’t help being angry when I saw her. She was making a mockery of us all” (*RBTF* 46). The main protagonist of the novel, Chachcho, suffers silently at the hands of her husband. She doesn’t utter a single word to him and keeps on doing her duties as a wife with utmost devotion as “the Indian woman has been trained to be self-effacing, subordinate, and obedient to males through many years of institutional and cultural conditioning, enabling her to suffer in silence as a victim of

patriarchy” (Duggal and Agarwal 284). The patriarchal culture stereotypes women from birth in such a manner that they just keep on bearing the suffering silently without making any complaints about it.

Svati P. Shah points out that during the Gujarat riots, “the role that sexual violence played in the execution and aftermath . . . and horrific stories of sexual violence during partition” shows how women become the centre of the target in such situations (33). Such issues of discrimination against women during ethnic riots in Assam are depicted by Arupa Pathangia Kalita in her novel, *The Story of Felanee*. The main protagonist of the novel, ‘Felanee’ or ‘Falani,’ which means ‘trash’ in English, is born during the 1960s when there was a lot of fire, gunfire, and death. She was tossed in a pond shortly after birth, yet she escaped, metaphorically implying that her life has been a struggle, but she must survive the pyre, find some peace, and follow a path of peace. During the unrest of the late 1970s, the novel depicts a comprehensive and effective connection between a group of exiled females that allows them to create new identities, solace, embrace, and endure their separated circumstances. Kali Boori, Felanee, Jon's mother, Minoti, Ratna's mother, Nabin, Jaggu, and others are a group of poor and helpless individuals with no information of their caste or creed who may have arrived as immigrants such as Felanee to establish a hamlet and integrate themselves into the larger Assamese community.

“Women empowerment and economic development are closely related: in one direction development alone can play a major role in driving down inequality between men and women; in the other direction, empowering women may benefit development” (Duflo 1051). In her novel, Arupa also emphasises women’s fight for income and existence, woman companionship, and solemn promise to one another while

acknowledging the social realities of the surroundings. Felanee escapes the violence and massacre, but she loses her spouse, unborn child, and home. She epitomises the position and status of females and triumphs over adversity; she gathers and embraces the females in her life, teaching them how to enjoy life through all degrees of struggle.

As Kali Boori asserts, “Women should be like the white chilli; small to look at, but the fire inside the mouth” (*SOF* 256). Kali Boori gives the example of Goddess Kali, who has complete influence over mankind, and Felanee has made it her life's aim to be alone in her sorrow and weep like a champion within without the aid of any man. Felanee creates a survival mechanism, accepting women's empowerment like Minoti, Mira's mother, Jon's mother, Ratna's mother, Sumola, Jaggu's wife, and bind people including the comment stream of the sisterhood who proceed to yearn for a family union and loving partner, thanks to this power within her.

Arupa Pathangia Kalita indirectly urges females to strive for economic survival and to conquer life's challenges. Felanee prepares puffed rice, whereas others go to the market to sell vegetables and beans. After the outbreak of riots, everything was destroyed so people, especially women, had to struggle for daily bread and butter. At the end of the novel, all the women characters after “remembering the work waiting to be done at home . . . started walking fast. The reeds had to be dried. The roofs had to be thatched” (*SOF* 312). This symbolises that after the bloodshed and destruction done by the males during ethnic riots, now women have to bring life back to normal.

“The constitution of India grants Muslim and other minorities equality of status opportunities with other citizens” and “the women's question today is no longer an issue confined to the position of women within the family, but also their right to equality” (Parveen 305). Fateema, the central character, of Ila Arab Mehta's *Fence* also

has to face a lot of discrimination at the hands of traditional thinkers like her own brother. Although her parents, especially her mother, were so kind and equally supportive to all their children whether males or females. When some of their relatives ordered Fateema to work in the house with her mother instead of reading books. Fateema's mother replies, "I don't need girls' labour. They will not be taking the cattle to graze. In fact, Fateema is learning English now!" (*Fence* 16). Therefore, it shows how much support Fateema gets from her mother for her studies and in fact, her mother is the real strength that Fateema has to fight against every odd in the way of her education.

But her brother, having a traditional patriarchal mindset, is against Fateema's higher education and asks his parents to marry her instead. His friend Anwar tries to misguide Fateema that colleges spoil girls, therefore, the girls must avoid going to college. One of Fateema's teachers praises her for becoming a teacher and says, "Muslim parents are particularly reluctant to send their daughters to school. A teacher like you, who is self-reliant, independent and fearless . . . would be a great role model for other girls" (*Fence* 108). Her brother Kereem even warns Fateema to wear a burkha when he asserts, "We intend to advise every family to make its women wear a burkha. You will also have to wear one" (*Fence* 122).

This shows how women are forced to do something which may be against their will and comfort. However, scholars and critics have different opinions over hijab as Inger Furseth points out, "On the one hand, many non-Muslim assume that women who wear the hijab are forced to do so, and some Western feminists contend that the hijab represents oppression and the subordination of Muslim women. . . . On the other hand, the proponents see it as a more complex matter related to identity" (365). But who

cares, if you are a woman then you must follow what the man of the house says without asking and thinking. This is what women are expected to do in most of Indian rural societies.

Discrimination against women is the result of long-standing disparities between males and females in many aspects of life. Gender discrimination takes on various dimensions and degrees depending on culture, politics, ethnicity, location, country, and economy. Gender inequality, on the other hand, is seen as a major impediment to development and as a contributing cause of aggression against females. As a result, women's rights are now a source of concern for global policymakers, owing to the need to increase economic growth while also ensuring the continuation of the development process. The current concern for gender equality in order to further the development process has a deep historical foundation.

For ages, women have been struggling for equality and K. R. Meera's *Hangwoman* depicts the same struggle for equality in the form of Chetna's quest to become the first female executioner of India. *Hangwoman* is a story set in Chitpur, Kolkata that deals with gender discrimination. Throughout the novel, the power dynamics of gender are a constant undertone. Chetna, the twenty-two-year-old daughter of eighty-eight-year-old Phanibhushan Grddha Mullick, a self-professed veteran of 451 hangings, is at the centre of *Hangwoman*. Chetna has inherited the protruding eyes that earned the Mullicks the moniker of Grddha, as well as the other inextricable shackles of their ancestry. She is a compulsive knoter of 'tiny but perfect' nooses at the ends of her torn old dupatta. The male-dominated society isn't ready to accept the fact that a woman can be strong enough to execute anyone's hanging. "Throughout history, male writers have portrayed and marginalized women as inferior and feeble in their works" (Duggal and Agarwal 283).

Gender discrimination is a significant issue in West Bengal, with women facing various forms of discrimination, violence, and oppression in both public and private spheres. The patriarchal system still dominates in many areas of West Bengal society, limiting women's access to education, employment opportunities, and political representation. Women often face harassment and assault on the streets and on public transport, and domestic violence is also a prevalent issue in the state. Chetna's wishes and opinions were not taken into account when it came to her schooling and marriage. It is evident from the statement Sanjeev Kumar makes to Chetna, "Your father's agreed to register the marriage as the earliest. . . . [and] given me his word that you'll be thrown out of your house if you don't cooperate!" (*Hangwoman* 275).

Men, on the other hand, have the luxury of owning things, which society has accepted as their right to claim and feel courageous enough to make their own choices. But "Women have been treated as second-class citizens from the very beginning of our civilization, and they have been denied equal rights, protections, opportunities, and political agency" (Duggal and Aggarwal 285). Therefore, Chetna is also reduced to a second-class citizen in the men's institutionalized customs. Chetna has been creating the note for posting from the day she was born, if not before. When she was still in her mother's womb, she made a noose out of the cord code. She even attempted and succeeded in making a noose out of her dupatta under duress.

Chetana has always been treated indifferently by her father Grddha Mullick for being a girl. Even if he wants her to be his successor, he feels she wouldn't be able to achieve anything without his help. He believes that women should be kept under males' control and that without a man, a woman is nothing. When Chetna tells him that she is willing to take on the role of the executioner by herself as he has also done it all by

himself. Grddha Mullick exclaims with pride, “‘Huh! Listen to that! Haven’t I been doing it alone! I am a man whereas you are a mere woman!’” He further brags, “‘The fact that you are a woman and hence have many limitations is the practically correct thing!’” (*Hangwoman* 396). As J. McGrigor Allan points out, “‘Woman is doubly entitled to man’s protection; not only as smaller and weaker than himself, but as being, on account of her sex, more or less always unwell’” (cxcix).

Therefore, everyone looks at Chetna as a weak female who won’t be able to perform the role of an executioner which requires a strong mind and body. She is being discriminated against even for having the desire to do a job which meant only for men as per the patriarchal culture and customs as Meera remarks, “‘Like the world outside, the jail too was a man’s world’” (62) and some patriarchal promoters advises her parents, “‘Chetna is a woman, she must get married and settle down to family life’” (*Hangwoman* 71). Therefore, discrimination based on gender is quite prevalent in Indian rural societies as depicted by the select women writers through the incidents that happen with their women protagonists. All the female characters face discrimination in their respective societies and even in their own families. Their indifferent treatment shows that Indian societies still discriminate against individuals on the basis of their gender and every single woman is ill-treated everywhere in rural regions of India.

Objectification and Representation

“Objectification—often loosely described as treating people as things—has long been a central concern of feminism (especially with respect to the treatment of women as things)” (Saul 45). In patriarchy, women are always objectified and represented as timid tools to fulfil the needs of men and take care of the family. “Scholars have long argued that women are denied a basic sense of humanness—are objectified—when focus

is directed toward their physical rather than mental qualities. . . . [Therefore,] a focus on the physical aspects of women by others causes women to be perceived like, and act like, objects lacking mind” (Heflick and Goldenberg 225). For conservative thinkers in patriarchy, women have always been objects, means of enjoyment, and objects of enslavement.

Most of the intellectuals who have addressed objectification have viewed it as morally dubious behaviour. This is especially true in debates about obscenity by feminists. Some feminist theorists have noted that women in our society are more recognized and connected with their physicality than males and that they are cherished more often for their appearance than males are (Bordo 143). So women are always under a lot of mental pressure to alter their physique and look in particular in order to be socially accepted or to adhere to the objectified appearance that prevailed at the time (Saul 144). All these things contribute negatively to the psyche of the women and they also start to think of themselves as a thing to be gazed upon and decorated.

In *The Taming of Women*, Anandhayi is married to a womaniser and she is expected to just bear his children as long as her body is fertile. However, her husband Periyannan objectified his wife as his slave with whom he can do whatever he likes. He is a tyrant in his handling of the females in his life, whether it is his wife, his concubine, his elderly and sick mother, his children, or the many other ladies for whom he has a voracious hunger. Periyannan tries to persuade Lakshmi to keep moving into his family dwelling even though his wife, Anandhayi, is in labour when his young son dies at home and he makes it hard to care for two families and handle his legal duties. “‘Saami . . .’ Let the slut come down and she will get it from me. She who has climbed up has to climb down” (*TOW* 4) Anandhayi assures herself.

It's also a depiction of the kind of misguided hate that females have for one another, a cultural and social dialectics in which the harshest prejudice and judgement come from other females (Beasley 34). Rather than directing her rage at her openly unfaithful husband, Anandhayi's rage is directed towards the females with whom he sleeps. Therefore, she blames only the women objectified as whores by society rather than her husband who brings the woman to his house. Females in the families are not considered safe even by the mothers as Anandhayi remarks, "Having a girl in the house is like having a fire in the belly. . . . I will have peace only when I hand her over to a husband" (*TOW* 108). Only she has to take care of her children and Periyannan just comes to Anandhayi whenever he has no option outside to feed his sexual desire. It shows how he just treats women as mere sexual objects to play with.

Periyannan is the ruler of everything he observes until he meets and is enthralled by Lakshmi's beauty, whom he brings home as his second wife. Lakshmi reinforces the stereotype of a poor lady who ends up as a concubine. She, like Nagamani and Thangam, is a childless widow. Several men have taken advantage of her body, the last of whom abandons her in a lodge. Her uterus has been injured as a consequence of her sexual abuse, and she is incapable of procreating. Periyannan is presented to her as a wealthy childless widower (he does, in reality, have a wife and six children) who is enamoured with her beauty and arranges for her to live in a house in the town apart from his family. He spoils her with clothing, jewellery, and vacations to a hill station. Lakshmi being born to a poor family enjoys living with Periyannan.

The wife is often referred to as the 'other lady' in *The Taming of Women*. While Periyannan has innumerable relations with sex workers, close cousins, and the nurse Muthakka, who comes to visit to assist his wife in the delivery of his fifth child,

Anandhayi remains caged by repetitive pregnancies, an incredible number of domestic chores, as well as collaborate at the far-flung family property, and is constantly exposed to harsh conflict by her husband. Periyannan even throws her to the floor, attacks her, and climbs the stairs to sleep with another lady while she is in labour. Periyannan exerts his patriarchal authority by committing numerous instances of violent aggression against all of the ladies in his home, including his elderly mother, teenage children, wife, and concubine. “At theoretical level, the reason . . . for domestic violence is male patriarchy in Indian society. Male patriarchy is . . . a system of male dominance legitimated within the family and the society through superior rights, privileges, authority and power” (Visaria 1742).

Periyannan torments Lakshmi’s body nearly every night, despite his affection for her. He is always insecure about her, won’t allow her to speak to anybody, and has violent sex with her regularly. While he is justified in inflicting abuse on his wife and pinning her down via repeated pregnancies, he locks his concubine up in a chamber, nicely equipped but shut off from physical interactions. Periyannan’s method for wielding control over females is to cage or keep a woman’s body prisoner, inflicting mental anguish. He doesn’t even spare his old mother if she tries to intervene as on one occasion when she questions, “Dey, Madman! Why are you hurting her? A blow landed on the old woman. Without a word she fell on the wall” (*TOW* 84). He never provides his wife with enough money to maintain the household while trading off portions of his property or mortgaging his residence to give Lakshmi extravagant presents.

Periyannan is wealthy, therefore he is unconcerned with Lakshmi's impoverished but upper-caste family. He slams a bundle of cash in her father's face and takes Lakshmi back to his home. Therefore, for him, a woman is just a sexual toy that

he can buy whenever he needs it. While motherhood binds Anandhayi, preventing her from even attempting suicide (she tries once but untangles the noose when she sees her newborn children resting at her feet), Lakshmi is bound to him by her financial needs. Lakshmi has to keep putting up with whatever tactics her lord uses to obtain satisfaction from her as a concubine.

She is relegated to nothing more than a body, a sexual product. This gives them immense pleasure when they see that all the women in the house are under their control. When Periyannan brings Lakshmi home he brags to her, “Anandhayi is a patient woman. She got married to me as a very young girl. She is scared of me and will not even squeak” (*TOW* 99). Although Anandhayi keeps putting up with Periyannan's violence because she is responsible for her children, his mistreatment of her has bred callous, violent behaviour in her children, who dread their father's power and see their mother as weak and therefore, disposable.

During one of his infrequent trips to the house, her father notices her reading. When he comes to know that the books are from a boy, he goes mad in rage and beats her up by asking, “Who gave you the guts to go and beg a man for books, eh? Has your mother let you loose to roam the streets?” (*TOW* 37). He spins around and smacks another daughter for eating undercooked rice before grabbing his wife's hair and slaps her by questioning her ways of raising the children (*TOW* 37). One day Mani sees Dhanam talking to a boy, Daniel, “he gave Dhanam a hard punch in the eye. . . . He dragged her to the cowshed and thrashed her under Peritannan's watch” (231). This is how women are being treated in their families by the males, therefore, women are just seen as objects at the hands of patriarchal males. Therefore, being a girl is a kind of sin in such narrow-minded families where the man wants to keep females under his sole

control. Men are allowed to do whatever they wish but women can't even talk to any male other than the family.

In *The Roof Beneath Their Feet*, Geetanjali Shree shows how Lalna has been objectified as a tool for pleasure by every male. "All they were interested in was Lalna – the magnet to which all their curiosity had attached itself" (8). They want her in their thoughts, dreams and arms at night and in the day, all ready to spit on her face and criticize her. As Lalna was poor and when her husband died, her father-in-law had "tried to force her into prostitution, which was why she ran away" (*RBTF* 7). No one in the Laburnam House, except Chachcho, sees her as human. Everyone just looks at her as an opportunity to fulfil their lust and as a tool of sexual objectification. According to the patriarchal representation of women, a good woman is one who like "Chachcho covered up more and more of her body. . . . Long, loose sleeves, coming down to her fingers. The pallu covering her head, down to her forehead, . . . face wrapped tight in her aanchal . . . [and] feet covered in shoes or lost under her saari" (*RBTF* 13).

Those like Lalna who defy these customary women stereotypes are condemned as "She came from nowhere. People like her belong nowhere. They get nowhere" (*RBTF* 153). Geetanjali Shree points out that as per patriarchal objectification of females, "A woman who can't be fathomed is no woman!" (*RBTF* 103) and "A woman's not a woman if she doesn't behave like one" (*RBTF* 71). And if "there are such women, . . . they must be held up as an example of what one would not become" (*RBTF* 141). Through the characters of Chachcho and Lalna, Geetanjali presents the two types of women representation as per patriarchal culture and customs as how they want a woman to be timid, silent, caring like Chachcho and not be rebellious, free minded and defying patriarchal stereotypes as Lalna.

In *The Story of Felanee*, Arupa uses the female characters to depict their personal life as well as their position at home and in the bedroom, where they are deemed less significant economically and have little control over their bodies. They are members of a disadvantaged minority that lacks a voice yet works hard for existence and financial nourishment, only to be punished with rape and brutality. Sumala is assaulted and mutilated till she dies. Her nude body showed evidence of brutality, “In place of her breasts there were two raw bleeding wounds. Her emaciated genital passage was a huge open wound” (SOF 246). This is how women’s bodies are seen and desired by the male-dominated society which sees women’s bodies as mere physical pleasure. Some frustrated men try to show their power over their wives as Jaggu “goes home and beats his wife!” (SOF 111). His wife cries, “My husband is out there enjoying himself with the whore. He puts the day’s hard-earned money in her hands, and comes home to beat me” (SOF 118). Therefore, the incidents show how males treat females as objects in their lives as per their needs. To fulfil their sexual desires, they go to whores and in order to satisfy their pride they used to beat their wives at home.

In *Fence*, Ila Arab Mehta points out that in the Muslim community, a woman is not allowed to come out of her house alone and without covering her face with a burkha. They are not allowed to keep any part of their body uncovered even in hot and humid conditions. Fateema becomes a self-reliant woman with her strong desire and good education and therefore, defies this custom of wearing a burka by saying that she will not become like such a woman who follows her husband’s steps and just has only one work which is to please her husband and having no intellect. That is the reason why their community does not allow women to study so that they may not become aware of their fundamental rights and can be used as an object or tool for fulfilling men’s desires and needs.

As Rajib Ali asserts, “girls in our quam shouldn’t be studying so much” (*Fence* 67). For the same reason, Kereem cautions Fateema to just complete her matric and then sit at home. Being uneducated they won’t be able to think beyond their home, husband and bearing as many children as their husband wants. In order to fulfil her dream to be self-reliant she knows that she has to defy these social stereotypes/roles as imposed on her psyche by patriarchy. One day she realizes, “If you wish to study and survive alone, you must also get used to travelling and eating alone” (*Fence* 111). Mehta depicts how females are being treated just as ornamental and usable objects by males in Indian societies.

Numerous studies have demonstrated that social media and the entertainment industry have a detrimental impact on young girls’ psychological well-being. Due to such social pressures, “women internalize people’s objectification of their bodies, resulting in them constantly criticizing their own bodies. Girls and women compulsively monitor their own body’s outward appearance. They become overly concerned about how others may perceive their physical appearance” (Sen). The social media and the entertainment industries like TV serials, Bollywood, Hollywood etc. also have stereotyped women negatively for ages, as Sen points out, “The roles, and behaviours of women in films, music videos and commercials are too stereotypical and a far cry from equality.

Along with objectifying women, glorified male masculinity, male dominance in media and mass media have deep impacts on shaping up a children’s mind” (Sen). The women who are even more skilful in some works than men and have achieved many feats still not be able to get the desired respect in people’s hearts. As Bartkey points out, “whatever else she [a woman may become, she is importantly a body designed to please or to excite” (80).

In *Hangwoman*, Sanjeev Kumar Mitra regards Chetna as a mere sexual object, and Grddha Mullick, who has no understanding of women's grandeur, represents the chauvinistic attitude of males. He has no regard for his wife or daughter. The idea of 'pativrata' has been emphasised through the figures of Chetna, her mother, and her grandmother. A modest female who is moralistic and has vowed to be a 'pativrata,' chaste female throughout her life is referred to as a 'pativrata.' The qualities of 'pathivrityam' look forward to her heart, mind, and soul being loyal. The fact that there is no male term for 'pativrata' is intriguing. This indicates that there is obvious discrimination based on gender. They were forced to use the terms despite the fact that they were recognized to be discriminatory in pronunciation, context, and concepts. When a woman claims she is proud of India's rich cultural 'pythrikan' (paternity), she is unaware that the term 'pythrikan' excludes her gender. Words like 'virgin,' 'whore,' and 'pativrata' are also anti-women (Ajeesh and Kumar 4073-74). It shows how women are objectified in different images by patriarchy.

Because of their need to survive, women's exceptional awakening increases their ego. Women have the ability to move into a new area and establish a new persona. Chetna completely ignores Sanjeev Mitra, who serves as a barrier, in order to pave the way for her real existence by putting a noose around his neck. Detachment from others and commitment to her real self provide a great foundation for the feminine in her to unleash her rejuvenating power. Chetna, on the other hand, prefers to be a hangwoman rather than a hangman's daughter. She transforms from an obedient, silent daughter to India's first hangwoman. Sanjeev Kumar Mitra, her fiancé, claims that she represents women's inherent power and morality and that he wants to marry her, but he is just interested in her as an item to use, a simple body to him. He firmly grasps her breast and casually declares, "I want to fuck you hard, even if only once!" (*Hangwoman* 27).

It shows how he approaches Chenta merely as a sexual object. On many occasions, as Meera points out in the novel, he behaves in a lustful manner with Chetna which signifies the patriarchal objectification of females in male-dominated societies. Chetna also remembers that once her father tries to fuck her mother even in public view. Such incidents show the thinking of men for women who see them as just sexual objects in a patriarchal culture which advocates men to be assertive and women to be submissive. Chetna's blossoming of her own femininity is both repelled and drawn to this crass approach since she has never experienced compassion or grace from the males in her life (Hari 245-48).

Unless their scenario is unbearable, each female in society tends to go with the flow. It is from the untamed men's environment that one emerges and discovers her true self. Women who are forced to face harsh realities discover their vigour and blossom out of requirement. Some voices within these inspire the suppressed femininity to spread her wings and fly. K. R Meera's novel *Hangwoman* is a scathing condemnation of society's harshness, double standards, and hypocritical attitude toward females. *Hangwoman* is more than just a novel with a unique plot structure that portrays a strong woman; it is a step against the subjective historical analysis of history as male-centred, a call to write 'her story,' and a dismantling of gender discrimination. It tears females from history's pages, considering that history has never done them justice, and hopes to correct that within this description.

Chetna emerges as one of the most powerful and resourceful female characters ever imagined in literature. She demonstrates that there is nothing a female cannot accomplish in this way. Kate Millett in *Sexual Politics* says "Female under patriarchy it is for the most part marginal residents if they are citizens at all" (25). She further adds,

“Their position is much like other minority, here characterised not as reliant on the numerical number of the group, but on its standing” (27).

The discussions show that sexual objectification and representation of women in Indian societies is very common as depicted in the select novels. In *The Taming of Women*, Anandhayi and Lakshmi are used as mere sexual objects by Periyannan. Geetanjali Shree depicts how Lalna is objectified as a characterless woman by all the people of the Laburnum society. In *Felanee*, Kalita's depiction of many women characters shows how women are seen as mere objects in the male-dominated patriarchal culture where a man can use his wife the way that suits him. *Hangwoman* shows how Sanjeev Kumar Mitra always gazes at Chetna with sensuous feelings and never treats her more than a low-class woman whom he can buy with money. Therefore, most of the female characters are presented as mere objects having no individual identity in the Indian rural societies which shows how patriarchy impacts the psyche of men to repress women and try to use them according to their needs.

Social Stereotypes

Throughout India, gender stereotypes come into practice as soon as people learn about the sex of the newborn. From that point itself, they start to assign the baby to masculine and feminine attributes. In literature and cinema, women are always associated with stereotypical femininity. Everywhere, “Female occupations are mostly traditional and less prestigious while the characters are predominantly introverted and passive in terms of personality traits. Women are also shown to be mostly involved in domestic and indoor activities while men have a higher presence in professional roles. Systematic underrepresentation of females is evident” (Islam and Asadullah 1) in literature and cinema.

Women in rural regions are always accustomed to live timidly and in a conservative manner as compared to men who can do whatever they like. Boys are always treated with special care in most of the Indian middle-class families. On the other hand, all men are conditioned since childhood to acquire masculine qualities without considering their true nature which creates a conflict in their character as Sivakumar and Manimekalai assert:

From a younger age, boys are taught that expressing sorrow/crying is not a trait of real men. The male child is conditioned not to express normal human feelings like fear, or sorrow and that is why the male mind has to banish the feelings of tenderness, rectitude, and sensitivity from his mindset, and create a defensive armour of audacity emanating estrangement, and loneliness. There begins his search for power and control to feel a sense of security. The race for power leads to the vicious circle of the inability to develop human relationships and then not realizing their worth. (430)

Therefore, such males develop a false/negative identity in which they end up dominating others especially women whom they find as an easy target. Males are expected to be assertive and forgo frailty, while females are expected to be caring and shun domination.

These traditional notions of male and female, as well as stereotypical gender conditioning of sexes, result in violence and discrimination when males try to dominate females and threaten their self-respect and personal rights. “The proportion of women to men in higher status positions is a key indicator of gender inequality prevailing in Indian organizations. This . . . traditional social and stereotypical role of women, as only the ‘caretaker’ for house and children and therefore women’s access to top

managerial jobs has remained severely restricted” (Punia 189). One of the barriers preventing girls from having equal opportunities to receive a high-quality education is the stereotypical notion that women’s roles are limited only to taking care of home and family.

It further has an impact on an individual’s own image and might even prevent some women from pursuing important positions in fields they think they can’t be successful even after having the necessary qualifications. Male-dominated literature is also full of such stereotypes of women in society as one of the postmodern feminists Elaine Showalter remarks while expressing the two modes of feminist criticism, “The first mode is . . . concerned with the feminist as reader, and it offers feminist readings of texts which consider the images and stereotypes of women in literature, the omissions and misconceptions about women in criticism, and women-as-sign in semiotic systems” (182).

Postmodern feminism holds that societal and cultural factors define sexuality, rather than biology. They contend that women have endured oppression not for the reason they are considered less powerful than men physiologically, but rather as a consequence of their political and cultural marginalization in a patriarchal society.

Teresa L. Ebertis of the view:

Patriarchy works through a double move that, on one hand, asserts and depends on binary oppositions of gender differences but, on the other hand, naturalizes these necessary differences as biological and thus the inevitable effect of ‘nature,’ thereby making them ‘unnoticeable’ and not in need of change. Woman, as feminist theorists, have repeatedly demonstrated, has thus been rendered the silent, invisible other in patriarchy; her ‘difference’ is both

nominally acknowledged and not deemed worth noting. In particular, her 'different' condition—the inequality, injustice, and oppression of women based on this difference is largely unseen. Patriarchy, in other words, feigns an 'indifference' to the very difference (woman/gender) on which its existence depends. (888)

Therefore, patriarchal societies always create a barrier between males and females on the basis of their physical strength labelled as masculine for males who are considered biologically strong and feminine for females who are considered weak. K. R. Meera through the portrayal of her character Chetna as a powerful woman in *Hangwoman* traverses this barrier. As V. P. Prasaja points out, "Female body has been employed as a commodity for the carnal gratification of male desires. . . . The inherent potential of a woman to resist domination and power relations is epitomized through . . . Chetna. By projecting the daring and determinant protagonist, the novelist is reversing the cultural images of women; the thereby investigating in the power of women" (143).

In terms of culture, the patriarchal legacy in India is complicated by society's contradictory stance towards women. She is admired as a mother while being mistreated as a daughter and wife. Simon de Beauvoir, in *The Second Sex*, aptly remarks, "One is not born, but rather becomes a woman" (301). Culture moulds her and forces her to conform to its expectations. This is what K. R. Meera expresses through the depiction of her main protagonist Chetna in *Hangwoman*. Chetna is born a human being, but her elders give her a feminine identity. Chetana was always treated differently by her father since she was a girl. Even if he desires her to be his heir as an executioner, he feels she wouldn't be able to achieve something like that without his help. He believes that women should seek refuge under males since, without a guy, a

woman is nothing. Phanibhushan says to Chetana as she declares her determination to take up the role of the executioner by herself, “Huh! Listen to that! Haven’t I been doing it alone! I am a man whereas you are a mere woman!” (*Hangwoman* 396).

Therefore, the gender of an individual is a socially constructed concept that has nothing to do with the sex of the individual. As Ramesh H. Patil remarks, “Society expects men and women to behave differently. In general, society has stated certain things about what a woman should do, how she should behave, mainly housework, cooking, child rearing are related to women, while men are expected to do hard work outside the family” (24). It is the patriarchal customs and traditions that expect both men and women to behave differently irrespective of their own nature. Society forces a woman to be timid and a man to be assertive.

The family, as the source of patriarchal behaviour, prepares the young to embrace sexually divided duties. Gender difference emerges at an early age; therefore, socio-cultural propaganda plays an important part in separating the female kid from the male child. As a girl gets older, she is subjected to gender prejudice and is unable to fully embrace her existence. Chetna as well as her brother used to roam in public as children, oblivious to social scrutiny. After she became an adult, however, the circumstances changed. As Chetna recalls her childhood, “When we were children, Ramu da and I used to run into the street to gather the hailstones. The last time it hailed, large hailstones fell which looked like tiles of the sky’s glass roof. By then I had grown up so I could only stand leaning against the wall, making a noose with my dupatta and watching them melt” (*Hangwoman* 2).

Chetna, who is raised by the patriarchal mouthpiece Phanibhushan Grddha Mullick, is isolated from the rest of society as well as restricted to her home. Chetna’s

father, Phanibhushan, used to manage and monitor her by putting all of his choices on her. Chetna struggles to establish her uniqueness by violating gender conventions, caught between socially conditioned preconceptions of bearers of culture as well as perpetuity. She is schooled and groomed to never say anything negative about her father. It is often believed that being feminine makes one look weak, useless, and meek. As Chetna's father once says, "The fact that you are a woman and hence have many limitations is the practically correct thing!" (*Hangwoman* 396).

Chetna, on the other hand, defies this concept. Any statement she makes is meant to detract from her femininity and beauty. She makes more firm judgments than a conventionally formed lady, and as a result, she stands out. She challenges the past, society, and moral principles in their entirety. By depicting Chetna as a competent practitioner of the gendered occupation of hanging, the writer challenges the prevalent idea that women are less competent. As a result, she became a global icon of power and self, "Miss Chetna Grddha Mullick, the first and only hangwoman of India!" (*Hangwoman* 427).

K. R. Meera has shown women's predicament in modern India. Even the simplest aspects of Kolkata have been brilliantly represented by the author. The red street of Sonagachi is represented all across the story. Meera imagines Sanjeev Kumar's mother, Trilokyadebi, as a prostitute. Chetana's Kaki Ma was killed by Phanibhushan when he saw her in a problematic scenario in Sonagachi Nagar. The traditional Indian guy constantly wishes for his family's girls to stay pure, although he has no qualms with whoring often in areas like Sonagachi. India is both a nation wherein women are revered as goddesses and a place where women are more oppressed as a result of male supremacy.

Furthermore, in her greatest piece, Meera has changed the nation's brutality, unfairness, and vanity. K. R. Meera also asserts, "Those who did not seek them out would never know that they had indeed lived" (*Hangwoman* 434). Meera is of the view that when these women grasp who they are as well as what they are worthy of, they rise from the ashes by becoming embodiments of strength and power. Meera intends to highlight masculine chauvinism in Indian culture via Chetana, portraying Chetana as the ultimate authority in a male-dominated society.

P. Sivakami, a regional female writer from Tamil Nadu, has portrayed how women are seen in the rural parts of India. Her novel, *The Taming of Women*, makes a strong remark about how boys and girls in the very same family are raised differently. The males in Anadhayi's family are supposed to have a feeling of ownership of the home as well as the world surrounding them, whereas the women are meant to be thankful for being let in. Because of this discrimination, males grow dictatorial and possess a feeling of dominance over girls and women mostly around their society from an early age. As Sivakumar and Manimekalai opine:

Men in society are expected to become "protectors" of and 'providers' for their families. Society implicitly, and often explicitly, required men to be strong, aggressive, and without emotions. Of course, not all men or masculinities are the same. The appearance of patriarchal masculinity, characterized by male sexual dominance and unequal gender roles, coupled with a lack of sexual experience and knowledge, some men seek to assert their manhood through sexual prowess (433).

Sivakami expresses this discrimination in *The Taming of Women*, in which Anadhayi's daughters Kala, Dhanam, and Arul are severely mistreated by her father

and siblings. Mani, Anandhayi's oldest son, explains his dominance by saying, "If I don't be tough with her now, she would come to regret it later" (*TOW* 25). On an occasion, when Dhanam is beaten by her husband and she comes back home, Periyannan says, "Good! At least now she'll learn to shut up and behave" (238). When she replies back to him, he further says, "Shut up. You must have backchatted like this there as well. Open your mouth and I'll throw you out in the street" (*TOW* 238). This is how women are being stereotyped in Indian societies as even if they are right, they must not backchat with anyone.

Unlike Anandhayi, Lakshmi shows great bravery in confronting patriarchal stereotypes. She continues to plot her escape from Periyannan. She even kicks Periyannan as well as attempts to assault him with a sickle at one point. Though she partly manages in her final effort to flee from him, she knows that she is doomed to be captured by Periyannan and his soldiers. As a result, she commits herself to a permanent solution for her liberation. In that she endures Periyannan's cruelty and along with him, yet strives endlessly to achieve freedom for herself, Lakshmi's figure is a mix of women from the past and present. Lakshmi is an example for all individuals who are oppressed by patriarchy yet want to be free, thanks to Sivakami's excellent portrayal. Whenever Periyannan beats her, she always fights back and responds, "Are you hitting me? Try it and I shall kill you" (*TOW* 219). Even Anandhayi praises her after her death, "She was a strong one. That's why she suffered so much. . . . Poor woman, he practically killed her with his bad treatment" (*TOW* 225).

Arupa Patangia Kalita, being a prominent feminist from Assam, writes substantially on issues of society and especially about the problems of women. She acknowledges that her job involves earning some respect for women. Her *Ayananta* and

The Story of Felanee depict how a patriarchal society always gives men minimal household duties whereas women are bound to that only. She also implies that the males are aware of their responsibilities but always try to run away from them. They stand out in their families due to their lack of duties. Men may not engage in household activities because they want to be free of their duties and obligations.

In a culture characterised by patriarchy, inequality, insurrection, ethnic disputes, violence, resistance, and continuous protest movements, the tales are told by marginalised women, but there are a few marginalised males who tell of their lives of secure aspirations, personal hardship, and losses. They have an unbreakable determination to endure solitude and sadness, and they are confident in their ability to handle internal and external problems (Becker 27-29). Felanee's newly awakened self-awareness motivates her to work for the repair of her shattered self. Felanee's encounter is crucial to the story's conclusion. Felanee was tossed into a marsh and left for dead as her mother passed away in a blazing riot-torn town due to ethnic strife, yet she and hundreds of others survived against the every odd. The story's central characters are the rootless residents of refugee centres and temporary shanties.

Geetanjali Shree in *The Roof Beneath Their Feet* points out women's stereotyping in the patriarchal system and how a middle-class Indian society expects a woman to be. "“Woman should be quiet and restrained, otherwise they'll regret it . . . A woman's not a woman if she doesn't behave like one.”" (*RBTF* 59). The character of Chachcho is the true representation of what patriarchy wants a woman to be like and live without asking a single question from her male counterpart. She must be compassionate, selfless, timid, obeying and living as she is asked by her husband. On the other hand, the husband is free to do whatever he likes.

As Geetanjali points out, “Poor thing, people must have said. She was so nice, . . . See, how compassionately she let her husband’s lover stay, even after becoming a widow” (*RBTF* 47). Further, ““You’d never hear a peep out of her about her husband’s ways, and now she’s even taking care of that other woman out of pity for her swollen stomach”” (*RBTF* 64). Patriarchal society expects a woman to bear every pain silently and still keep on ignoring the wrong deeds of others towards her because “a true woman is one who understands the heart of her man. Forgives him. Lets him return after he has strayed” (*RBTF* 64). But Indian societies never let a woman to live if she even expresses just friendly feelings towards any other man. As Sivakumar and Manimekalai assert, “Indian society like a number of ‘classical’ societies is still patriarchal. Patriarchal values regulating sexuality, reproduction, and social productions are expressed through specific cultural metaphors” (427).

Whenever a girl behaves or does something which isn’t allowed to a woman in accord with the traditional customs then she has to face such questions from everyone as Lalna has to. “Why should she approach anyone with her head held high? Why lead our sons on by playing I Spy with them? Why wreak havoc on the roof by flinging her dupatta aside and taking her slippers off, going barefoot and bareheaded?” (*RBTF* 40). Lalna never cares about what people think or say about her she just does whatever her heart desires to do. She always follows her own feelings irrespective of what is being expected from the people living in the society. As she always defies the social stereotypes and lives freely as she likes, she has to face false blame from society like “the whole world knew how this girl behaved” (*RBTF* 49). Chachcho, who has always followed the stereotypical customs of society and never goes outside the patriarchal boundaries set by society for women, has to go through a lot of mental torment due to that and ultimately, she also has to revolt against it by getting the strength from Lalna.

Similarly, Fateema in *Fence* also defies these social women stereotypes with the help of her good education and mental strength. She fights against the Muslim tradition of wearing a burkha for a woman. “Religious patriarchy works as a vehicle for coercing women to accept gender oppression through religion, in order to maintain the cohesion of the male-dominated social system in India” (Kuttikat 21). When Fateema notices women in her religion “locked behind burkhas, surrounded by five or six children, dragging their feet behind their husbands,” she asserts to herself, “No that’s not for me” (*Fence* 71). She was also cautioned by her brother not to go for higher education “Finish your tenth grade. That’s enough” (*Fence* 62) but with her strong determination and her mother’s support she kept studying further. Her brother, his friend and other community people want her to be like a traditional woman wearing a burka, living inside the four walls of the house, and bearing and rearing children but Fateema defies all such stereotypical roles which are always being imposed on women under patriarchy. Her mother provides her immense support to Fateema and she always remembers her words, “These girls are weak, I tell you. If that was me, I would have jumped off the cart. Or whipped him” (*Fence* 71).

Therefore, stereotypical conditioning of both sexes is one of the reasons for gender discrimination in patriarchal societies as both males and females are always expected by others to behave in a masculine and feminine manner respectively. Due to such masculine stereotypes in societies, some males develop a fake/traumatic identity which could be the reason for their becoming cruel individuals towards others and in extreme conditions become womanizers to demonstrate their masculinity.

Whenever females try to defy such stereotypes as in the case of Lalna, Lakshmi and others, they are considered unsocial and uncultured individuals. These stereotypes

are the real hurdles in the way of a woman to get real success in her life. Women always get tangled in these imposed roles upon them by society and therefore, are unable to be free-minded to focus on their career to become self-reliant. So these masculine and feminine social stereotypes in patriarchal culture are the root cause of males' negative psyche and the ill-treatment of women in societies as they always try to be assertive even if wrong.

Physical and Psychological Trauma

Mental and physical harassment of women is very common in Indian societies as “Social history and novels in many Indian languages record violence against married women in India, mainly perpetrated by their husbands” (Visaria 60). Such incidents create a negative impact on the psyche of women and they are not even safe inside their own household. They are considered inferior to men in every aspect and decision-making in any family. “Most feminist literature in India defines violence against women as any form of coercion, power, or control perpetrated against a woman by her intimate partner or his extended kin and includes physical, sexual, verbal, and mental abuse” (Purkayastha et al. 515). Due to the unending efforts of some feminists and other social reformers, the condition of women in Indian urban societies has improved a bit but in the interior regions, the condition remains more or less the same.

Jonathan Evans and others in a survey assert that discrimination against women is about 23% which is higher than any other type of discrimination and violence against women has also doubled in keeping with the registered police cases from 2010-2019. Around 65% of people feel that violence especially against a woman is a very serious problem in India. Women do not feel safe anywhere in the world and especially in the workplace they have to face a lot of sexual discrimination and harassment. Shafiq

Mohiuddin opines, “Sexual harassment at the workplace is a form of systematized violence against women. Most of the working women . . . face this kind of violence from their colleagues, bosses or employers” (179).

Chiranjit Paul’s *The Fragrance of Rose*, which is a woman-centric novel in third person narrative, highlights the sexual abuse and harassment faced by the central woman character, Rinita (Gupta). But sexual and mental abuse is not only faced by working women, even those at home also face such discrimination at the hands of their husbands and in-laws. Anandhayi faces such physical and mental abuse from her husband in *The Taming of Women* by K. R. Meera. The novel was originally written in Tamil in 1992 and it depicts the physical and psychological trauma of Anandhayi, her daughters, Lakshmi and even the old mother of Periyannan have to face in the novel.

Periyannan is the radical face of the patriarchy that does not spare any woman who comes into his life. As the narrator points out, “Periyannan, his torso bare, came thundering down the steps. He released the woman from Anandhayi’s grip and pushed her aside. Anandhayi crashed to the ground with a loud sob” (*TOW* 4). Periyannan, who is completely inhumane to his wife, is likewise inhumane to his daughters. Through Kala’s cycle-riding event, Sivakami highlights the conventional authority over women in a household. Periyannan, Kala’s father, arrives with a broomstick when he sees his grown daughter riding a bicycle with a male friend. He smacked Anandhayi till she passed out for allowing their daughter to roam freely. When his mother attempted to stop him, she could not save her from his wrath. The incident shows his narrow-mindedness towards women and he has no trust even in his own daughter. “The global as well as domestic scenario suggests the life of women being inflicted with violence, especially by their close ones, including spouse and his kin, and others include murders

related to dowry deaths, violent honour revenge leading to killings” (Bhandari 227). Kala’s parents-in-law also ill-treat her for dowry and her husband beats her almost every day for the same.

Mischievous men always cause spontaneous hindrances and difficulties for women in any society. Therefore, beyond the towering lemon tree as well as fences, Kala, as well as Dhanam, could see a bunch of young guys peeking at them as they bathed in the garden, skirts hiked to their breasts. As Niranjana Bhandari writes, “The violence also occurs through rapes, marital rape, modesty violation, human trafficking and forced prostitution, invisible domestic violence through the infliction of various types and forms of abuse, forced child marriage, acid throwing, abduction, sexual assault, verbal and symbolic abuse, emotional and physical coercion and perpetuation” (227).

Kala pleads with her mother that she does not want to marry her father’s selection. Periyannan chastises her, “Is she going to be his wife or just sleep with him? How dare she say she doesn’t like him? Let her say that once more and I’ll skin both the mother and daughter alive” (*TOW* 113). So there is no choice of freedom for a woman and Kala is not even permitted to voice her displeasure with her wedding proposal. As Malladi Subbamma asserts about women, customs, and culture, “Women’s situation has to undergo a transformation, only laws won’t do. The Constitution of India gives equal rights to women, but in reality that is not so” (7). Especially if one sees the case of rural areas in India as depicted by a number of regional authors in their writings.

Periyannan, on the other hand, never attempts to rein in his youngest son Anbu, who is prone to wrath and outbursts. Furthermore, he is heartened by the fact that his

temperament is identical to his father's. Several other woman characters appear in Sivakami's *The Taming of Women*: Anandhayi's elderly mother-in-law, her children Kala, Dhanam, and Arul, Periyannan's mistress Lakshmi, and Poongavanam and Neeliveni, two rural women with out-of-the-box thoughts. Each of them has their own story of oppression and misery for being a female. Anandhayi's daughters, Kala, Dhanam, and Arul, are a burden to Anandhayi and incompetent for Periyannan since they are women.

They are exposed to severe physical and mental trauma for the most insignificant of reasons, such as responding to a question, attending school, or riding a bicycle. All this is due to the fact that Indian rural women have to rely on males for financial support as they are not able to inherit any of their ancestral property despite the rights that have been given to them by the Indian Constitution. As Soha Khan points out, "History records that framing of property laws tend to be heavily loaded in favour of men, with little scope for questioning their inherent unequal character. Thereby, the whole concept of equality becomes merely academic" (139).

Another minor character, Neelaveni, is a spinster with her own story of woe. She is coveted by all the guys in the hamlet since she is a local beauty. However, her circumstances force her to live alone. Her choice to live however has a negative impact on her reputation, and the locals label her as promiscuous. However, Neelaveni's determination to live alone is an example of women's bravery as an alternative to patriarchy's dominance. When she was in school, two of her teachers sexually exploited her and after that, "she became a plaything to everyone" (*TOW* 29). Therefore, due to the psychological trauma, she has to undergo in her past, she decides to rebel against patriarchal dominance over her body and rejects every male in her society.

Sivakami uses these peripheral female characters to show the readers the many threads that affirm the pathetic condition of all women in Indian societies who are subjected to gender discrimination. Sivakami describes how women of all ages and ethnicities are subjected to physical assault, sexual exploitation, and gender inequality. Poor Lakshmi is compelled to end her life due to the physical and psychological trauma she is subjected to by males in Indian societies, as portrayed in *The Taming of Women*. Lakshmi, the mistress of Periyannan, is a character totally opposite to Anandhayi who is always a passive receiver of her husband's brutality. Periyannan, the embodiment of greed and power, believes himself to have control over everything his gaze falls upon, whether it is land or women. Lakshmi, a lady described as "saffron bathed in warm milk—or a rose petal," (*TOW* 91) attracts Periyannan at first sight and he compels her to become his mistress and live with his family using his physical and political might.

Even Lakshmi's beauty, for which she was imprisoned by Periyannan, isn't enough to save her from his cruelty. Lakshmi makes numerous efforts to flee the clutches of Periyannan, all of which fail, and she is always forcibly taken back home by Periyannan who sexually and mentally thwacks her. However, unlike Anandhayi, Lakshmi is courageous and whenever Periyannan tries to harass her physically or mentally she always fights back. As on one occasion, when he beats her, "Lakshmi turned around, hysterical. She bent her knee and kicked his balls. . . . Even as Anandhayi and Mani edged towards her, Lakshmi challenged aloud, 'Adey . . . come on. I am Seenidevan's daughter. Stand up to me, even, if you have the guts!'" (*TOW* 127-28). Yet he makes her life quite miserable due to which she faces immense traumatic experiences with him.

Most of the incidents in the novel show the physical and mental harassment that women have to face in lower cast male-dominated societies in rural India. The way

Periyannan treats women in this novel, it won't be wrong to say that, "In a paternal society woman is treated no better than a slave. Women are deprived of means of production and have been restricted to the four walls of home and are treated but as a commodity" (Vihan 49). Men are socially stereotyped since their birth to use power in order to keep the women of their house in control which results in the development of psychic males like Periyannan in societies who tries every mean to keep the women under their control no matter what.

Indian society, like many traditionally patriarchal societies, is the reason for such cruel behaviour from the males as "gender norms are constructed around masculinity and a man's sense of self hinges on his ability to control women. Until the daughter is married, her protection and chastity are considered as a mark of the father's honour and masculinity" (Sivakumar and Manimekalai 427). Therefore, the cultural conditioning of the sexes in society creates a negative psyche of the males and females in societies which results in conflicts among them.

During war among nations or any ethnic riots among different communities, it is always the women of both sides who face the utmost adversities in the form of mental, physical or sexual harassment. This is because they are seen as an easy target to take revenge on the males of the other group as Arunima Day points out, "The violent acts on women's bodies were not targeted at them as individuals. In fact, women's mutilated and raped bodies were a way to send out a threat to the men of the religious group to which the women belonged. A woman's body became a site where one group tried to prove its religious supremacy over the other" (107). Similar incidents, against women in communal bloodshed in Assam, are depicted by Arupa Pathangia Kalita in *The Story of Felanee*. The novel is named after the protagonist, which means 'thrown

aside' or 'discarded' in English. Felanee and her companions represent the people outside of society.

Felanee has been described by reviewers as a raw account of the unfathomable miseries of Assamese society's disadvantaged groups, which was a result of separatism or ethnic activities that ravaged the state's socio-economic fabric. Females are the main sufferers of these pains, which vary from extremely bodily to very severe psycho-social ones. Kalita has a reputation for being a powerful craftsman with a knack for revealing the feminine mind. Felanee is a story about a fight for survival. Most of the individuals in this story have gone through a variety of traumatic events of varying degrees of severity. As a result, it serves as a key foundation in the creation and growth of the narrative as well as the novel's protagonists.

Aggression and trauma are two ideas that are inextricably linked. Psychological and physical aspects are the main characteristics of violence. Physical abuse has an effect on the body, while psychological abuse has an effect on the soul. They are mutually beneficial, with one leading to the development of the other. "The boundary between interpersonal violence is not particularly clear," Galtung remarks, "because it is feasible to affect physical motions using psychological methods, and conversely: physical restrictions undoubtedly have mental consequences" (175). Trauma research should include both physical and psychological symptoms, which are usually hidden. The incorporation of human rights concepts into the process of negotiation has increased the necessity for research into physical abuse and the resulting traumatic disorder.

Kali Boori's persona, in *The Story of Felanee*, adds a new depth to how pain is absorbed and manifested on an interpersonal basis. It may differ from one person to the

next. Unlike Sumola or Felanee, Kali Boori responds differently to her traumatic experiences, for which the author masterfully creates the legendary figure of Kali -- one of the world's rare unorthodox and rebellious representations of female goddesses. When Kali Boori was 17 years old, she was sexually exploited by two separate people who left her unattended during her pregnancy.

Felanee first encountered Kali Boori when she was an elderly woman with a frail body but a powerful voice. As she was a gorgeous woman with great sensual attraction, it's easy to conclude that her supernatural reincarnation is nothing more than her self-created protection system. In her seized times, she acts like a god with superhuman abilities, expressing all of her traumatic experiences. It was also utilized as a carefully constructed barrier of sexual and mental protection for a sensitive soul who had to endure the brunt of sexual trauma at a young age. Her status as a dispossessed, destitute woman forced her to seek shelter in Goddess Kali, whose authoritative power is difficult to deny by ordinary men.

Kalita while portraying violence and its effect on ordinary people's lives, concludes with the picture of Felanee, Maya, Minoti, and others walking out to gather reeds from the river bank to rebuild their houses or spaces that have been devastated by the violence. The laughter of these females who have lost not only their family members but also a part of their presence that tries to revive the river bank positions towards some kind of utilisation of the physical environment overshadowed by abuse with their powerful enthusiasm for preservation; the female couldn't perceive one another's faces because they were obscured by the wet reeds. War always has been a man's world for centuries as in every culture they are being conditioned/forced to take the role of fighters and protectors of their families. In the past, it has always been the

man who fought, died, and achieved glory or disgrace on the battlefield. “Traditionally it is the man who always fights, dies, and achieves glory or shame on the battlefield” (Choudhury 572).

Lalna, in Geetanjali Shree’s *The Roof Beneath Their Feet*, has to face a lot of mental and physical abuse from the people of the Laburnam house. People living over there always question her past and “in Laburnam house, rose a rumour that Lalna had been seen on the roof sneaking up to meet a man! Each time a new lover” (*RBTF* 37). Everyone kept on saying that she has “an unspoken but sullied past” (*RBTF* 39). Once a very reputed person from the Laburnam House, Premanand-ji beats Lalna with his kicks and a hockey stick when he hears a rumour about Lalna that she forced his underage nephew to have sex with her. Lalna is always ill-treated and mentally abused by everyone in the Laburnam House except Chachcho. When Chachcho finds the truth that it was Premanand-ji’s nephew who spread the rumour about Lalna, Chachcho slaps him in front of many people in the Laburnam House.

Chachcho who is a selfless woman and devoted herself fully towards her husband has to face psychological trauma due to her insensitive husband. As her nephew says, “Uncle could never understand. Why the quiet Chachcho, the Chachcho who would shrivel up if he so much as gave her a stern look” (*RBTF* 11). Her marriage with Om Babu is like as Lalna says, “The irony of it – when Behan-ji had wanted a husband, Om Babu abandoned her and went off. . . . [and the] terrible moments at night . . . when Behan-ji would thrash about like a caged animal” (*RBTF* 103). Due to such cold treatment from her husband, she keeps on tormenting herself mentally. He is not concerned with her feelings and does “not know what sort of respect to grant which woman?” (*RBTF* 103). “He seemed to think that buying his wife things and more things

was enough. He'd buy all sorts of rubbish and heap it upon her" (Shree 93) but was never able to understand what's her real desire.

She provides everything at her husband's hand and serves him like a poor servant, but when she desires some warm feelings from him he always betrays her by saying, "Because I want a woman, not you" (*RBTF* 63). Poor Chachcho goes through psychological trauma due to alienation but never ever questions the supremacy of her husband. Chachcho's timid behaviour is all due to the rude/cold treatment she receives from her husband as Lalna once points out, "She had always been quiet, but whether people knew it or not, I knew that this wasn't her usual quietness. Chachcho had decided to not talk to Uncle" (*RBTF* 65) because he never tries to understand her feelings and she decides to suffer silently.

The physical and mental harassment of women in patriarchy is quite evident in different forms in Indian rural societies as depicted in literature by select regional women writers. Women have to face physical and psychological trauma due to wars and ethnic riots as depicted by Arupa Pathangia Kalita through the experiences of her female characters, especially Felanee. Every woman character has to undergo psychological trauma in her life, however, the incidents as depicted in the select narratives show that only low-caste women like Anandhayi, Lakshmi, Lalna and some minor characters in Felanee have to undergo some inhumane treatment and physical bashing from some culturally conditioned men in Indian societies.

Whereas upper-class women like Chachcho and educated women like Fateema and Chetna aren't the victims of physical harassment which shows an individual's class and caste also play an important role in the treatment they receive in patriarchal societies. The main reason for the mental and physical agony of women is the

traditional cultural conditioning of men in Indian rural societies where men are treated as the superior sex and are forced to be masculine possessing enduring qualities. Such men in patriarchal societies become psychologically ill individuals who try to control women and whenever any woman revolts against it, the man takes it as his defeat and uses violence against the woman to repress her and restore his supremacy.

Marriage as an Institution

In India, marriage is not just a union of two individuals but also a union of two families. It is considered a sacred bond and is given utmost importance in Indian society. The life of a male without a female and vice-versa is not considered good in Indian societies. “Indian woman follows customs and traditions blindly and considers her husband like God” (Singh and Gupta c760). They are conditioned by the implications of religion, culture and fear of society since their childhood. The concept of arranged marriages is still prevalent in many parts of India, where families choose a partner for their children based on various factors such as social status, education, financial stability, and family background. “The Manusmriti treats marriage as a means for procreation, and the woman must satisfy her husband in all possible ways. . . . In marriage, women’s preferences or desires are not considered. It is the father’s interests and choices that determine the future groom for a girl.” (N. M. and Kuruvilla 25). Therefore, those women who choose their own grooms are not easily accepted by their parents and society.

During the Vedic period, women were seen with respect and enjoyed an equal status in Indian societies. The condition of women in India only started degrading with the introduction of such ‘smritis’ and more after the Muslim invasion of India. Later under the male-dominated patriarchal system, the situation of women got adverse.

Under patriarchal dominance, for the last few centuries/decades, women have been treated as their bridal slaves by traditional thinkers, especially in the rural parts of India. So a number of social reformers and feminists in India raised their voices against such cruelties with women in their marriages. As Shyam Prakash Pandey is of the view that:

Feminist theory asserts that marriage promotes male superiority and power over women. It conceptualizes men as the providers operating in the public sphere and women as the caregivers operating within the private sphere. Traditional heterosexual marriage imposes an obligation on the wife to be sexually available for her husband and an obligation on the husband to provide material/financial support for the wife. The performance of dominant gender roles by men and submissive gender roles by women influence the power dynamic of heterosexual marriage. (64)

Similar situations are depicted in P. Sivakami's *The Taming of Women*, Geetanjali Shree's *The Roof Beneath Their Feet* and Arupa Pathangia Kalita's *The Story of Felanee*.

The Taming of Women depicts this traditional forced marriage between Periyannan and Anandhayi in which he is the brutal dominator and she is the passive receiver of his inhuman treatment. He abuses and even thrashes her physically whenever he feels like it. As she is illiterate, therefore, totally dependent on him and like many other married Indian women she accepts him as her God. Anandhayi's daughter Kala faces the same situation in her marriage life. Her husband also beats her for dowry and over other trivial issues, therefore, she wants to run away but marriage is seen as a lifelong commitment, and divorce is still considered taboo in many parts of

India. Therefore, when Dhanam returns home after a dispute with her spouse, she is told she has no hope and is cautioned by her father, “Do not come here again” (*TOW* 241). Her father wants to convey to her that after her marriage she has now no right to live at her father’s house. Whenever she comes back after such a fight Anandhayi says, “When you are born a woman, you have to learn to control your tongue and hands. . . . You don’t want to do so, then be prepared for the kicking” (*TOW* 239).

This shows the patriarchal psyche of women in Indian rural societies where a woman is always expected to remain quiet whatever adverse the situation may be, and on the other hand, a man can have every right to treat women as he feels right. Dowry is really a serious problem of violence against women in the rural parts of India as depicted by Sivakami through the story of Anandhayi’s elder daughter Dhannam who is being ill-treated and physically tortured by her husband and in-laws for dowry.

Dowry is also one of the social deformities in India due to which no parents in India want to have a girl child as dowry on her marriage costs a substantial amount of money. “A bride's parents may believe that a generous dowry is essential to ensure that their daughter is treated well” (Srinivasan and Lee 1109). Sometimes the pressure from the groom's family may last even after the couple has married. Whenever the bride's family's requests are not met, the woman is tormented. Among Indian households, domestic violence is common. It is not uncommon for dowry tragedies to happen in rural India. According to Sonia Dalmia and Pareena Lawrence, “The custom of dowry is responsible for a number of ills against women in India. The most serious of these being the mental and physical abuse of wives, and bride-burning or murder of brides due to the inability of a bride's family to meet the dowry demands of the groom's family” (72).

Dhannam's husband always accuses "her of coming without a dowry, continuing batter her" (*TOW* 240) for the same. Likewise, once Periyannan says to his brother-in-law, "You are free to take your sister, but don't touch my bulls. What am I to do without my bulls . . . don't make me say things I might regret" (*TOW* 43). Both Anandhayi and her daughter are not happy in their marriage and both are even physically abused by their husbands still they ought to stay in their marriage such is the importance of the institution of marriage in rural parts of India. On the other hand, the patriarchal-conditioned males like Periyannan take women as their bridal slaves whom they can treat as pleased.

Women are often expected to be submissive and obedient to their husbands, and there is a societal pressure on them to conform to traditional gender roles such as being a homemaker and taking care of the family. Chachcho, in *The Roof Beneath Their Feet*, also has the same mindset and she considers her husband as God. She bears all the torments silently without ever uttering a single word to her husband. As Geetnajali Shree ironically remarks, "A true woman is one who understands the heart of her man. Forgives him. Let him return after he has strayed" (64). Some people would say, "You'd never hear a peep out of her about her husband's ways" (*RBTF* 64).

Arupa Pathangia Kalita has also depicted the issues faced by her protagonist due to her inter-state/inter-cultural marriage in *Felanee*. Intercultural marriages in India can be a challenging proposition for many couples. India is a diverse country with several cultural and religious communities, and inter-cultural marriages often face resistance and opposition from family members and society at large. One of the primary issues faced by inter-cultural couples is the clash of cultural values and traditions. During such cultural and ethnic conflicts in the form of the 'Assam

Movement' which took place in the late 1970s and early 80s, Felanee had to suffer a lot due to her inter-cultural marriage as her father was a Bengali and she got married to a Koch in Assam.

Most of the married women are suffering at the hands of their husbands yet they do not raise a voice against them. Arupa shows how these women take care of their ill, drunkard and penurious husbands without raising any forced voice against them. Most of the women portrayed work hard to earn money and serve their indolent husbands with full devotion. The psyche of women is culturally constructed in Indian rural societies in such a manner that a woman's life "is nothing without a husband. . . . You may be the Prime Minister of India tomorrow, but when you come home, you automatically become your husband's wife. If you forget, you are finished" (Jain 21).

To sum up, the issue of marriage is central to the plot of *The Taming of Women* and is portrayed as a site of gender inequality and oppression. The novel highlights the unequal power dynamics in marital relationships and the ways in which women are often expected to submit to the authority of their husbands and in-laws. Through the character of the protagonist, the author critiques the institution of marriage and calls for a re-evaluation of traditional gender roles and expectations. The novel thus raises important questions about the role of marriage in perpetuating gender inequality in Indian society. *The Roof Beneath their Feet* also depicts an emotionless marriage of Chachcho. Kalita in *Felanee* shows how the protagonist's intercultural marriage becomes a site of problems for her during the ethnic riots in Assam. Overall, while the institution of marriage holds great significance in Indian society, there is also a need to address the issues of gender inequality and traditional gender roles within marriages to make them more equitable and fulfilling for both partners.

Role of Education in Women's Empowerment

The issue of women's education has been a topic of great concern in Indian society for a long time. The Indian regional literature, written by women authors, has explored this issue in depth. The authors have highlighted the struggles faced by women in getting an education, as well as the impact of education on their lives. This section discusses how the regional women writers have portrayed the importance of education for women and how it can transform their lives. *Fence* by Ila Arab Mehta highlights the challenges faced by women in getting an education. They explore the societal norms and patriarchal mindset that restrict women's access to education. These novels also depict how education can empower women and help them break free from the shackles of societal norms. As Seema Sathesh and M. Nagalakshmi assert, "Dalit women writers, have to a great extent articulated the woes and sufferings of the Dalit women by means of their literary works and have strived greatly for their emancipation by stressing on education as the need of the hour.

Both Bama and Sivakami are prolific dalit women writers who have carved a niche for themselves in the realm of literature" (3493). Therefore, most of the regional women writers know the importance of education in a woman's life to emancipate her. Education can help women become financially independent, make informed decisions, and challenge gender stereotypes. It can also help women participate in the workforce and contribute to the economy. Education has always been the basis of an individual's intellectual and overall financial growth. An educated woman efficiently fights against the patriarchal system as compared to the uneducated one.

Education for women is as important as for men in order to achieve gender equality and to promote the development of any nation. As Pandit Nehru once

expressed “If you educate a man you educate an individual, however, if you educate a woman you educate a whole family. Women empowered means mother India empowered...You can tell the condition of a nation by looking at the status of its women” (Shetty and Hans). It would not be inappropriate to say that the development of any nation in its true sense happens only if half of its population i.e. women get good education opportunities. “Education is considered as a basic requirement and a fundamental right for the citizens of any nation. It is a powerful tool for reducing inequality as it can give people the ability to become independent” (Singh 40). Therefore, for women to become self-reliant, the role of good education is vital in their lives which further enhances the development of the nation. As Mander points out, “When girls are educated, countries become stronger and prosperous.”

Education only enables a woman to be aware of her fundamental rights and can challenge anyone who violates them and discriminates against any woman. Therefore, education plays a very vital role in the empowerment of women and good education can only enable a woman to stand against patriarchal tyranny and be capable enough to contribute positively towards the development of their nation. “Education of any kind will help empower women, but it is higher education that will prove the key in increasing the upward mobility of women” (Shibulal). Education is very important in the improvement of the status of any individual especially in the case of women.

The Taming of Women by P. Sivakami portrays uneducated women characters who are financially dependent on Periyannan, the antagonist and are forced to bear his inhuman treatment. Likewise, in *The Roof Beneath Their Feet* by Geetanjali Shree, both Chachcho and Lalna are uneducated and hence totally dependent on males for their livelihood. In *The Story of Felanee* by Arupa Pathangia Kalita, all the women

characters are also more or less the same. Such women are always being forced to bear the discrimination imposed on them by patriarchal tyrants as uneducated women remain financially dependent upon them. As Amruta Bhaskar opines, “Women empowerment is a pivotal part of any society, state or country. It is a woman who plays a dominant role in the basic life of a child . . . Education as a means of empowerment of women can bring about a positive attitudinal change. It is, therefore, crucial for the socioeconomic and political progress of India.” Therefore, Chetna in *Hangwoman* is able to make the correct decisions due to her knowledge and awareness as she is educated at least till higher secondary.

Women's empowerment requires higher education, which empowers them to respond to difficulties and question their patriarchal roles, and only education can transform their lives. Fateema, in Ila Arab Mehta's *Fence*, could buy an independent house of her own only due to her higher education. She has to face a lot of struggles due to patriarchal customs and poverty. She is the daughter of a scrap collector with the dream of having an independent house of her own amid society. In the end, she is able to fulfil her dream as she was educated which made her financially capable of achieving that. Fateema was quite a bright student during her school days as one of her teachers remarked, “She's is one of our scholarship girls” (*Fence* 14).

Even her mother is also very supportive of her education and once she tells one of her relatives, “I don't need the girl's labour. They will not be taking the cattle to graze. In fact, Fateema is learning English now!” (*Fence* 16). Fateema struggles a lot to be educated in a male-dominated patriarchal culture which never permits a woman to go to college for higher studies. Her brother keeps forcing her to get married and lead a life of a tame housewife. However, Fateema is a very strong-willed girl and she faces

every situation quite bravely and continues her studies even after completing her graduation. She isn't financially capable of doing that but somehow, she manages to do an MA in History and ultimately gets the job of a teacher to fulfil her dream.

Fateema has nothing except her good education which paves the way for her to stand on her own feet and own an independent house of her all alone without anyone's help. Without education, it would not have been possible for her to achieve this at all. Moreover, she also has a strong eagerness and willingness to learn despite having no resources at all. "Never mind that the uniform she wore was donated by the school, the walls of her house were baked with mud, her food comprised only split gram: her palms were wide open, ready to receive" (*Fence* 26). Fateema always has to fight for books with her brother as Mehta points out, "Fateema had attempted a raid, but Kareem had pounced on her, pulling her back by her hair, then dealt her a couple of blows" (13). Despite all her struggles she does not accept defeat and keeps on fighting for her education and ultimately completes her higher education. Fateema is so firm and confident about her dream that when she sees a few women in burka and surrounded by many children, she thinks, "No, that's not for me. . . . I want to become a teacher. I want to study" (*Fence* 71). With the support of her parents, her hard work and education, she is able to emancipate herself and become financially independent.

Being educated Fateema and Chetna are confident and "they have come to recognize their rights and want to be equal to men in every aspect of life. They now demand the same fidelity, which men demand from them" (Jain 21). Especially, Fateema is able to own an independent house of her own in the midst of the Hindu community despite being a single Muslim woman only through her hard work which she did as her best friend Chandan remarks, "Sages in our religion meditate at one

place and that's 'tapas,' penance. But our guru says that when human beings carry out their work quietly and ethically, help others and become better human beings, that's also a penance. So when you and I study properly, that's all penance, you know?" (*Fence* 225). Therefore, Fateema does a lot of hard work and struggles to get her education which in turn transforms her into a confident and self-reliant person. On the other hand, Anandhayi, Lakshmi, Lalna and others have to suffer a lot as being uneducated they are not aware of their rights.

To sum up, the discussions in the present chapter reveals different aspects of gender-based inequalities which work invisibly in Indian societies, especially in rural areas. The social stereotyping of males and females is the main reason for gender inequalities in India. Since birth, the patriarchal culture starts conditioning men to be masculine and women to be feminine. Men are expected to be strong, assertive, dominating, and control their emotions which impels them to create a fake masculine identity to look powerful and emotionless. Such enforced stereotypes create a negative impact on the psyche of some men and they become excessively dominating and over-assertive.

Women, on the other hand, are always expected to be timid, speak less, be emotional and be confined to the house only with very little freedom of choice. Such stereotypical conditioning of women creates a conflict in their individuality as by nature if they want to oppose men, the traditional society won't allow that as depicted by the select women writers in their respective novels. Men in patriarchal societies are given the duties of protector, nurturer and breadwinner for their families so in that sense they feel it natural to use power to subdue their families and, in that way, some men cross their limits and abuse women during conflicts with them.

This social stereotyping of the sexes is the main reason for conflicts between the two sexes and ultimately in extreme conditions is one of the reasons for violence and discrimination against women by men. As in P. Sivakami's *The Taming of Women*, all women are treated as slaves by Pariyanan for being females and uneducated. Likewise, in *The Roof Beneath Their Feet*, Chachcho suffers silently and Lalna isn't allowed to behave in the manner she likes because of her sex as only the boys are free to do such activities which Lalna does. The role of religion and culture is very important in Indian rural areas as it conditions women to be the bearers and men to be the repressors. Moreover, the traditional thinking of not allowing women to get higher education is also a violation of their fundamental rights.

Education plays a vital role in the emancipation of women and their progress in Indian rural societies. Before 2000, women's education in India was not a priority for many families and the government. Girls were expected to get married and take care of the household duties. Education for girls was limited and often seen as a waste of time and resources. Many families preferred to send their sons to school, as they believed that it was a better investment for the family's future. Additionally, girls were often discouraged from pursuing education due to societal pressure and gender-based stereotypes.

The Taming of Women by P. Sivakami was written around the 1990s, *The Roof Beneath their Feet* by Geetanjali was written around 2000 and *Felanee* by Kalita around 2003. All these novels show how uneducated women remain dependent on men for their financial needs which becomes the root cause of their discrimination as is in the case of Anandhayi, Lakshmi, Lalna and others. Whereas educated women like Fateema in *Fence* and Chetna in *Hangwoman* become capable enough to fight for their

rights and financially efficient to not rely upon men for anything. Both these novels are written after the year 2010 and over the last decade, there has been a significant increase in women's education in India.

The increase in women's education is due to various government initiatives such as the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan and the Right to Education Act, which have aimed to provide free and compulsory education for all children between the ages of 6 and 14. Additionally, there has been an increase in the number of girls-only schools and colleges across the country, providing a safe and secure environment for girls to pursue their education. Therefore, to achieve gender inequality and stop discrimination against women one needs to understand that equal treatment of both the sexes is required since their birth. Equal opportunities in higher education for women in the rural regions of India will gradually decrease discrimination against women as they become aware of their rights.

CHAPTER III

ROLE OF CASTE AND RELIGION IN WOMEN'S SUBJUGATION

The present chapter explores the multi-level subjugation that a woman has to face because of her caste and religion. The chapter also dwells upon the connection between caste, gender, and religion in women's subjugation. The chapter focuses on the discrimination against women based on their caste as depicted in P. Sivakami's *The Taming of Women*, and discrimination based on religion as depicted by Ila Arab Mehta in *Fence*.

While discussing the condition of low-caste women in South India, Navya points out that dalits are prohibited from pursuing an education in a conventional caste culture, therefore, people are adopting Christianity to get an opportunity in higher education (23). "Despite recent socio-economic changes which have tended to blur such caste/class identifications, class status can still be often identified with caste status; this is especially true at the lower levels of the caste hierarchy in the rural areas" (Kasturi 3). Therefore, in the interior regions of India where caste and class are of great importance to people, women have to face double or triple discrimination as Alka Sarmah asserts, "Man not only directly oppresses women, but in addition to it, they have an indirect ability to make women feel inferior and unaware of alternative ways of living. Moreover, women also have to remain satisfied with their traditional 'wife-mother' role syndrome as they suppose that this satisfaction will not be possible if they enter the masculine world" (883).

Recognizing women's oppression versus male supremacy in the socio-cultural as well as economic worlds is crucial because it elucidates how caste and gender segregation interact. "In the poem 'My Last Duchess' Browning expressed his class

difference . . . [through] the harshness and the egoistic nature of the high-class people. . . . In the novel *Adam Bede*, . . . the novelist brings out that people who belong to the common middle class undergo punishment and people belong to the high class are left free” (Selvi 33). Shulamith Firestone, a radical feminist, in *The Dialectic of Sex: The Case of Feminist Revolution* is of the view that sex itself is a social class in our male-dominated societies. She divides all males and females into different classes and the male class is dominating the female class. Male dominance over females results from capital’s hegemony over workers/slaves. The main characteristics of social structures—class connections and the social inequality of one class by another, determine the form of gender dynamics. Family is considered as capital in which females are just like labourers whose work is to reproduce, childcare and perform other household activities so that the males can go out to work (8-10).

The repression of women was a crucial measure for the perpetuation of the caste system in rural India. Throughout history, men have held a significant advantage over women in all areas of life, across different societies. In Indian literature, the subjugation of women has been a recurring theme, and unfortunately, it is still prevalent today, particularly in rural regions where an individual's caste plays a crucial role. As Chakravarti points out, “The Dharmashastras recommended severe punishments for violations, including death for the lower caste man and mutilation, physical punishment and excommunication for the offending woman” (63). At both the material and intellectual levels, this subjugation is socially created and perpetuated, one supporting the other. What is even more essential to note here seems to be that, although women's subjugation is a global occurrence, the degree and form of women's subjugation are influenced by their societal, economic, and intellectual surroundings. Uma Chakravarti asserts, “The structure of social relations that shaped the

dominant/hegemonic model of gender, and of caste, in early India was consolidated and reproduced by achieving the compliance of women” (74).

The present chapter examines the role of caste and religion in women’s oppression as depicted by the select female authors in their respective novels located in different states/cultures/languages of rural India. The purpose of this chapter is to examine the connection between caste, religion and culture in Indian society and how it impacts the status of women in modern India. Notwithstanding the importance of caste in Indian demography and arguments over whether class or caste should be the deciding component of socially disadvantaged, only a few academic researches, have examined the connection between castes and classes. Tabish Khair says, “Indian English writers tend towards the ‘universal’ and the ‘pan-Indian’ in a bid to address a readership which is thinly smeared across the length and breadth of multicultural India, and it becomes evident that . . . might not be either ‘universal’ or even ‘pan-Indian’” (78).

Therefore, he is of the view that the Indian mainstream writers always ignored the low caste people and even those works that represent rural life are “largely middle class and (rural or urban) upper caste terms, the Indian English novelist denies the existence of the Indian ‘other’ which is neither middle-class nor upper caste . . . with the partial exception of Mulk Raj Anand, the lower caste character has been described from an upper caste perspective” (Khair 79). Although, Preetha Mani points out, “Nayi Kahani writing offered aspirational middle-class belonging to resolve the dilemma of caste hierarchy. . . . Collapsing caste, class, religion, and gender in the figure of the middle-class, savarna (caste Hindu) male, these stories portrayed this figure’s inner turmoil as universal by cloaking it in the rhetoric of modernist-realist

disconsolation” (133). However, the theme of caste was dealt with in a capitalistic manner by most of the regional upper-class writers as Preetha Mani further asserts:

For example, Rakesh’s “Mis Pāl” (Miss Pal) portrays its mountain-dwelling villager characters as ignorant, superstitious, and backwards. They are contrasted to the urbanized male protagonist Ranjit and his friend Miss Pal, who intellectualize and psychologize the conditions of post-independence existence. Ranjit’s and Miss Pal’s economic status, level of education, and elevated Hindi diction immediately signal their savarṇa identity to any Hindi reader. Nonetheless, the story distinguishes these characters from the peripheral village dwellers through the class norms of propriety, civility, and hygiene—rather than through the terms of caste hierarchy. (133)

The majority of Indian literature is comprised of works by higher caste males, where the real voices of those from lower castes and, specifically, the voices of females are lost. Male-dominated structures and ideologies have impacted women's thinking and authorized certain cultural standards to give them precedence in the framework of society. Vijay Tendulkar, the Marathi high-caste Hindu brahmin playwright, is of the view that dalit youth are quite inhuman and rough in their behaviour towards everyone, especially women. In his plays, he expresses that males always remain uncultured even if married to a high-caste girl. As a result, a distinction is not always linked to the elimination of caste disparities. Tamizh Selvi points out, “Vijay Tendulkar’s 1983 Marathi play *Kanyadan* consists of the major issues of the society such as class, caste, and gender. In this play, the playwright seems to have expressed that inter-caste marriages will not be a solution to bring equality in the society” (34). Tendulkar has discussed caste in his writings in a colonized manner where he doesn’t seem to like the idea of high-caste girls marrying low-caste boys. This may be due to the psychological

conditioning of Tendulkar's mind by social and cultural aspects of Indian rural societies as women are seen as stepping stones into the conceptual structure, primarily as entrance points. As a consequence, the caste's coherence might well be preserved by carefully guarding women, who act as the centre to a family's chastity.

The ceremonial character of caste blood has always been bilateral, meaning it comes from both parents. As a result, both parents should preferably belong to the very same caste. The terms 'anuloma' as well as 'pratiloma' are essential to consider at this point. "An anuloma union is one between a man of a superior and a woman of an inferior varna, and, subject to certain conditions, it is accepted. . . . Pratiloma, on the other hand, is the union of a woman of a superior varna with a man of an inferior one, and it is condemned in the severest possible terms" (Beteille 492). In essence, children born from this kind of union were regarded as outcasts. The notion being stressed would be that a woman's role as a protector of 'purity' should not be reduced, but rather elevated. The innocence of women is closely connected to the blood purity of lineage as well as the status of families inside the larger cultural order. Women are thought to be the keepers of family honour.

Moreover, "The early writers who thematized the discriminatory practices of the caste system in the nineteen seventies had a Marxist background and largely subsumed caste to class struggle. Many of their stories were published in the leftist little magazines of the time" (Keshavamurthy 122). Sandrine Soukai also asserts, "Many world-renowned Indian writers have expressed their support to the Dalit cause. . . . Nonetheless, like several other minority groups, Dalits have been concerned about having their voices silenced by the non-Dalits claiming to speak for them. Dalit literatures have thus been at the heart of a debate about who is legitimate to authorise Dalit writing and represent Dalits." Baby Kamble, a Marathi novelist, voiced against

the colonized treatment of the low-caste by the upper-caste writers in her novel *Jina Amucha* as Aditya Raj and Pooja point out, “Kamble’s work criticizes Brahminical domination and speaks out for the female of the community who stand in opposition bearing the continuous exploitation of patriarchal power and caste factor” (57). Therefore, low-caste people have been treated indifferently in Indian societies since ancient times.

In Vedic literature, according to the philosophy of Manu, the ‘Varnas’ concept was used to divide Hindu casts into four main groups: Brahmin, Kshatriya, Vaishya, and Sudra in ascending order. Different caste groupings were used to experimentally represent the ‘Varnas’ paradigm. Interactions among castes are controlled, among many other things, by the idea of cleanliness and contamination, while within castes, maximum commonality occurs. Castes are social communities with distinct lifestyles whose participation is decided by birth rather than selection or merit. As a result, caste is a categorical title. Every caste has its own set of traditional occupations that force women to double torment at the hands of the males of their own caste as well as from the upper caste men.

Women's rights relate to the degree to which males' and females' chances and results are limited or improved simply because of their gender. Even some of the Hindu religious texts like *Manusamriti* also advocate gender inequality as Sophie M. Tharakan and Michael Tharakan point out, “In childhood, a woman must be subject to her father, in youth to her husband and when her lord is dead, to her sons. A woman must never be independent” (119). “In most of the settled societies, women in all classes have experienced very low status, oppression and lead towards their exploitation. Women have been enslaved by men in every class and in every society”

(Akhter). On the other hand, membership to a wealthy class may assist women in overcoming obstacles that women from less prosperous groups face.

Societal stratification is the process through which groups of individuals in society are classified in a power structure, typically based on the levels of authority, status, and wealth its members have. On the other hand, 'Social Inequality' means the presence of culturally produced disparities. The concepts behind this strategy have been questioned by contemporary feminist research, which contends that gender disparities are a fundamental aspect of the class structure and should be taken into account in the analysis of class in our society (Sorensen 28). Therefore, it can be said that social stratification is also a form of gender discrimination as it feels that the whole family is a single class. The notion that comes with being a man or a woman is determined by social contexts and situations.

Culture plays a vital role in determining the behaviour of both the sexes and those men/women who defy these traditional stereotypes are condemned in patriarchal societies. Gender is undoubtedly a contributing factor in social inequity. When it comes to caste, although being lower caste is clearly a distinct source of inequality, its effect is amplified when the lower-caste families are also extremely impoverished. Caste is predicated on ritualised purity, with the Brahmana at the pinnacle and the (former) 'untouchables' or low caste at the base.

Therefore, in Indian rural societies caste, religion and culture play an important role in women's subjugation. As Sultana points out, "The main cause of women's subordination is the negative impact of tradition, religion, patriarchy, seclusion or purdah and paternalistic attitudes in the socio-economic and legal spheres" (15). In such conditions, "women's labour power, women's reproduction, women's sexuality,

women's mobility and property and other economic resources – are under patriarchal control” (Walby 20). “Patriarchy is a system whereby women are kept subordinate in a number of ways. The subordination that we experience at a daily level, regardless of the class we might belong to, takes various forms – discrimination, disregard, insult, control, exploitation, oppression, violence – within the family, at the place of work, in society” (Sultana 7). She further asserts, “Feminists mainly use the term ‘patriarchy’ to describe the power relationship between men and women. Thus, patriarchy is more than just a term; feminists use it like a concept, and like all other concepts it is a tool to help us understand women's realities” (2).

“Some feminists have argued that a woman's class position should be determined by her own employment and work history, whereas Goldthorpe has argued that the family is the basic unit in class analysis, with the husband's occupation determining the class position of all family members, including the wife's” (Toomey 389). Owners are at the pinnacle of the class ladder, while dispossessed labourers are at the bottom, reflecting a distinct type of inequality maintained by caste. In an evaluation of the current situation of the gender-caste overlap, Deshpande claims that women's economic position is still determined and limited by their caste rank. “The literature on the overlap between caste and gender is even smaller, and within that literature, economic analyses of this overlap are very few indeed” (Deshpande 735).

Caste and gender disparities interact with endogamous as well as other systems that exert control over women's employment and sexuality. In contrast to their upper-caste colleagues, lower-caste women have far more liberty in seeking lucrative work outside the house, yet they are not better off since they belong to a club that is literally at the bottom rung of the ladder. In terms of quality of living, family decision-making,

and the incidence of domestic abuse, dalit women are worse off than upper-caste women implying that caste, class, and gender interact in increasing or reducing women's vulnerability. Several academics have challenged the conventional simplified 'varna' system, which maintains class and gender disparities predicated on purity pollution, since the 1960s and 1970s. "While caste oppression affects every member of the Dalit community, the heaviest brunt of retributory wrath is borne by women. Dalit women occupy the lowest position in society according to the archaic Varna system" (Joshi).

The easiest sexual violence targets are the females of the lower class as there is no hearing of their sufferings and most of them will not even dare to go to the police to lodge any complaint against the assaulters. As Nishant Joshi further asserts, "Dalit women have no 'honour' to begin with, their rights to preservation against sexual violence are met with limited redress if any [and this situation is adverse in the interior regions of India as] stories of sexual violence against women in cities manage to engage the public attention, rural narratives fail to see the light of day." The empirical reality suggests a more complex picture in which not only do distinct castes have various hierarchical elucidation, but then those castes who actually find themselves in exceedingly demeaning and subordinate roles fail to admit the hypothesis of Karma and purity-pollution when it comes to caste ordering (Deshpande 748). Consequently, social scientists have started to discover that caste identification is both permanent and irreversible and that the distinction between 'clean' and 'impure' castes has become the strong and most lasting representation of contemporary caste life.

Most of the interior regions of India are characterised by discrimination, marginalization, and abuse based on class, caste, religion, and gender. Discrimination based on these factors becomes the norm for gaining access to resources and therefore

surviving. Before understanding how inequality and discrimination show themselves in the Indian regional literature, one must first examine and comprehend how inequity manifests itself in a society. Without an awareness of these facts, ideas for bringing gender equality would be impossible to find. In the present environment, there is a dynamic link between class, caste, and gender that must be recognised. The connection between these three groups is seldom observed or understood, and each of these categories is often regarded in isolation.

The struggle between the classes of workers and owners, on the other hand, has attracted radicals. The structure of classes has evolved through time and varies depending on the situation. From feudal to capitalist societies, the class has shifted, resulting in new social and production connections. Welfarism and social dominance are used to legitimise class. Women are given equal status in the constitution and likewise “Shashi Deshpande in *That Long Silence* has presented a concept of a new woman with an appeal for the rightful place of a woman in modern Indian Society. Though equal status for women with equal opportunities in life has been guaranteed in our constitution, still she is neglected, embarrassed and harassed in wider circles of society” (Marwaha 527).

The present chapter is concerned with exposing the structural deformities of the patriarchal culture to locate gender-specific power relations and women’s subjugation within the constructions of caste and class supremacy, and unfairness, as well as exploring connections between caste, religion, and gender. Whereas a philosophy of distinction is essential for highlighting oppressive dimensions and experiences, grappling with a complex and constantly changing social reality requires critical sociological knowledge of social connections that produce structural differences and similarities. It also tries to comprehend caste-class-specific gender relations and

patriarchal forms, as well as account for significant disparities and divides among women. Preethika Mani points out:

By the 1950s the Hindi and Tamil literary spheres . . . not only portrayed male and female characters who questioned traditional gender roles but also began to integrate the voices of women writers into their circles in an effort to create a more broadly appealing and comprehensive humanist aesthetic. . . . In this transitional context, during which women writers were considered as potential but not yet properly 'literary' writers, Mannu Bhandari and R. Chudamani rose to prominence. (161)

It's also important to comprehend how formal schooling may disrupt existing caste and class reproducing mechanisms, with a focus on the perspectives of young, educated dalit youths. Dalit group, which has historically been regarded outside of the four-tier caste system, has long been associated with public cleaning activities including such as manual scavenging and trash collecting. Dalits have historically been shunned in both villages and cities, with little to no recourse to any sort of education and limited contact with other groups.

Caste is defined by M. N. Srinivas as a "hereditary, endogamous, usually localized group having traditional associations with an occupation and a particular position in the local hierarchy of castes" (155). Women's 'subjugation and vulnerability' in India is rooted in Hindu caste systems and patriarchal familial customs, which place women in a disadvantageous position in their daily lives. Catherine Argiropoulos and Indhu Rajagopal opine, "Although the Indian government formally abolished the caste system in 1949 by legislation, it is still a part of the social fabric in India because of its traditional moorings. . . . Women can still be condemned

to a life of poverty depending on their position within the caste system” (614). The present chapter discusses the role of caste in women’s subjugation as depicted by P. Sivakami in *The Taming of Women*. The author of the novel belongs to the dalit community, so it is relevant to provide a brief overview of dalit literature in order to compare the representation of caste in her novel.

Dalit literature “offers a vital insight into Dalit culture . . . [through the works of] Dalit writers, including Namdev Dhasal, Daya Pawar, Prahlad Chandvarkar, Tryambak Sapke, Arjun Dangle, Prakash Jadhar and Shiva Ingole portrayed more authentically the challenges, suffering, and torment endured by and witnessed by the group” (Singh 9). Ravindra Kumar Singh further points out that in Maharashtra dalit literature became visible with the incidents of the conversion of dalits to Buddhism which gave them a new religious and political identity. However, he opines, “caste consciousness and social differences are subjects of Dalit writings, there are many similarities-issues of gender and the question of human dignity. The subjugation of Dalits by the privileged in the name of religion and tradition is delineated in such writings” (9).

Bama is one of the most renowned names among the feminist women writers in Indian Regional Literature who takes the plight of Dalit Women’s subjugation. Bama is a Tamil writer and in her novel *Sangathi*, which was originally written in 1994 and later translated into English by Lakshmi Holmstrom, she “adopts appropriate style to depict the exploitations and marginalisation of women in the patriarchal society” (Navya 21). Bama’s *Karukku* in Tamil and Urmila Pawar’s *The Weave of My Life* in Marathi are examples of first-person dalit feminist writings from the regional female authors in Indian Literature who have shared their own experience of being a female and a dalit. Likewise, Baby Kamble through her autobiography *The Prisons We Broke*

brings out the plight of dalit women as Aarti Vishwakarma asserts, “The text foregrounds the practice of untouchability and the atrocities hurled by the patriarchal system on Dalit women. It showcases Dalit women’s triple marginalization i.e. in terms of gender, caste, and class. . . . For Dalit women, gender discrimination, caste discrimination, and patriarchal domination go hand in hand” (110). Through their autobiographies, they have depicted the condition of low-caste dalit women in Indian societies.

Dalits have been oppressed as well as controlled by higher castes from the beginning of existence. People are denied all fundamental necessities, and people are denied the equitable footing in their community that they need. Since they pertain to the lowest social strata, individuals are shunned and driven to the outside of civilization. The plight of dalit women becomes even worse. As Christi A. Merrill points out, “The title of Kausalya Baisantry’s 1999 autobiographical account, *Dohra Abhishaap* (Doubly cursed), announces that she is writing with a specific goal in mind: to protest the combined curses of untouchability and patriarchy in India” (52). So in the rural parts of India women face double oppression of gender and caste. The life of low-caste women is very miserable in India and a number of incidents report almost everyday about some injustice towards dalit women. “The targeted killings of Dalit women and ritually sanctioned forms of violence have a formidable presence in Dalit women's life in comparison to upper and/or middle caste women” (Srivastava 41).

Therefore, special attention should be paid to how they manage as well as live in these appalling conditions. “Dalit women’s status is that of a beast that carries the burden of the whole family, the household and also the society in a mute and deaf condition almost like a beast of burden” (Raj and Pooja 58). The greatest part of dalit

women live in rural areas with few basic facilities and low socioeconomic status. The majority of them are normal wage or farm labourers, and others attempt to involve them in low-level jobs to support their families, but this also does not assist their case since women are paid much less than males. In her book *Gender and Caste* (2005), Anupama Rao says:

Caste relations are embedded in the Dalit woman's profoundly unequal access to resources of basic survival such as water and sanitation facilities, as well as educational institutions, public places, and places of religious worship. On the other hand, the material deprivation of Dalits and their political powerlessness perpetuates the symbolic structures of untouchability, which legitimizes the upper caste's access to Dalit women for sexual exploitation. (11)

So being a woman and also a dalit is a sin in a patriarchal culture and society where an individual's caste and sex play a vital role in one's treatment by the people surrounding her.

A great deal of the Indian Regional Literature on dalit women focuses on discrimination and abuse that arises from the interconnections of class, caste, and gender. Nitya Rao asserts, "Women's bodies, sexuality, and reproductive choices are linked to the ideological hegemony of the caste—gender nexus in India, with marriage and sexual relations playing crucial roles in maintaining caste boundaries" (410). Limiting low-caste women's liberty is essentially how the caste system is maintained. "Dalit women's narratives that reflect multiple concerns and dilemmas about marital choice and violence, generating in the process a deeper understanding of agency, voice, and gender relations, as fluid, dynamic, and intersecting in response to changing experiences" (Rao 410).

Most of the dalit women's writings deal with the theme of violence against their women characters for different reasons. P. Sivakami has also used domestic violence as one of the central aspects of women's subjugation in their families. Rural women frequently encounter assault and intimidation, which are actions and attitudes that violate the rights of others and hurt people physically, emotionally, or sexually, in addition to discrimination and unequal treatment. Males and females hold different levels of power, which contributes to violence against women. It can also be committed against individuals who do not fit into predetermined societal standards (Veur et al. 43).

Dalit women are double oppressed in Indian societies; first for being a low caste dalit and then a female. Their experiences are always different from those of upper caste/class women as Bhushan Sharma points out, "The 'outsider within' social location of Dalit women gives them a distinctive perspective on social, political, economic, and intellectual realities. He further asserts, "*The Weave of My Life* and *The Prisons We Broke*, reveal and discuss their idiosyncratically different suffering, interlocking oppressions of caste, class, and gender, and also explicate the factors that bring this difference into existence" (37). The main characters of Baby Kamble and Urmila Pawar also explain the complexities of their own lives as well as the intricate web of numerous females in their neighbourhood. By creatively utilising their social position and bringing attention to the marginalised opinions of those who are socially excluded perspectives and have a deeper knowledge of society as a whole as a result of their deprived circumstances, dalit female writers construct a 'Dalit Feminist Stance' (Sharma 28). Bhushan Sharma further opines:

To maintain their caste and gender ideology, women are prevented from going to court, and the decision of the Panchayat is final. The full account of

Mariamamma in Bama's *Sangati* (2005) and Thangam in P. Sivakami's *The Grip of Change* (2006) are testimonies to this social cruelty. Therefore, the standpoint made by Dalit women writers echoes Kimberle Crenshaw's assertion (1991) that the feminist theory addresses only one form of marginalized identity (gender) but neglects the intersection of multiple operational identities of caste, gender, and class. Indian feminism has not broadened its perspective to encompass the concerns of Dalit women, and a sisterhood cannot be assumed based on gender only. (30)

India is a multilingual and multicultural nation and most of the population resides in rural areas where the social deformity of caste is as integral as the concept of gender. Therefore, for women residing in the interior regions of India, the problem of caste is as important as gender inequality as depicted by numerous women low-caste writers in their writings. The problem of the caste system is deeply rooted in Indian societies and "caste has made and remade over a long period of time. The fluidity of caste has existed and persisted because of India's remarkable cultural diversity and physical environment, the diversity of its States (provinces) and political systems" (Kanhaya 260). Gender and caste disparities are firmly entrenched in Indian society, as well as the unexpected rise in wealth has resulted in power politics by a few patricians robbing minorities of fundamental rights.

The majority of dalit women live in rural areas with limited access to basic services and are economically disadvantaged. Almost all of them are normal wage workers, farm labourers, and others who endeavour to hire them for low-skilled jobs to assist their families. However, this does not support their issue, considering women are paid significantly less than men. They are even sexually exploited by men of the upper

caste/class and physically abused by men of their own caste. As they are unable to take revenge upon the upper caste/class men they beat up their own wives/daughters. Therefore, women of the lower caste have to face discrimination at multiple levels and hence caste plays a very vital role in her sufferings.

This is the reason why Dalit Feminist Theory “redefines feminism by introducing the category of Dalit into the core of feminist thought. It supplements feminism by adding caste to its study and praxis; it also re-examines and rethinks Indian feminism by replacing it with a new paradigm, namely, that caste-based feminist inquiry offers the only theoretical vantage point for comprehensively addressing gender-based injustices” (Arya and Rathore ii). Indian feminism cannot be complete in its true sense without the inclusion of the struggle of Indian low-caste/class women. As Sumit Srivastava points out, “There is an ongoing struggle by those at the periphery to be included in the core of the movement. The Dalit women in the Naxalite movement in Bihar represent the same cause and concern” (31). This only justifies the cause of dalit women as they are doubly oppressed in Indian classical patriarchal societies which is the root cause of their sufferings in the culturally governed power structure where women are oppressed at different levels.

As Anupama Rao in *Gender and Caste* asserts, “Women are embraced by ‘multiple patriarchies’ distinguished by the customary practices of caste and religious communities . . . new form of inequality amongst women by projects of gender reform, and suggest that gender justice will need to be re-conceptualized as dispersed and multiply inflected by the prevalent forms of gender inequality within caste communities” (27). Many regional women writers have taken up the issue of caste in their writings. *The Grip of Change* by P. Sivakami “draws attention to the Dalit woman

as a fictional figure for the fraught relations between caste, gender and sexuality. The novel centres on the exploited and supposedly violable body of the Dalit woman, which is inscribed with inter-caste struggles for power even as it is constituted as a site of power and resistance” (Keshavamurthy 124).

The dalit minority, particularly in rural India, suffers the burden of caste discrimination, which includes limited accessibility to freshwater, property, commerce, and religious establishments. The majority of their business takes place outside of traditional physical bounds. While caste discrimination affects all members of the dalit community, women bear the brunt of retaliatory fury. According to the ancient Varna system, dalit women are at the bottom of society. Women are often victimised as a result of traditional ideological views on chastity as well as conformism since they are easy targets. BR Ambedkar, a dalit activist and philosopher, saw women as portals to the caste system, irrespective of the hierarchical roles they hold within or outside the Varna system. Because of women’s perceived weakness, he believed that controlling women in a society converted into imposing power over the whole society. Upper-caste and dalit women have been subjected to continuous subjection for the sake of upholding tradition and establishing obvious social class divisions (Pardeshi).

It emerges from the discussions above that most of the dalit women’s literature divulges that the patriarchal social power structure of caste and gender is the root cause of women’s oppression in Indian societies. It further reveals that the condition of a dalit woman is far more vulnerable as compared to the upper caste women and even a dalit man. This patriarchal power structure forces a dalit woman to undergo multiple levels of oppression in Indian rural societies. By depicting their own experiences via autobiographies, most of the dalit women writers have given voice to the cause of the

dalit community. Sivakami in *The Taming of Women* also explores a dalit woman's exploitation by her own husband however it's not autobiographical and she also points out the male dalit leader's politics against the women of their own community. Before taking up the textual analysis, it would be appropriate here to discuss how various scholars and critics have commented upon the issue of caste in Sivakami's novel to find the voids in the research and take up the same in the present analysis.

Kiran Keshavamurthy in "P. Sivakami: The Caste and Gendered Body" points out the double oppression of dalit women in Sivakami's *The Grip of Change*. Deepa Nair and N. Nila, in "Docile Bodies and Dividing Practices in P. Sivakami's *The Taming of Women*" discuss the pathetic condition of women under patriarchal dominance. Yash Raj and others in "Raising the Voice against the Atrocities: A Critical Study of P Sivakami's *Taming of Women*" assert how dalit women are double oppressed in rural Indian societies. Shanmathi in "Ceaseless Sadism against Women in P. Sivakami's *The Taming of Women*" observes the sexual exploitation of a dalit woman in her own house. Pratibha Somkuwar and others have explored the double oppression of the dalit women and their struggle against it in Sivakami's *The Grip of Change*.

Therefore, the review of P. Sivakami's *The Taming of Women* shows that not many critics have explored the novel in a detailed manner so far. Several critics have commented upon gender inequality and sexual exploitation of women in P. Sivakami's *The Taming of Women* but only a few like Yash Raj, Siva Nagaiah Bolleddu, Venkata Ravi Kumar and Kola Aravind have discussed the role of caste in it. Further, no one has observed how Sivakami being a dalit herself exposes the politics of some rich male dalit leaders who discriminate against the women of their own community instead of helping them. They even sexually exploit the poor women of some other castes as well.

Caste in P. Sivakami's *The Taming of Women*

In *The Taming of Women*, Sivakami highlights the patriarchal domination in the lives of women through the portrayal of Periyannan, the antagonist, who grows up in an impoverished hamlet. He is always greedy for money and power, and he never cares about his family, particularly his wife Anandhayi and his sick mother. The novel depicts Periyannan's wicked character, as he used to abuse his wife and other women. He wants to live his life on his terms, with little regard for others. Sivakami exposes Anandhayi's terrible situation at the hands of her husband Periyannan. There are many instances in the tale that tell the reader about Anandhayi's trauma and suffering. The novel depicts the battle between males and females in modern society.

Sivakami is a Tamil Dalit writer and she has depicted the issues of women as prevailing in the State of Tamil Nadu. Tamil Nadu is a patriarchally dominated culture as C. Tamilarasi points out, "The women in Tamil Nadu were economically, socially, politically or even in matter of ritual completely dependent on men. It was thought that they did not deserve to be educated and had to be kept subjugated. They were tightened in the grip of men from birth to death" (408). Tamil Nadu is a State in India where caste and gender play a significant role in determining a woman's social status.

The caste system in Tamil Nadu comprises four major castes, namely Brahmins, Kshatriyas, Vaishyas and Shudras. Dalits, also known as the oppressed castes, occupy the lowest rung of the caste ladder. Women belonging to the dalit community in Tamil Nadu are subjected to multiple forms of discrimination, including social, economic and political marginalization. In addition, women in Tamil Nadu have to face gender-based oppression, which is further compounded by the intersection of caste and gender. The patriarchal structure of the society reinforces the notion that women are inferior to men,

and this is reflected in the low status accorded to women from lower castes. Women from the upper castes, on the other hand, enjoy greater privileges and are less likely to face discrimination. Therefore, the intersection of caste and gender in Tamil Nadu creates a complex web of oppression that affects women from the oppressed castes more severely.

The novel's first chapter portrays the plight of the female protagonist Anandhayi in the words of her mother-in-law, "What the hell do you have to weep for, I say? Why should a woman who's just given birth starve? So, the husband went to a whore, uh! Still, why should you go hungry? Is he all that you have in your life?" (*TOW* 17). Periyannan has brought another woman into his room to sleep with him when Anandhayi is pregnant. This demonstrates men's inhumanity towards women in their homes.

Periyannan pushes Anandhayi forcefully in this condition without having any regard for her health. Due to Periyannan's pathetic conduct, his mother never expects anything from him. He never cares about the health of his elderly, sick mother, which irritates her further. She has made the decision not to live at the mercy of her son. Periyannan after receiving a large construction deal flung a bundle of money at her feet and humiliated his own mother by saying, "Have you ever seen this much money before?" (*TOW* 63); this conduct testifies to his disobedient character. She wishes death would come and steal her life. Most of the time, her husband's memories struck her. Periyannan's father attempted suicide by consuming 'yergum' (toxic plant juice), and his mother could never forget how he used to ill-treat her as well. Periyannan's attitude towards women becomes quite clear from his dialogues with his wife when he says, "Adiye, why the hell should I be scared of you? I only have to whistle and I can have any woman I want" (*TOW* 59).

On the basis of her research on the status of the low-caste women in Tamil Nadu, Nitya Rao asserts, “I analyze Dalit women’s narratives that reflect multiple concerns and dilemmas about marital choice and violence, generating in the process a deeper understanding of agency, voice, and gender relations, as fluid, dynamic, and intersecting in response to changing experiences, positionalities, and subjectivities” (410). Sivakami in this narrative also portrays the pathetic condition of these low-caste women in the rural areas of the State. Through the character of Periyannan, Sivakami reveals how money and power are spoiling the minds of dalit males like Periyannan who after being powerful tries to suppress the easiest target available to him i.e. women.

Indirectly the novelist may be targeting dalit leaders and powerful people who instead of helping the poor people of their own community try to dominate and control the helpless dalit males and especially females. As Kiran Keshavamurthy points out in Sivakami’s *The Grip of Change*, “It wasn’t simply that the upper castes exploit the lower castes. A lower caste leader might exploit his own people. It is not only upper-caste men who prey on lower-caste women. Men like Kathamuthu are perfectly capable of taking advantage of vulnerable women” (135). Similar is the stance of Periyannan who tries to control every woman he encounters whether his own wife, mother, daughters or even a high-caste helpless poor woman like Lakshmi. Therefore, in *The Taming of Women*, Sivakami targets the corruption prevailing at every level in Indian rural societies dominated by a hypocritical patriarchal culture where women are subjugated at multiple levels.

Sivakami in this novel holds that gender discrimination predominates over caste as Lakshmi who belongs to a higher caste suffers even more adversely than Anandhayi.

Although most of the dalit writers have presented their cases by always throwing the blame on higher caste males for that they have been even criticized for political gains, however, Sivakami, on the other hand, portrays the reality of the hypocritical patriarchal deformities pertaining to even in her own society leaving aside the issue of caste. So Sivakami through her narrative wants to highlight that gender disparity works at multiple levels where a rich and powerful low-caste male can sexually exploit even a poor woman of any upper caste.

Caste relationships are embedded in the dalit woman's severely uneven accessibility to elements of simple substances like freshwater and sewage services, as well as academic facilities and public places, including sites of religious worship. In *The Taming of Women*:

The basic amenities play a vital role in the growth of the story. The food changes according to the gender and class of the characters. The dressing is also affected by the status in the family and society. The husband's identity directly affects the home, which provides shelter to the women in the novels. The women in the novels depend on the family and cannot see themselves as self-determining women. (Kumar and Jaisre 104)

The economic privation of dalits and their legislative helplessness, on either hand, perpetuate the symbolic frameworks of casteism, legitimising higher caste admittance to dalit women's sexual enslavement. Sivakami clearly explains how social prejudice has hindered dalit women's progress in their very own neighbourhoods.

Athira S Kumar and V. Jaisre assert, "The food also portrays the role of women in the household. Even though the women in the house prepare the meals, they must be served to the men first, then the wife or daughter can eat them. Kanji is served as the

staple food in *The Taming of Women* and millets, and corn is served on special festive occasions” (104). Such illustrations show the poor food habits of the lower caste people. Women have to spend quite economically on food items and they need to serve to males before they can have some. Sivakami not only portrays the gloomy side of the equation, but she still emphasises the lighter side of this argument by portraying the dalit women's determination and endurance.

The caste system serves as a barrier to domestic growth in a country such as India, which is claimed to be expanding and rising in international forums. Low-caste women are mainly oppressed in this as Bhushan Sharma and K. A. Geetha point out, “The lower social, political, and economic status of Dalit women makes them undergo the rigidities of double patriarchal oppression. One is intrinsic patriarchy, which is the oppression of Dalit women by the men of their community. They are taxed, abused, and beaten by the men the families” (3). In Sivakami’s *The Taming of Women* Anandhayi, her daughters and even her mother-in-law are the victims of intrinsic patriarchy which conditions men to become the Hitlers of their own domestic sphere. Pariyanan is the true embodiment of this patriarchal conditioning who tries to keep every woman under his control by even using physical violence against them. “The second is the extrinsic patriarchy, which is the oppression and exploitation of Dalit women by the men of dominant castes. They experience economic and labour exploitation and also endure violence by men of the dominant castes” (Sharma and Geetha 3).

However, Sivakami has depicted an opposite situation of extrinsic patriarchy through the illicit relationship of Lakshmi and Pariyanan. Here Pariyanan, a rich dalit male, physically and mentally assaults Lakshmi who is the daughter of a high-caste but extremely poor family. So when she ran away from his clutches to her home he flings a bundle of cash on her father’s face and brings her back with him without being

concerned about her high-caste. The incident shows that in India the status or class of a family also plays a vital role in the treatment of women. A number of incidents are reported in India where a father himself gives away his daughter for the sake of money as for him she doesn't have any importance. For instance, on May 24, 2023, *The Times of India* reports, "A seven-year-old girl was bought for Rs 4.5 lakh in Virjapura village of Maniya PS area and was married to a man aged 28-30. The family which bought the girl was arrested and upon interrogation, they confessed that they bought the girl from her father for Rs 4.50 lakh."

Therefore, being a dalit, Sivakami has taken a brave stance of pointing out such social deformities where a low-caste rich male can also assault a high-caste poor girl in order to take revenge or for any other motive. Like a true feminist, she gives more importance to gender disparity than the problem of caste in Indian societies.

Women act in self-limiting ways not because they are socialised as women, but because they are trapped in a culture where women lack decision-making authority, are invisible, and have many roles. *The Taming of Women* by P. Sivakami emphasises the need for continuous efforts by both males and females to eliminate socio-cultural obstacles, stereotyped attitudes, and abuse of women in order to achieve a gender-balanced society. On one of the occasions when Lakshmi raises her voice against Pariyanan's cruelty, Anandhayi thinks, "I've never seen a woman. Perhaps any beautiful woman, even if she came straight from the sky, will want to keep the man under her control and even slap him around ..." (*TOW* 129). Like many other traditional civilizations, Indian society is still patriarchal. Specific cultural metaphors are used to convey patriarchal ideals governing sexuality, reproduction, and social production. There are overt restrictions preventing women from participating in some key activities and depriving them of some privileges.

Metaphor, on the other hand, is a much more delicate manifestation of patriarchy, i.e., sending messages of women's inferiority via tales that emphasise the self-sacrificing, self-effacing pure picture of women. It is also reflected in liturgical activities that highlight the role of women as loyal spouses and pious moms on a daily basis. Women are also taught not to speak up against inequality, subjugation, oppression, and subjection at all levels of society (Shivakumar and Manimakalai 433). In contrast, men even in their teenage are conditioned to be proud of even if they misbehave/illtreat a woman. As Sivakami depicts when Lakshmi rises against Pariyanan's physical assaults and tries to oppose his beatings, "Anandhayi held Lakshmi as Mani kicked her on her chest, cursing, 'Do you even call yourself a woman?'" (128) Which demonstrates the patriarchal conditioning of the psyche of the males and females of a society where a man can do anything with a woman but she not even has a right to defend herself. Such gender disparities are easily accepted in Indian low-caste families and even teenage males like "Mani feel as if he was the man of the house. He walked about with a newfound dignity" (129). Men develop such a psyche due to the social and cultural deformities based on caste and gender discrimination in Indian societies.

"In India, the problems of women are compounded by the complex and oppressive caste matrix. If women have it hard in a patriarchal, Brahminical society, Dalit and Muslim women have it much, much harder" (Chanda-Vaz). For Indian society, caste and class structure is a curse. It separates Indian culture into sectarian and social strata. As K. R. Meera points out, "Your caste mattered most in the old days" (119) and "Wonder caste is such a glaring reality in this country even now" (331). The caste system is deep-rooted in Indian societies and in *Gendering Caste* Uma Chakravarti asserts:

The basis of inequality underlying the caste system in India is the application of evaluative— value-based—standards in placing particular castes as high or low. These standards are rooted in the Dharmashastras, the religio-legal texts of the Hindus. As the system developed, the high and the low were opposed to each other because of their respective associations with notions of pure and impure in terms of purity of blood and the nature of work. (10)

As the majority of the Indian population is quite religious, therefore, they blindly follow the religious scriptures without understanding their true meaning.

Violence against women in the home is an age-old story in which males believe it is their right to enslave and undermine older women and generations. Melody Graulich finds “violence against women as the widespread and inevitable consequence of the historical belief that men have the right to dominate women and to use force to coerce compliance with their wishes. Abuse of women appears as socially acceptable rather than aberrant behaviour” (14). Women are subjected to a variety of atrocities under patriarchy, ranging from perversion of speech to sexual assault by spouses in the guise of wedding to rendering women the family’s silent members and pushing them into poverty.

Feminism crawled into all areas of life and every nook and cranny of society to change women’s lives. It was somewhat effective in strengthening the socio-cultural, economic, and financial circumstances of women on all frontiers. Feminism's triumph was aided by legislation, the constitution, art, and culture. Literature has helped to popularise feminism and raise awareness about the dangers of gender inequality. The result was feminist literature, whose goal was to promote equal rights for women and depict existing inequality as harmful to families and society as a whole. But feminism

in India is still unable to provide enough justice to the low-caste or class women and their issues are still marginalized in the powerful patriarchal and caste structure in India.

Therefore, the caste system is a real curse in Hindu societies. Due to the power structure in the caste hierarchy, the individuals of the lower caste are exploited by the members of the higher caste. The discussions in the chapter show that dalit women are the worst victims of the caste system in the Hindu religion. dalit women are double or triple oppressed in the hierarchy of casteism in India. P. Sivakami who is herself a dalit, points out the patriarchal oppression of dalit women in their households. Sivakami in *The Taming of Women* quite boldly points out the patriarchal politics of dalit men on the women of their own caste. She portrays how powerful patriarchal men like Periyannan exploit physically and mentally not only the women of their society but also the high-caste poor women like Lakshmi. Through her narrative, Sivakami exposes the patriarchal politics at all levels of Indian societies where a woman has no escape since her birth and she is discriminated against during her whole life as a daughter, as a wife and even as a mother.

Religion and its Role in Women's Subjugation

Religion also plays a very complex role in the sufferings of people as depicted by Ila Arab Mehta in *Fence*. The novel is set in the western Indian State of Gujarat where religious practices hold immense value. Hinduism dominates as the primary religion in this region with Islam and Jainism trailing behind it. The State boasts numerous eminent pilgrimage locations for Hindus including Somnath Temple, Dwarkadheesh Temple and Akshardham Temple among others. Aside from these sacred sites, vibrant celebrations such as Navratri, Diwali and Uttarayan define Gujarat's colourful cultural

landscape too. The region has a thick layer of rich history which displays itself through its people notorious for their welcoming attitude towards believers of all religious denominations.

Carolyn Heitmeyer observes, “The role of religion in contemporary Gujarat remains both contradictory and highly contested: the rise of politicised Hinduism and Islamism, which has gained strength in recent decades, remains at odds with the many forms of everyday religious practice which blur the boundaries of more reified religious doctrine” (485). Gujarat is a Hindu-majority State where Muslims are seen as others as Sanderien Verstappen opines, “India witnesses a proliferation of ‘Muslim’ and ‘Hindu’ residential areas, which reflect deepening segregation along religious lines . . . ‘Muslim areas’ in Indian cities and towns can be seen as centres of urban and rural–urban connectivity, but are usually portrayed as sites of isolation and ‘ghettoisation’” (53).

This hints towards some serious Hindu-Muslim conflicts in Gujarat. Yogesh Chandrani in his doctoral research finds out that Muslims are treated as others in Gujarat and Hinduism is one of the main reasons for the same as it is a Hindu-dominated State. During his research, he finds that several “Muslims in Gujarat continue to suffer from the effects of the violence, and the very real injustices and injuries that were inflicted upon them have yet to be acknowledged” (248).

Therefore, an orthodox approach to religion leads to conflicts with the people of other religions as is the case in Gujarat. Further, the patriarchal propagators also use religion to discriminate against women and to prove them inferior to males. “Religious patriarchy is the systematic exclusion of women from roles of religious authority – often based on the presupposition that god is male. . . . The patriarchal mindset is the foundation of most religious institutions in India, particularly Hinduism, Christianity

and Islam” (George 21). M. T. Stepaniants opines, “Feminists are fully justified in their observation that Christianity remains a ‘men's religion’ that upholds stereotypes against women” (241).

“In Christianity, woman is symbolically represented by two persons: Eve and the Virgin Mary. In the first case woman is a personification of Evil, for the responsibility for man's Fall is borne by Eve, while Mary personifies absolute chastity and ‘eternal femininity’” (Stepaniants 242). However, Jamal A. Badawi opines, “Woman according to the Quran is not blamed for Adam's first mistake. Both were jointly wrong in their disobedience to God, both repented, and both were forgiven.” This shows the patriarchal aspects of Christianity have discriminated against women in a number of ways in the name of religion and traditional culture.

Mostly men are seen as religious preachers, ritual performers and transmitters of God's message to the whole of humanity. Therefore, “Attitudes developed around patriarchal interpretations of religious belief have defined and shaped the social and cultural contexts of Indian women resulting in their disempowerment and second-class status” (Saldanha). Males have always used religion as a tool to keep women under their control in the name of morality and faith. As Virginia Saldanha further asserts, “The language, symbols and culturally conditioned interpretation of religious scriptures have evolved a practice that alienates women and even influences exploitation and violence towards them.” Women are forced to live in a feminine way by showing them the fear of their faith and religion. Frances Raday is of the view that religion and culture both get influenced by each other but only “religions, not cultures, have codified custom into binding source books that predate the whole concept of gender equality and have both the legal and the institutional structures to enforce their principles” (669).

Due to this a number of cultural practices in the name of religion get difficult to challenge in law anywhere especially in a country like India where most people follow the religion blindly. Therefore, many illegal/inhuman practices against women are defended in the name of religion and culture. In the Hindu religion patriarchal practices like preference for a son which leads to female infanticide, dowry, forced marriages, honour killing of females by their own family members, “a husband’s right to obedience and power to discipline or commit acts of violence against his wife, including marital rape” (Raday 671) and “restriction of women to the roles of housewives or mothers, without a balanced view of women as autonomous and productive members of civil society” (Raday 670).

“Religious patriarchy is the systematic exclusion of women from roles of religious authority –often based on the presupposition that god is male” (Kuttikat 21). Religious customs along with culture also play a part in the subjugation of women as “in Indian patriarchal society, a servile obedience is demanded from women. Women are conditioned not to expect an elevated status like men” (Irshad et al. 16). Religion and culture are the two major forces in India that contribute quite significantly to creating the psyche of an individual in any Indian society. Moreover, religious and cultural propagations are very much controlled by patriarchy in every region of India.

As Naseera N.M. and Moly Kuruvilla opine, “Religion is the most potent force and institution behind patriarchal social life and structure. The majority of organized religions propagate male supremacy and repression over women and subdue their sexuality, mobility, and reproductive choices. They characterize women as physically, mentally, emotionally and sexually inferior to men” (22). Religious patriarchy is the most problematic hurdle in the lives of Indian women as almost every Indian is quite

religious in nature and follows anything in the name of religion quite blindly and rigorously.

“The status of women in society is an outcome of the interpretation of religious texts and of the cultural and institutional set-up of religious communities” (Klingorova and Havlicek 2). Many Hindu religious scriptures and mythological texts have a great role in stereotyping the images of women in Indian Hindu societies. A woman in Hindu societies is always associated with qualities like chastity, fidelity, purity and honest servitude towards her husband and her family. As Jayasree K. Kuniyath and K. C. Sankaranarayanan opine:

Indian Hindu mythology especially related with women has mainly associated with the deities and their human incarnations, sage’s wives, curses or boons and the idea of karma about life. Forsooth substantiate morally indefensible attitude towards women man made stories, epics, folk stories and narrations made chastity, virginity, fidelity, obedience of women as good qualities and fickleness of women as a controllable element of women character to create faceless, self-sacrificing dump women who is absolutely ready for serving her husband and his family.

However, being a religious country, in India, earlier religion was never suspected as a patriarchal tool to discriminate against women but later on many feminist activists started to observe it as one of the major cultural aspects in stereotyping the image of women and a reason of gender inequality in literature and society. In the name of religion, patriarchy moulds the individuals differently and projects women as inferior to men in every sphere of life, thus, resulting in the conflicts among sexes and women’s discrimination in Indian societies.

Through her reading of Hindu religious texts, Ibameai Hepsa Nongbri holds that Manu made the observation that men were meant to be the ones who carried on the family line, while women were meant to be mothers and endure offspring. Additionally, Manu says that the male is the germinating agent and the woman is the fertile soil. In the patriarchal home, having children is perceived as the most critical requirement for a bride, and being childless is viewed as unimportant. According to Manu, the woman is the apparent manifestation because she bears and raises the child. Through her reading of *Yajnavalkyasmriti*, she observes that according to this text, the sole purpose of a woman's life is to bear a male child and that is only possible if she remains a submissive wife and an obeying daughter (81).

This shows that male child was preferred as compared to female and women were expected to live under the control of men. She must cling to her duties even after the death of her husband even in the early days of her marriage. However, many positive conceptions of women are also depicted in these Hindu religious scriptures like women being worshipped as Goddesses but the patriarchal-dominated cultural societies only propagate male-centred texts like *Dharamshastras* and *Manusamritis* which are discriminative towards women.

In the Muslim religion, many scholars are of the view that the *Quran* gives equal status to both men and women. "The *Quran*, in addressing the believers, often uses the expression, 'believing men and women' to emphasize the equality of men and women in regard to their respective duties, rights, virtues and merits" (Rahman). As Manjur Hossain Patoari also asserts:

Islam is such a religion which has first given to women a place of dignity and honour because, before the advent of Islam, there was huge discrimination

towards women. Islam abolished inhumanity, inequality, and discrimination towards women as well as giving a complete code of conduct for both males and females. Prior to the arrival of Islam, the pagan Arabs used to bury their female children alive, make women dance naked in the vicinity of Ka'ba during their annual fairs and treated women just like slaves or chattels and they used women only for their sexual contentment who possess no rights, dignity, honour or position. (1212)

Likewise, Jane I. Smith points out, "From the Muslim perspective, Islam provides women with a position of honor and respect, with clearly stated rights and obligations. The Quran affords legal protections in the areas of marriage, divorce, and inheritance that are considered to mark a vast improvement over the situation of in pre-Islamic society" (517). However, Manjur Hossain Patoari opines, "Islam has ensured gender equality and women's rights in every sphere of their life. Islam has guaranteed the rights of men and women in an equal degree and there is no discrimination between men and women. But due to the prevailing socio-cultural norms and practices . . . sometimes the guarantee of Islam does not get translated into tangible actions" (1211). So it is only the patriarchal culture and customs that manipulate the religion as per their needs.

Therefore, the ruling dominant patriarchal preachers have moulded the writings/sayings of the *Quran* as per their preferences and projected the same through their preachings to all the ignorant people of their religion as the majority of the population never read the holy scriptures in the first place. "The patriarchal mindset is the foundation of most religious institutions in India, particularly Hinduism, Christianity and Islam . . . and it inflicts deep psychological wounds on those who are

dominated. Patriarchy is the root cause of the exclusion of women from roles of religious authority, and it must be exorcised from all the major religious traditions” (George). Further, the discussion on religion in Gujarat shows how Hindu-Muslim orthodox propagators turns the people of opposite sides against each other in the name of religion.

In a religious country like India, the role of religion is vital in creating a sound impact on the psyche of the individuals. In all the religious scriptures and traditional customs, men are always considered superior to women whatever the reasons may be for the same. However, this hierarchal representation of the sexes has given great room for the patriarchy to subjugate women and keep them always in a subordinate position in all aspects of life. This psychological conditioning of the minds of the individuals has created a negative impact on gender equality as both males and females have been following these religious customs for ages. A number of feminist writings “reveal an acute understanding of the gendered nature of religion and the political agenda behind the centuries-old systematic vilification of women by men” (Nath 186). In this way, traditional societies use religion as a weapon against women to keep them always in subordinate positions in society by showing the fear of religion. Many Hindu religious scriptures and Brahminical texts/preachings are also responsible for dividing Indian societies into various upper and lower castes. Before discussing the novel, it is appropriate here to give a brief of views or comments of various scholars and critics about Mehta and especially on her novel.

In a book review on *Feminism in India*, Poulomi Pal points out Mehta’s emancipation of a girl belonging to a minority in the Hindu-dominated State of Gujarat. She also highlights how women still struggle to hold property rights in India. Sudhagee

points out Mehta's exploration of Fateema as an independent woman in a male-dominated society. Nilanjana S. Roy opines that Fateema receives more assistance in her struggle from strangers instead of people from her own religion. Nipam Chauhan observes that being a feminist, Mehta aptly portrayed a woman's emancipation and her fight for equality in a male-dominated culture where all the privileges are given to men only.

It emerges from the above reviews on Mehta's *Fence* that most of the critics talk about a single woman's emancipation and her fight to hold equal property rights with men in Indian rural societies. So the following section discusses the role of Muslim religion in the subjugation of women as depicted by Ila Arab Mehta in *Fence*. It further seeks to problematize a Hindu writer Ila Arab Mehta's stance on dealing with the Muslim religion and on the stereotypical portrayal of the Muslim Jihad which has been totally ignored in the research conducted on the novel so far.

Religion in Ila Arab Mehta's *Fence*

The story of Ila Arab Mehta's *Fence* revolves around the struggle and emancipation of a Muslim girl, Fateema in a Hindu-dominated society. She belongs to a poor family yet her parents provide their full support to get their children educated including Fateema. Some of the traditional males like her brother Karim are against a woman's higher education and they try everything to halt the same but Fateema never gives up and with her hard work and dedication she completes her higher education and ultimately gets a job as a college teacher. As the story progresses, Fateema begins to question the restrictions placed on her by her religion and culture. She is torn between her desire for freedom and the expectations placed on her by her family and community. The education of women is given the utmost importance in the novel through the struggle of

Fateema. It is only education which can contribute immensely to women's empowerment, especially in the rural regions where there is no other scope. Mehta explores Fateema as a strong independent woman who fights against every odd in her life and at last owns an independent house to live alone beside a Hindu community.

In *Fence*, Ila Arab Mehta depicts how Muslim people use their religion and cultural conditions to keep women under their control. The narrative is set in the Hindu-dominated State of Gujarat where Hindu-Muslim conflicts are quite common. Many critics are of the view that the ruling party in Gujarat “triggered communal violence that ended with the police arresting many more Muslims than Hindus—a pattern repeated in Madhya Pradesh and Rajasthan. Two months later, Muslim women alleged a biased response and violence by the state police, while they battled for survival as husbands, fathers, brothers, and sons were jailed or fled to escape arrest” (Raj and Gurmat). Kaushik Raj and Sabah Gurmat further reveal that the condition of Muslim women becomes dreadful as “Shakarpur and Hassan Nagar were emptied of their men, as those who were not arrested, fled, leaving behind the women, who spoke with Article 14 about living in fear, barely making ends meet, while they waited to hear from fathers, husbands, brothers and sons, but did not dare call, fearing the police may track them down.”

Similarly, in the context of Hindu-Muslim conflicts in Gujarat, a Human Rights Activist, J. S. Bandukwala asserts, “The current political situation will eventually mandate for a disturbed area act on a national level, and eventually Hindus and Muslims will live in separate areas. Many people outside Gujarat don't see it coming, but we do” (qtd. in Ankita). Therefore, there is a strong fence dividing Hindus and Muslims in Gujarat which has resulted in a lot of communal riots over there. Therefore,

in such a hateful environment among Muslims and Hindus, Mehta's depiction of a Muslim girl, Fateema who fights against the patriarchal Muslim customs to be an economically independent woman and own a house for herself with the support of Hindus seems quite unrealistic.

Fence by Ila Arab Mehta explores the intersection of religion, gender, and identity. Religion and its traditional customs are at the core of Indian societies. Indian regional literatures and even Indian English literature are also very much influenced by the profound impression of religion and traditional culture. The mythology depicted in *Vedas*, *Puranas*, *Smritis* and great Indian epics like *Ramayana* and *Mahabharata* have a strong influence on Indian literary texts and “until the 19th century, themes, motifs, and forms in the literature composed in modern languages in India were largely traditional. . . . Subjects were mostly taken from the huge stock of religious imagination developed in the Sanskrit *Purānas* and in Sanskrit epic literature” (Wessler 659). This in turn has a permanent mark on the psyche of the individuals residing in Indian societies. These epics and their mythical stories still have a permanent presence in the mind of Indians as Sri Aurobindo opines, “They represent Indian way of life and a view of family system and society. These epics represent an overview of ancient Indian culture and traditions which are still being carried by Indians” (qtd. In Jindal 252). Such an orthodox religious psyche of individuals becomes a problem for gender equality in Indian societies as Mehta depicts through the story of Fateema who is forced to give away education and sit at home as according to religious practices women are not allowed to do so.

Therefore, religion is deeply rooted in the lives of Indian people as Madhu Jindal further asserts, “Religion and the attitude to religion has been a strong strand in

fiction, for religion intrudes into every sphere of life: learning, worship, rituals, birth, marriage and death, as well as the workplace, the social system, and the caste attitudes. It is also reflected in the philosophical beliefs and thus encompasses the personal, the interpersonal and the socio-political sphere” (252). So literature in a way becomes the propagator of religious customs and cultural traditions through the patriarchal lenses. Mostly these religious propagandists use the faith of the people in a negative way to serve their own political ends. As Mehta in *Fence* portrays the characters of Islamic Moulavies who propagate false Islamic sayings to the people in Madrasas. However, Mehta depicts all the Muslim male characters except Fateema’s father in a stereotypical manner as Muslim Jihadis which seems quite biased on her part.

The history of India shows how writers and critics have major reasons for focusing on spiritual and cultural defence methods that prevail in societies. During Hindu-Muslim rifts in the colonial period, works like *Anandamath* by Bankimchandra Chatterji in 1881 which contains the famous Indian hymn ‘Bande Mataram’ and “It is still used as a patriotic hymn in contemporary India, even though it contains a deeply rooted anti-Muslim message” (Wessler 660). Due to the cultural differences between Hindus and Muslims, Bankimchandra Chatterji aligns in his writings Hindus to the ‘self’ and all Muslims to the ‘other’ so “Bankim in his novels critically engages with these cultural power relations between Hindus and Muslims. His novels suggest a pattern; from an implicit expression of uncrossable boundaries between the two communities, the novels subsequently assume forms of absolute dichotomy” (Das and Das 579).

However, it is a fact that India’s golden past declined with the invasion of the Muslims and later by the Britisher’s colonial rule. Therefore, it remained the subject of

Indian regional literatures and many Indian writers like Michael Madhusudan Datt, Maithili Sharan Gupt, Mahavir Prasad Dwivedi etc wrote their poetry to keep it in the conscience of the Indian Hindus. Indian Sahitya Academy President Umashankar Joshi asserts, “While the reformers virulently attacked inhuman customs, superstition, dead rituals, and rigid dogma, the new writers, especially the new university graduates, developed a secular vein of writing. Patriotism, personal love, and social realities came to be the subject of poems, plays and novels.” Heinz-Werner Wessler opines, “Towards the end of the 19th century, tradition was more and more perceived in terms of a monolithic construction of culture cum religion baptized as ‘Hinduism’” (660). The purpose of discussing this is to show how religion can even impact the psyche of any writer as well and the writer can sometimes work as a religious propagator which might be the case why Mehta in *Fence* portrayed all Muslim males as jihadis.

Ranjana Das and Ranjan Das opine, “Though Bankim's nation fails to incorporate the Muslims and fundamentally indulges in the tasks of rejuvenating Hindu religion and culture, nevertheless, it was not anachronistic in its presumptions” (585). Since then Indian societies are divided in the name of religion and they are mentally conditioned by their respective religions through their literature and culture. In *Fence*, Ila Arab Mehta points out this fence or division which is always there in the life of the Indians due to which they are unable to accept the ‘other’ easily. This ‘other’ can be a person of a different religion or in patriarchy it applies to a woman as well in Indian societies as Mehta depicts through the life of her main protagonist in the novel.

This ‘other’ is evident through one of the incidents in the novel when one of Fateema’s friends once pointed out her name as “a differently sounding name” (34). In addition, these religious differences seem clear when Fateema wants to buy a house in

the midst of a Hindu society, her friend tells her, “Fateemaben, can I be honest? You . . . belong to another religion. If we sell you a house, we won’t be able to sell the rest” (*Fence* 227). Likewise, once one of her teachers chides Chandan, Fateema’s friend, when he says, “You are eating with a Musulman!” (*Fence* 228). There are a lot of differences in the practical life of people in Indian society based on their religions.

However, through this novel, Mehta desires a real society where there are no fences of caste, class or religion among people living in India. One day after Fateema’s class is over, a bright young man called Manish Dave approaches her to speak and he asks her, "Ben, you're a Muslim, aren't you?.. And yet you look like us, you speak like us” (*Fence* 3). At this Fateema replied, “Arre Manish, I am like you. I'm one of you! My teachers and friends are also...” and she further asserts, “My religion is different, but I am not” (*Fence* 3). Ila Arab Mehta's moving and astute narrative follows a woman's struggle to find her place in a world torn apart by communal violence, to reconcile her conflicting loyalties to her family and friends, and to find a place she can call ‘home,’ a place where fences – between societies, among people – are no longer required. As Fateema thinks, “We were supposed to hold hands in this country and progress together, why this fence then?” (232). Therefore, “Fateema, takes the house. Living together will bring down the prejudice, ignorance and contempt and, of course, the fence” (232). But in reality, such a dream in a State like Gujarat where Hindu-Muslim conflicts are quite evident seems quite mythological or even nearly impossible.

Fateema goes on to shatter a lot of barriers by landing a job in a large metropolis. She agrees to purchase a home until she realises that the builder may construct a wall between the two blocks of flats — one for Hindus and the other for Muslims. She firmly asserts, “I am a Muslim inhabitant of the multi-religious,

multicultural, multilingual republic of India is what I want to communicate” (215). At the end of the novel Mehta seeks a reply from the readers, “Do you think Hindu-Muslim unity can be achieved?” (215). That doesn't seem like an insurmountable objective, given her beliefs and attitude to all religions. However, the historical incidents of past and present in a Hindu-dominated State like Gujarat don't seem possible on practical grounds. The history of Gujarat shows a number of communal riots that had happened between Hindus and Muslims. Last to mention is:

an anti-Muslim pogrom in Gujarat, India, that began on February 28, 2002, and lasted for three days—approximately seventy-two hours. Officials rationalized the violence as a reaction—*pratikriya*—to the aggression of its victims. . . . Several mass killings were followed over a few months by many instances of violence on a lesser scale. Muslim homes and religious structures were desecrated and destroyed; Muslim commercial establishments were boycotted. (Ghassem-Fachandi 1)

Such incidents are always against humanity but the extremist people in every religion are the root cause of such communal bloodshed. Whenever anti-religious and brutal incidents like this happen in any society, it becomes nearly impossible for individuals of one religion in such society to accept the ‘other’ which Ila Arab Mehta is trying to propagate through her novel *Fence*.

Mehta depicts the negative attitude of Islam towards women's education as one of Fateema's teachers, Gaekwad, once points out, “You know, Fateema, how far behind we are with women's education, generally speaking. Muslim parents are particularly reluctant to send their daughters to school” (*Fence* 108). Once Fateema dreams about college life and shares her views with Kareem “he just glared at her: ‘Finish your tenth

grade. That's enough'" (*Fence* 62). Through the words of a Moulviji, Mehta asserts that Islam doesn't allow Muslims to study in English schools with students of other religions as the Moulviji instructs Fateema's father, "If your kids are studying here, that's not a good thing. And what is this, your daughter does not wear a burkha? You know about Islamic tenets, don't you?" (*Fence* 63). Some other characters in the novel like Rajab Ali, Anwar and Ammiji also have similar views towards women's education and freedom in Islam.

Through the character of Kareem, Mehta shows the negative implications of religion on the minds of the youth and how the brainwashing of young males is done by the extremists. Women in the Muslim religion are not given much freedom and they are not even allowed to go out without any male and burkha as Fateema recalls Kareem's words, "Shut up! Your tongue's wagging too much these days. We intend to advise every family to make its women wear a burkha. You will also have to wear one" (*Fence* 122). He once slapped her and threatened her by saying, "Bitch! You've become an infidel by hanging out with infidels! Mark my words, Islam will conquer the entire world one day" (*Fence* 4). Similarly, Ila Arab Mehta through the character of Fateema appropriates that 'Muslim Jihad' is a battle against oppression and tyranny. Islam is a religion of peace and submission. Islam forbids the killing of innocent people. As Fateema says in one of the lectures, "To kill innocents and cause harm to life and property is prohibited by the *Koran*" (167). Hundreds of slaves were freed from servitude and returned to their homeland by the Prophet. But to portray every Muslim male character in a stereotypical way as a propagator of Muslim Jihad hints towards the socio-political elements in the novel.

Several researches on communal riots show the active involvement of politics in it. As Iyer and Shrivastava point out, "Religious riots have complex underpinnings

frequently social, economic and political factors are involved” and “these riots may influence voter behaviour and the incentives of political parties” (37). Thus, their research finds out that many inhuman politicians through “exogenously caused riots, [strategically help their parties to get] benefits from the riots, may establish that there is a clear incentive for this party to cause riots for electoral benefit. Therefore, our findings have important implications for the relationship between ethnic violence and electoral politics” (37). This shows how politicians participate actively in such situations and to suit their purpose they take hold of social media and literature to befool the people.

Sometimes literature can also be used as a tool for the same as literature is a reflection of society, therefore, it sometimes propagates the socio-political issues of society. As Jaysinh B. Zala asserts, “It may be described as the mirror of the society. But the quality and nature of the reflection depends upon the writer's attitude of mind, whether he is progressive in his outlook or reactionary. Naturally, conservative-minded writers will stress those aspects of social life, which put the traditional ways of life in the best possible way” (28). Mehta's portrayal of every Muslim male character as a follower of jihad also points towards her conservative thinking for Muslim males. “Literature has the power to shine a light on a society's beliefs and practices. It forces readers to ask questions, start conversations and look for answers. The themes, characters and lessons in literature are ones that can all be compared to the people and events readers see in the real world” (Besa 8). So when one reads such extremist characters as portrayed by Mehta in *Fence*, one may feel that every Muslim male must be somehow involved in the jihadis activities which seems quite impossible.

The “choice of the literary world clearly affects the way one responds to the world, in ways that tend to have both desirable and undesirable effects” (Woodcock 778). Except for Fateema and her parents, everything else in Islam is associated with negativity by Mehta in this novel. Being a feminist expressing her concerns for females is quite appropriate on Mehta’s part but as a Hindu writer dealing with Islam and commenting upon their cultural customs seems quite questionable.

For instance, in *Fence* through the character of the main protagonist Fateema, Mehta asserts that wearing a burkha is a burden on Muslim women and they are forced by the patriarchy to wear one. However, many critics opine that several Muslim women do not take it as a burden to wear a burkha and even they relate it to their religious identity as Inger Furseth points out, “In addition to giving religious reasons for wearing the headscarf, many also speak about the hijab as a symbol of religious identity” (372). She interviews a number of Muslim women and finds that:

the hijab emerges as a symbolic boundary that separates public and private space. The covered women tend to describe male sexuality in negative terms. They refer to male sexuality by using words such as "unwanted," "harmful," and "the wrong kind of people." For them, male sexuality seems to be an uncontrollable phenomenon against which women must protect themselves. This is evident when they speak about the covering as a protection that provides feelings of safety. (Furseth 373-74)

Anna Piela in her article “Muslim Women and the Politics of the Headscarf” is of the view that wearing hijab has no direct lineage from the holy Quran but it does advocate its use for a modest woman and most of the religious Muslim women feel it as a compulsory part of their dress and a symbol of identity of their religion and culture.

However, “The hijab and the niqab have become controversial because they have been coopted into political symbols, stripped of any religious import, and exploited by geopolitical actors and movements which use their purported attitude toward Islamic dress as a form of political posturing” (Piela).

In India Muslim women are also being marginalized by the dominant Hindu religion and “Muslim women were rendered invisible in the limelight of the archetypal Mother India, denying their social, political, cultural and literary participation. They were thus subjected to constitutional othering by the mainstream socio-political entities (who subjected them) at the onset of nationalism, which continues to exist in post-colonial discourses” (Rahmath et al. 12). This indicates that due to such situations in the life of Muslim women, they are forced to face a conflict between their religious and national identity. Therefore, Mehta’s stance to radically oppose a burkha through her character Fateema seems quite doubtful.

Hamideh Molaei and Sahar Hussain Babaei opine that during BJP’s administration in India, most of the Bollywood movies and even literature portray the Hindu-Muslim conflicts. Muslims are depicted in an intensively negative manner so that such portrayal may invoke the psyche of every non-Muslim individual in India especially the rural people that India was once invaded by “a group of Muslims named Mughals attacked India in a very brutal way. They killed their men, took their women as captives and destroyed and burnt their houses wherever they went. This provides an unconscious justification for the Hindus and other non-Muslim groups in India that the current discrimination against Muslims is not impartial;” (395) but everyone feels that it is the rightful and legal revenge of all those misdeeds done by Muslim rulers on Hindus. It shows the real psyche of the individuals when they see such incidents around

them. Therefore, Mehta on the one hand expresses her desire to have no boundaries between Hindus and Muslims in Gujarat and on the other hand she portrays their religion in a compromised manner seems questionable.

Similarly, Azhar ul Hassan Sumra is of the view that for the last many decades, media has emerged as the strongest tool for the propagation of any positive or negative ideas throughout a nation and even the entire world. The issues can be of any type against an individual or any community, the “repeated contact with such information can lead to the formation of an associative link between a social group and the stereotypical traits promoted by the media” (227). He further opines that only Muslim religion and Islam is stereotyped in a negative way throughout the world by various propagandist media persons and:

Islamophobic mindsets are controlled by the media because the media is such an easily accessible resource. . . . The sole purpose of such media campaigns is to distort the image of Islam with imposition and aggression. Four specific tactics of the global media are practiced in this regard. First, distortion of Islamic practices worldwide. Second, showing the practices of individuals and radical Muslim groups with Islam. Third, describing = Islam as a social threat to society. Fourth, justifying aggression against Muslims. With these points, Islam is presented as a negative force and leading to violence and oppression. (Sumra 227)

Similar are the views of Faisal Kasirya when he asserts, “Women in general have been marginalized and represented with all sorts of images in the media. Specifically, when it comes to how Muslim women are pictured especially in the Western media, . . . reporting on Muslim women include being financially oppressed, terrorists, extremists, uneducated, housewives and sexual objects for men.”

Sumaiya Maaz opines, “The image of Indian Muslim women as ‘victims’ of Islam has been over-exploited by the mainstream discourse that Muslim women need protection from their religion and community. This furthers the alienation and marginalisation of the Muslim community and women at large.” By examining interconnected contemporary life and gender intersecting reality in the backdrop of Kerala, Sherin B.S. offers an alternative perspective to the flawed fabrication of the Muslim woman's identity in *Gendering Minorities: Muslim Women and the Politics of Modernity*. This presents an alternative perspective on Muslim women and highlights the biases in traditional literature in order to establish a historical and cultural framework through anecdotal and documentary experiences of Muslim women (Maaz).

Bahman Jabar Mohammed in his analysis of the post-colonial readings of E. M. Foster's *The Passage of India* and Hosseini's *The Kite Runner* opines, “The stereotypical images of Islam produced by colonial discourse have been consistent and all the Muslims are seen as strange, mysterious and exotic, which are actually misrepresentations rather than real images of Islam” (57). He is further of the view that Muslim women are stereotyped as victims, discriminated and reduced to mere objects in the hands of men in order to represent Islam negatively.

Although all religions are, in one way or another, at odds with some of the concepts and ideas of modernity, Islam is, intentionally or unintentionally, highlighted when it comes to treatment and rights of women, and this is evident in both the novels. It is also interesting to mention that Islam as a religion is reduced to some cultural values in *The Passage to India*, and to mullah's preaches in *The Kite Runner*. (Mohammed 57)

Therefore, most of the Muslim critics/scholars are of the view that Islam has been portrayed in a negative manner in every aspect of life whether it is literature, media or Bollywood. They feel that purposely stereotypical images (as violent, aggressive, brutal and inhuman) of Muslims have been projected to the world via using these mediums by the anti-Muslim propagandists in every sphere of the world. “Consequently, the notion that Muslim women’s status in India is attributable to certain intrinsic, immutable ‘Islamic’ features or that their social status derives solely from Muslim laws, is widely prevalent” (Kazi 31).

The reason for the same may be the socio-political interests of anti-Muslim groups as Seema Kazi further opines, “The political ascendance of the Hindu right-wing and its inherent link between politics and religion has threatened India’s secular fabric. The rise of communal violence in the last two decades has undermined secular law and violated constitutional ideals of religious non-discrimination, protection of human rights, implementation of social justice” (31) for the equal treatment of all citizens of India.

However, there are a few Muslim writers like, a prominent South Indian Muslim women writer, Sara Aboobacker who writes on the themes of the issues of Muslim women in Indian societies. Her narratives explore “the three primary religious concepts of talaq or divorce, polygamy and purdah, and conveys that though Aboobacker’s female characters are situated in a local environment, their concerns mirror some of the issues pertinent to Muslim women around the world” and also “problematizes the gendered, inter-ethnic and inter-religious connections in Aboobacker’s works through which she constructs the heterogeneous identity and experience of South Indian Muslim women parallel to the female issues of all

downtrodden classes in a multicultural society like India” (Ayshath et al. 215). But such examples from Muslim women writers or critics are rare as most of them feel that their religious customs and Muslim culture are being targeted consciously by anti-Muslim people.

Muslim women were deliberately distanced from the nationalist discourse during the priming of Mother India, which was overwhelmingly encrypted in Hindu religious elitism. [An extensive research shows] that nationalism homogenised different schisms of caste, class and religious disparities, the multitudes of disunities, within the title of a unified democratic Indian nation. (Rahmath et al. 28)

Moreover, there are a number of pieces in literature and past incidents in Indian societies that indicate that women in the Hindu religion are also being discriminated against based on their religion and cultural practices.

Therefore, these reviews by various critics show the negative use of media and literature during the religious conflicts between Hindus and Muslims. The discussions in the chapter show that several Muslim critics feel that most Hindu writers and reporters represent the stereotypical images of Islam and portray Muslim women as a victim of their own religion as done by Ila Arab Mehta *Fence* by Ila Arab Mehta is a narrative of the adverse experiences of a Muslim girl and portrays some negative aspects of Islam which intrigues a socio-political angle of the novel as it is written by a Hindu Feminist writer. Moreover, the novelist is from Gujarat a Hindu-dominated State with Muslims as minorities, therefore, it is not inappropriate to see the novel as a socio-political text with some sort of political motives.

To sum up, in a religious, multilingual and multicultural nation like India the role of caste and religion is vital in the life of women as portrayed by select regional women writers through their female characters. The caste system has been very deeply rooted in India for ages and Indian societies are divided into different castes based on their respective works. The hierarchal power structure of the caste system is quite discriminative towards the people of the caste at the bottom i.e. dalits. Moreover, if you are a woman and a dalit in Indian rural societies, the situation just doubles up your miseries as depicted by a number of dalit women writers in their own language and literatures in India. P. Sivakami who is herself a dalit, her narrative *The Taming of Women* also portrays the difficulties in the lives of dalit women in Indian societies.

The present study finds that being a dalit women writer P. Sivakami in this novel takes a brave stance of exposing the politics in her own caste as the leaders and the economically strong males of her own caste are more discriminative towards dalit women than anyone else. For this, she faces a lot of criticism from the people of her own community but as a true feminist, she presents the real picture of patriarchal discrimination even if it is there in her own house. Sivakami explores this through the portrayal of the antagonist of the novel, Periyannan who not only exploits the women of his own caste but also the poor woman like Lakshmi of slightly upper caste. Therefore, through this novel, Sivakami is of the view that patriarchal politics is everywhere in Indian rural societies. The dalit leaders who are supposed to support the needy people of their own caste also sometimes mentally and physically exploit the women of their own caste.

The discussions in the chapter show how religious propagators and politicians mould religion in order to serve their political purposes. Male dominance in religion to

control women in the name of religion is also quite common in Indian rural societies. *Fence* by Ila Arab Mehta is also a similar narrative of subordinating women to an inferior position in the Muslim religion. Fateema, the main protagonist of the novel, has to go through a lot of struggle and discrimination for being a woman in a patriarchal society. The narrative depicts how religion is used to discriminate against women and they are being devoid of their fundamental rights. However, the discussions also explore that a number of Muslim critics charge anti-Muslim organizations with stereotyping the images of Islam through literature and media.

This stereotypical representation of Islam as a religion of extremists is also presented by Mehta through the depiction of her male characters like Kareem, Anwar, Rajab Ali and Ammiji etc. as the true representatives of the 'Muslim Jihad' with the motive to conquer the whole world. A bulk of research shows the use of religion as a socio-political tool by many writers and journalists against people of other religions. The use of religion as a political weapon and as a tool of patriarchal domination is quite common in Indian societies. Therefore, being a Hindu writer Mehta's motive for choosing to write on the deformities in the Muslim religion and its culture seems quite questionable.

CHAPTER IV
REPRESENTATION OF WOMEN'S IDENTITY
IN SELECT NARRATIVES

The present chapter examines women's identity as portrayed by select Indian regional women writers in their respective novels. The chapter investigates a Dalit woman's identity as portrayed by P. Sivakami in *The Taming of Women* and how patriarchal stereotyping of sexes in Indian societies, discrimination and alienation of Chachcho and Lalna force them to find peace and happiness in a lesbian relationship with each other in *The Roof Beneath their Feet* by Geetanjali Shree. The chapter further explores the multi-ethnic identity of Felanee in *The Story of Felanee* by Arupa Pathangia Kalita, and how it becomes the main reason for her psychological trauma and suffering during the ethnic riots in the State of Assam. The chapter dwells on Fateema's identity as an unreal heroine in Ila Arab Mehta's *Fence*. The chapter also examines how Chetna, in *Hangwoman* by K.R. Meera, defies the stereotypical images of patriarchy which assigns masculine to represent power and feminine to represent timidness. Chetna in her quest for identity ultimately ends up becoming the 'new woman' in rural India.

The present chapter explores the theme of women's identity as depicted in the novels of prominent women writers in English and the regional women novelists from different regions of India to see any similarities/differences in their depiction of women. Further, the chapter takes a look at the views of various critics/scholars on select authors and their works before analysing select novels. The objective is to locate the similarities/differences in the experience of women characters portrayed in novels written by novelists belonging to different regions of India. The present study inspects the condition of women over the last two decades in the rural parts of India to investigate whether women have made any progress from the margins to the centre.

Judith Kegan Gardiner opines, “‘Identity’ is a central concept for much contemporary cultural and literary criticism, which, along with its even vaguer terminological twin, the ‘self,’ has become a cliché without becoming clear. The word ‘identity’ is paradoxical in itself, meaning both sameness and distinctiveness and its contradictions proliferate when it is applied to women” (347).

She further expresses that feminists see the ‘quest for identity’ as an underlying theme in most of the women’s writings but still, “the quest for female identity seems to be a soap opera, endless and never advancing, that plays the matinees of women's souls. A central question of feminist literary criticism is, who is there when a woman says, ‘I am’?” (Gardiner 348). A number of feminist critics have explored the writings of women in order to find any profound differences that everyone believes they do have as compared to men. Minakshi Sharma asserts, “The concept of female identity illustrates how female experience is turned into female awareness, typically in response to male paradigms of female experience” (383).

Although there has been a considerable improvement in the condition of women after the advent of feminism, still there has been no revolution or even a significant shift in the circumstances that control the lives of a lot of indigenous people. The people residing in the Indian rural societies do not want any girl to be born in their families and “a society that prefers a male child has already condemned its women to an unequal world. The fondness for sons remains strong” (Bishnoi) in the people living especially in the rural parts of India. In economic terms “they continue to see boys as an investment and girls a liability” (Bishnoi). Most parents still have this traditional thinking in Indian societies. Male children are favoured and given more freedom while females are restricted from even small things. After marriage, “women were devoid of

the right to be ‘coparcener’...owing to the belief of them being part of another family” (Maheshwari), and no one questions as most of the women are not even aware of their constitutional rights.

The situation has improved a bit and most of the upper-class and urban “women of the present time are now endowed with equal inheritance rights like sons” (Maheshwari), however, women living in rural and interior regions of India often lack basic fundamental rights, such as equal opportunities for higher education. Additionally, many parents don't consider their daughters' share in their father's property after they get married. This situation arises due to the patriarchal conditioning of people's minds. They still view women as dependent individuals rather than independent ones. As a result, after a father marries off his daughter, he forgets her right to his property. Similarly, the daughter, who has been conditioned from birth to accept such stereotypes, never asks for her share and remains content with whatever her husband provides.

Further, they accept these biases to avoid spoiling their relations with their brothers. Women are often reduced to their imposed roles in patriarchal societies, lacking individuality. This is evident in the different ways patriarchy operates in urban and rural areas. The next section investigates the theme of women's identity in the works of Indian women novelists in English and Indian regional women writers. It will also examine works written in English and in Indian Regional languages by women for similarities or dissimilarities in the construction of women's identity in the novels.

Women's Identity in the Novels of Indian Women Writing in English

Feminists infiltrated all spheres of life and every nook and cranny of civilization in order to change women's lives. Across all fronts – cultural, legal, and economic – it was

partially effective in changing women's circumstances. Women have a lot of help from the legislation, constitution, arts, and society to achieve such triumph. Writing has also aided in the popularisation of feminism by raising awareness about the dangers of gender inequality. Feminism fiction emerged, as a result, to promote women's equality and portray current prejudice as harmful to families and communities as a whole.

The postcolonial women writers in India, both in English and regional literatures have evolved as a great force against patriarchal discrimination and women stereotyping in Indian societies, residing especially in the rural regions. A number of prominent English writers like Anita Desai, Bharati Mukherjee, Manju Kapur, Kamala Markandaya, Shashi Deshpande, Kiran Desai, Nayantara Sehgal etc. have made a great impact in the realm of Indian writing in English and “mainly written about female experiences, sexual politics, gender relationship, women's status in society and her quest for identity. They describe the lives of women under the impact of rural background also” (Goyal 139).

All these women writers depicted the issues of women as faced by them in the Indian patriarchal male-dominated culture which stereotypes the images of both males and females in order to subjugate women. “Toru Dutt, a nineteenth-century Indian poet, expressed her pain and grief through her poem ‘Sita’ and questioned the dominance of Indian patriarchal society” (Chetty and Das). These women writers portray the real images of the miseries of women and how they are defying strongly all these problems. Arundhati Roy in *The God of Small Things* (1997), rebelliously challenged the stereotypical images of women in literature and her “protagonist, Ammu...defies the planet altogether. She seems to assert that women like every other human being have a voice of their own. She has the ability to shape her own destiny and is as capable as men. They have their own identity and individuality” (Krishnaveni 57).

The theme of west-east interactions is chosen by Kamla Markandeya. Her *Nectar in a Sieve* portrays “the real suffering of a peasant woman in rural India” (Chetty and Das). The novel depicts the condition of Indian rural women and how these females living in the interior parts of India have to face a lot of discrimination at the hands of a rigidly patriarchal society. It shows how these rural girls are devoid of good education and hence remain unemployed and financially dependent upon their husbands for everything. Rupa Bajwa’s *Tell Me A Story* “depicts the theme of a sense of loss and hope, the Quest for Identity (by Rani, a protagonist), the struggle of middle-class people, the suppressive and down status of women in society, the role of education, etc” (Gaurav et al. 1473).

Shobha De portrays a modern woman who utterly despises the traditional way of life. The contemporary feministic discourse focuses on the identity, freedom and decision-making capabilities of women in Indian societies. As “Shobha De has highlighted the emotional and sexual needs of an Indian middle-class woman through her story ‘Second Thoughts’” in which “the author has exhibited the importance of emotion and sexuality and their interdependence in maintaining healthy relationships” (Chetty and Das). Bharati Mukherjee, an Indian-American diaspora writer’s protagonists “are seen caught in the flux of tradition and modernity. Neither can they completely detach themselves from their past, nor do they have any certitude in the future” (Wagh 2604). Kamla Das looks into the struggles that women face on a daily basis. The financial situation of Parsi women is highlighted in Bapsi Sidhwa.

Romabati Devi points out, “Shashi Deshpande, in her novels gives a clear reflection about women’s struggle and achievement...Her writings provide a clear vision to bring out the revolt of women for equality and liberation against the

traditional voices and different assumptions” (2969). Shashi Deshpande is a prominent Indian author who has written extensively on women's issues in her novels. Her works traverse such themes as gender inequality, patriarchy, women's identity and their unshackling. In her novels, Deshpande portrays the experiences of women who are caught between tradition and modernity, and who are struggling to find their place in a male-dominated society. Shashi Deshpande handles women's regretful states and in *That Long Silence*, “makes an aesthetic plea to free the female psyche from the conventional male control” (Sankararaman 34). The novel tells the story of Jaya, a middle-class woman who is struggling to find her voice and assert her independence in a society that men dominate. “Here she talks about the institution of marriage and its power to destroy the freedom of women” (Krishnaveni 56).

In her novel *The Dark Holds No Terrors*, Deshpande inspects the theme of patriarchy and its impact on women's lives. The novel tells the story of Sarita, a young woman who is forced to marry a man she does not love, and who is trapped in a loveless marriage. Through Sarita's story, Deshpande highlights how patriarchal norms and expectations can limit women's choices and opportunities. About Shashi Deshpande's *Roots and Shadows* Parvati Bhatnagar says, “The novel deals with a woman's attempt to assert her individuality and realize her freedom. It depicts how it brings her into confrontation with the family, with the male world and the society in general” (qtd. in Saxena 21).

Shashi Deshpande in “*The Binding Vine* (1993), through the narrator-protagonist Urmila, . . . takes up the issue of rape both within and outside marriage” (Krishnaveni 56). “Her women characters seem submissive to the subjugation of social orthodoxy. Like other women novelists, she does not hold decisive protest in action. . . .

[However,] they are sentimental but not suppressed characters” (Jadhao 4). Overall, her novels offer a powerful and insightful exploration of women's issues in India. Through her works, she highlights the challenges that women face in their quest for identity, liberation, and empowerment, and offers a vision of a society in which women are free to live their lives on their own terms.

Feminists grew in popularity worldwide, resulting in the establishment of various egalitarian rights, including the ability of women to participate, the right to be treated equally in salaries, access to education, and the ability to inherit wealth. Society's landslide wins in the socio-political sphere resulted in the achievement of several constitutionally protected privileges for women (Irigaray 68). As in Rama Mehta's *Inside the Haveli*, Manjusha D. Suryavanshi observes the “position of women, space of women, and struggle of women for the quest of identity in the extremely traditional world. This novel also depicts the beginnings of social change in the life of women who live in the haveli of Udaipur” (303).

Mohammad Shafiqul Islam and Rama Islam point out “in Desai's famous novels *Clear Light of Day* and *Fire on the Mountain*...two of her leading characters, Bimla and Nanda Kaul, who struggle to conquer the challenges of patriarchy, and seek freedom, identity, voice and dignity” (51). Nayantara Sahgal is a renowned Indian writer who has illustrated various themes in her novels, including women's identity. In her novels, she has depicted women as strong, independent, and resilient characters who stand up against the patriarchal norms and stereotypes prevalent in Indian society. She opines that women should receive sex education and learn to have self-respect as “social set-up is geared towards the domination of men over women in marriage, in sexual relationship, in childbirth and even in adultery it is the woman who is victimized” (Chawla 364).

The fiction of Manju Kapoor often delineates themes of family dynamics, gender roles and societal norms in modern-day India. Her novels delve into the intricacies of relationships, particularly those between women and their families, and the challenges they face in navigating traditional expectations while also seeking personal fulfilment. Kapoor's work frequently addresses issues such as class, caste, and religion, and their impact on individual lives. R. Saradha Sankararaman asserts, "Manju Kapur has thus presented in her novels the predicament of sensitive women characters, . . . Her women become victims of the traditional modes of existence without a strong terrarium, which makes them intensely, conscious of their lack of identity" (30).

The human conditions of persisting women are significantly managed by Anita Desai. Anita Desai's *Voices in the City* also focuses on the theme of freedom and equality for women living in the regional parts of India. The protagonist of the novel has to fight against the rigid patriarchal customs to get some sort of freedom in her family where she is being captured like a bird in a cage. While reviewing this novel, Ashis Sengupta opines, "Desai subverts the 'quintessential' feminine ideal rooted in Hindu mythology and manifests in the cultural nationalism and socioeconomic sectors of both pre-and post-independence India" (182). He further asserts, "Deconstructing the stereotypes of selfless mother and submissive wife, as it were, she challenges the patriarchal underpinnings of Indian society. Seeking fulfilment in unfettered solitude, Otima prepares to divest herself of all bonds... In her portrayal of Otima as Kali, Desai overturns the ideal representation Of the Indian woman as a self-effacing being" (Sengupta 192). Therefore, contemporary women writers defy the age-old traditional stereotyping images of women created in society who have no individual identity.

As S. Rajeshwari illustrates, "Women writers have moved away from traditional portrayals of enduring sacrificing women, towards conflicts, female

characters searching for identity, no longer characterized and defined simply in terms of their victim status” (59). Jahnavi Barua from Assam show a real-life picture of people living in Assam and deals with themes like women’s self-redemption. In the writings of Kamala Das, who wrote both in English and Malayalam, “quest for identity is directly the progeny of an old social setup, oriented towards the total annihilation of the feminine personality . . . to liberate women from the bondage of slavery in a man-dominated society. Her poems have recorded the subjugation of male's hegemony over females” (Sankararaman 34).

The review of mainstream English women writers in India shows that women’s issues in cities are varied and complex. As in contemporary times, women residing in the cities and those educated understand their oppressed situation and are quite ready to raise their voices against it. Some of the most common issues include gender-based violence, unequal access to resources and opportunities, lack of representation in decision-making positions, and limited mobility and safety in public spaces. Women also often face discrimination and harassment in the workplace and may struggle to balance work and family responsibilities.

These issues can have a profound impact on women's well-being, mental health, and overall quality of life. It is important for policymakers and community leaders to take these issues seriously and work towards creating more inclusive and equitable cities for all residents, regardless of gender. This can include measures such as improving public transportation, increasing access to affordable childcare, promoting gender diversity in leadership positions, and implementing policies to prevent gender-based violence and harassment. Most of these women writers “create many characters from real life existence and bring their feelings, mood swings, identity crisis, tortures and many psychological and emotional imbalances” (Rajeshwari 59).

Their novel's characters are on a relentless pursuit of freedom, yearning to break free from the shackles of oppressive societal norms. All these women writers brilliantly illustrate the struggles of women to secure their self-identity and self-respect. By reconstructing the patterns of womanhood, they challenge the status quo and pave the way for a better tomorrow. This powerful portrayal of the quest for freedom is both inspiring and thought-provoking, urging readers to join the fight for gender equality and the right to self-determination. As the “volume of Indian literature written in English is smaller than that written in the various regional languages” (Sharma 30), therefore, the purpose of the present study is to highlight the first-hand experiences of the regional women writers dealing with the issues of women’s freedom and their quest for identity in the rural areas of India.

Women's Identity in Indian Regional Literatures by Women

Due to the stereotypical images of women in patriarchal societies and their struggle for freedom, there arises an identity crisis for women and there is always a quest for identity for women in India as depicted by many women writers in their respective works. However, in the rural parts, “Indian women do not seem ready yet to speak about themselves, at least in any considerable number. I suspect that when they do, the stereotypes of Indian womanhood foisted on them by priestly tradition and its variations and apologists will wither away” (Kirkpatrick 129).

Indian regional women writers “depict the psychological suffering of the frustrated housewife, this subject matter often being considered superficial compared to the depiction of the repressed and oppressed lives of women of the lower classes that we find in regional authors writing in Hindi, Bengali, Marathi, Malayalam, Urdu, Tamil, Telugu, and other native languages” (Wagh 2603). Sudha Murthy, in *Gently*

Falls The Bakula originally written in Kannada, represents the theme of women's problematic identity. "This novel has been dedicated to all the women in India who allow family commitments and responsibilities to overpower their own aspirations. When their aspirations are suppressed identity foreclosure arises. This psychological development leads to identity crisis" (Rajeshwari 60).

Ashapura Devi through her narratives raises enquiries about women's position in Indian societies and "has voiced the pain and concern of numerous women from both the rural and urban corners of Bengal . . . women across cultures have been able to identify with her characters and have encountered an understanding and appreciation that they have been looking for over a long period of time" (Chattopadhyay 91). Sutanuka Ghosh observes that a number of Bengali women writers during the twentieth century like Manikuntala Sen and others traverse the negotiation of the self with 'modernity' and asserts, "Consequently, the 'female self' in these autobiographies is not a securely rooted and stable entity but is constantly 'becoming', as the various fragments try to cohere around an elusive centre, 'modernity', which is itself a nebulous, unstable product of multiple discourses" (105).

Sudha Murty, a Kannada writer, has written a number of novels and short stories which have been translated into all major languages. "Her novels spell our view on charity, hospitality and self-realization through fictional narratives" and her short stories "deals with common lives, hospitality and realization" (Rajeshwari 60). While analysing the works of Ashapura Devi (Bengali), Mahadevi Verma (Hindi) and Lalithambika Anantjanam (Malayalam), Chandra P. Agrawal asserts that all these writers create a paradise of love "in their hearts and in their passionate, painful, or analytical language. Simultaneously, they daringly exposed the shameful sagas of the

lower and middle-class man's brutality towards the woman" (134). Apart from this they also consider the real strength of a woman in motherhood and all their women characters "aspire to be mothers, perform their motherly duties with the utmost sense of fulfilment, and feel robbed of their "self" if they lose their motherhood" (Agrawal 134).

In Assam identity is the real issue as most of the Assamese critics are of the view that the people of Assam have always been alienated and the "question of regional identity, in relation to national consciousness, is a primary issue in the writings of many Assamese novelists and short story writers. Swarna Bora, Lakshminandan Bora and others have written about it" (Bhagawati 123). Almost every Assamese women writer has also chosen it one of the major themes of their works. Arupa Pathangia Kalita's women protagonists "are portrayed possessing ambition, grace, they navigate family, bear the violence and suffer the trauma and are yet resilient" (Himabindu and Kumar 63) in *Written in Tears* and *The Loneliness of Hira Barua*. They indulge in "their unending quest for identity and selfhood exemplify honesty, trust and fight their own battles. The female characters display independent thought processes and are found to be far more simple, fair, fearless and more assertive in nature going through the hardships that they encounter in their everyday lives." (Himabindu and Kumar 68).

Other writers from Assam like Rajabala Das and Nalinibala Devi sketch the women's psyche through their autobiographical narratives in their own language. This provides a good idea for future writes as Lakhipriya Gogoi opines, "The impact of this can be vividly seen in later women's autobiographical writings where women are seen working on the construction of self through personal episodes of illness, physical accident, rebellion against the state etc among many other such 'sites' of identity-construction" (10). Indira Goswami's female protagonists suffer from the dilemma of

the dual existence of being in the traditional ways of orthodox values or being a liberal and independent person to lead a life of pure freedom. There are hardly any female characters in “Goswami’s writings who transcends her sufferings and acquires a dignified tragic poise or who achieves a triumphant fulfilment of her dreams, against all odds” (Misra 30). Therefore, due to the socio-political conditions in Assam, the theme of identity is the main issue for most of the Assamese writers.

A prominent Punjabi writer Amrita Pritam in her writings “poignantly reflected upon the woman who was raped during the partition and the poor city woman who is raped on a regular basis in the course of earning an honest living” (Agrawal 136). Chandra P. Agrawal further observes that some rebellious women writers during the mid-seventies demolished the age-old traditional notions of the patriarchal society as the Telugu writer, Muppala Ranganayakam in *Janaki Vimukti* (1978) “achieved what many writers from the beginning of this period had tried consistently—to free Sita from her husband. In reclaiming the autonomy of the woman's self, it was a rare triumph over an image that had clutched the woman's psyche for two thousand years” (141). Therefore, in a way they have constructed rebellious notions of a wife’s importance as an individual which is something new in Indian traditional societies.

C. S. Lakshmi (Ambai), a Tamil writer, breaks away from the traditional women stereotypes and her women characters are revolutionary in nature. Her stories are based on men-women relationships and women’s quest for self. U. Pushpalatha observes that the women protagonists in the works of Gita Hariharan and Rajam Krishnan “sacrifice their life, their individuality, losing identity and living for the sake of family members but the family members failed to recognize these women. They are not ready to accept and appreciate their sacrifice. They have an opinion that women must obey and stoop down to husbands and in-laws” (446).

Ganesh Chintaman Wagh points out that a Marathi novelist, Asha Arvind Bage, provides a “fresh perspective on woman and the reality that surrounds her. Her characters depict an activist dealing more directly with contemporary issues. Her writing is largely based on self-experiences... Her most notable works which worth to mention are *Bhoomi*, *Setu* and *Zumbar*, where we find her representation of identity and selfhood” (2607). A prominent Hindi writer, Usha Priyamvadais “writes prolifically in her novels on the current issues concerning women, and adopts a questioning, daring and challenging stance in her writings... She has released Hindi literature from the closed and suffocating orthodoxies of women’s issues into the open spaces of thoughts, in a way that no Hindi writer has done before” (Wagh 2608).

Shanti Joshi, in *Machhli aur Mara Jal* depicts the “long, painful inner struggle of the protagonist between her intellectual self and her emotional self faithfully represents the torturous struggle of the wounded woman in separating her real human self from the socially constructed image of it” (Agrawal 138). As Aparna Basu asserts, “We have to see women as a force in politics, as reformers, revolutionaries, searching for an identity in their nation, their class, themselves. Women as producers, peasants, workers, artisans, domestic servants, in their roles in the family, as wives, daughters and mothers have to become visible” (181).

It emerges from the reviews above that the writings of women writers in English and those writing in regional literatures differ in terms of language, style, and cultural contexts. Women writers in English have access to a wider audience and a global readership, which gives them more exposure and opportunities for recognition. They also tend to write in a more standardized form of English, which is more easily accessible to a global readership. On the other hand, women writers in regional literatures write in their local languages and often draw from their specific cultural

contexts and experiences. This makes their writing more grounded in the local culture and specific to the region they are writing about. They also face the challenge of limited readership and recognition outside their region. However, this does not diminish the significance of their work, as it plays a crucial role in preserving local cultures and histories.

Moreover, the themes and issues represented in the writing of women writers in regional literatures are often different from those illustrated by women writers in English. While the latter may focus more on individualism, identity, and agency, women writers in regional literatures may sketch themes such as community, tradition, and cultural norms. Therefore, the role of regional writers is more important as Dr Sanskritirani remarks, “My impression is that in India, regional literature is much more powerful than Indian writing in English. Each language has its own flair” (qtd. in Deodhar).

In this way, the role of regional women writers becomes more crucial in raising the issues faced by women in their own societies in order to have a change from within. As Naresh A. Parmar opines, “They have boldly expressed the social inhibitions and cultural taboos laid down by the society . . . in the first decade of the new millennium so to say, we have witnessed a spurt of women writers who have shunned all inhibitions accepting bravely the challenge of projecting, delineating, analysing and discussing the real status and factual roles of contemporary Indian women” (41).

Before taking up the select novels for a detailed textual analysis of the theme of women’s identity, as depicted by the respective women writers through their female protagonists, it is important here to consolidate observations of various scholars and critics on the select novels. Tanmoy Singha in “The Voice of the Voiceless: a Study of

The Taming of Women” asserts, “Sivakami’s women in the novel *The Taming of Women* are not generally subjugated to male chauvinism rather they flare at the oppression inflicted by men. They bring feminist consciousness to empower themselves as Dalits and women in order to emerge as free individuals” (59). A number of critics explore gender and caste discrimination in Sivakami’s novel. Pratibha Somkuwar and Raj observe a Dalit woman’s plight against patriarchy and a tyrannical man in *The Taming of Women*.

No one except Kuhu Chanana in “Plurality of Lesbian Existence in Modern Indian Writers: Manju Kapur, Rajkamal Chaudhary and Geetanjali Shree” observes the lesbian relationship which the present chapter explores in Geetanjali Shree’s *The Roof Beneath their Feet*. Hemjyoti Medhi, Sultana, Basumatary and Rao discuss briefly in their articles the issue of gender and identity politics in Arupa Pathangia Kalita’s *The Story of Felanee*. Therefore, the present chapter dwells on the detailed analysis of the multi-ethnic identity of Felanee.

Except for some rare book reviews and articles, no one has commented in detail on Ila Arab Mehta’s *Fence*. The present study explores in detail the struggle of Fateema to be an independent woman in the midst of a Hindu male-dominated society. Only M. G. Hari in “Negotiation of Identity in K. R. Meera’s *Hangwoman*” and V. P. Prasaga in “Traversing the Feminine: A Postmodern Feminist Reading of *Hangwoman*” show Chetna’s struggle to defy the feminine and masculine stereotypes of the patriarchal culture and to emerge as a powerful woman in the male-dominated society. Therefore, the present chapter examines Chetna’s identity in detail to understand her transition to the ‘new woman’ in modern India, especially in rural West Bengal. The next section focuses on the detailed analysis of select novels to explore the theme of women’s identity.

Textual Analysis of the Select Narratives

a. Dalit Woman's Identity in *The Taming of Women*

P. Sivakami is a dalit women writer and a prominent feminist from Tamil Nadu. *The Taming of Women* is set in a small dalit village in Tamil Nadu and depicts the story of gender discrimination and power politics between a debauchee, Periyannan, and the women characters in the novel, especially Anandhayi and Lakshmi. Anandhayi, the wife of Periyannan, is the main protagonist of the novel who is subjected to extreme physical and mental domestic torments by her husband. Sivakami pictures the identity of a common Dalit woman in Indian rural societies who is financially dependent on her husband and for the sake of her children, she silently bears the extreme torments of her husband.

Through the character of Periyannan, Sivakami criticises the dalit male leaders who misuse their power and money to exploit not only the women of their own caste but also to take sexual advantage of poor high-caste women like Lakshmi. Lakshmi tries so hard to get herself free from the dominant clutches of Periyanna but all in vain and ultimately dies due to his ill-treatment of her body. Overall, *The Taming of Women* is an insightful and powerful work of literature that sheds light on the struggles and oppression faced by dalit women in Indian society. It highlights the importance of education, financial independence, and the fight for equal rights and opportunities for women belonging to marginalized communities.

Dalit women in Tamil Nadu grapple with manifold hardships stemming from their caste and sex. They find themselves caught between the dual prejudices of casteism and traditional gender roles, leading to their marginalization in different aspects including academics, work sphere and political activities. Further evidence of

this discrimination is seen as they fall victim to physical or sexual abuses - acts commonly swept under the carpet or deemed acceptable by those holding higher societal positions. As Nitya Rao points out, “Based on research in rural Tamil Nadu, I analyze Dalit women 's narratives that reflect multiple concerns and dilemmas about marital choice and violence, generating in the process a deeper understanding of agency, voice, and gender relations, as fluid, dynamic, and intersecting in response to changing experiences, positionalities, and subjectivities” (410). Despite these challenges, there have been efforts by dalit women to organize themselves and fight for their rights. For instance, the Tamil Nadu Women’s Forum, a dalit women-led organization, has been working towards empowering dalit women and addressing issues such as violence against women, land rights, and political representation.

Dalit literature from Tamil Nadu portrays the double oppression that a dalit woman has to endure. The first Tamil novel *Pazhaiyana Kazhithalum* by a dalit woman condemns “caste fanatics by using fiction with biographical elements to describe how human beings are shackled and tangled among themselves. Instead of being the journey of her individual voice and consciousness, it is a unanimous expression of the youth of this oppressed community, ‘Parayar,’ eager and waiting for change” (Subashini and Princelin 108). The Dalit Women’s Movement in Tamil Nadu has also been active in raising awareness about the intersectional discrimination faced by dalit women and advocating for their rights. Overall, the situation of dalit women in Tamil Nadu remains challenging, but efforts are being made towards empowering and advocating for their rights.

The Taming of Women by P. Sivakami delineates the identity of a dalit woman, Anandhayi and shows how these poor women “suffer double marginalization because

they suffer as they belong to the lower class and the suffering is augmented because of the patriarchal system” (Subashini and Princelin 108). Dalit women are often seen as inferior to men and women from higher castes, and are subjected to discrimination and violence. The most extreme kind of patriarchy is when males abuse women to show their power over them. It is a serious issue for dalit women which Anandhayi faces in this novel. Because of their low caste, dalit women are among the most widely discriminated against groups in society.

In contemporary rural Tamil Nadu, the condition of dalits has improved a bit as S. Anandhi asserts, “During the past 10 years, with access to higher education and employment outside the village, the conditions of the Paraiyars in Valluvapuram has significantly improved to the extent that they are treated as equal to the middle castes in the village – especially in terms of their socio-economic conditions” (68). However, only a “Gradual development can be seen but the state of living is unchanged for Dalit women. On the whole, men see women as an object, not as a living being. Women also have their own well and wishes, and expect respect, dignity and happiness in life. The worst thinking of men can be changed only when women stand independently” (Sangeetha and Peruvalluthi 146).

Through the character of Periyannan, Sivakami expresses that this situation for women in Tamil Nadu is due to some powerful dalit leaders who misuse money and power to subjugate poor women of any caste. He has always been greedy for power and money, because he had little regard for the females in his family, particularly his spouse, Anandhayi, or his mistress, Lakshmi. The main female protagonist, Anandhayi, is depicted in the story's first section in a pitiful state. Periyannan has brought another woman into his bedroom and sleeps with her while Anandhayi is suffering from labour

pains and she is about to give birth to their baby. When the baby is born, she is very upset while “thinking about the husband who did not come down at his newborn’s cry, Anandhayi shut her tear-filled eyes” (*The Taming* 5).

She once says, “I cannot count the number of blows I have received. But I am bearing all this pain only for my children” (*The Taming* 217). Anandhayi's depiction may serve as an encouragement towards many women who really are attempting to navigate their lives in the face of many challenges. On some occasions, Anandhayi tries to raise her voice against him, but whenever she does so, he thrashes her so mercilessly that she becomes helpless in front of him.

Anandhayi and Lakshmi are totally dependent on him as they don't have any other source of income to sustain their life. That is the reason he wants to have complete rights over their bodies and loves to treat them as animals. Therefore, Sivakami's depiction of rural women is quite pathetic in this novel, and it shows how women are still being treated like sexual objects and pet animals in the rural parts of India. The males violate the fundamental rights of women in their families, and females are not provided with any sort of equality even to make any decision in their lives. They are always bound by the decisions taken by their male counterparts. For ages women have been treated as slaves by males as Periyannan brags to Lakshmi, “Anandhayi is a patient woman...She is scared of me and will not even squeak” (Sivakami 99).

“Dalit women have largely been homogenized, their triple burdens of economic marginalization, caste discrimination, and gender subordination almost taken for granted” (Rao 411) in Indian rural societies. A similar identity of a dalit woman is characterized by Sivakami in *The Taming of Women*. Shobha Warriar quotes from one

of Sivakami's interviews where she asserts that due to patriarchal dominance, Indian society "still does not accept women leaders unless they are thrust upon people from the top." The first-hand experiences of an educated dalit woman like Sivakami show that the identity of dalit women is seriously under threat in patriarchal societies.

In a reply to whether she is being discriminated against by her seniors, Sivakami replies, "It is so minute that only those who are sensitive will feel it. It is like going to a wedding, but not finding anyone you can talk to. You can't say it is harassment, but you don't feel alright. You feel isolated and not part of the crowd" (qtd. in Warrior). Sivakami renders that a Dalit woman's identity points to the "pervasive nature of violence and the sense of perpetual threat and its presence in everyday life, as emerging from the hierarchies and inequalities generated by the interlocking structures of caste, class, and gender" (Rao 428).

Therefore, Dalit women in Tamil Nadu have been making strides towards reclaiming their identity and challenging the social norms that have kept them oppressed for centuries. In her novel, *The Taming of Women*, P. Sivakami presents the identity of dalit women and how they are forced to navigate the patriarchal society they live in. Overall, Sivakami's novel is a powerful delineation of dalit women's identity in Tamil Nadu through the character of Anandhayi. It sheds light on the struggles that these women face, while also showing that they are capable of overcoming the obstacles in their way and achieving their goals.

b. Chachcho and Lalna as Lesbians

Geetanjali Shree is a Booker prize-winning novelist from Manipuri, Uttar Pradesh and currently resides in New Delhi. *The Roof Beneath Their Feet* by Geetanjali Shree is undoubtedly a masterfully created plot that reveals the story by weaving the narrative

of past and present together with numerous plot twists. The novel presents the theme of women's relationships and their struggle for identity in rural India. The story is about two women, Chachcho and Lalna, who find peace and happiness in a lesbian relationship with each other due to patriarchal stereotyping, discrimination, and alienation of women in Indian societies.

The novel highlights the struggles and challenges faced by women in rural India and how they navigate through them to find their own identity. The novel presents a thought-provoking insight into the complexities of gender, identity, and sexuality in India. The roof of the Laburnum house is a symbol of freedom from the tormenting life for both Chachcho and Lalna. As the narrator remarks, "Uncle didn't find anything about the roof interesting . . . he'd put it down to childishness. As for the rest – like Lalna – it could only be the sign of an unruly heart" (*RBTF* 32).

Chachcho with her frigid husband dwells in Laburnum House, a society of a dozen or even more homes under one roof. The location of Laburnum House is not explicitly mentioned. However, it is described as a house with a common roof, situated in a remote area, surrounded by dense vegetation. The novel is set in the city of Allahabad, in the northern Indian State of Uttar Pradesh. The State has a diverse cultural and social fabric, which has been depicted by many writers in their literary works. When it comes to exploring women's identity, the works of regional women writers in Uttar Pradesh have played a significant role. These writers have portrayed the lives of women in different social and cultural contexts, highlighting the various challenges they face in their everyday lives. Mostly, the works of regional women writers in Uttar Pradesh have contributed significantly to the discourse on women's identity. These writers have evoked various themes and issues related to women's

identity, highlighting the challenges and struggles faced by women in different social and cultural contexts.

Chachcho lives a solitary life until she brings in Lalna, a woman who has been deserted by her spouse. Several people are put off by their proximity. Then one day, Lalna is forced to depart, just to rejoin following Chachcho's death. As Chachcho's nephew struggles to put together his recollections of the two women, none of whom is his mother, there are whispers that chatter inside the neighbourhood. The information he seeks might ruin them for all time, yet not knowing is no longer a viable alternative. Chachcho know that women must be quiet and restrained, otherwise, they have to bear the adverse consequences of it. "A woman's not a woman if she doesn't behave like one" (*RBTF* 59).

Patriarchy has imposed a stereotypical identity on women in Indian societies and they are supposed to be in that role of a timid wife and a quiet mother only. Therefore, unwillingly Chachco is forced to play her role as wife because she has no escape from this identity as K.D. Upadhyaya points out, "The wife has no separate existence apart from the husband who is all-powerful. Kalidas has mentioned in *Shakuntala* that the overlordship of the husband is fully maintained as regards his wife. Manu, the ancient Hindu Lawgiver, has proclaimed the dictum that women should never be let free" (82). So this is the real identity of a woman living in rural regions of India where there are fixed roles for both males and females in society. Therefore, such an imposed stereotypical role on a woman forces her to struggle for her real self as she has to constantly negotiate between her real self and the imposed identity upon her by society.

Judith Kegan Gardiner feels that through those differences one can formulate a female theory of identity. Erik Erikson, a renowned modern identity theorist, popularizes the idea of ‘identity crisis’ and expresses, “The person with a successfully achieved sense of individual identity feels unique, whole, and coherent, although in pathological cases identity formation may fail and the person suffers from ‘identity diffusion.’ Identity as Erikson conceives it is both formed and manifested through social relation” (qtd. in Gardiner 349). Therefore, to have a strong identity every individual needs to have a healthy environment otherwise his real identity gets hampered. Chachcho’s life was meaningless before Lalna’s entry into her house. Chachcho lives like a trapped bird inside an iron cage with her husband who doesn’t treat her as his wife. He has never cared for Chachcho’s feelings and she, being accustomed to a patriarchal mindset, finds solace in her agony.

When Lalna comes to Laburnam house, “the relationship between Chachcho and Lalna takes them into a story they build for themselves, empowering them to get away from their respective tyrannies into something that makes life a little more colourful” (Sinha). As both of them are being treated indifferently by the patriarchal society and have no hope of any betterment, therefore, they find peace and pleasure in being a lesbian relation with each other.

After her friendship with Lalna, Chachcho, “started waiting for the girl as if to see how far her own courage would take her – the proof of that courage being the girl who had become her mirror” (*RBTF* 23). There is nothing disgusting about it. Chachcho, the monk, buried more or more of her body behind the plain-bordered sari each day. Somebody would exclaim, “Poor Chachcho,” . . . You'd never hear a peep out of her about her husband’s ways, and now she’s even taking care of that other woman

out of pity for her swollen stomach” (*RBTF* 64). Chachcho would be honoured to be welcomed to any joyful, sorrowful, or celebratory event. Therefore, for Chachcho's sake, once Lalna decides to come she is gratefully welcomed as well. Such a kind-hearted woman she is; she forgives her husband over adultery and allows him to return home after suffering from diabetes, but could it be considered a homecoming?

Due to this now he has to stay with Chachcho alone and therefore, she wonders, “What a way to become sweeter!” (*RBTF* 64). Uncle is always aware of her presence but never responds positively. He pretends to think that his wife needs only money and nothing else so “he threw himself into making money and more money. He seemed to think that buying his wife things and more things was enough. He'd buy all sort of rubbish and heap it upon her” (*RBTF* 93) but never cared to know that what she wants. That is why Chachcho questions Lalna, “Is this really giving?...What has he given me? . . . Even Bitwa I got from you” (*RBTF* 93). Chachcho's life with her husband is totally mundane and meaningless so she is forced to find her real self in her relationship with Lalna which is the only meaningful relation she ever had in her whole life.

Even the physical appearance of Chachcho also illustrates her mundane life with her careless husband as once Lalna remarks about her, “Just cut her open and see, this Chachcho doesn't have blood running through her veins, but the juice of jamuns!” (*RBTF* 20). This shows the colourless, pale life Chachcho is forced to live with her frigid husband and still, she never complains about it to her husband who never treats her with the love she always craved for. As Lalna again remarks, “Before my very eyes, Behen-ji started retreating further and further into herself. And on the outside, she became emptier and emptier. Shining, bright, white, pure, shimmering” (*RBTF* 108). As in *Hangwoman* K. R. Meera remarks, “Good women are those who bury their woes within themselves, child” (110).

Uncle never cares for Chachcho but once he is drunk “he’d unroll bolts of colourful nylon and Dacron over her body and Chachcho would quietly let him do it as if this . . . would keep doing what it was programmed to until it finally wound down” (*RBTF* 42). In the “morning, Uncle would forget all about it. He also forgot Chachcho’s slap. That she had landed on his cheek one night when he went on like this with no sign of stopping” (*RBTF* 42). And when Chachcho’s heart craves for her spouse’s love he heartlessly rejects her love and poor Chachcho asks in agony, “Why not? says Chachcho’s hurt voice” and he mercilessly replies to her, “Because I want a woman, not you” (*RBTF* 63). Therefore, once Chachcho tells Lalna, “He comes when he wants to, but when I...” (*RBTF* 103). Such incidents show that he loves Chachcho deep in his heart yet restrains himself from showing his real feelings towards her. But all these things bring her closer and closer to Lalna where she forgets her every misery of mundane life and tries to find her real self.

Due to such incidents, Chachcho becomes more and more submissive and “She had always been quiet, but whether people knew it or not, I knew that this wasn’t her usual quietness. Chachcho had decided to not talk to Uncle” (*RBTF* 65). He further asserts, “This is how joint families stayed joint. This is how unbreakable the non-speaking relationships were. In our house, it was Chachcho and Uncle” (*RBTF* 67). She tried everything with him but all in vain which is why she remarks, “Don’t beg for anything – not for relationships, not for food. How many more pieces can I break my heart into?” (*RBTF* 104). The episodes show that her marital relationship is totally meaningless in which there is no love and respect for her real self. Her husband never pays any heed towards her as she cannot bear a child for him. This seems to be the reason for her husband’s coldness towards her.

Chachcho is always immensely pleased to give her every possession to Lalna for the friendship and happiness she brings in her meaningless life. She, “bring out her jamavars, pashminas, phulkaris and wrap them around her saying, when do I wear them” (*RBTF* 33) and “Chachcho with one black shawl, and Lalna with a new colour every day” (*RBTF* 34). Even she shares her husband with her without making any complaints whatsoever. Her life was so hopeless that after her death the narrator remarks, “Sometimes pain turns into a dark, heavy blanket that wraps itself around you, and you fall into a strange, lifeless sleep. Pitch darkness, no sound, no movement, you even forget to feel sad – why should I not call it peace?” (*RBTF* 44). Chachcho only finds some meaning in her life with her relationship with Lalna but one day when Lalna leaves her due to societal pressure, Chachcho again remains all alone. Although Chachcho had Bitwa with her after her husband’s death, yet her real happiness was only when she was with Lalna.

About Chachcho’s generosity, the narrator remarks, “Poor thing, they say again and again. See, how compassionately she let her husband’s lover stay, even after becoming a widow” (*RBTF* 47). Once Premanand-ji’s nephew drags Lalna into his dirty tricks and even Uncle was also cursing Lalna unnecessarily then, “Chachcho went down, and the crowd saw her slap Premanand-ji’s nephew” (*RBTF* 58). Even Uncle couldn’t say anything to her on that day. Thereafter, Chachcho starts finding solace and comfort in her friendship with Lalna and she is quite happy with her wild manners. In the form of Lalna’s friendship at least Chachcho has someone to share her feelings with for which she was ever struggling with her careless husband.

On the other hand, Lalna has no family and nothing is sure about her family members. No one knows where she has come from and everyone calls her, “a woman

with an unspoken but sullied past” (*RBTF* 39). Therefore, people always see her with doubt even if she isn’t a characterless lady. On one occasion Lalna expresses to Chachcho that “even if I’m in my bed, sleeping, they’ll say they saw me in someone’s lap or embracing someone else. Then why shouldn’t I do as I please?” (*RBTF* 38). The whole society of the Laburnum house wants to get rid of Lalna, it is only Chachcho who sees Lalna with respect. One day, “Lalna started driving Uncle’s scooter, no one was happy except Chachcho” and the narrator says that he was also very angry at her because “she was making a mockery of us all” (*RBTF* 46). Lalna is ill-treated by all the people of Laburnum house and even once the narrator remarks, “Premanand-ji was . . . kicking Lalna like a football and hitting her with a stick like a hockey ball” (*RBTF* 49). During such episodes, Chachcho empathises with Lalna and she visualizes herself in her place. Although she never had to undergo such physical discrimination, however, she has to undergo a lot of mental agony and finds herself tangled in the role of an ideal woman. These feelings further strengthen her relationship with Lalna and strengthen her bond with Lalna.

Due to such treatment that Lalna receives from the people of Laburnum house even without doing anything wrong, she never cares about anyone and does whatever her heart desires or what she feels is right. Through Lalna, Shree questions the patriarchal society that treats women always in a negative sense. Judith Kegan Gardiner opines, “Since women do not, like men, experience gender itself as a problem, social attempts to make it a problem for them may cause confusion and anxiety” (359). As Lalna tells Bitwa, “Spare her, why are you killing that poor dead woman all over again? Why do you want us friends to be invisible? How obsessed you people are with seeing us without our selves inside us!” (*RBTF* 98-99). Therefore, Geetanjali Shree in a way questions the psyche of the people living in Indian societies who always see such homosexual relations as illicit.

The dynamics of lesbianism which Geetanjali Shree has represented through the relationship between Chachcho and Lalna is quite a new and kind of forbidden thing in Indian culture especially in rural regions. In Indian societies and even in academics such queer homosexual representation of relations is quite marginalized but no one can deny the fact that they are a real part of one's imagination and happiness. Therefore, it is quite daring of an Indian regional women writer like Geetanjali Shree to talk about such human wishes and desires explicitly.

c. Multi-ethnic and Multi-cultural Identity in *Felanee*

Arupa Patangia Kalita is an Assamese novelist who has written extensively on women's sufferings. *The Story of Felanee* is a novel by Arupa Pathangia Kalita that tells the story of Felanee, a woman of multiethnic lineage who is forced to confront her past and come to terms with her identity. The novel is set against the backdrop of the ethnic riots in the State of Assam in the 1970s and 1980s. Felanee's journey takes her through the complexities of identity, where she discovers the importance of acknowledging her roots and embracing her cultural heritage. Through her struggles, Felanee emerges as a strong and resilient character who inspires others to do the same. The novel explores themes of identity, belonging, and the effects of violence on individuals and communities.

Assam is a State in northeastern India that is known for its rich culture and diverse population. Women in Assam, like in other parts of India, have struggled for equality and empowerment in a society that is often patriarchal and conservative. Assam in the 1980s witnessed a period of political unrest and violence due to the demand for autonomy by different ethnic groups, particularly the Assamese-speaking people. The movement was known as the Assam Movement or the Assam Agitation,

and it aimed to address issues such as illegal immigration from Bangladesh and the economic marginalization of the indigenous people. The movement turned violent at times, leading to clashes with the security forces and communal riots. The ethnic tensions and violence during this period had a deep impact on the people of Assam, particularly those belonging to minority communities, who faced discrimination and violence. The novels of regional writers from Assam, such as Arupa Pathangia Kalita's *The Story of Felanee*, reflect the experiences of people during this period and render the identity issues faced by individuals belonging to different ethnic groups.

These ethnic conflicts go on in Assam regularly as “in October 2008 the Bodos launched an assault against Muslim immigrants. Such violent assertions are a fight for control over dwindling natural resources, the most important being land” (Tripathi 522). Bodos are the main inhabitants of Assam and whenever there is illegal infiltration occurs, it results in their violent reaction against such people as they feel insecure about their identity and especially their land. Therefore, ethnic conflicts are quite common in Assam and Assamese people’s identity is constantly under threat from these illegal infiltrates. Women are the main victims during such riots as Arupa illustrates the multi-ethnic identity of women in Assam and how it becomes a factor in their psychological trauma and suffering during ethnic riots. The novel portrays the story of Felanee, a woman who belongs to the Tai-Ahom community, and the challenges she faces in the face of ethnic and political violence.

Arupa Patangia Kalita is quite vivid “in her attempts to portray the realistic and reliable picture of the weak position of women in the society, and throws light on the gender inequality between the genders” (Himabindu and Kumar 68). *The Story of Felanee* by Arupa is situated in the politically volatile State of Assam. Felanee, which

means 'thrown aside,' is the narrative's main female protagonist. The story of the novel spans many generations, beginning with Ratnamala's experience as a young widower. Ratnamala is a member of the noble Mouzadar clan. She marries a wild Mustang called Kinaram Bodo. She lives in the Bhutanese foothills. Karam's shrapnel corpse is found by locals as she dies giving birth to Jutimala. The villagers nurture their daughter Jutimala when they die. Jutimala matures into a lovely young lady when she marries Khitish Ghosh, a grocer.

Meanwhile, disturbances erupted in Assam, causing homes to be burned down, individuals to be murdered, and even Jutimala to be slain soon after the delivery of her daughter. The linguistic campaign to make Assamese the official language in Assam inflamed anti-foreigner sentiments. Jutimala and Khitish's deaths may be viewed as a reflection of those turbulent times. Khitish's sibling Rattan saves the baby that Jutimala threw in the pond seconds after her death. "He saw how the roof had almost fallen on the unconscious Jutimala. Suddenly he heard a splash. Someone had thrown the newborn baby into the pond!" (*Felanee* 9).

Felanee, the novel's main protagonist, is born from her. After Felanee married Lambodar Koch and had a son named Moni, a new issue arose: the fight against illegal immigration in Assam, known colloquially as the Assam movement. Felanee and her spouse are trapped in the agitation's severe consequences. Felanee's husband, Lambodar Koch, is murdered, but she and her son Moni flee the bloodshed and get shelter in a refugee camp. "The smell of medicines along with groans and cries overwhelmed her. When she got used to the strange light, she found herself on a camp cot (*SOF* 30).

The novel vividly portrays people's suffering whose existence is abruptly flipped upside down by politically unpredictable upheavals. Felanee's identity in her

own country is shattered, and she becomes a fugitive. All through the narrative, this desire to build up a cohesive personality haunts her. For example, she gets caught in a blind when a doctor in the refugee centre confronts her regarding their identification. Her brain starts to flutter with images of her ancestor Ratnamala as Kinaram Bodo, her parents Jutimala (an Axomiya) and Khitish Ghosh (a Bengali), and her husband, Lambodar (a Koch).

When a young doctor asks her about her ethnicity, she gets perplexed by the inquiry and continues to just look at his face. The youngster returns her gaze. He wonders why she is taking such a long time to reply to a basic inquiry. Felanee is unable to provide a definitive response to the question of her origins. Her mind was overwhelmed with her multi-ethnic identities, therefore, “She, in turn, muttered the question to herself. ‘What are you?’ Yes, she thought, what am I? ‘Just a human being, what else?’” (*SOF* 32). During the latter 1970s upheaval, Arupa's novel presents a comprehensive as well as successful link among such a band of deported ladies, allowing them to build new names, enjoy life, get aid, and survive their divided lives. With the introduction of such a multi-ethnic persona who's now a Bodo, a Bengali, as well as an Assamese, the writer questions the traditional concept of identity as a single, unitary entity.

Felanee's grandparents were the inhabitants of the Bodoland Territorial Region of Assam which is the northeast part of Assam and consists of only five districts. Later they migrated to the main Assam and her mother got married to an immigrant Bengali. “Felanee was born to a Bengali father and a Bodo mother. She was born on the day when her father succumbed to the violent attacks of the agitators...on the same night, her mother also died at childbirth. Soon after her birth, the rioters found the baby

Felanee and threw her in the pond to die” (Nyori and Riba 136). Then she got married to a Koch who is “a small trans-border ethnic group of Assam . . . and the Hindu caste called Koch in Upper Assam which receives converts from different tribes” (“Koch People”). Such different cultural linkages form a multi-ethnic identity of the main protagonist of the novel.

This lineage caused her lots of trouble during the ethnic riots in Assam due to the ‘Assam Movement’ in the early 1980s. She is always on the attack of indigenous Assamese people due to by birth being a Bengali and then married to a Koch, a Hindu. This issue is so intense in Assam that even till contemporary times “insurgency and violence had almost become a way of life, and the citizens lived precarious lives in this heavily militarised region. Large-scale illegal migration from neighbouring countries had further added to the socio-political unrest in the region” (Mandal 738). Rimi Nath asserts, “In Assam, the question of foreigners versus authentic citizens has been the reason for the region’s political and social volatility. The definition of ‘Assamese’ still remains a matter of debate and contestation” (7).

Felanee and other women characters are the main victims of this ethnic conflict and violence as they are considered the easiest target to hurt and take revenge upon the other group. As Nipa Mandal opines, “Women as a whole are specifically targeted in anti–insurgency operations and the women are the more marginalised communities, the disabled and otherwise underprivileged groups, or individuals are more at risk of violence, victims of sexual violence have to go through psychological and social marginalisation” (742). Therefore, the novel's story explores Felanee’s identity amid communal unrest and how her multi-ethnic identity is the major cause of her problems. However, she fights bravely against every odd with a number of narrow escapes against

the rioters. The novelist also portrays the women's companionship and their strength to fight against every problem to sustain their families in difficult times. The portrayal of Kali Boori in the novel by Arupa is the true resemblance of such feminine power in the male-dominated society who is ready to do anything in order to survive and help the needy.

Kalita has challenged the oppressive psychosocial frames against women with her depiction of such characters as Felanee and Kali Boori in *The Story of Felanee*. Kali Bhoori is an important character in the tale. She has presented a method to challenge repressive psychological frameworks towards women through the Goddess Kali. Goddess Kali is a deity who embodies qualities that transcend beyond the concept of socially constituted gender. Annalisa Merelli is of the view that “Kali is the quintessential embodiment of *shakti*, female power . . . she is a scary, bloodthirsty embodiment of destruction and the ultimate protector against evil.” Ashis Sengupta says, “Kali is but one dimension of this divine feminine. Kali is Shakti, or primal energy. She is *svatantra*, independent, her existence contingent upon nothing extraneous to herself; As the ancient deity of our times, . . . Kali will annihilate the patriarchal universe to reveal the truth of things and restore to us the divine feminine long lost” (191).

Women's company, empathy, and forgiveness are examined in *The Story of Felanee*, Kali Boori, a woman of divinity with total control over males, often consoles Felanee that standing alone in sadness and crying like a victor inside without the aid of a man, without the aid of a woman. She reconfigures women's roles and wins against hardship, showing women how and where to continue living in the midst of conflict at all phases. As Felanee points out, “Kali Boori had this infinite capacity of depriving herself while looking after the temple. She had tremendous willpower” (*SOF* 269).

The novel is based on true events that occurred in Assam during the 'Assam Movement' in the late 1970s and early 1980s. The movement was started by the 'Assam Students Union' against the illegal infiltration of Bengalis in Assam which not only causes a threat to their identities but also to their economy and land. "What makes the Assam case unique is that it has faced both internal as well as illegal international migration in massive scales giving rise to intense existential fear and apprehension among its smaller indigenous communities" (Mandal 735). As Gail Omvedt opines, "the basic Assamese fear is not so much of losing jobs to Bengalis (or other 'outsiders') but of losing their land. This is a much more basic issue because it calls into question one of the defining characteristics of a nationality" (qtd. in Guha 1699).

So, the Assamese people felt that illegal infiltration was a threat to their culture and identity. The reason behind these infiltrations was as Nipa Mandal asserts, "Immigration into Assam started since 1874. Assam's immense economic potential, coupled with the reluctance of the indigenous people to do toilsome and hard work, and the absence of capital and entrepreneurship made such immigration imperative... Partition of the country led to more immigration." (734). Due to immigration, people in Assam develop multi-ethnic identities which causes them problems as happens in the case of Felanee, the main protagonist of Kalita's novel. "The Assam movement ostensibly aimed at stopping the inflow of foreign nationals into Assam but it failed to do so because of external as well as its own internal constraints. The problem left unresolved, causing existential concern for both the majority and the minority of Assam" (Das 893). With this backdrop, Kalita emphasises the problems of social inequality and the abuse of women in the name of ethnic politics. She has always raised her voice for the cause of the welfare of women and says:

I am a woman and hence, I write about women in my society. In this uneven society that I belong to, I always feel I have a lot to say about women as a woman. . . . I take a gendered view of it. . . . Women are thrown away like garbage, oppressed, marginalized, and rejected, but even in the midst of this are vibrantly asserting life. And I glorify their existence. (qtd. in Himabindu and Soujanya 63)

She has received many awards including the Sahitya Akademi, Bharatiya Bhasha Parishad, Katha Award, and Prabina Saikia Award.

The main protagonist of the novel, Felanee's life, centres on her memories of losing her family during the 1960s fight against ethnic riots, immigration, and indigenous culture preservation. Her parents immigrated to Assam and during revolts in Assam, "immigrants are almost always the first people to be blamed whenever something goes wrong in the country that they are living in. This is a common occurrence. Consequently, they are subjected to acts of violence and aggression" (Sharma 1395). She is the epitome of true women's strength and struggle. Her character represents how strong a woman can be when she herself sees and realizes her true strength.

Felanee fights against every adversity that comes her way during her life and after the death of her husband, she takes care of her son alone. Once she was living a royal life and after the riots, she is forced to live a life of a beggar but she does not give up and sustains herself with whatever she can through hard work and her companionship with other such suffering women. The novel shows the struggle of women in a male-dominated society in order to sustain themselves independently and become self-reliant women. In their quest for identity, Felanee and other victims of

ethnic riots in Assam lead an independent life without the help of any male with pride and dignity.

Felanee's situation is like that of the Urdu writer Manto's Bishen Singh in the story, *Toba Tek Singh*, who has been unable to face the painful reality of his village becoming divided left him unwilling to determine if he is an Indian or a Pakistani. Felanee, unlike Bishen Singh in the Urdu writer Manto's tale, resists the identity crises that surround her. She is proud of her multi-ethnicity. It is her multi-ethnic character that has put her into such a difficult situation. She becomes a target of insurgencies during the Assam agitation. Felanee also cautions the reader to accept her Bodo tribe's customs and traditions by wearing the Dokhona during the Assam march. Felanee is a homage to the tenacious character of those dwelling on the fringe, navigating the difficult times before rising as a survivor. She is proud of her multi-ethnicity yet sometimes she wonders, "What shall she wear? What would she take? Baishya had asked her to remove the 'shakha-pola' if she wanted to be alive. Bulen says she must wear the 'dokhna' if she wants to live. The young men with guns have warned her against mixing with outsiders" (*SOF* 155). Therefore, many times in her life she faces this dilemma of what to do and what not to do. However, she is very much aware of her multiethnic lineage and discovers herself as a proud multiethnic individual.

Like other characters in the novel, Felanee is pulled between the temptation of emerald Assam and the innate necessity to live. Felanee as well as the other female characters in the novel are transferred again to the Assamese group's slaughter. "In most cases of violence the victims were Bengali Muslims or Bengali Hindus; their villages were attacked, their homes torched" (*SOF* 313). The protagonists' hearts and minds are also engraved with agony from having to wake up to the loud crack of such a

bomb or gunshots fired at a juncture distance. Because historical experiences of violence infiltrate into the present and affect the individuals living in these regions, an emphasis on building instead of demolishing buildings emerges.

Felanee's soul is drawn to the hills' beauty, but she is quickly confronted with the savagery of the highland. According to Felanee, the hill's beauty as a location represents a delusion; it is what Michel Foucault referred to as 'heterotopia.' The term describes locations that have more layers of significance than what would initially be apparent. Heterotopia is indeed a physical or mental realm of 'separateness,' suggesting that area doesn't really exist independently though it is in relation to crucial systems such as emotions, people, etc. (Sudradjat 30). The hill serves as a magnificent curtain for insurgents to hide their extremism in the novel. "Fearing the wrath of the Mauzadar they had disappeared into the hills" (*SOF* 7). Therefore, hills everywhere in the novel are the symbol of dreadful predictions and destiny concerning Felanee too.

The use of the term 'boys' to refer to insurgents in the novel aptly conveys university students' brainwashing into dark alleys of aggressiveness and extremism. Notwithstanding their terrible pasts, the writer has a tremendous deal of sympathy for such teenage boys. Minoti protects the children from the Indian military's watchful eyes, while Bulen, who's already returned to the Bodo insurgent group, is viewed warmly by Felanee. The territories of individuals like Felanee, Bulen, Minoti, Kali Boori, and others who dwell on the periphery of society are persecuted by both democracies as well as military activities done by diverse organisations for their own nation or territory. As Arupa Pathangia Kalita asserts:

The people who came to take gamosas from her were the destitute, helpless people with not the least idea of their caste or creed. They were a group of dirty

people. Jon's Ma, Minoti, Kali Boori, Phool, Jaggu, Jaggu's ailing wife, Bulen, Sumala, Nabin, Ratna's Ma, and with his shaky limbs and hunchback, even the old tailor – Bura Dorjee! (168)

The Assam revolution evolved from large protests opposing undocumented immigrants towards cultural genocide, the formation of numerous military organisations, and also the desire for statehood by different ethnicities inside the region. Arindam Borkataki opines, “The geographical location of the northeastern States has always deprived them of a central Indian identity. Even in the past, the cultural variety of this region had been a hindrance to its assimilation into the Indian identity. . . . Of course, this difference was political, created by the political formality of the creation of the Indian Union.” So politics is also one of the reasons for having such issues at a certain place as Arupa also highlights the same in the novel.

Kalita shows the issues faced by other women characters in the novel like Jon's mother is a victim of domestic violence, as well as mental and sexual assault by her husband. Once during a conversation with Felanee, she shows her the brutality of her husband and Felanee notices, “the woman's firm black breasts were scarred with numerous wounds, that looked red and raw” (*SOF* 80). Children are exposed to both physical as well as mental suffering while being the family's primary source of income. *The Story of Felanee* depicts a comprehensive and effective connection between a group of exiled females that allows them to create new identities, solace, embrace, and endure their separated circumstances. Whenever the Assamese separatist struggle and yearning for freedom were at their peak, the administrators and hierarchy benefited the most, whereas women, children, and the elderly endured the most affecting the usefulness of friendships. The novel depicts shattered friendships, persecution,

disagreements, and even emotional agony. Several female characters do need to have their own identities; instead, they are referred to by the identities of their kids or husbands.

As a consequence of actions centred on a desire for a unique region in a certain society, people like Felanee, Kali Boori, Bulen, Minoti, and others who live on the outskirts of communities are encroached upon by the members of the dominant subgroup. The privileged classes in such uprisings have a great proclivity to occupy public areas in order to display their control. Inside the novel, democratic and military groups, both state-sponsored and anti-State, seize, dismember, and destroy public spaces. That space is neither a crimping, blank, or impartial location, nor it is determined solely by topography, climate, or ethnicity. Kali Boori, Felanee, Jon's mother, Minoti, Ratna's mother, Nabin, Jaggu, and others are a group of poor as well as defenceless individuals who have no concept of their caste or creed and may have come to establish a colony to make a living and integrate themselves with the larger Assamese culture.

Even the phrases used to welcome the female protagonists demonstrate how women are humiliated. This is shown in part by Minoti's argument with the driver's wife, "Hey, you bitch, why do you abuse my guest? . . . "You whore, I'll cut your tongue off; you just wait and watch" (*SOF* 83). Furthermore, readers note that many of the female protagonists do not have their own names; they are called by their children's or husband's names: Moni's Ma, Ratna's mother, the driver's wife, Jon's Mother, Jaggu's wife etc. This shows that in lower or middle-class people identity of a woman is only with the name of any male member of her family. Individually she doesn't have any existence of her own as shown by Kalita as she addresses most of the women with the

names of their family members, never individually. It shows how patriarchy stereotypes a woman only as someone's mother, wife, daughter or sister but never as an independent individual like men.

India Against Itself: Assam and the Politics of Nationality by Sanjib Baruah, like *Felanee* by Patangia, is about political and strategic factions attempting to reconstruct public areas in order to assert their domination and influence. He claims that the long-running conflict and counter-insurgency operations in the region have weakened democracy and imposed totalitarian rules. There is indeed a growing 'disconnection' between the idea of ancestral hometown and the country's political economy, which enables ethnic strife and refugee flows relatively easily. There have been no unambiguous anti-insurgency and pro-insurgency views, but instead complex issues with really no solutions (Chadda 370).

Assamese people centre their identity "around the Assamese language, the root of which has been discussed through history and culture. However, the question of identity for Assam and the Assamese people in the national context continues to be a cause for contradiction. Instead of being an answer to the problem, it has always remained a question" (Borkataki). The story's characters show a slow moulding of life amid the debris, which is filled with sounds of hefty footfall as gunshots representing the military's power and extortion messages, abductions, and executions representing insurgents on either end. Similar incidents are depicted by Arupa in *The Story of Felanee* and the novel ends with Felanee, Maya, Minoti, and many others venturing and "remembering the work waiting to be done at home they started walking fast. The reeds had to be dried. The roofs had to be thatched. The walls had to be made and plastered" (SOF 312).

The story depicts how Felanee survived bravely the pathetic situations in her life and ultimately shares her identity in the form of a strong companionship among other women. All these women stand against the patriarchal conflicts in their lives by supporting and sustaining each other in their bad times. This identity which these women characters revealed, is making them happier and stronger to fight against every odd with each other's help. Felanee also seems quite content with this new shared identity as a 'woman companion' which gives her immense pleasure and satisfaction to help and sustain each other at the end of the novel.

Homelessness is also one of the main aspects of the novel as most of the characters lose their ancestral homes during the ethnic riots and are forced to live in refugee camps with their surviving family members. All these people especially women share a common identity amid ethnic conflicts in Assam. Therefore, later on all these women construct a new habitat together at a place to lead their lives. "Homelessness causes lots of stress for women and the community as a whole. The novelist, through the experiences of Felanee, tries to rationally explain the shocking and violent agitations in Assam that had led to the death of many people. The novel also addresses the situation faced by the marginalised people who became refugees in their own home state" (Nyori and Riba 138). Such people suffer from identity crises because of their unstable lives which affect society in an adverse manner. "According to Lichtenstein, society depends on the stable identities of individuals. When the cultural storehouse of available roles fails to fit the identity themes of enough people, the mismatched persons may suffer identity crises and the culture suffer catastrophic change" (Gardiner 350). Due to these revolts and ethnic riots in Assam, the people remain unstable as every now and then they have to move away from their habitats in order to save their lives in such bloodshed.

Arupa Pathangia Kalita through her depiction of Felanee shows the multicultural and multiethnic identity of many Assamese women due to their family lineages. Felanee has to undergo a lot of stress and psychological trauma and ultimately through her introspections she reveals her real self as a multiethnic individual having a unified identity. The happy companionship of a larger number of women living together in society also shows that women like Felanee feel happy about these multiple identities and they no longer see it as trouble to their lives as appears at the beginning of the novel when Felanee was being targeted during the ethnic riots in Assam and she always has to hide her real identity as she is neither a true Bengali nor a true Assamese but a 'multiracial' due to her multi-cultural and multi-ethnic lineages.

d. Fateema's Identity as an Unimaginable and Unreal Heroine

Fence by Ila Arab Mehta is the story of a Muslim girl Fateema and her quest for identity to make herself capable enough to buy an independent house of her own amid a society where Hindu and Muslim communities reside beside each other. Ila Arab Mehta is a well-known Gujarati novelist who is a well-known feminist. Readers encounter Fateema Lokhandwala, a teenage Muslim girl in modern-day Gujarat, in this adaptation of the exquisite as well as deftly built novel *Fence*. Fateema lives in a divided world separated by religion and class. She fights to build out a position for herself as a part of such a Muslim minority, finding her own identity as well as destiny. The novel follows Fateema's journey towards self-discovery and self-realization as she strives to become a strong, independent woman. She tries to break free from her conservative Muslim society and the patriarchal society that surrounds her. She defies the traditional expectations placed upon her by her family, including an arranged marriage. The novel highlights the challenges that Fateema faces as a woman in a male-dominated society, including sexual harassment and discrimination in the workplace.

Gujarat is a Hindu-dominated State in India where Muslims are minorities. The identity of Muslim women in Gujarat has been a topic of interest for many researchers and scholars. In the context of Gujarat, the identity of Muslim women is complex, as they face discrimination on the basis of both religion and gender. The communal riots of 2002 in Gujarat further exacerbated the situation for Muslim women. Mariya Salim points out that Zakia Soman, the co-founder of the Bhartiya Muslim Mahila Andolan (BMMA), “became conscious of her Muslim identity while interacting with women survivors of the Gujarat riots in 2002 in Ahmedabad. During these riots, many Muslim women were singled out and subjected to sexual violence.”

In her novel, *The Hour Past Midnight*, Salma Ansari explores the experiences of Muslim women in Gujarat during the 2002 riots. Ansari argues that the riots had a profound impact on the identity of Muslim women in Gujarat, as they were forced to confront their identity as both Muslim and female. She explores how Muslim women coped with the violence and trauma of the riots, and how this affected their sense of identity. Therefore, the identity of Muslim women in Gujarat is complex and multifaceted. They face discrimination based on both religion and gender, and events such as the partition of India and the 2002 riots have had a profound impact on their sense of identity. Researchers and scholars need to continue exploring this topic, to gain a better understanding of the experiences of Muslim women in Gujarat.

The Hindu-Muslim rifts in Gujarat have been a long-standing issue that has plagued the State. The State has been marred by communal violence, particularly between the two religious communities, which has often led to loss of lives and property damage. The 2002 Gujarat riots, which resulted in the deaths of over 1,000 people, mostly Muslims, remain one of the most tragic episodes of communal violence

in the State's history (Raj and Gurmat). Addressing the root causes of communal tension, ensuring justice for the victims of communal violence, and promoting inter-community dialogue and reconciliation are some of the steps that need to be taken to resolve the issue.

In such a setting, Mehta, a Hindu writer, depicts the struggle of Fateema how being a low-class poor, Muslim and especially a woman, Fateema has to suffer at the hands of some orthodox Muslims like her brother and his friends. Such Muslim men want to keep all women under men's control, therefore, they don't let females to get higher education, as her brother asserts, "Finish your tenth grade. That's enough" (*Fence* 62) and Rajab Ali says, "Girls in our quam shouldn't be studying so much" (*Fence* 67). When Fateema reaches the city for her higher studies, her brother chides her and says, "You should have stayed with Abbajaan at home. I had told them not to send you" (*Fence* 77). His friend Anwar is of similar views for women when he utters, "Colleges like this spoil girls" (*Fence* 81). Further, one of Fateema's teachers informs, "how far behind we are with women's education. . . . Muslim parents are particularly reluctant to send their daughters to school" (*Fence* 108). Mehta depicts Fateema as an innocent victim of such traditional patriarchal Muslim males who don't want a woman to succeed. Therefore, indirectly Mehta blames Muslims that they are against women's higher education in Indian societies.

Once a Moulviji interrogates her father in a threatening voice, "What is this, your daughter does not wear a burka? You know about Islamic tenets, don't you?" and he further orders her father to "put an end to Fateema's education" (*Fence* 63). In Islam, wearing a burqa is considered a form of modesty and a way to protect a woman's privacy and dignity. While it is not mandatory, some Muslim women choose

to wear it as a personal choice and as a way to express their faith or identity. However, opinions on the matter vary among different Islamic scholars and communities. Some argue that the burqa is not required by Islamic law and that modest clothing is enough to fulfil the requirement of modesty (Furseth 374). Ultimately, the decision to wear a burqa or not is a personal one and should be respected.

Through the character of Fateema, Mehta clings burkha to a patriarchal stereotypical way of restricting Muslim women at home and has nothing to do with their identity, therefore, Fateema objects to her brother when he forces her to wear one. He threatens her by saying, “Shut up! Your tongue’s wagging too much these days. We intend to advise every family to make its women wear a burka. You will also have to wear one” (*Fence* 122). One night, Kareem brings her a burka and he hands over the packet to Fateema. When she asks about what is there in the packet, he replies, “Your identity” (*Fence* 123). It shows that Muslim men feel their women should wear burkha because it is their cultural identity. While some women may choose to wear a burkha as a sign of religious devotion, others may wear it as a symbol of cultural identity or for personal reasons (Piela). It is important to respect the choices of individuals when it comes to their dress and cultural practices.

Mehta gives a stereotypical image of most of the male characters in the novel and they are linked to the extremist people in Islam who are exponents of ‘Jihad.’ As the story reveals when Fateema comes to know about Kareem and his friend’s reality as she finds a briefcase with “Jihadi literature? Was Kareem a jihadi?” (*Fence* 131), she questions herself while she was in utter disbelief after knowing this. Kareem’s friend Anwar, Anwar’s mother, Moulviji and other males are depicted as the profound propagators of jihadi culture in Islam.

Despite numerous obstacles in her way, Fateema is determined to complete her higher education and get a job for herself in order to become a self-reliant woman. When Manuben says that her family must be looking for a groom for her now because in her *quam* this is what happens with a girl child. Fateema replies, “No, no, I want to do an MA” (*Fence* 94). After confronting all the obstacles that come her way in her quest to become a self-reliant woman and own an independent house, Manuben proudly tells her that after whatever she has achieved with her hard work, “You have a right to be respected” (*Fence* 139). Ultimately Fateema is able to own an independent house of her own as she has dreamt beside a Hindu colony with a fence dividing them.

The history and literature of India show that religious conflicts between Hindus and Muslims are always there. The novel is situated in a state like Gujarat which is a Hindu-dominated state and Hindu-Muslim conflicts have been reported quite often. In the midst of such conflicting realities in Gujarat, the existence of Fateema and her dream of having an independent house beside a Hindu society seems only imaginable. Moreover, throughout the novel most of the male Muslim characters are depicted by Mehta in a stereotypical image of Jihadis. On the one hand, Mehta through the portrayal of Fateema wants to dismantle the barrier between Hindus and Muslims and on the other, she is portraying most of the Muslim characters except Fateema and her parents in a stereotypical manner. How one can expect a positive response from the people of the ‘other religion’ (Muslim) when Mehta herself being the ‘other’ (Hindu) is pointing towards the negative side of their religion? Therefore, keeping these things in mind the identity and existence of Fateema seems quite unimaginable and unreal.

e. K. R. Meera's Chetna's as the 'New Woman'

Hangwoman is a novel by K.R. Meera that tells the story of Chetna, a young woman who defies the patriarchal culture of Indian rural societies and becomes India's first female executioner. Chetna's journey towards self-identity and acceptance is a central theme of the novel, as she struggles to reconcile her desire for power and independence with the social expectations placed upon her as a woman. Meera's novel traverses the complex intersections of gender, power, and identity through Chetna's story, ultimately offering a powerful critique of the ways in which society constructs and limits individual identity. Through a number of incidents in the life of Chetna, Meera shows how everyone except Chetna's Thakuma discourages her from the idea of taking up the job of a hangwoman. But all these negations and obstacles further strengthen her decision to be a strong woman both physically and mentally who can even perform the task of a hangman which has never been done by any woman in the history of India.

History of India also plays a very important role in the construction of the plot of the novel as K. R. Meera through the stream of consciousness of Chetna goes back and forth in the history of India to mention the number of strong women administrators and rulers from India in order to show that women have done it in past and they are quite capable to repeat the same in future as well. Through recalling such powerful women from the history of India Chetna gets her mental strength to accept the job of an executioner. As Ann Chastain remarks, "Regular positive thinking will help you develop inner peace, success, improved relationships, better health, happiness and personal satisfaction. Positive thinking can be your key to success!" The negative thoughts around her also keep on intriguing her to become further confident about her real physical and mental strength.

The novelist is from Kerala but the narrative of the novel is set in West Bengal. While replying to the question of the aligned setting of her novel Meera asserts, “I had always wanted to write a book on women empowerment in India, but I was not sure where to place my characters. It was at this time that I came to know about the hanging of Dhananjay Chatterjee (convicted for killing a teenage girl), in Kolkata, on August 14, 2004” (qtd. in Sebastian). This is the reason why Meera sets the story of this novel in Bengal. In order to locate the background of the novel the following section discusses the position of women in Bengal for the last two decades to compare it with the other novels selected in the present study.

Bharati Ray is of the view that for the last many decades, Bengali women have been fighting hard to remove the gender inequalities in their society and getting articulated, educated and actively participating in public life. As a “nascent ‘feminist’ consciousness was emerging among them; they revealed a growing awareness of gender asymmetry and initiated moves to counter it. They left a legacy for the latter-day women to work upon for a society free from gender discrimination” (Ray 21).

However, Pallav Mukhopadhyay opines, “Despite the land of various political, social, economic and cultural movements, the State has failed to organize a movement for development and upliftment of women as an entire class” (1). Therefore, the condition of women especially in the rural parts of West Bengal more or less remains the same as it was a few decades back. But there is no denying the fact that slowly it is improving day by day as compared to a century ago or so. The role of education is very important for the same, therefore, “Expansion of education of women in West Bengal should be aimed at ending injustice and enhancing the individual potential as well as social contribution of those member of society who have limited opportunities” (Mukhopadhyay 28).

K. R. Meera's *Hangwoman* is a stinging condemnation of current societal cruelty, dual morals, and immoral attitudes toward females. *Hangwoman* is much more than merely a novel with a distinctive narrative that shows a powerful woman; instead, it is a social critique of a subjectively chronological analysis of the male-centred history, a call to write her tale, and a dismantling of gender norms in a patriarchal culture. So in a way, Meera has targeted the masculine and feminine concepts of gender discrimination in Indian societies. B. June West is of the view that the concept of 'New Woman' in literature is described as a female character who "emphasizes the identity of interests that all human beings have. While she recognizes the diversity involved in true equality, she sees that the diversity isn't necessarily on sex lines, but on the lines of what each individual has to contribute to society" (67). Chetna emerges as among the most powerful and stubborn female characters yet imagined in Indian regional literatures.

The story depicts her quest to become a symbol of power in the male-dominated world and earns a 'New Woman' title for herself by showing sheer mental and physical strength. Hareesh K and Sreenath Muraleedharan K opine, "The challenging quest starts with the title *Aarachar* itself, denotes the 'hangman' in Malayalam which did not even have a feminine counter word" (197). Therefore, Meera "throws light into a new area of womanhood by analysing the gender schematization in *Hangwoman* along with analysing the elevated journey of a woman from the constructed femininity to the emerged self" (KG and K 197). Chetna is up against authorities, stuck in a situation where she must deal with one of the most humiliating unjust inhumanities by a man, she both loves and hates. All through the novel, she is not ever publicly confined by authorities but is continuously driven into a position of servitude by the ideals that surround her. Further, the section explores Chetna's quest to become the 'new woman'

to throw off the shackles of the hackneyed images created by patriarchal societies for women in India. Minakshi Sharma opines, “Identity becomes dangerous when individuals cannot achieve an identity because they are not invited by those who already possess it. Individuals may be members of multiple groups and therefore assume different identities. Identities are imagined identities; they are what we believe ourselves to be and what we must be” (1384).

Hangwoman connects with Foucault's thoughts on control because of this complicated representation of leadership. The novel is founded on Foucault's idea of subjectivity construction, which states there's enough space to create the ‘self’ or to have numerous relationships with ourselves and inspired by Foucault's idea of the objective to explore, wherein a woman's actions of reality are varied because each link includes a distinct political battle. Numerous linkages inevitably lead to a plethora of authoritative disputes, which in turn contribute to the rise of diverse specific topics. Those subject arrangements, on the other hand, aren't set in stone. Every time you execute, you construct a modern type of bond with yourself. Species, including humans, inevitably lead to a plethora of power disputes that lead to the formation of various specific topics (Hari 244). K. R. Meera's character is distinct in that, notwithstanding her servitude, she is capable of maintaining a separation from full submission and shows the fortitude to revolt. Chetana aspires to be tougher, but her father would not let her walk on her own. Phanibhushan Mullick is a representation of the average Indian father concerned about his daughter's chastity yet like all other stereotypical males in the patriarchal culture he wants to keep her always under his control as he feels she is just a weak woman who is not yet capable enough to take her own decisions.

Sanjeev Kumar Mitra argues that the destitute suffering in Kolkata has become less important than the diary of the Hangwoman. The character of Sanjeev Kumar Mitra points out the darker side of news and media as it shows how Indian media has, “crept into a world of politics, bureaucracy and sensation driven media and the sensational story makers . . . where news making has become a creation for entertainment, the ways and means the newsmakers create sensational stories to raise the viewer’s rate, has posed several questions on humanity” (K.G. and K.T. 2206). He tries to use Chetna as a puppet for his own interests when he thrusts her “suddenly into the public eye and undesired media attention. Thrown into a world of politics, bureaucracy and sensation-driven media, the mechanics of subjugation surrounds her when she becomes a pawn in the hands of a quintessentially ambitious journalist Sanjeev Kumar Mitra” (Jose 980). As she loves him, therefore, his actions completely jolt her individual psyche towards men.

K. Mini says that Sanjeev Kumar Mitra is “an embodiment of the new media capitalism. He is even ready to share his life to achieve such a valuable media object. He is not obsessed with the woman named Chetna but with owning that media object” (g301). It shows how the media wants to caricature the situation of Chetna’s becoming the first hangwoman in Kolkata. Her father also tries to use media to show off his own capabilities as an executioner who has executed 84 criminals during his tenure as a hangman. He along with Sanjeev Kumar tries to politicize the situation for more channel rating points and money. Instead of focusing on the real issue of a woman “Chetna is ready to take on the work done by traditional men in order to preserve the family heritage (Mini g303), the media tries to caricature the situation by focusing on nonsense things. “However, she still keeps her dreams alive. Chetna shows that despite gaining a lot of money and fame, she values personality above everything. . . . Chetna

is a role model for a woman with a personality that has not surrendered to money, glory or masculinity” (Mini g303). It shows her identity as an honest individual who despite being a female takes up the ancestral job of an executioner as her brother is a limbless person unable to perform the task and her father is too old to remain in this position of a hangman. Therefore, she commits herself to keeping their ancestral lineage alive.

One day when Sanjeev told Chetna’s father that she is the one who speaks against the death penalty, her father says in disgust, “The sireless bitch! Let her raise her voice against me and I shall cut out her tongue!” (*Hangwoman* 280). On another occasion, he goes on to say, “Disobedient hussy! She’s stuffed with pride! I’ll kick her out if she doesn’t do what I say! Then she will have neither this family nor this house!” (*Hangwoman* 294). Her father goes to prostitutes on occasion and when he is asked why he killed his brother’s wife he replied, “I killed her so that I won’t have to grab her! I can’t accept a cheap whore as my sister-in-law!” (*Hangwoman* 399). This shows the double standards of the man towards a woman that on the one hand, he himself seeks prostitutes for pleasure and on the other hand if one is there in his family itself then it becomes an intolerable problem of honour for him.

Chetna investigates her own individuality as she seeks knowledge about the skills of an executioner throughout the novel, as she walks across strange stories and facts concerning hangmen. The river Ganges may be able to help her achieve her goal because streams were holy in their origins as well as a powerful supernatural resource to ensure success. As the story progresses, Chetna learns that the best way to exercise liberty is to consciously connect with the networks of authority. That is the reason why she accepted the offer of Sanjeev Kumar Mitra to give an exclusive interview on his channel and signed the contract even when her father was not happy with her decision.

Her father wants Chetna to be under his control and expects her to follow his every instruction strictly to do the job of an executioner. He feels and brags that he is the most experienced executioner his family ever had with the greatest number of executed hangings.

Further, he considers Chetna weak because of her being female as he brags, “‘Huh! Listen to that! Haven’t I been doing it alone! I am a man whereas you are a mere woman!’” (*Hangwoman* 396). That is the reason why he wants his son Ramu to be the executioner after him but he was disabled after one bad incident. Chetna recalls that at the time of her birth her disappointed father questions, “‘Eh, what? Not a boy?’” and even her mother also repents “‘that she had brought into this world yet another unfortunate creature’” (*Hangwoman* 198).

As K. D. Upadhyaya points out, “‘In Hindu Society, the importance of a wife is estimated by the number of sons she begets. . . . In one of the folk songs a father expresses the pangs of his heart thus: ‘O daughter! as soon as you were born, I became the object of contempt and abuse for others’” (83). Therefore, Chetna’s father also wished to have a son at her birth which itself marks a negative impact on the psyche of a female child as she feels herself as an unwanted child. This shows the mentality of most of the Indian rural parents who want only boys not desire to have a female child and even after the birth of the baby girl they keep on lamenting their luck.

An executioner’s job is to hang even his own family member if he is guilty of a crime and there is no escape from the duty. Therefore, the task is not as easy as everyone thinks, “‘Pride swelled in Thakuma’s voice: ‘No ordinary person can do it. The mind must be firm, the hand must be strong and you’ve got to have brains.’” (*Hangwoman* 12-13). When a minister was not ready to accept a woman as an

executioner, he doubts, “No, no, no . . . this is not a job a woman can do . . . it requires a lot of strength . . . of mind and body . . .” and to which a young man asks, “Do you mean to say that women lack in the strength of mind and body?” He replies, “No, not that . . . but this is not a job like any other.” (*Hangwoman* 18). On one occasion during a visit to jail, an IG remarks, “These women . . . by their very nature they are second-thoughts. This isn’t a job for them” (*Hangwoman* 58). Further, in a disgusting manner, he told them, “For this job, there’s just one qualification. It has to be a man, over five feet four inches tall . . . that’s all . . .” (*Hangwoman* 57-58). Sanjeev Kumar also remarks, “Women can’t take a decision!” (*Hangwoman* 270).

During one incident some people stone a lady named Annapurna and pontificate, “A woman’s nirvana lies in her service to the husband and children” (*Hangwoman* 270). Some wonder that “a woman could attain bliss by means other than her husband, children, clothes and jewels” (*Hangwoman* 272). Hence everyone tries to discourage Chetna from her decision to become a hangwoman as they visualize Chetna not as an individual but only as a weak meek woman who is powerless and dependent upon men. However, Meera explores Chetna’s identity as an individual who fights against every obstacle that lies in her way through introspection and ultimately ends up as a strong individual who needs no one, not even her father to perform this job because “Chetna is a woman who carries out the role of samhara. Meera, by presenting Chetna as a new woman is trying to make society aware that a spark of rebellion may be present even in the most submissive woman” (Prasaja 146). Despite all the hurdles in her way, Chetna, at last, gets the job of a ‘hangwoman’ after the retirement of her father.

After seeing the determination and willingness of Chetna even her father proudly asserts, “Don’t rule her out because she is a woman. She is my daughter, she

has all the strength and genius of the Grddha Mullicks” (*Hangwoman* 67). He further adds, “She is a symbol of strength and self-respect to the whole world now . . . don’t forget that” (*Hangwoman* 71). When Chetna successfully executes the hanging, Sanjeev Kumar Mitra in a live show on his channel astonishingly remarks, “Miss Chetna Grddha Mullick, the first and only hangwoman of India!” (*Hangwoman* 427). In a gruff voice, he asks, “Chetna di, today a woman touched, all by herself, the lever which has been operated only by men all through the history of independent India. This is a great achievement for all the world’s women. What do you say about that?” (*Hangwoman* 427). Chetna asserts that at that moment he felt very weak as a man and she felt strong being a woman. Ultimately Chetna is able to achieve alone which everyone doubts about including herself. With her immense courage and self-belief, she is able to understand her real identity as a strong and powerful woman.

Chetna struggles throughout her life against the dominating world of males: in the form of her father, her would-be husband and many other male characters who feel incapable of doing the job of being the first female executioner. But Chetna is quite determined to break any form of obstacle which comes her way and she, “does not want to be a hangman’s daughter but rather a hangwoman. She changes from a voiceless obedient daughter to India’s first hangwoman” (KG and K 199). She also decides not to marry the selfish Sanjeev Kumar Mitra because now she understands that, “Marriage should only take place between equals” (*Hangwoman* 142). Now she is sure of the fact that he doesn’t suit her as her bridegroom. The one whom she will choose to marry must be an honest and strong person as once her Thakuma tells her, “You are not an ordinary woman, but a hangwoman! You can’t be married to an ordinary man” (*Hangwoman* 370). He is not a good match to her in any sense as once

she told him, “You are a weak man. You have no strength . . . no honesty . . . no stamina . . .” (*Hangwoman* 288).

Once Chetna was too disappointed with both the men in her life; her father and Sanjeev Kumar Mitra, she remarks, “I could find no man about whom I could say: This is my God. Everyone demanded worship. Not one could prove he deserved it” (*Hangwoman* 44). At last, Chetna’s hardships, “prove that there is no job that women can’t do” (*Hangwoman* 68). Her superhuman inner strength becomes quite evident when Sanjeev tries to woo her in a very sentimental way in which any woman has yielded but not Chetna and she firmly replies, “No, Sanju babu, I cannot trust you anymore. You will never realize how I loved you” (*Hangwoman* 304). Chenta in her quest for identity becomes the symbol of power and strength to all women of India and this is how Meera depicts the story of Chetna. Meera shows how Chetna achieves success with the help of education, mental strength, self-reliance and her willingness to fight against all odds in her life.

By portraying a woman in the role of an executioner the “novelist redefines the dominant cultural norms and shows how power functions and shapes the understandings of womanhood. Hither she presents a woman who transcends the limitations imposed by society” (Prasaja 143). In most of the male-dominated literature, women are always depicted as a puppet in the hands of men as V. P. Prasaja opines, “There is hardly any documented history glorifying female characters. Instead, it documents women as submissive self yielding to physical, psychological and sexual persecution” (143). Therefore, by depicting Chetna as a ‘new woman,’ Meera defies this age-old traditional culture that always sees women as weak and dependent creatures having no individual identity of their own.

To sum up, *The Taming of Women* illustrates a Dalit woman's identity in Tamil Nadu where casteism is a very prominent issue. In *The Roof Beneath Their Feet*, Geetanjali Shree portrays Chachcho and Lalna as lesbians who seek sexual freedom and desires. Both the protagonists can't find solace and happiness in the stereotypical femininity imposed upon them by their society. However, they react differently against this in their negotiation of the real identity. Chachcho becomes timid, silent and confined to herself without making any complaints to her husband and decides to suffer silently, on the other hand, Lalna reacts violently against the suppression posed upon her by the male-dominated society that condemns her as unsocial and a really bad woman with a filthy character.

Kalita on the other hand depicts the multi-ethnic and multi-cultural identity of women like the main protagonist Felanee who is a blend of many ethnic lineages and cultures. Kalita challenges the age-old traditional concept of 'singular identity' and presents a new 'multi-racial' identity of the people living in the State of Assam which is constantly being infiltrated by the people from the neighbouring areas especially West Bengal and Bangladesh. This infiltration is the real threat to the true identity of most of the people residing in Assam and like Felanee most of them have multiple identities.

In *Fence*, Fateema's characterization as an independent woman seems quite unreal and unimaginable due to her religious identity. In a Hindu-dominated State like Gujarat where Muslims are minorities, Ila Arab Mehta being a Hindu herself portrays a Muslim girl, Fateema, who defies all the obstacles in her way and owns an independent house to live alone beside a Hindu colony. Although she is an educated and self-reliant woman If one observes the Hindu-Muslim rifts in the State of Gujarat such a dream seems quite unreal and unimaginable in reality.

In *Hangwoman*, K. R. Meera sketches Chetna as a 'New Woman' of Kolkata and as an epitome of power and strength for all women in India. She is constantly being forced to see herself as inferior to males by her father, her fiancée, other police officials and even her mother as well. But she takes up all these obstacles in a positive manner and keeps on encouraging herself about her real inner physical and mental strength through which she feels she can do any task. The situation of the execution of a teenage rapist and murderer also gives Chetna more strength and courage to take up this task to teach such people a lesson that they should never think of committing such a brutal crime. Above all the main reason for Chetna's accepting the job of an executioner is to carry on their ancestral role of being the official executioners in Kolkata. While crossing all the obstacles successfully Chetna becomes the first female executioner from the state of West Bengal and even from India.

CHAPTER V

CONCLUSION

The literary representation of women in rural India, as depicted by regional women writers in their respective regional languages, shows how their characters perceive, interpret, engage and conduct their lives in the fictional narratives. The present study explores the status of women living in the interior regions of India as depicted in the works of select regional women writers in their respective regional languages, later translated into English. The purpose of the study is to show any similarities or differences in the lived experiences of the women residing in the different locales of rural India as the novels are selected from the different States/regions of India. Further, the selection has been confined to the novels written in the last two decades to assess any progress in the status of women in rural societies during this period. The select novels are *The Taming of Women* (2011) by P. Sivakami (originally written in Tamil in 1992), *The Roof Beneath their Feet* (2013) by Geetanjali Shree (originally in Hindi in 2001), *The Story of Felanee* (2011) by Arupa Patangia Kalita (originally in Assamese in 2003), *Fence* (2015) by Ila Arab Mehta (originally written in Gujarati in 2011) and *Hangwoman* (2016) by K. R. Meera (originally written in Malayalam in 2012).

Several prominent women writers from India have depicted some strong women characters in their works and challenged the age-old stereotypical images of women in literature. Several women writers from regional areas have also depicted similar issues faced by rural women in their works written in their regional languages. The role of women in literature has undergone some changes over the years, but until recently, male authors are primarily acknowledged while women's involvement in writing is evidently prejudiced against. Feminism's rise against patriarchy is due, in part, due to the inadequate or biased representation of women in literature.

Indian feminism evolved as a response to the patriarchal social structure and the discrimination faced by women in various spheres of life. It has been influenced by the women's suffrage movement, anti-colonial struggles, and the global feminist movement. Indian feminists have fought for equal rights and opportunities for women, including the right to education and employment, the right to live free from violence and discrimination, and the right to participate in political and social life. This results in some prominent women writers writing about the issues faced by women residing in Indian societies, yet there are only a few who discuss the real problems of the women living in rural regions of India. A brief history of women's writing in Indian literature reveals that, even in the ancient and medieval periods, the majority of literature was composed of folk songs and poetry, and that there were very few female writers overall.

As the present study is based on translated texts, therefore, it dwells briefly on Indian translation theories. In a multilingual and multicultural nation like India, there is a lot of role and scope for translation studies. The only way that cultural knowledge from any given location could be shared is if literature is translated into the reader's local tongue or another global language. However, this process of translation isn't that easy especially considering the multicultural aspect of India. The literature of India's regional languages has several linguistic and cultural distinctions. A set of unified Indian translation theories is vital in order to provide any kind of standardization in the practice of translation. Therefore, the study proposes the use of theories like transcreation, Aurobindo's psycho-spiritual, Tagore's theory of Creative Translation, and Indian Poetic theories. The role of the translator becomes quite crucial in the true and honest translation of Indian regional literatures into different languages, especially in English, the global language.

Indian literature in English cannot adequately convey the real essence of India as a nation on its own. What is required can only be accomplished by a thorough translation of the entirety of Indian literature into an international language like English. Nevertheless, it is startlingly difficult to get high-quality Hindi and English translations of texts from India's huge canon of regional dialects. The country's regional literary treasure is thus still largely unexplored due to a lack of good translations of the same. By equating languages and challenging the supremacy of specific ones over others, translation advances a free society by showing that certain ideas, even feelings, can be expressed in all languages and are possible to translate regardless of their distinctions.

As regional writers may write in their native languages, which are later translated into more widely used and acknowledged languages, it also enables those in the lower echelons of society to be considered. Regional writers express more accurately the condition of women residing in their particular region in their local language. Therefore, there is a need to look more at the works of regional authors translated into English to bring those issues to the global level. For that, there is a need for good translations of famous regional works in English. Indian regional literature is very huge in volume so it is necessary to explore the unexplored.

Several regional women writers are writing in their regional language and depicting the first-hand experiences of women living in rural regions of India. These issues of the rural women cannot come out of that particular region unless these works get a global readership through their translation into English. Therefore, the role and scope of translation in India is more than anywhere else in the world. Good English translations of regional writers' works will surely enrich India's native literature while

also contributing significantly to international literature. A detailed review of the select authors and their respective works shows that there is a lot which is unexplored so far. The present study explores in detail the various aspects of gender inequality in the form of lived experiences of women living in Indian rural societies as depicted in the selected narratives. Further, it traverses the role of casteism in women's subjugation in Sivakami's *The Taming of Women*, religion in Ila Arab Mehta's *Fence*, and regional women's identities as showcased by the select women writers in their respective novels.

A discussion of P. Sivakami's *The Taming of Women* concludes that caste, class, and gender have a very devastating effect on women's subjugation in Indian rural societies. The novel is situated in Tamil Nadu where casteism is quite an issue and Dalit women are doubly or triply oppressed as depicted by Sivakami. The analysis of the novel shows how women are subjected to physical and psychological trauma in their domestic lives. The main protagonist, Anandhayi, suffers from domestic violence from her tyrannical husband who doesn't even spare any of his daughters and beats them very badly over trivial matters. The episodes from the marital life of Anandhayi's daughter Dhannam show that dowry is also a very serious matter in the rural areas where a daughter's parents don't have enough money to fulfil the greed of their daughter's in-laws.

Sivakami also highlights the power politics of some Dalit leaders who are supposed to solve the problems of the poor people of their caste but instead, they misuse their powers. The brutal treatment of Lakshmi, the daughter of a slightly high-caste poor farmer, shows how these powerful leaders not only sexually exploit their wives at home but also some poor women like Lakshmi. The analyses show how

Anandhayi and Lakshmi are merely seen as sexual objects by Periyannan which results in their physical and psychological trauma. Further, one of the main causes of gender discrimination in a patriarchal society is the stereotyped conditioning of both sexes, since people expect men and women to act in particular ways at all times. Because of these negative, stereotypical ideas about men in society, some men create a false or traumatized identity. This may be the cause of their eventual cruelty to others and, in the worst cases, their transformation into womanizers in an attempt to prove their manhood as is the case of Periyannan.

The study finds how the caste and class of a woman further increase her woes. The financial dependency of Anandhayi and Lakshmi forces them to stay with Periyannan despite his cruelties. Lakshmi, however, opposes him on several occasions and tries to run away from his cruel clutches as well but the case of Anandhayi is worse as she has to stay with him only for the sake of her children. Such is the picture of a Dalit woman in Tamil Nadu which the writer explores through the character of Anandhayi. With the iconic image of Anandhayi, Sivakami's work deftly explores the identity of Dalit women in Tamil Nadu. It highlights the difficulties these women encounter while also demonstrating their capacity to get over roadblocks and realize their objectives.

The textual analysis of *The Roof Beneath their Feet* by Geetanjali Shree holds that patriarchal objectification and social stereotyping of sexes immensely contribute towards gender inequality in societies. Stereotypes are preconceptions and idealized representations of genders that negatively impact how we view, relate to, and treat individuals. Such presumptions constrain the individuals they target, give them responsibilities that may not be appropriate for them, and make it more difficult for

them to be true to themselves. The characters of Chachcho and Lalna show the negative impact on the psyche of individuals due to such stereotypical conditioning of individuals in patriarchal societies. The study shows Chachcho isn't happy with her insensitive husband who doesn't fulfil her bodily desires for which her heart keeps craving for. He is always very cold towards her. She keeps suppressing her feelings due to her psychological conditioning since her birth and even loses her desire to live before the entry of Lalna into her life.

On the other hand, Lalna has an aggressive nature and she opposes openly against the patriarchal suppressions from the people of society. She never behaves in a stereotypical manner as society expects from a woman; therefore, society considers her as a wild woman with a bad character. Her character is exactly what Chachcho wants to be from deep inside but due to social constraints, she always keeps resisting herself. So with the advent of Lalna in her life, she starts liking and protecting her from everyone in the Laburnum house who unnecessarily raise their finger upon her character. Lalna's treatment in the novel shows how a traditional society looks upon a woman who doesn't conform to the stereotypical ideals decided for them.

Due to the ill-treatment, they receive in a male-dominated culture, they start seeking refuge on the roof of the Laburnum house which is the symbol of their entrapped wild feelings. With their relationship, they find the true beauty and meaning of their life which has been colourless. Shree hints towards their lesbian relationship and shows how they find solace in each other's company. In Indian culture, especially in rural areas, the dynamics of lesbianism that Geetanjali Shree depicts through Chachcho and Lalna's relationship is relatively new and rather taboo. No one can dispute the reality that queer gay relationships are a genuine part of people's imaginations and joys,

even in Indian society and among academics where they are highly marginalized. Geetanjali Shree is from New Delhi where there are not many issues like caste or class as depicted by P. Sivakami from Tamil Nadu. Whereas, Anandhayi from *The Taming of Women* is discriminated against for even basic things in her life and she is financially dependent upon men. On the other hand, a financially sound woman like Chachcho from *The Roof Beneath their Feet* has some different issues to deal with which shows the difference in gender inequality based on the caste and class of an individual in Indian rural societies.

The Story of Felanee by Arupa Pathangia Kalita is located in the background of ethnic conflicts in the state of Assam during the late 1970s and early 1980s. The history of Assam shows the State constantly reports some mild or severe incidents of ethnic riots since the state's existence. The story of the novel is set during the Assam Movement with the inception of the 'Assam Students Union' to save the cultural identity and the land of the true Assamese people. The State is under the constant threat of illegal infiltration of Bengali and Bangladeshis which not only endangers their identity but also their ancestral land. Due to the illegal migration of the people from Bangladesh even the national identity of the native people of Assam is also at risk. Therefore, the Bodo inhabitants of Assam constantly revolt against such illegal infiltration which results in ethnic conflicts in the state as it is inhabited by people of various ethnic groups/cultures.

The analysis of the novel shows how wars and ethnic riots create traumatic conditions for women and children and how they become easy targets for the rioters from both sides. Women characters in the novel especially Felanee undergo physical and mental torments during the ethnic riots in Assam. She becomes the victim of these

ethnic riots not only once but twice. At the time of her birth, her parents die in an outbreak of violence and later after the birth of her son she faces a similar situation and loses everything except her son. Therefore, due to such violent experiences in her life, Felanee suffers from psychological trauma and she remains under the impact of the trauma for a long time. One of the characters, Bulen's wife also suffers sexual exploitation during one of such riots and loses her mental balance due to the psychological trauma she has to go through at that time. Such episodes from the novel suggest that women suffer the most during such situations at any place.

Due to constant migrations from and into Assam, the people of Assam develop multiple identities which sometimes becomes a problem for them which has been explored by the writer through her depiction of the central character of the novel, Felanee. Felanee's identity crumbles in her own society, and she goes into hiding. The author challenges the conventional idea of identity as a single, cohesive entity by introducing a multi-ethnic character who now has a multiracial identity; a Bengali due to her father, a Bodo due to her mother and a Koch due to her husband. The study shows most of the women residing in the state of Assam battling the problem of identity where identities are constantly mixed due to illegal migration. The analysis conveys that the issues of women living in Assam as depicted by Arupa Pathaniga Kalita are totally different from those living in Tamil Nadu as depicted by P. Sivakami.

It also emerges that in Ila Arab Mehta's *Fence* religion is one of the factors in women's subjugation and gender inequality in a religious nation like India and the effect of the same is adverse in rural regions. The foundation of Indian societies is their religion and culture. The textual analysis of the novel shows how the main protagonist, Fateema who is a Muslim girl, is forced to wear a burkha and give up her higher studies

on the orders of some of the orthodox Islamic people including her brother, Karim. The narrative of the novel shows how Mehta caricatures a Muslim girl who fights against every odd in the name of religion and ends up completing her higher education to be an independent woman and own an independent house beside a Hindu colony to live independently.

However, the present study finds that despite some positive developments, there is still a long way to go in terms of improving Hindu-Muslim relations in Gujarat. It is important for the government and civil society to work towards promoting inter-faith dialogue and understanding, and to ensure that incidents of communal violence are dealt with swiftly and impartially. Therefore, such a representation of a Muslim girl in the setting of a state like Gujarat seems quite unreal and unimaginable as the history of the state proves that Hindu-Muslim conflicts are quite common over there. Moreover, none of the critics so far have touched upon the socio-political angle in the novel which seems quite obvious as Mehta who is a Hindu writer, fault-finds negative aspects of the Muslim religion. The narrative shows how Mehta is quite critical towards Muslim women wearing burkha whereas several Muslim women do not find it a burden but as a symbol of their distinct identity and a part of their attire.

The present study finds that Mehta depicts stereotypical images of males in Islam by associating them with 'Muslim Jihad' which suggests bias of the writer being a Hindu. Although Mehta's stance of advocating women's rights and equality is fairly justified, but as a Hindu, her perception of the Muslim religion is not free from bias. There are many issues pertaining to the lives of Hindu women and the Hindu religion, but still Mehta chooses to write about the 'other' religion and seems to be creating Muslim stereotypes through her male characters in the novel.

K. R. Meera's *Hangwoman* suggests that gender discrimination, patriarchal stereotypes and objectification of women are the main reasons for gender inequality in the rural regions of West Bengal. Gender-based discrimination and violence against women are still prevalent, and many women are not aware of their rights and entitlements. The lack of infrastructure and resources in rural areas also poses a challenge for women to access basic amenities. The narrative shows how a poor girl Chetna is discriminated against and psychologically traumatized by the male-dominated orthodox people after her father proposes her name to be the next executioner from their family. The social stereotypes of the sexes in Indian societies come into force and everyone starts questioning the capabilities of a woman to perform the extremely hard task of an official executioner. Some point out her sex and others refer to physical attributes required to be an executioner and solely reject the idea of a patriarchally labelled stereotyped 'weak' woman taking up a job that is only meant for a patriarchally labelled stereotyped 'strong' man.

However, Meera through her depiction of Chetna, defies the age-old ideas of feminine and masculine that prevail in Indian societies. Thus, Meera represents Chetna as a new woman in rural India. The term 'new women' refers to a feminist ideal that emerged in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. The new woman is a departure from traditional gender roles and expectations, embodying independence, education, and a desire for social and political equality. This idea is quite popular in modern literature and the media and is often associated with the suffrage movement. The new woman is also seen as a threat to traditional values and societal norms and is often met with resistance and criticism. Despite this, the concept of the new woman continues to inspire and influence feminist movements around the world.

One finds how Chetna defies gender discrimination, social stereotypes, and patriarchal objectification faced by the male-dominated culture and comes out victorious after successfully completing her first official execution without the help of her father. Through her mental and physical strength, she proves to everyone that there is nothing a woman cannot do with her dedicated approach. Further, Meera shows that the patriarchal stratification of power is so biased in Indian societies as males are associated with masculine attributes and are supposed to be physically and mentally stronger than females who are associated with feminine qualities and are supposed to be emotionally and physically weak. This social stereotyping of the sexes is one of the main reasons for gender inequality in Indian patriarchal societies which makes one sex superior to the other and creates differences.

One also comes across the capitalistic attitude of the Indian media, which gives more importance to money than anything else. The media is ready to play with the rights and emotions of people for the sake of being more popular and maximising their capital gains out of any news. Meera shows how the capitalistic media caricatures the sensitive issue of gender equality by playing with the emotions of Chetna and the family members of the accused. This shows the insensitivity of media persons towards the feelings of those involved in any incident and their sole purpose is to increase the Target Rating Point of their channels. Through the character of Chetna, Meera exposes the evil plans of today's selfish media.

There are similarities in the depiction of women's issues in aspects like gender discrimination, social stereotyping, patriarchal objectification and marriage as an institution in different States/regions of Indian rural societies as portrayed by the select

writers through their women characters residing in different locales. However, there are also differences in the experiences of the women based on the aspects peculiar to a particular State or region to which the narrative belongs.

As casteism is the main issue in Tamil Nadu, therefore, P. Sivakami's depiction of a Dalit woman, through the character of Anandhayi, is absolutely different from those of the other women characters portrayed by the writers from the other States/regions. She is the most physically and mentally tormented woman character of all. Geetanjali Shree from New Delhi, expresses her concerns for freedom and equality for women in establishing relationships with anyone. The problem of her women characters is explicitly different from other select regional women writers.

Felanee's issues as depicted by Arupa Pathangia Kalita due to her multi-ethnic identity are quite peculiar to a State like Assam where the identity of people is constantly under threat because of the incidents of illegal migration and ethnic riots. Likewise, in a state like Gujarat where religious conflicts between Hindus and Muslims are quite common, Fateema's experiences are utterly different from those of the other characters situated in different locales. The studies on Bengali women show that Bengali women are a diverse group of individuals with a rich history and culture. They have made significant contributions in various fields such as literature, art, music, and politics. Bengali women are known for their strength, resilience, and intellectual prowess. Similar is the depiction of a Bengali girl Chetna by K. R. Meera in her *Hangwoman*, who defies the traditional social stereotypes of masculinity and femininity in male-dominated Indian societies.

One also finds that there has been a slight change in the status of women in Indian rural societies for the last two decades. There has been a slight transition of

women from the margins to the centre in the last two decades. It is right to say that education plays a vital role in the emancipation of women in Indian rural societies. Before 2000 the literacy rate of females was quite low as compared to 2011 or later. P. Sivakami's *The Taming of Women* which was originally written in 1989 shows how uneducated women like Anandhayi and Lakshmi are brutally tortured due to their financial dependency on males. Similarly, Geetanjali Shree's *The Roof Beneath their Feet* which was originally written in 2001 depicts uneducated women characters like Chachcho and Lalna and one of the reasons for their discrimination is also their illiteracy.

However, educated women as depicted by K. R. Meera and Ila Arab Mehta in their novels are aware of their fundamental rights and financially empowered. Meera in *Hangwoman* which was originally written in 2012 depicts Chetna as a self-reliant woman. Ila Arab Mehta in *Fence* which was originally written in 2011 portrays Fateema as a highly educated and empowered woman who succeeds in purchasing an independent house. This shows how education empowers a woman and emancipates her to reach and share the power centre with men.

Limitations of the Present Study and the Scope for Future Research

The present study remains confined to the exploration of the thematic aspects of the problems faced by women as depicted by the regional women writers and does not take up exploration of the formal aspects of their novels. Therefore, one can further explore the differences in the form and structure of the regional women writers from the different States of India. One can also compare the form and structure of the novels of the regional women writers with those of the mainstream women writers who write in

English. On similar lines, an exhaustive comparative study can also be undertaken comparing English and regional women writers in their depiction of issues concerning rural women to observe any differences or similarities in their portrayal.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Primary Sources

Kalita, Arupa Pathangia. *The Story of Felanee*. Translated by Deepika Phukan, Kindle ed., Zubaan, 2011.

Meera, K. R. *Hangwoman*. Translated by J. Devika, Kindle ed., Penguin, 2016.

Mehta, Ila Arab. *Fence*. Translated by Rita Kothari, Zubaan, 2015.

Shree, Geetanjali. *The Roof Beneath their Feet*. Translated by Rahul Soni, Harper Perennial, 2013.

Sivakami, Palanimuthu. *The Taming of Women*. Translated by Pritham K Chakravarthy, Penguin, 2012.

Secondary and Online Sources

a) Books

MLA Handbook. 9th ed., Modern Language Association of America, 2021, bibliotecadefilologia.usal.es/MLA_Handbook_9ed_2021.pdf

Arya, Sunaina, and Aakash Singh Rathore, editors. *Dalit Feminist Theory: A Reader*. Taylor & Francis Group, 2020, p. ii.

Balakrishnan, Anita. *Transforming Spirit of Indian Women Writers*. Authorspress, 2012.

Bartky, Sandra-Lee. *Femininity and Domination: Studies in the Phenomenology of Oppression*. New York: Routledge, 1990, p 80.

Beasley, Chris. *What is Feminism? An Introduction to Feminist Theory*. Sage Publications, 1999.

Beauvoir, Simone de. *The Second Sex*. Vintage Books, 1973, p. 301.

- Bordo, Susan. *Unbearable Weight*, Berkeley. CA: University of California Press, 1993, p. 143.
- Chakravarti, Uma. *Gendering Caste: through a feminist lens*. SAGE Publications, 2018.
- Cowley, Jason. "Why We Chose Arundhati?" *India Today*. Oct, 27, 1997.
- Das, Sailen D., and Rubul Patgiri, editors. *Gender Issues in Northeast India: Bridging the Gap*. 1st ed., New Delhi: Authorspress, 2015.
- Firestone, Shulamith. *The Dialectic of Sex: The Case of Feminist Revolution*. 8th ed., USA, Bantam Books, 1978, pp. 8-10. teoriaevolutiva.files.wordpress.com/2013/10/firestone-shulamith-dialectic-sex-case-feminist-revolution.pdf.
- Gupta, Pallavi, et al. "Taking Services to the Doorstep: Providing Rural Indian Women Greater Control over Their Fertility." *Women's Empowerment and Global Health: A Twenty-First-Century Agenda*, edited by Shari L. Dworkin et al., 1st ed., University of California Press, 2017, pp. 29–56. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/10.1525/j.ctv1wxrqm.6.
- Irigaray, Luce. *This Sex Which is Not One*. Translated by Catherine Porter and Carolyn Burke, Cornell University Press, 1985.
- Kinsley, David R. *Hindu Goddesses: Visions of the Divine Feminine in the Hindu Religious Tradition*. University of California Press, 1988. *Academia*, www.academia.edu/8085791/Hindu_Goddess.
- Mani, Preetha. *The Idea of Indian Literature: Gender, Genre, and Comparative Method*. USA, Northwestern UP, 2022, escholarship.org/uc/item/7ch193mg.
- Millett, Kate. *Sexual Politics*. University of Illinois Press, 2000.
- Makdisi, Saree. "Literature, National Identity, and Empire." *The Cambridge Companion to English Literature, 1740–1830*, edited by Thomas Keymer and Jon Mee, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2004, pp. 61–79.

- Millett, Kate. *Sexual Politics*. Great Britain: Rupert Hart-Davis Limited, 1971.
- Mohan, Sarala Jag. "Twentieth-Century Gujarati Literature." *Handbook of Twentieth-Century Literatures of India*, edited by Nalini Natarajan, Greenwood Press, 1996. *Omnilogos*, omnilogos.com/twentieth-century-gujarati-literature/.
- Myles, Anita. *Feminism and the Post-Modern Indian Women Novelists in English*. Sarup & Sons, 2006.
- Narayan, R. K. *The Guide*. 79th ed., India, Indian Thought Publications, 2011.
- Paranjape, Makarand. "Vernacularizing the 'Master' Tongue: Indian English and Its Con-Texts." *Indian English and 'Vernacular' India*. Ed. Makarand R. Paranjape and G.J.V. Prasad. Noida: Pearson India, 2010.
- Rao, Anupama. *Gender and Caste (Issues in Contemporary Indian Feminism)*. United Kingdom: Zed Books, 2005.
- Rathod, Rakesh. *Indian Writing in English: Pre to Post Independence*. 1st ed., India, Excel Publications, 2019. *Google Books*, books.google.co.in/books?id=iaszEAAAQBAJ&printsec=frontcover&source=gbs_ge_summary_r&cad=0#v=onepage&q&f=false.
- Sharma, Sangeeta. *Gender Issues; Fictional World of Shashi Deshpande*, New Delhi: Atlantic Publishers & Distributors (P) LTD, 2016.
- Srinivas, M. N. *Social Change in Modern India*. Berkeley: University of California Press. 1968.
- Subbamma, Malladdi. *Women: Tradition and Culture*. New Delhi: Sterling Publishers, 1985.
- Saul, Jennifer. *Feminism: Issues and Arguments*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2003.

Scarborough, William J., and Barbara J. Risman. "Gender Studies." *Companion to Women's and Gender Studies*, edited by Nancy A. Naples, Wiley Blackwell, 2020. *Google Books*, [www.google.co.in/books/edition/Companion to Women and Gender Studies/WS_fDwAAQBAJ?hl=en&gbpv=1](http://www.google.co.in/books/edition/Companion_to_Women_and_Gender_Studies/WS_fDwAAQBAJ?hl=en&gbpv=1).

Sotiropoulos, Carol Strauss. *Early Feminists and the Education Debates: England, France, Germany 1760-1810*. Cranbury: Associated University Presses, 2007.

Tharu, Susie, and K. Lalita, editors. *Women Writing in India: 600 BC to the Present*. New York, The Feminist Press, 1991.

Veur, Dennis Van Der, et al. *Gender Matters: A Manual on Addressing Gender-based Violence With Young People*. Budapest, Council of Europe, 2007.

Walby, S. *Theorizing Patriarchy*. Blackwell Publishers Ltd.: Oxford, UK and Cambridge USA, 1990.

Weissbort, Daniel, and Astradur Eysteinnsson. *Translation: Theory and Practice: a Historical Reader*. United Kingdom, Oxford University Press, 2006.

Wilde, Oscar. *Colour Classics Picture Of Dorian Gray (Penguin Classics S.)*. Edited by R Mighall, New Ed, Penguin Classic, 2006.

Willis, Michael, editor. *Translation and State*. De Gruyter, Sept. 2022.

b) Articles

Abraham, Febi. "Paradigm of Perseverance: Trauma Theory and Feminism in K. R. Meera's 'Arachaar' in Comparison With the Malayalam Movie 'Kannezhuthi Pottum Thottu.'" *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, vol. 9, no. 9, Sept. 2022, p. c453, www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2209275.pdf.

Ackerly, Brooke, and Jacqui True. "With or Without Feminism? Researching Gender and Politics in the 21st Century." *European Journal of Politics and Gender*, vol. 1, no. 1–2, Bristol UP, July 2018, pp. 259–78. *Crossref*, doi:10.1332/251510818x15272520831210.

- Agnihotri, Reeta. "The Role and Scope of Translation Studies in the 21 Century." *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, vol. 1, no. 1, Jan. 2013, pp. 312–21, ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT1134347.pdf.
- Agrawal, Chandra P. "Configurations in Ashes: Twentieth Century Indian Women Writers." *Indian Literature*, vol. 34, no. 4 (144), 1991, pp. 132–44. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/23332925.
- Akhter, Tawhida. "Gender Inequality and Literature: A Contemporary Issue." *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, vol. 510, Jan. 2020, p. 593. *ResearchGate*, doi:10.2991/assehr.k.201219.090.
- Allan, J. McGrigor. "On the Real Differences in the Minds of Men and Women." *Journal of the Anthropological Society of London*, vol. 7, 1869, p. cxcv–ccxix. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.2307/3025361.
- Anandhi S. "The Mathammas: Gender, Caste and the Politics of Intersectionality in Rural Tamil Nadu." *Economic and Political Weekly*, vol. 48, no. 18, 2013, pp. 64–71. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/23527310.
- Anisha, Dr. "Translation in India: Then and Now." *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, vol. 5, no. 6, June 2018, pp. 340–47, www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR1806295.pdf.
- Argiropoulos, Catherine and Indhu Rajagopal. "Women in Poverty: Canada and India." *Economic and Political Weekly*, vol. 38, no. 7, 2003, pp. 612–14. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/4413213.
- Asghar, Jamil. "The Power Politics of Translation: A Study of Translation-Ideology Nexus." *NUML Journal of Critical Inquiry*, vol. 13, no. 2, 17 Jan. 2019, pp. 32-49, www.academia.edu/38170005/Power_Politics_of_Translation_pdf.

- Ayshath, S. R., et al. "Muslim Women in South India: Reading Selected Narratives of Sara Aboobacker." *ASIATIC*, vol. 10, no. 2, Dec. 2016, pp. 215–29. [www.academia.edu/30724212/Muslim Women in South India Reading Selected Narratives of Sara Aboobacker](http://www.academia.edu/30724212/Muslim_Women_in_South_India_Reading_Selected_Narratives_of_Sara_Aboobacker).
- Basu, Aparna. "Women's History in India: An Historiographical Survey." *Writing Women's History*, Palgrave Macmillan UK, 1991, pp. 181–209. *Crossref*, doi.org/10.1007/978-1-349-21512-6_10.
- Basumatary, Jasmine, et al. "The Days of Trial: Textualization of Conflicts in Arupa Patangia Kalita's - *The Story of Felanee*." *International Journal of Education and Applied Research*, vol 10, no 1, Jan-June 2020, pp. 16-18, www.ijear.org/vol10/issue1/3-jasmine-basumatary.pdf.
- Bayeh, Endalcachew. "The Role of Empowering Women and Achieving Gender Equality to the Sustainable Development of Ethiopia." *Pacific Science Review B: Humanities and Social Sciences*, vol. 2, no. 1, Jan. 2016, pp. 37–42, [doi:10.1016/j.psrb.2016.09.013](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psrb.2016.09.013).
- Becker, Mary. "Patriarchy and Inequality: Towards a Substantive Feminism." *University of Chicago Legal Forum*, vol. 1999, no. 1, pp. 21–88. chicagounbound.uchicago.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1266&context=uclf.
- Behtash, Esmail Zare, and Fatemeh Sajjadi. "Literary Feminism in India." *Journal of Subcontinent Researches*, vol. 4, no. 11, 2012, pp. 107–17, ensani.ir/file/download/article/20121212084505-9578-51.pdf.
- Besa, Lynn M. "Literature and Sociopolitics." *ICSAI*, Dec. 2018, icsai.org/procarch/12iclice2imelt/12iclice-016.pdf.
- Beteille, Andre. "Race, Caste and Gender." *Man*, vol. 25, no. 3, 1990, pp. 489–504. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.2307/2803715.

- Bhagawati, Ashok. "Assamese Scene: Personal Voice." *Indian Literature*, vol. 34, no. 3 (143), 1991, pp. 121–26. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/23332962.
- Bhandari, Niranjna. "Domestic Violence and Women's Health." *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, vol. 6, no. 6, June 2019, pp. 226–40, www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR1907033.pdf.
- Biswas, Chaiti Sharma, and Ishita Mukhopadhyay. "Marital Status and Women Empowerment in India." *MedCrave Online*, 15 Feb. 2018, medcraveonline.com/SIJ/SIJ-02-00030.pdf.
- Buden, Boris, et al. "Cultural Translation: An Introduction to the Problem, and Responses." *Translation Studies*, vol. 2, no. 2, June 2009, pp. 196–219. *Taylor & Francis Online*, doi:10.1080/14781700902937730.
- Carver, W. O. "Book Review: Anita: A Tale of the Philippines." *Review & Expositor*, vol. 22, no. 4, 1925, pp. 499–500. *Crossref*, doi:10.1177/003463732502200420.
- Chadda, Maya. "India Against Itself: Assam and the Politics of Nationality." *Political Science Quarterly*, vol. 115, no. 2, summer 2000, p. 320. *Gale Academic OneFile*, link.gale.com/apps/doc/A64688932/AONE?u=googlescholar&sid=bookmark-AONE&xid=3479b94c.
- Chakraborty, Puja, and Krishanu Adhikari. "Women at Crossroads: Reconfiguring the Gender Roles in Select Indian Genre Fiction." *Rupkatha Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*, vol. 12, no. 5, 2020, pp. 1–12, doi:10.21659/rupkatha.v12n5.rioc1s15n2.
- Chakravarti, Uma. "Conceptualising Brahmanical Patriarchy in Early India: Gender, Caste, Class and State." *Economic and Political Weekly*, vol. 28, no. 14, 1993, pp. 579–85. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/4399556.

- Chanana, Karuna. "THE DIALECTICS OF TRADITION AND MODERNITY AND WOMEN'S EDUCATION IN INDIA." *Sociological Bulletin*, vol. 39, no. 1/2, 1990, pp. 75–91. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/23634527.
- Chanana, Kuhu. "Plurality of Lesbian Existence in Modern Indian Writers: Manju Kapur, Rajkamal Chaudhary and Geetanjali Shree." *Indian Literature*, vol. 54, no. 3 (257), 2010, pp. 190–219. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/23349472.
- Chandrashekharamma. "The Condition of Women in Contemporary Indian Society: Anita Nair's Ladies Coupe." *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, vol. 6, no. 2, Apr. 2018, pp. 826–30, www.ijert.org/papers/IJCRT1813562.pdf.
- Chattopadhyay, Suchorita. "Ashapura Devi's 'Women' — Emerging Identities in Colonial and Postcolonial Bengal." *Argument*, vol. 21, 2012, pp. 75–95. philarchive.org/archive/CHAADW.
- Chawla, Vijay Kumar. "A Study of Individual's search for Freedom and Selfrealization theme in The Novels of Nayantara Sahgal." *International Research Journal of Management Sociology & Humanity*, vol. 7, no. 5, 2016, pp. 352–66, www.academia.edu/37273305/A_STUDY_OF_INDIVIDUALS_SEARCH_FOR_FREEDOM_AND_SELF_REALIZATION_THEME_IN_THE_NOVELS_OF_NAYANTARA_SAHGAL.
- Chen-qing, CAI. "Freedoms and Restrictions of Translator's Subjectivity in Literary Translation." *Sino-US English Teaching*, vol. 12, no. 4, David Publishing Company, Apr. 2015, pp. 294–98. *Crossref*, doi:10.17265/1539-8072/2015.04.008.
- Chhibber, Bharti. "Women's Rights Are Human Rights." *World Affairs: The Journal of International Issues*, vol. 22, no. 1, 2018, pp. 122–35. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/48520052.

- Chitra, S. "Mother's Role in Indian Culture, With Reference Anita Nair's Ladies Coupe." *Adalya Journal*, vol. 9, no. 6, 2020, p. 16, doi:10.37896/aj9.6/002.
- Choudhuri, Indra Nath. "Towards an Indian Theory of Translation." *Indian Literature*, vol. 54, no. 5 (259), 2010, pp. 113–23. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/23348221.
- Choudhury, Mompi. "Violence and Marginalization of Women in Arupa Patangia Kalita's *The Story of Felanee*." *International Journal of English, Language, Literature and Humanities*, vol. 2, issue 5, September 2014, pp. 572-76, ijellh.com/papers/2014/September/54-570-578-sept-2014.pdf.
- Christi A. Merrill. "Crafting a Feminist Dalit Consciousness in Translation." *World Literature Today*, vol. 88, no. 3–4, 2014, pp. 52–56. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.7588/worllitetoda.88.3-4.0052.
- Dagar, Sakshi. "Analysis on Quest of Identity and Prominent Women Feminist Writers in India." *Journal of Advances and Scholarly Researches in Allied Education*, vol. 15, no. 12, Dec. 2018, pp. 498–504, ignited.in/I/a/130314.
- Daiya, Kavita. *Violent Belongings: Partition, Gender, and National Culture in Postcolonial India*. Temple University Press, 2008. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt14bt2fc.
- Dalmia, Sonia, and Pareena G. Lawrence. "The Institution of Dowry in India: Why It Continues to Prevail." *The Journal of Developing Areas*, vol. 38, no. 2, 2005, pp. 71–93. *JSTOR*, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4192976>.
- Das, Jogendra Kr. "Assam: The Post-Colonial Political Developments." *The Indian Journal of Political Science*, vol. 66, no. 4, 2005, pp. 873–900. *JSTOR*, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/41856173>. Accessed 28 Sept. 2023.
- Das, Ranjana, and Ranjan Das. "The Nation and the Community: Hindus and Muslims in the novels of Bankim Chandra Chatterjee." *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress*, vol. 73, 2012, pp. 578–87. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/44156251.

- Das, Saswat S., and Bipasha Som. "The Play of Contestatory and Contesting Perspectives: Exploring the Debate about Representation of Nation in Bhasa Writing and Indian Writing in English." *Indian Literature*, vol. 55, no. 3 (263), 2011, pp. 171–203. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/23341973.
- Dasgupta, Subhas. "Tagore's Concept of Translation: A Critical Study." *Indian Literature*, vol. 56, no. 3 (269), 2012, pp. 132–44. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/23345972.
- Davis, Richard H. "Wilkins, Kasinatha, Hastings, and the First English 'Bhagavad Gītā.'" *International Journal of Hindu Studies*, vol. 19, no. 1/2, 2015, pp. 39–57. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/24631792.
- De, Aniket. "Hicky's Bengal Gazette: The Untold Story of India's First Newspaper." *South Asian History and Culture*, vol. 11, no. 2, Apr. 2020, pp. 230–32. *Crossref*, doi:10.1080/19472498.2020.1755130.
- Deshpande, Ashwini. "Overlapping Identities under Liberalization: Gender and Caste in India." *Economic Development and Cultural Change*, vol. 55, no. 4, 2007, pp. 735–60. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.1086/516763.
- Devi, Lairellakpam Romabati. "Women in the Novels of Shashi Deshpande." *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, Sept. 2020, pp. 2967–73, ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT2009379.pdf.
- Dey, Arunima. "Violence Against Women During the Partition of India: Interpreting Women and their Bodies in the Context of Ethnic Genocide." *Revista De Filologia Inglesa*, vol. 37, Mar. 2016, pp. 103–18, dialnet.unirioja.es/descarga/articulo/5858222.pdf.
- Dharwadker, Vinay. "Some Contexts of Modern Indian Poetry." *Chicago Review*, vol. 38, no. 1/2, 1992, pp. 218–31. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.2307/25305599.

- Dharwadker, Vinay. "Translating the Millennium: Indian Literature in the Global Market." *Indian Literature*, vol. 52, no. 4 (246), 2008, pp. 133–46. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/23347959.
- Duflo, Esther. "Women Empowerment and Economic Development." *Journal of Economic Literature*, vol. 50, no. 4, 2012, pp. 1051–79. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/23644911.
- Dutta, Sangeeta. "Relinquishing the Halo: Portrayal of Mother in Indian Writing in English." *Economic and Political Weekly*, vol. 25, no. 42/43, 1990, pp. WS84–94. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/4396896.
- Ebert, Teresa L. "The 'Difference' of Postmodern Feminism." *College English*, vol. 53, no. 8, 1991, pp. 886–904. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.2307/377692.
- El-dali, Hosni Mostafa. "Towards an Understanding of the Distinctive Nature of Translation Studies." *Journal of King Saud University - Languages and Translation*, vol. 23, no. 1, Elsevier BV, Jan. 2011, pp. 29–45. *Crossref*, [doi:10.1016/j.jksult.2010.01.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksult.2010.01.001).
- Everett, Jana. "The Upsurge of Women's Activism in India." *Frontiers: A Journal of Women Studies*, vol. 7, no. 2, 1983, pp. 18–26. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.2307/3346281.
- Filipowicz, Halina. "'Am I That Name?' Feminism, Feminist Criticism, and Gender Studies." *The Polish Review*, vol. 59, no. 1, 2014, pp. 3–15. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.5406/polishreview.59.1.0003.
- Fox, Richard G. "Varna Schemes and Ideological Integration in Indian Society." *Comparative Studies in Society and History*, vol. 11, no. 1, 1969, pp. 27–45. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/178286.

- Furseth, Inger. "The Hijab: Boundary Work and Identity Negotiations Among Immigrant Muslim Women in the Los Angeles Area." *Review of Religious Research*, vol. 52, no. 4, 2011, pp. 365–85. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/23055567.
- Galtung, Johan. "Violence, Peace, and Peace Research." *Journal of Peace Research*, vol. 6, no. 3, 1969, pp. 167–91. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/422690.
- Gardiner, Judith Kegan. "On Female Identity and Writing by Women." *Critical Inquiry*, vol. 8, no. 2, 1981, pp. 347–61. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/1343167.
- Garg, Mridula. "Intervention of Women's Writing in Making of Literature." *Indian Literature*, vol. 57, no. 4 (276), 2013, pp. 181–90. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/43856809.
- . "Metaphors of Womanhood in Indian Literature." *Alternatives: Global, Local, Political*, vol. 16, no. 4, 1991, pp. 407–24. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/40644725.
- Gaurav, Kumar, et al. "Quest for Identity: A Study of Rupa Bajwa's *Tell Me a Story*." *Eur. Chem. Bull.*, vol. 12, no. 5, 2023, pp. 1473–77, doi:10.48047/ecb/2023.12.si5a.023.
- George, Miriam. "Religious Patriarchy and the Subjugation of Women in India." *The International Journal of Interdisciplinary Social Sciences*, vol. 3, no. 3, Common Ground Research Networks, 2008, pp. 21–30. *Crossref*, doi.org/10.18848/1833-1882/cgp/v03i03/52558.
- George, Sabu M., and Ranbir S. Dahiya. "Female Foeticide in Rural Haryana." *Economic and Political Weekly*, vol. 33, no. 32, 1998, pp. 2191–98. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/4407077.
- Ghassem-Fachandi, Parvis. "Introduction." *Pogrom in Gujarat: Hindu Nationalism and Anti-Muslim Violence in India*, Princeton University Press, 2012, pp. 1–30. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt7t0nz.4.

- Ghosh, Sutanuka. "Expressing the Self in Bengali Women's Autobiographies in the Twentieth Century." *South Asia Research*, vol. 30, no. 2, SAGE Publications, July 2010, pp. 105–23. *Crossref*, doi.org/10.1177/026272801003000201.
- Gita Wolf. "Construction of Gender Identity: Women in Popular Tamil Magazines." *Economic and Political Weekly*, vol. 26, no. 43, 1991, pp. WS71–73. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/4398216.
- Gogoi, Lakhpriya. "The 'Self' That Is Very 'Public': A Reading of Assamese Women's Autobiographical Narration." *Dibrugarh University Journal of English Studies*, 2018, pp. 1–13. www.academia.edu/49271216/The_Self_that_is_very_Public_A_Reading_of_Assamese_Womens_Autobiographical_Narration.
- Goyal, Ruchi. "Role of Literature in Advancing Women's Economic Empowerment." *Governance Reforms and Development in India, Rajasthan, India*. Inspira Research Association, 02-03 February, 2018, pp. 137-42. inspirajournals.com/uploads/Album/1704700446.pdf.
- Graulich, Melody. "Violence against Women in Literature of the Western Family." *Frontiers: A Journal of Women Studies*, vol. 7, no. 3, 1984, pp. 14–20. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.2307/3346235.
- Guha, Amalendu. "Little Nationalism Turned Chauvinist: Assam's Anti-Foreigner Upsurge, 1979-80." *Economic and Political Weekly*, vol. 15, no. 41/43, 1980, pp. 1699–720. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/4369155.
- Gupta, Charu. "Portrayal of Women in Premchand's Stories: A Critique." *Social Scientist*, vol. 19, no. 5/6, 1991, pp. 88–113. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.2307/3517875.
- Gupta, R. K. "Feminism and Modern Indian Literature." *Indian Literature*, vol. 36, no. 5 (157), 1993, pp. 179–89. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/23339720.

- . "Trends in Modern Indian Fiction." *World Literature Today*, vol. 68, no. 2, 1994, pp. 299–307. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.2307/40150154.
- Handique, Dipshikha. "Women's Social Position Reflected in Arupa Patangia Kalita's Short Stories." *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*, vol. 3, no. 10, Oct. 2020, pp. 43–45. [www.ijhssi.org/papers/vol9\(10\)/Ser-2/G0910024345.pdf](http://www.ijhssi.org/papers/vol9(10)/Ser-2/G0910024345.pdf).
- Hareesh, KG, and Sreenath Muraleedharan K. "Evolved Femininity: An Analysis on K R Meera's Novel *Aarachar*." *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 7C, May 2019, p. 197, www.ijitee.org/wp-content/uploads/papers/v8i7c/G10410587C19.pdf.
- Hari, M. G. "Negotiation of Identity in K R Meera's *Hangwoman*." *Rupkatha Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*, Vol. 9, No. 2, 2017, pp. 243-50, doi:10.21659/rupkatha.v9n2.25.
- Heflick, Nathan A., and Jamie L. Goldenberg. "Seeing Eye to Body: The Literal Objectification of Women." *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, vol. 23, no. 3, 2014, pp. 225–29. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/44318776.
- Heitmeyer, Carolyn. "Religion as Practice, Religion as Identity: Sufi Dargahs in Contemporary Gujarat." *South Asia: Journal of South Asian Studies*, vol. 34, no. 3, Informa UK Limited, Dec. 2011, pp. 485–503. *Crossref*, doi.org/10.1080/00856401.2011.620557.
- Hilliker, J. F. "Lord William Bentinck's Resolution of 1835 on Indian Education: A Rejected Draft." *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland*, no. 1, 1981, pp. 40–45. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/25211178.
- Himabindu, S., and R. Soujanya Kumar. "Women and Their Quest for Identity in Arupa Kalita Patangia's Short Stories." *Integrated Journal for Research in Arts and Humanities*, vol. 3, no. 1, Jan. 2023, pp. 62–70. *ResearchGate*, doi:10.55544/ijrah.3.1.12.

- Howell, Samantha. "The Evolution of Female Writers: An Exploration of Their Issues and Concerns from the 19th Century to Today." *University of Hawai'i at Hilo*, vol. 13, 2015, pp. 23-25, hilo.hawaii.edu/campuscenter/hohonu/volumes/volume13-2015.
- Irshad, Ayesha, et al. "Portrayal of Socially Subjugated Indian Women in Desai's 'The Domestic Maid.'" *European Journal of English Language and Literature Studies*, vol. 3, no. 5, Oct. 2018, pp. 13–18, ejournals.org/ejells/vol-3-issue-5september-2015/portrayal-of-socially-subjugated-indian-women-in-desais-the-domestic-maid/.
- Islam, Mohammad Shafiqul, and Rama Islam. "Representation of Postcolonial Indian Women: Bimla and Nanda Kaul in Anita Desai's Clear Light of Day and Fire on the Mountain." *South Asian Review*, vol. 40, no. 1–2, Apr. 2019, pp. 51–64. *Taylor & Francis Online*, doi:10.1080/02759527.2019.1593754.
- Israel, Hephzibah. "Translation in India: Multilingual Practices and Cultural Histories of Texts." *Translation Studies*, vol. 14, no. 2, May 2021, pp. 125–32. *Crossref*, doi:10.1080/14781700.2021.1936149.
- Jadhao, Manoj T. "Quest for Women Identity in *The Binding Vine* by Shashi Deshpande." *Research Journal of English Language and Literature*, vol. 9, no. 3, Sept. 2021, pp. 1–4, www.rjelal.com/9.3.21/1-4%20Dr.%20Manoj%20T.%20Jadhao.pdf.
- Jain, Gunjan. "Significance of Marriage as Social Institution in Indian English Writings." *Social Values & Society*, vol. 1, no. 1, 2019, pp. 17–22, doi:10.26480/svs.01.2019.17.22.
- Jain, Shruti. "The Rising Fourth Wave: Feminist Activism on Digital Platforms in India." *Observer Research Foundation*, no. 384, July 2020, pp. 1–16, www.orfonline.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/ORF_IssueBrief_384_Online_Feminism.pdf.

- James, Kate. "Cultural Implications for Translation." *Translation Journal*, 20 Apr. 2005, www3.uji.es/~aferna/H44/Cultural-implications.htm.
- Jayakumar, R., and T. Deivasigamani. "The Portrayal of Patriarchy and Gender Inequality in Sivakami's the Grip of Change and the Taming of Women." *Specialusis Ugdymas*, vol. 1, no. 43, 2022, pp. 6671–84. sumc.lt/index.php/se/article/download/934/730.
- Jha, Priti, and Niti Nagar. "A Study of Gender Inequality in India." *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, vol. 2, no. 3, June 2015, pp. 46–53, oaji.net/articles/2015/1170-1428777528.pdf.
- Jindal, Madhu. "Religious Influence on Indian Literature." *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, vol. 2, no. 8, Aug. 2015, pp. 251–57. www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR1701040.pdf.
- Jose, Reshma. "Noose Around the Noose Maker - a Study of Media-Cannibalism in K R Meera's *Hangwoman*." *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, vol. 6, no. 6, June 2019, p. 980-85. www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR1907284.pdf.
- K, Ajeesh A., and Dr. R. Pranesh Kumar. "Translation, Culture and the Loss of Meaning in K R Meera's *Aarachar*." *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 3, BEIESP, Sept. 2019, pp. 4070–75. [Crossref, doi:10.35940/ijrte.c5295.098319](https://doi.org/10.35940/ijrte.c5295.098319).
- K. G., Hareesh, and Sreenath Muraleedharan K. "Evolved Femininity: An Analysis on K R Meera's Novel *Aarachar*." *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 7C, May 2019, pp. 197–99. www.ijitee.org/wp-content/uploads/papers/v8i7c/G10410587C19.pdf.
- K. G., Rekha, and Manjula K.T. "Review of Literature: Women's Struggle for Domestic, Social, Political and Economic Space in K.R. Meera's Feminist Fictions." *International Journal of Law Management & Humanities*, vol. 5, no. 1, 2022, pp. 2199–211, [doi:10.1000/IJLMH.112751](https://doi.org/10.1000/IJLMH.112751).

- Kadu, Umesh. "Feminism as a Literary Movement in India English Literature." *Aayushi International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, vol. V, no. III, Mar. 2018, p. 113-18. www.aiirjournal.com/uploads/Articles/2018/03/2982_26.Umesh%20Vithalrao%20Kadu.pdf.
- Kapur, Kirti. "Role of Translation in the 21st Century." *Translation Today*, vol. 8, pp. 45–56, www.ntm.org.in/download/ttvol/Volume8/Articles/Article_2.pdf.
- Kashyap, Himakshi. "Giving Voice to the Subaltern Women: A Study of Arupa Patangiya Kalita's Felanee and Ayananta." *A Peer - Reviewed International Journal of English Language and Literature*, vol. 3, no. 1, May 2021, pp. 71–77, doi:10.5281/zenodo.52031.
- Kasirye, Faiswal. "The Portrayal of Muslim Women in Western Media. A Content Analysis of the New York Times and the Guardian." *SAGE Publications*, Mar. 2021. *Crossref*, doi.org/10.31124/advance.14156915.v1.
- Keerthika, S. "Literature and Society: How Literature Reflects Society." *International Journal of Science, Engineering and Management*, vol. 3, no. 4, Apr. 2018, pp. 471–72, www.technoarete.org/common_abstract/pdf/0/v5/i4/Ext_82439.pdf.
- Keshavamurthy, Kiran. "P. Sivakami: The Caste and Gendered Body." *Journal of the Department of English, Vidyasagar University*, vol. 11, 2014, pp. 121–38. inet.vidyasagar.ac.in:8080/jspui/bitstream/123456789/2045/1/13.pdf.
- Khair, Tabish. "Caste in Indian English Fiction: More Oppression?" *Kunapipi*, vol. 19, no. 1, 1997, pp. 78–84, core.ac.uk/download/pdf/224958439.pdf.
- Kirkpatrick, Joanna. "Women in Indian-English Literature: The Question of Individuation." *Journal of South Asian Literature*, vol. 12, no. 3/4, 1977, pp. 121–29. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/40872162.

- Kishore, S. Henry. "The Evolution of Indian Women Psyche: A Chronological Study of Women and Woman Writers in India." *ResearchGate*, Dec. 2017, www.researchgate.net/publication/327366126_The_Evolution_of_Indian_Women_Psyche_A_Chronological_Study_of_Women_and_Woman_Writers_in_India.
- Klingorova, Kamila, and Tomas Havlicek. "Religion and Gender Inequality: The Status of Women in the Societies of World Religions." *Moravian Geographical Reports*, vol. 2, no. 23, June 2015, pp. 2–11, *ResearchGate*, www.researchgate.net/publication/279526649_Religion_and_gender_inequality_The_status_of_women_in_the_societies_of_world_religions.
- Köksal, Onur, and Nurcihan Yürük. "The Role of Translator in Intercultural Communication." *International Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*, vol. 12, no. 1, 2020, pp. 327–38, files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1249472.pdf.
- Krishnaveni, KP. "The Indian Women Writers and Their Contributions to Indian Literature." *Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science*, vol. 9, no. 4, 2021, pp. 56–57, www.questjournals.org/jrhss/papers/vol9-issue4/I09045657.pdf.
- Kumar, Athira S., and V. Jaisre. "Social Endurance of Women in P. Sivakami's Novels *The Grip of Change* and *The Taming of Women*." *The Journal of Social Sciences Studies and Research*, vol. 3, no. 02, Apr. 2023, pp. 103–05. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7807506.
- Kuniyath, Jayasree K., and K. C. Sankaranarayanan. "Divine Gender Inequality: A Study of Mythological Degradation of Hindu Women in India." *Social Science Research Network*, RELX Group (Netherlands), 1 Jan. 2017, doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2949781.
- Kuttikat, Miriam. "Religious Patriarchy and the Subjugation of Women in India." *The International Journal of Interdisciplinary Social Sciences*, vol. 3, no. 3, Sept. 2008, pp. 21–30, doi:10.18848/1833-1882/CGP/v03i03/52558.

- Mandal, Nipa. "Understanding the Immigration History of Assam Through Contemporary Assamese Literature (1947-2016)." *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress*, vol. 78, 2017, pp. 734–46. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/26906147.
- Mani, Preetha. "Feminine Desire Is Human Desire: Women Writing Feminism in Postindependence India." *Comparative Studies of South Asia, Africa and the Middle East*, vol. 36, no. 1, May 2016, pp. 21–41. muse.jhu.edu/pub/4/article/615049/pdf.
- Margaret, Racheti Anne. "The Indian Women Writers and Their Contribution in the World Literature- a Critical Study." *International Journal on Studies in English Language and Literature*, vol. 4, no. 10, Oct. 2016, pp. 32–36, doi:10.20431/2347-3134.0410006.
- Marwaha, Amol Rattan. "The Issues of Racial and Gender Inequality in Modern Literature." *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, vol. 5, no. 10, Oct. 2018, p. 527, www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR1810978.pdf.
- McCabe, Helen, and Lauren Eglén. "'I Bought You. You Are My Wife': 'Modern Slavery' and Forced Marriage." *Journal of Human Trafficking*, July 2022, pp. 1–25. *Taylor & Francis Group*, doi:10.1080/23322705.2022.2096366.
- Medhi, Hemjyoti. "Gender and Identity Politics: Arupa Patangia Kalita's *Felanee* (the *Story of Felanee*) and Rita Chowdhury's *Ei Samay Sei Samay* (Times Now and Then)." *Asiatic*, vol. 10, no. 1, June 2016, pp. 43–53. *Academia.edu*, [www.academia.edu/65933720/Gender and Identity Politics Arupa Patangia Kalitas Felanee The Story of Felanee and Rita Chowdhurys Ei Samay Sei Samay Times Now and Then](http://www.academia.edu/65933720/Gender_and_Identity_Politics_Arupa_Patangia_Kalitas_Felanee_The_Story_of_Felanee_and_Rita_Chowdhurys_Ei_Samay_Sei_Samay_Times_Now_and_Then) .
- Mini, K. "Influence of Media in *Hangwoman*." *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, vol. 9, no. 5, May 2021, p. g299-303, ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT2105695.pdf.

- Mishra, Deepanjali. "Pleasure: Redefined by Women in Shobha De's Novels." *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, vol. 3, no. 4, Dec. 2012, pp. 15–20, www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-jhss/papers/Vol3-issue5/C0351520.pdf.
- Misra, Jugal Kishore. "Empowerment of Women in India." *The Indian Journal of Political Science*, vol. 67, no. 4, 2006, pp. 867–78. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/41856270.
- Misra, Tilottoma. "Indira Goswami: Brave, Gentle and Bold." *Economic and Political Weekly*, vol. 46, no. 53, 2011, pp. 29–31. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/23065632.
- . "Literary Cultures in North East India: Shrinking Frontiers." *Economic and Political Weekly*, vol. 51, no. 38, 2016, pp. 46–54. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/44003738.
- Mitra, Mayurakshi. "Insidious Interlocking of Gender and Caste: Consequences of Challenging Endogamy." *Journal of International Women's Studies*, vol. 22, no. 10, Oct. 2021, pp. 44–56, vc.bridgew.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2674&context=jiws.
- Mohammed, Bahman Jabar. "Image of Islam in Postcolonial Novels: E. M. Forster's a Passage to India and Khaled Hosseini's the Kite Runner." *Journal of Raparin University*, vol. 4, no. 13, Dec. 2017, pp. 49–58. ojournal.uor.edu.krd/No_13/English/77.pdf.
- Mohi-ud-din, Shafiq. "Sexual Harassment of Women in India at Workplaces: Strategies for Preventing It." *Journal of the Punjab University Historical Society*, vol. 32, no. 1, June 2019, pp. 179–87. *Research Gate*, www.researchgate.net/publication/338236003_Sexual_harassment_of_women_in_India_at_workplaces_Strategies_for_preventing_it.

- Molaei, Hamideh, and Sahar Hussain Babaei. "Portrayal of Muslims in Bollywood: Case-Study of the Tanhaji Movie." *Journal of World Sociopolitical Studies*, vol. 4, no. 2, 2020, pp. 379–400. doi.org/10.22059/WSPS.2021.314905.1185.
- Moore, Henrietta. "'Divided We Stand': Sex, Gender and Sexual Difference." *Feminist Review*, no. 47, 1994, pp. 78–95. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.2307/1395255.
- Mourya, Kamalesh Kumar. "The Image of Woman in Hindi Fiction: An Outline of Krishna Sobti's Select Novels in Translation." *The Creative Launcher*, vol. 5, no. 6, Perception Publishing, Feb. 2021, pp. 101–10. *Crossref*, doi.org/10.53032/tcl.2021.5.6.14.
- Muehlenhard, Charlene L., et al. "Gender and Sexuality: An Introduction to the Special Issue." *The Journal of Sex Research*, vol. 40, no. 1, 2003, pp. 1–3. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/3813765.
- N. M., Naseera, and Moly Kuruvilla. "The Sexual Politics of the Manusmriti: A Critical Analysis With Sexual and Reproductive Health Rights Perspectives." *Journal of International Women's Studies*, vol. 23, no. 6, May 2022, pp. 21–36. vc.bridgew.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2845&context=jiws.
- Nair, Deepa, and N. Nila. "Docile Bodies and Dividing Practices in P. Sivakami's *The Taming of Women* and Nawalel Saadawi's *Woman at Point Zero*." *Our Heritage*, vol. 68, no. 1, Jan. 2020, pp. 854–63. *Research Gate*, www.researchgate.net/publication/339997822_Docile_Bodies_and_Dividing_Practices_in_P_Sivakami's_The_Taming_of_Women_and_Nawal_El_Saadawi's_Woman_at_Point_Zero.
- Nath, Rimi. "The Question of the 'Foreigners' in Select Fictional Narratives From Assam." *Rupkatha Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*, vol. 14, no. 2, Aesthetics Media Services, June 2022. *Crossref*, [doi:10.21659/rupkatha.v14n2.ne25](https://doi.org/10.21659/rupkatha.v14n2.ne25).

- Navya, V. K. "Caste, Gender and Resistance: A Critical Study of Bama's Sangathi." *Socrates*, vol. 2, no. 1, Mar. 2014, pp. 20–27, core.ac.uk/download/pdf/287781677.pdf.
- Nongbri, Iameai Hepsa. "Women in Brahmanical Literature: Some Aspects." *The NEHU Journal*, vol. XVI, no. 1, June 2018, pp. 79–97. nehu.ac.in/public/downloads/Journals/Jan-June-2018/The-Nehu-Journal-Jan-June-2018-85-103.pdf.
- Nyori, Karngam, and Bompi Riba. "Homelessness in Arupa Patangia Kalita's Felanee." *Literary Herald*, vol. 7, no. 4, Dec. 2021, pp. 135–39, tlhjournal.com/uploads/products/17.karngam-and-bompi-article.pdf.
- Ojha, Purnima. "Women's Issues in India: Role and Importance of Media." *The Indian Journal of Political Science*, vol. 72, no. 1, 2011, pp. 87–102. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/42761809.
- Pande, Rekha. "The History of Feminism and Doing Gender in India." *Estudos Feministas*, vol. 26, no. 3, 2018, pp. 1–17. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/26538500.
- Pandey, Nistha. "Reading K.R. Meera's *Hangwoman* as a Critique of Biopolitical Control." *Journal of Comparative Literature and Aesthetics*, vol. 43, no. 3, 2020, p. 54, jcla.in/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/JCLA-43.3_Autumn-2020_Nishtha-Pandey.pdf.
- Pandey, Shyam Prakash. "Changing Dimensions of Institutions of Marriage in India: A Socio-Legal Evaluation." *International Journal of Law Management and Humanities*, vol. 4, no. 2, 2021, pp. 58–72, www.ijlmh.com/paper/changing-dimensions-of-institutions-of-marriage-in-india-a-socio-legal-evaluation.
- Parveen, Ghazala. "MUSLIM WOMEN IN INDIA: PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS." *The Indian Journal of Political Science*, vol. 75, no. 2, 2014, pp. 305–14. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/24701138.

- Patoari, Manjur Hossain. "The Rights of Women in Islam and Some Misconceptions: An Analysis From Bangladesh Perspective." *Beijing Law Review*, vol. 10, no. 05, Scientific Research Publishing, Inc., 2019, pp. 1211–24. *Crossref*, doi.org/10.4236/blr.2019.105065.
- Piela, Anna. "Muslim Women and the Politics of the Headscarf." *JSTOR Daily*, 7 Apr. 2022, daily.jstor.org/muslim-women-and-the-politics-of-the-headscarf.
- Prasaja, V. P. "Traversing the Feminine: A Postmodern Feminist Reading of *Hangwoman*." *Literary Endeavour*, vol. X, no. 2, Apr. 2019, p. 143, <https://www.literaryendeavour.org/files/xorjrst2ld49lpxqfdk/2019-04%2032.%20Traversing%20the%20F%20minine%20A%20Postmodern%20Feminist%20Reading%20of%20Hangwoman%20-%20%20Prasaja%20V.%20P..pdf>.
- Punia, B. K. "Emerging Gender Diversity and Male Stereotypes: The Changing Indian Business Scenario." *Indian Journal of Industrial Relations*, vol. 41, no. 2, 2005, pp. 188–205. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/27768007.
- Pushpalatha, U. "Consciousness of 'Self' in Gita Hariharan's *The Thousand Faces of Night* and Rajam Krishnan's *Lamps in the Whirlpool*." *Journal of the Gujarat Research Society*, vol. 21, no. 11, Nov. 2019, pp. 444–47. *ResearchGate* www.researchgate.net/publication/338423117 Consciousness of Self in Gita Hariharans The Thousand Faces of Night and Rajam Krishnans Lamps in the Whirlpool.
- Qun-xing, Zhang. "Translator's Voice in Translated Texts." *Journal of Literature and Art Studies*, vol. 6, no. 2, Feb. 2016, pp. 178–85. *Crossref*, doi:10.17265/2159-5836/2016.02.007.
- Rahmath, Ayshath Shamah, et al. "Archetypal Motherhood and the National Agenda: The Case of the Indian Muslim Women." *Space and Culture, India*, vol. 7, no. 4, ACCB Publishing, Mar. 2020, pp. 12–31. *Crossref*, doi.org/10.20896/saci.v7i4.590.

- Raj, Aditya, and Pooja. "Women in Dalit Literature: Voice, Agency and Subjectivity." *Journal of Exclusion Studies*, vol. 2, no. 1, Feb. 2012, pp. 55–62. *Indianjournals.com*, doi:10.5958/j.2231-4547.2.1.007.
- Raj, Yash, et al. "Raising the Voice against the Atrocities: A Critical Study of P Sivakami's *Taming of Women*." *Journal of Critical Reviews*, vol 7, no 4, 2020, pp. 654-55, www.jcreview.com/admin/Uploads/Files/61a92e4e236a00.72271300.pdf.
- Rajan, Kalyanee. "Chronicles of Sepia-Toned Love." *Indian Literature*, vol. 62, no. 6 (308), 2018, pp. 205–09. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/26792337.
- Rajeshwari, S. "Identity Crisis: A Search of Self." *Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science*, vol. 7, no. 1, 2019, pp. 59–62, www.questjournals.org/jrhss/papers/vol7-issue1/Ser%20-2/J0701025962.pdf.
- Ramesh H. Patil. "Social Status of Indian Women of Different Periods in the Patriarchal Society." *Research Ambition: An International Multidisciplinary e-Journal*, vol. 5, no. IV, Welfare Universe, Aug. 2021, pp. 23–31. *Crossref*, doi.org/10.53724/ambition/v5n4.06.
- Rana, Jyoti Rajlaxmi. "A Study of Female Characters in Selected Novels of Krishna Sobti: A Feminist Approach." *Social Science Research Network*, RELX Group (Netherlands), 1 Jan. 2012, doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2393850.
- Rao, Nitya. "Marriage, Violence, and Choice: Understanding Dalit Women's Agency in Rural Tamil Nadu." *Gender and Society*, vol. 29, no. 3, 2015, pp. 410–33. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/43669978.
- Ray, Bharati. "Women of Bengal: Transformation in Ideas and Ideals, 1900-1947." *Social Scientist*, vol. 19, no. 5/6, 1991, pp. 3–23. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.2307/3517870.

- Ray, Lila. "Role of Translation: The Translator: His Triple Role." *Indian Literature*, vol. 35, no. 3 (149), 1992, pp. 121–26. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/23338007.
- Rege, Sharmila. "Feminist Pedagogy and Sociology for Emancipation in India." *Sociological Bulletin*, vol. 44, no. 2, 1995, pp. 223–39. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/23619651.
- Rendall, Steven. "The Translator's Task, Walter Benjamin (Translation)." *TTR: Traduction, Terminologie, Redaction*, vol. 10, no. 2, Consortium Erudit, 1997, pp. 151–65. *Crossref*, doi:10.7202/037302ar.
- Riquelme, John Paul. "Oscar Wilde's Aesthetic Gothic: Walter Pater, Dark Enlightenment, and *The Picture of Dorian Gray*." *Project MUSE*, vol. 46, no. 3, Johns Hopkins University Press, 1 Sept. 2000, pp. 609 – 631 doi: 10.1353/mfs.2000.0056.
- Rowland-Serdar, Barbara, and Peregrine Schwartz-Shea. "Empowering Women: Self, Autonomy, and Responsibility." *The Western Political Quarterly*, vol. 44, no. 3, 1991, pp. 605–24. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.2307/448671.
- Sangeetha, V., and V. Peruvalluthi. "Women Marginality in P. Sivakami's *The Grip of Change*." *Shanlax International Journal of English*, vol. 6, no. 2, Mar. 2018, pp. 144–47. www.shanlaxjournals.in/wp-content/uploads/women_marginality_in_pshivakamis_the_grip_of_change.pdf.
- Sankararaman, R. Saradha. "Indian Women Novelists and Feminism." *Shanlax International Journal of English*, vol. 4, no. 1, Dec. 2015, pp. 29–38, www.shanlaxjournals.in/pdf/ENG/V4N1/ENG_V4_N1_005.pdf.
- Sarma, Ranjan Jyoti. "The Anuloma and Pratiloma Marriage: A Socio-Legal Study." *Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science*, vol. 10, no. 3, 2022, pp. 1–9. *Quest Journals*, www.questjournals.org/jrhss/papers/vol10-issue3/Ser-3/A10030109.pdf.

- Sarmah, Alka. "POLITICAL EMPOWERMENT OF WOMEN: A Case Study of Bodo Women of Assam." *The Indian Journal of Political Science*, vol. 71, no. 3, 2010, pp. 881–90. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/42748417.
- Satheesh, Seema, and M. Nagalakshmi. "Breaking the Fetters - Resonating Feminine Voices in Bama's and Sivakami's Select Novels." *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry*, vol. 12, no. 7, July 2021, p. 3493. bit.ly/47OZD1x. Accessed 17 Nov. 2023.
- Saul, Jennifer M. "On Treating Things as People: Objectification, Pornography, and the History of the Vibrator." *Hypatia*, vol. 21, no. 2, 2006, pp. 45–61. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/3810991.
- Saxena, Kiran. "Empowerment of Women: The Indian Context." *The Indian Journal of Political Science*, vol. 55, no. 4, 1994, pp. 391–400. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/41855710.
- Saxena, Rupali. "Quest for Identity in the Novel of Shashi Deshpande: With Special Reference to 'Roots and Shadows.'" *Aryavart shodh Vikas Patrika*, vol. 12, no. XII, 2018, pp. 19–21, www.aryavartsvs.org.in/uploaded_book/4%20%20Rupali%20Saxena.pdf.
- Scharf, Betty R. "Sexual Stratification and Social Stratification." *The British Journal of Sociology*, vol. 28, no. 4, 1977, pp. 450–66. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.2307/589421.
- Seguino, Stephanie. "Help or Hindrance? Religion's Impact on Gender Inequality in Attitudes and Outcomes." *World Development*, vol. 39, no. 8, 2011, pp. 1308–21, doi:10.1016/j.worlddev.2010.12.004.
- Selvi, S. T. Tamizh. "Role of Class, Caste, Race and Gender in Literature." *Notions*, vol. 6, no. 1, 2015, pp. 32–40, anubooks.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Not-Vol-6-No.-1-15-6.pdf.

- Sen, Shoma. "The Village and the City: Dalit Feminism in the Autobiographies of Baby Kamble and Urmila Pawar." *The Journal of Commonwealth Literature*, vol. 54, no. 1, SAGE Publications, July 2017, pp. 38–51. *Crossref*, doi.org/10.1177/0021989417720251.
- Sengupta, Ashis. "Anita Desai's 'Voices in the City': Reconstructing Indian Female Identity." *Indian Literature*, vol. 48, no. 6 (224), 2004, pp. 181–93. *JSTOR*, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23345870>.
- Shah, Svati P. "Gujarat Riots and the Role of Sexual Violence." *Economic and Political Weekly*, vol. 52, no. 52, 2017, pp. 33–35. *JSTOR*, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/26699159>.
- Shahane, Vasant A. "Translation as Art." *Indian Literature*, vol. 26, no. 4, 1983, pp. 5–19. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/23331474.
- Shanmathi, S. "Ceaseless Sadism against Women in P. Sivakami's *The Taming of Women*." *Language in India*, vol. 17, no. 12, Dec 2017, pp. 321–25, www.languageinindia.com/dec2017/shanmathitamingwomenfinal.pdf.
- Sharma, Anuradha. "Women in the Short Stories of Mannu Bhandari: Inner Desires Versus Social Expectations." *IJELR*, vol. 3, no. 4, Dec. 2016, pp. 573–76. www.ijelr.in/3.4.b.16/573-576%20ANURADHA%20SHARMA.pdf.
- Sharma, Bhushan. "Narratives of Dalit Women and 'the Outsider Within': Toward a Literary Practice of Dalit Feminist Standpoint." *Journal of International Women's Studies*, vol. 22, no. 4, April 2021, pp. 25–40, vc.bridgew.edu/jiws/vol22/iss4/3.
- Sharma, Kanhaya L. "Is There Today Caste System or There Is Only Caste in India?" *Polish Sociological Review*, no. 178, 2012, pp. 245–63. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/41969443.

- Sharma, Minakshi. "Exploring Women's Identity Through Chitra Banerjee's Novels." *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, vol. 9, no. 5, May 2022, pp. i383–97, www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2205C56.pdf.
- Sharma, Shikha. "Feminism in Indian English Literature: A Case Study of Contemporary Women Novelists." *Journal of Advances and Scholarly Researches in Allied Education*, vol. 16, no. 4, Mar. 2019, pp. 740–47, doi:10.29070/JASRAE.
- Sharma, Shiva Prasad. "Violence, Memories, Space and the Eternal Urge to Survive: An Analysis of Arupa Patangia Kalita's *Felanee* (2003) and *Written in Tears* (2015)." *Palarch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, vol. 17, no. 7, 2020, pp. 11018-11029, archives.palarch.nl/index.php/jae/article/view/4425/4322.
- Sharma, Vishwa Bandhu. "A Study of Gender Issues in Indian Writing in English." *Globus*, vol. 7, no. 1, Dec. 2015, pp. 30–31, globusjournal.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/714Vishwa.pdf.
- Shivakumar, I., and K. Manimakalai. "Masculinity and Challenges for Women in Indian Culture." *Journal of International Women's Studies*, vol. 22, no. 5, June 2022, pp. 427–36, www.researchgate.net/publication/352261370_Masculinity_and_Challenges_for_Women_in_Indian_Culture.
- Showalter, Elaine. "Feminist Criticism in the Wilderness." *Critical Inquiry*, vol. 8, no. 2, 1981, pp. 179–205. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/1343159.
- Singh, Aradhana, and Kuhu Dutta Gupta. "Gender Discrimination in The Novels of Ruth Praver Jhabvala." *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, vol. 10, no. 7, July 2022, pp. c759–63, ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT2207361.pdf.
- Singh, Khushboo. "Importance of Education in Empowerment of Women in India." *Motherhood International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research & Development*, vol. 1, no. 1, Aug. 2016, pp. 39–48, www.motherhooduniversity.edu.in/pdf/Publications/2016/Khushboo%20Singh.pdf.

- Singh, Sima. "Portrayal of Women in Literature – Through the Ages." *International Journal of Engineering Development and Research*, vol. 7, no. 4, 2019, pp. 39–41, www.ijedr.org/papers/IJEDR1904009.pdf.
- Singha, Tanmoy. "The Voice of the Voiceless: A Study of Sivakami's the Taming of Women." *An International Refereed/Peer-reviewed English e-Journal*, vol. 4, no. 2, Aug. 2018, pp. 52–59. tlhjournal.com/uploads/products/9.tanmoy-sigha-article.pdf.
- Sinsinwar, Jaya, and Mukti Upadhyay. "A Study of Representation of Caste and Feminism Issues by Indian Writers." *Journal of Advances and Scholarly Researches in Allied Education*, vol. 16, no. 1, Jan. 2019, pp. 211–15, ignited.in/p/58531.
- Sivakumar, I., and K. Manimekalai. "Masculinity and Challenges for Women in Indian Culture." *Journal of International Women's Studies*, vol. 22, no. 5, June 2021, pp. 427–36, vc.bridgew.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2461&context=jiws.
- Smith, Jane I. "Women in Islam: Equity, Equality, and the Search for the Natural Order." *Journal of the American Academy of Religion*, vol. 47, no. 4, 1979, pp. 517–37. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/1462273.
- Singh, Ravindra Kumar. "Caste Issue in Literature and Regional Literature." *Stallion Journal for Multidisciplinary Associated Research Studies*, vol. 2, no. 4, Stallion Publication, Aug. 2023, pp. 8–13. *Crossref*, doi:10.55544/sjmars.2.4.2.
- Singh, Sima. "Portrayal of Women in Literature – Through the Ages." *International Journal of Engineering Development and Research*, vol. 7, no. 4, 2019, pp. 39–41, www.ijedr.org/papers/IJEDR1904009.pdf. Accessed 7 Feb. 2023.
- Somkuwar, Pratibha. "Unjustified Justice in the Grip of Change." *International Journal on Studies in English Language and Literature*, vol. 2, no. 11, 2014, pp. 19–22, www.arcjournals.org/pdfs/ijsell/v2-i11/2.pdf.

- Sorensen, Annemette. "Women, Family and Class." *Annual Review of Sociology*, vol. 20, 1994, pp. 27–47. JSTOR, www.jstor.org/stable/2083358.
- Srinivasan, Padma, and Gary R. Lee. "The Dowry System in Northern India: Women's Attitudes and Social Change." *Journal of Marriage and Family*, vol. 66, no. 5, 2004, pp. 1108–17. JSTOR, www.jstor.org/stable/3600328.
- Srivastava, Sumit S. "Violence and Dalit Women's Resistance in Rural Bihar." *Indian Anthropologist*, vol. 37, no. 2, 2007, pp. 31–44. JSTOR, www.jstor.org/stable/41920038.
- Stepaniants, M. T. "The Image of Woman in Religious Consciousness: Past, Present, and Future." *Philosophy East and West*, vol. 42, no. 2, 1992, pp. 239–47. JSTOR, doi.org/10.2307/1399288.
- Subashini, C., and P. R. Princelin. "Women on Double Marginalization in Sivakami's the Grip of Change." *Online International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, vol. 8, May 2018, pp. 107–10. www.oijrj.org/oijrj/apr-may2018-special-issue/22.pdf.
- Sudradjat, Iwan. "Foucault, the Other Spaces, and Human Behaviour." *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 36, Elsevier BV, 2012, pp. 28–34. Crossref, [doi:10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.03.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.03.004).
- Sultana, Abeda. "Patriarchy and Women's Subordination: A Theoretical Analysis." *The Arts Faculty Journal*, June 2011, pp. 1–18, www.banglajol.info/index.php/AFJ/article/view/12929/9293.
- Sumra, Azhar ul Hassan. "Muslims and Islam in Indian English Press: Exploring the Islamophobic Discourse." *Islamophobia Studies Journal*, vol. 5, no. 2, 2020, pp. 226–37. JSTOR, www.jstor.org/stable/10.13169/islastudj.5.2.0226.
- Supriya, Y. "Sivakami's The Grip of Change: Revisited." *Journal of English Language and Literature*, vol. 4, no. 1, 2017, pp. 69–73, joell.in/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/69-73-SIVAKAMI%e2%80%99S-THE-GRIP-OF-CHANGE.pdf.

- Suryavanshi, Manjusha D. "The Quest of Identity in Rama Mehta's *Inside the Haveli*." *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, vol. 6, no. 1, Jan. 2019, pp. 303–04, www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR1901640.pdf.
- Tamilarasi, C. "Status of Women in Tamil Nadu Through the Ages." *International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management*, vol. 2, no. 6, Sept. 2020, pp. 407–09. ijaem.net/issue_dcp/Status%20of%20Women%20in%20Tamil%20Nadu%20through%20the%20Ages.pdf.
- Tamuly, Jayanta Madhab. "The Insane Women- a 'Trauma' Reading of *Felanee*." *Drishti: The Sight*, vol. IX, no. II, April 2021, pp. 66-70, www.drishtithesight.com/assets/resources/2021/01/drishti-vol-9-issue-2.pdf.
- Tharakan, Sophie M., and Michael Tharakan. "Status of Women in India: A Historical Perspective." *Social Scientist*, vol. 4, no. 4/5, 1975, pp. 115–23. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.2307/3516124.
- Thapan, Meenakshi. "Gender, Body and Everyday Life." *Social Scientist*, vol. 23, no. 7/9, 1995, pp. 32–58. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.2307/3517859.
- Thurber, S. "English Literature in Girls' Education." *The School Review*, vol. 2, no. 6, 1894, pp. 321–36. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/1074029.
- Toomey, Derek. "Linking Class and Gender Inequality: The Family and Schooling." *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, vol. 10, no. 4, 1989, pp. 389–402. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/1392985.
- Tripathi, Manoj Kumar. "Recent Ethnic Conflict in Assam: Implications to India's National Security." *The Indian Journal of Political Science*, vol. 75, no. 3, 2014, pp. 521–30. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/26575526.
- Uchem, Rose N., and Emmanuel S. Ngwa. "Subordination of Women in 21stcentury Africa: Cultural Sustainability or a New Slavery? Implications for Educational Development." *Developing Country Studies*, vol. 4, no. 24, 2014, pp. 143–50, core.ac.uk/download/pdf/234682096.pdf.

- Upadhyaya, K. D. "On the Position of Women in Indian Folk Culture." *Asian Folklore Studies*, vol. 27, no. 1, 1968, pp. 81–100. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.2307/1177801.
- Valiyamattam, Rositta Joseph. "Translating Indian Literatures Into English: Theory and Praxis." *The Quest -A Peer-Reviewed International Literary Journal*, vol. 28, no. 1, June 2014, pp. 10–32, www.researchgate.net/publication/308200658
Translating Indian Literatures into English Theory and Praxis.
- Verstappen, Sanderien. "Communal Living." *Contributions to Indian Sociology*, vol. 52, no. 1, SAGE Publications, Dec. 2017, pp. 53–78. *Crossref*, doi.org/10.1177/0069966717743383.
- Visaria, Leela. "Violence against Women in India: Is Empowerment a Protective Factor?" *Economic and Political Weekly*, vol. 43, no. 48, 2008, pp. 60–66. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/40278238.
- Vishwakarma, Aarti. "Depiction of Plight and Subjugation of Dalit Women in Baby Kamble's Prisons We Broke." *The Creative Launcher*, vol. 7, no. 3, Perception Publishing, June 2022, pp. 109–16. *Crossref*, doi.org/10.53032/tcl.2022.7.3.13.
- Wagh, Ganesh Chintaman. "Issues of Identity and Selfhood in the Novels of Bharati Mukherjee, Asha Bage and Usha Priyamvada: A Comparative Study." *Think India Journal*, vol. 22, no. 14, Dec. 2019, pp. 2602–10, thinkindiaquarterly.org/index.php/think-india/article/download/12858/8127.
- West, B. June. "The 'New Woman.'" *Twentieth Century Literature*, vol. 1, no. 2, 1955, pp. 55–68. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.2307/440970.
- Woodcock, John. "The Literary View of Politics." *College English*, vol. 40, no. 7, 1979, pp. 772–80. *JSTOR*, doi.org/10.2307/376300.

Yadav, Jyoti. "Charles Wood's Despatch 1854: A Re-Analysis." *A Refereed Research Journal and a Complete Periodical Dedicated to Humanities & Social Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 1, Jan. 2015, pp. 81–85. *Shodh.net*, www.shodh.net/phocadownload/vol-6-issue-1/Vol_6_Issue_1_Dr._Jyoti_Yadav.pdf.

Yadav, Manoj Kumar. "Role of Mother Tongue in Second Language Learning." *International Journal of Research (IJR)*, vol. 1, no. 11, Dec. 2014, pp. 572–82. *Research Gate*, www.researchgate.net/publication/283355564_Role_of_Mother_Tongue_in_Second_Language_Learning.

Zala, Jaysinh B. "Literature and Society." *International Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Sciences*, vol. 1, no. 5, July 2013, pp. 26–31. www.raijmr.com/ijrhs/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/IJRHS_2013_vol01_issue_05_05.pdf.

c) PhD Thesis

Brandeberry, Sarah Michelle. *Educating Women: Women Writers, the Domestic Novel and the Education Debate, 1790-1820*. 2015. Florida State University Libraries, PhD thesis. *Diginole.lib*, diginole.lib.fsu.edu/islandora/object/fsu:252926/datastream/PDF/view.

Chandrani, Yogesh. *Legacies of Colonial History: Region, Religion and Violence in Postcolonial Gujarat*. 2013. Columbia U, PhD thesis. *Academic Commons*, academiccommons.columbia.edu/doi/10.7916/D8D799T2

Chauhan, Nipam. *A Comparative Study of the Socio-Cultural Influences on Literature in the Selected Novels of Some Afro-American and Gujarati Female Novelists With Special Reference to Alice Walker Toni Morrison Kundanika Kapadia and Ila Arab Mehta*. 2015. Pacific University, PhD Thesis. *Shodhganga@INFLIBNET*, shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/340171/8/08_chapter%205.pdf.

Deepsikha, Saharia. *Gender Violence and the Word a Reading of the Cultural Dynamics in Arupa Pathangia Kalita's Fiction*. 2018. Gauhati University, PhD Thesis. *Shodhganga@INFLIBNET*, shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/249381/2/11-chapter-5.pdf.

Kasoob, Hassan S. *Cultural Translation Problems with Special Reference to English/Arabic Advertisements*. 1995. Glasgow University, PhD Thesis. *CORE*, core.ac.uk/download/pdf/281487.pdf.

Khera, Savi. *Narratives of Conflict Trauma and Recuperation a Study of Selected Works of Syed Abdul Malik and Arupa Kalita Pathangia*. 2021. Maharshi Dayanand University, PhD Thesis. *Shodhganga@INFLIBNET*, hdl.handle.net/10603/381156.

Purohit, Vibha. *Geetanjali Shree Ke Katha Sahitya Ka Vivechanatmak Adhyayan*. 2019. Mohan Lal Sukhadia University, PhD Thesis. *Shodhganga@INFLIBNET*, shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/303489/10/14.%20upsanhar.pdf.

Ramrao, Kamble Balika. *Geetanjali Shri Ke Kathasahitya Ka Anushilan*. 2020. Swami Ramanand Teerth Marathwada University, PhD Thesis. *Shodhganga@INFLIBNET*, shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/308662/12/12_conclusions.pdf.

d) Web Pages

“Koch People.” *Wikipedia*, 18 Sept. 2023, en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Koch_people. Accessed 28 Sept. 2023.

“Rajasthan: Father Sells 7-year-old Daughter for Rs 4.50 Lakh in Dholpur.” *The Times of India*, 24 May 2023, timesofindia.indiatimes.com/videos/news/rajasthan-father-sells-7-year-old-daughter-for-rs-4-50-lakh-in-dholpur/videoshow/100460586.cms. Accessed 17 Oct. 2023.

- “Regional Indian Literature.” *IndiaNetzone.com*, www.indianetzone.com/2/regional_indian_literature.htm. Accessed 28 Aug. 2023.
- “Ila Arab Mehta.” *Wikipedia*, 23 Dec. 2016, en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ila_Arab_Mehta. Accessed 11 Jan. 2022.
- “Women Movement in India.” *Unacademy*, unacademy.com/content/upsc/study-material/post-independence-india/women-movement-in-india. Accessed 14 Jan. 2023.
- Anjum, Zafar. "Review: *Hangwoman* by K R Meera." *Kitaab.org*, 14 September 2014, <https://kitaab.org/2014/09/14/review-hangwoman-by-k-r-meera/>. Accessed 14 April 2019.
- Anthony, Shinie. “Cornered Women.” *Deccan Herald*, 6 Oct. 2012, www.deccanherald.com/content/283408/cornered-women.html. Accessed 14 Jan. 2023.
- Armstrong, Aurelia. “Michel Foucault: Feminism.” *Internet Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, iep.utm.edu/foucfem. Accessed 11 Feb. 2023.
- Badawi, Jamal A. “The Status of Woman in Islam.” *IJUM*, www.ijum.edu.my/deed/articles/statusofwomen.html. Accessed 4 Nov. 2023.
- Baruah, Manjeet. “Translation and the Politics of Language.” *Block-2 Translation Problems and Possibilities*, IGNOU, 2017, pp. 75-87, <https://egyankosh.ac.in/bitstream/123456789/38995/1/Unit-3.pdf>. Course Pack.
- Bhaskar, Amruta. “Role of Education in Women Empowerment.” *SkillRary*, 8 Mar. 2021, www.skillrary.com/blogs/read/role-of-education-in-women-empowerment. Accessed 18 Jan. 2023.
- Bhattacharya, Deya. “Portrayal of Violence Against Women in Literary Fiction.” *The Curious Reader*, 2018, www.thecuriousreader.in/features/violence-against-women. Accessed 12 Feb. 2023.

- Bishnoi, Promila. "Rural Indian Women Will Be Truly Empowered When They Get Equal Rights." *SheThePeople TV*, 2020, www.shethepeople.tv/top-stories/opinion/rural-indian-women-empowered-equal-rights-freedom. Accessed 13 Feb. 2023.
- Blackwell, Sara. "The Human Rights Opportunity." *Shift*, Aug. 2018, shiftproject.org/resource/the-human-rights-opportunity-in-collaboration-with-wbcsd/gender-equality. Accessed 15 Feb. 2023.
- Borkataki, Arindam. "Thirst for Identity." *Frontline*, 6 Sept. 2012, frontline.thehindu.com/other/article30167264.ece. Accessed 15 Feb. 2023.
- Capan, Zeynep Gulsah, et al. "The Politics of Translation in International Relations." *SpringerLink*, 10 Jan. 2021, link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-56886-3_1. Accessed 15 Jan. 2023.
- Chanda-Vaz, Urmi. "Reading List: India's Women Writers Who Have Been Smashing Patriarchy for Generations." *Scroll.in*, 1 Dec. 2018, scroll.in/article/904082/reading-list-indias-women-writers-who-have-been-smashing-patriarchy-for-generations. Accessed 9 Feb. 2023.
- Chandran, Mini. "The Practice of Translation in India." *Sahapedia*, 1 Nov. 2016, www.sahapedia.org/the-practice-of-translation-india. Accessed 22 Aug. 2023.
- Chastain, Ann. "Positive Thinking Makes a Difference." *MSU*, 24 Aug. 2012, www.canr.msu.edu/news/positive_thinking_makes_a_difference. Accessed 26 Sept. 2023.
- Chetty, Priya, and Subrata Das. "The Portrayal of Women and Feminism in Indian Literature." *Project Guru*, 21 July 2022, www.projectguru.in/the-portrayal-of-women-and-feminism-in-indian-literature. Accessed 16 Feb. 2023.

- Das, Samantak. "Book review: K.R. Meera borrows liberally from the mystique of the Dhananjay hanging in *Hangwoman*." *The Indian Express*, 6 October 2014, indianexpress.com/article/lifestyle/books/the-executioners-song/. Accessed 15 April 2019.
- Debnath, Sisir. "Understanding Family Structure and Women's Empowerment." *ISBInsight*, 24 Nov. 2016, isbinsight.isb.edu/understanding-family-structure-and-womens-empowerment-2. Accessed 9 Feb. 2023.
- Deodhar, Neerja. "Women Writers, Regional Literature and Translation: Notes From a Multilingual Poets' Meet." *Firstpost*, 30 Mar. 2018, www.firstpost.com/living/women-writers-regional-literature-and-translation-notes-from-a-multilingual-poets-meet-4410687.html. Accessed 4 Feb. 2023.
- Deshmukh, Vinita. "Is a Girl Child Really Welcome in an Indian Family?" *Moneylife*, 21 Nov. 2011, www.moneylife.in/article/is-a-girl-child-really-welcome-in-an-indian-family/21563.html. Accessed 28 Feb. 2023.
- Evans, Jonathan, et al. "How Indians View Gender Roles in Families and Society." *Pew Research Centre*, 2 Mar. 2022, www.pewresearch.org/religion/2022/03/02/how-indians-view-gender-roles-in-families-and-society. Accessed 18 Jan. 2023.
- Gupta, Kaushal. "Book Review: *The Fragrance of Rose* - Chirajit Paul." *Errors and Kaushal - a Blog by Kaushal Gupta*, 27 Aug. 2017, www.errorsandkaushal.com/2017/08/book-review-fragrance-of-rose-chirajit-paul.html. Accessed 10 Mar. 2023.
- Harsha. "Book Review: *Aarachar* by K R Meera." *the pensive soul*, 15 April 2015, thepensivesoul.wordpress.com/2015/04/15/book-review-aarachar-by-k-r-meera/. Accessed 15 April 2019.
- Hildreth, Cade. "A Scientist Explains Why Gender (and Sex) Aren't Binary." *Cade Hildreth*, 7 Feb. 2023, cadehildreth.com/gender-spectrum. Accessed 9 Sept. 2023.

- Iyer, Sriya, and Anand Shrivastava. "Religious Riots and Electoral Politics in India." *ECONSTOR*, Nov. 2015, www.econstor.eu/handle/10419/125042. Accessed 10 Oct. 2023.
- Johnson, Donald, and Jean Johnson. "Jati: The Caste System in India." *Asia Society*, asiasociety.org/education/jati-caste-system-india. Accessed 10 Feb. 2023.
- Joshi, Nishant. "Caste Oppression and Gender Security in India." *The Security Distillery*, October 27, 2020, thesecuritydistillery.org/all-articles/caste-oppression-and-gender-security-in-india. Accessed 11 Feb. 2023.
- Joshi, Umashankar. "Religion: Its Influence on Indian Literature." *Wisdom Library*, 17 Mar. 2022, www.wisdomlib.org/history/compilation/triveni-journal/d/doc70853.html. Accessed 27 Aug. 2023.
- Kasturi, Leela. "Development, Patriarchy, and Politics: Indian Women in the Political Process, 1947-1992." *core.ac.uk*, core.ac.uk/download/pdf/162461716.pdf. Accessed 11 Feb. 2023.
- Kazi, Seema. *Muslim Women in India*. An MRG National Report, 98/2, Minority Rights Group International, February 1999. minorityrights.org/wp-content/uploads/old-site-downloads/download-130-Muslim-Women-in-India.pdf. Accessed 05 Aug. 2023.
- Kothari, Rita. "Fence, Translated From Gujarati." *Academia.edu*, Feb. 2014, www.academia.edu/12270951/Fence_translated_from_Gujarati. Accessed 12 April 2019.
- Maaz, Sumaiya. "A Welcome Counter-Narrative to Problematic Constructions of Muslim Women's Identity." *The Wire*, thewire.in/books/book-review-gendering-minorities-muslim-women-identity-modernity. Accessed 5 Nov. 2023.

- Maheshwari, Tanisha. "Women's Property Rights- Hindu Succession Act." *Manupatra*, 2022, articles.manupatra.com/article-details/Women-s-Property-Rights-Hindu-Succession-Act. Accessed 13 Feb. 2023.
- Majlis, Legal Centre. *A Comprehensive Guide to Women's Legal Rights*. Majlis, 2018. IITK. www.iitk.ac.in/wc/data/Majlis_Legal-rights-of-women.pdf. Accessed 15 Jan. 2023.
- Mandal, Pooja. "Women Education in Rural India: Meaning, Need and Barriers." *Your Article Library*, 11 Apr. 2014, www.yourarticlelibrary.com/essay/women-education-in-rural-india-meaning-need-and-barriers/34972. Accessed 13 Feb. 2023.
- Mander, Manav. "Educate a Woman and You Educate a Family." *Tribuneindia News Service*, 8 Mar. 2020, www.tribuneindia.com/news/ludhiana/educate-a-woman-you-educate-a-family-52673. Accessed 18 Jan. 2023.
- Merelli, Annalisa. "Kali Is the 3,000-year-old Feminist Icon We Need Today." *Quartz*, 8 Jan. 2020, qz.com/1768545/hinduism-kali-is-the-feminist-icon-the-world-desperately-needs. Accessed 23 Feb. 2023.
- Mohanta, Subhasnata. "Why Is Translation Important for Indian Literature?" *Adamas University*, 1 July 2022, adamasuniversity.ac.in/why-is-translation-important-for-indian-literature. Accessed 15 Jan. 2023.
- Mukhopadhyay, Pallav. "Problem of Gender Inequality and Expansion of Education of Women in West Bengal." *Indian Stastical Institute*, www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=2ahUKEwjvseqGr8uCAxWCR2wGHew5CgkQFnoECCsQAQ&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.isical.ac.in%2F~wemp%2FPapers%2FPaperPallavMukhopadhyay.doc&usg=AOvVaw39-C1s6Fjqpa_cxYSwwYVW&opi=89978449. Accessed 15 Feb. 2023.

- Nath, Dipti. "Gender and Religion." *eGyanKosh*, 2018, egyankosh.ac.in/bitstream/123456789/4474/1/MWG-006-B2-U5.pdf. Accessed 18 Jan. 2023.
- Pal, Poulomi. "Book Review *Fence: A Story of 'Us and Them' and Our Pieces of Sky.*" *Feminism in India*, 28 July 2016, feminisminindia.com/2016/07/29/fence-book-review. Accessed 12 April 2019.
- Pardeshi, Pratima. "Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar and the Question Of Women's Liberation In India – III." *The Leaflet*, 2022, theleaflet.in/dr-babasaheb-ambedkar-and-the-question-of-womens-liberation-in-india-iii. Accessed 11 Feb. 2023.
- Pathak, Nilima. "Sivakami, First Dalit Woman to Become a Novelist." *India – Gulf News*, 26 Aug. 2012, gulfnews.com/world/asia/india/sivakami-first-dalit-woman-to-become-a-novelist-1.1066120. Accessed 11 Jan. 2022.
- Pillai, Akshaya. "K. R. Meera: 'I Don't Write for Feminists. I Write so That My Book Will Convert Readers Into Feminists.'" *Vogue India*, 4 Sept. 2022, www.vogue.in/culture-and-living/content/writer-k-r-meera-i-dont-write-for-feminists-i-write-so-that-my-book-will-convert-readers-into-feminists-jezebel. Accessed 21 Mar. 2023.
- Prakash, Priya. "5 Indian Women Speak About Being the Only Girl Child in the Family." *SheThePeople*, 11 Oct. 2022, www.shethepeople.tv/top-stories/opinion/international-day-of-the-girl-child-2022-only-girl-child. Accessed 13 Feb. 2023.
- Radhakrishnan, Athira. "Countering Power: The Politics of Realignment in *The Hangwoman.*" *Ecologies of the New: Matter, Mind and Body*, edited by P. K. Bahu and others, MES Mampad College, Mampad, 2018, pp. 7–12. meskeveeyamcollege.ac.in/SSR-Documents/Criteria3/3.3.5/65%20Athira.PDF. Accessed 15 Jan. 2023.

- Rahman, Abdur. "Women in the Quran and the Sunnah." *IIUM*, www.iium.edu.my/deed/articles/woman_quran.html#:~:text=In%20Islam%20a%20woman%20is,liberty%20to%20choose%20her%20husband. Accessed 4 Nov. 2023.
- Raj, Kaushik, and Sabah Gurmat. "Since Ram Navami Violence, Gujarat's Muslim Women Wage a Silent Battle, Allege State Bias." *A14*, 14 June 2022, [article-14.com/post/since-ram-navami-violence-gujarat-s-muslim-women-wage-a-silent-battle-allege-state-bias--62a7f004a343b](https://www.a14.com/post/since-ram-navami-violence-gujarat-s-muslim-women-wage-a-silent-battle-allege-state-bias--62a7f004a343b). Accessed 11 Feb. 2023.
- Rao, Anupama, editor. *Gender and Caste*. New Delhi: Kali for Women, 2003, p. 27, cscs.res.in/dataarchive/textfiles/textfile.2010-03-11.8248362078/file. Accessed 13 Feb. 2023.
- Rao, Shruti. "Hangwoman [Book Review]." *Womensweb.in*, 28 August 2014, www.womensweb.in/2014/08/hangwoman-k-r-meera/. Accessed 14 April 2019.
- Renukamba, Sandhya. "Book Review of P. Sivakami's *The Taming of Women*." *Women's Web: For Women Who Do*, 18 Oct. 2012, www.womensweb.in/articles/the-taming-of-women. Accessed 11 Jan. 2022.
- Roy, Nilanjana S. "Translations: Ila Arab Mehta, Ismat Chughtai, Arupa Patangia Kalita." *Otter of Books*, 14 Oct. 2015, nilanjanaroy.com/2015/10/14/translations-ila-arab-mehta-ismat-chughtai-arupa-patangia-kalita. Accessed 15 Jan. 2023.
- Saldanha, Virginia. "The Power of Religion Over Women in India." *Global Sisters Report*, 10 Nov. 2016, www.globalsistersreport.org/column/equality/power-religion-over-women-india-43236. Accessed 8 Feb. 2023.
- Salim, Mariya. "Safia Niaz and Zakia Soman: Bonded to Change the Trajectory of Muslim Women in India." *Global Issues*, 10 Dec. 2021, www.globalissues.org/news/2021/12/10/29568. Accessed 28 Oct. 2023.

- Sebastian, Shevlin. "And Thereby Hangs a Tale..." *The New Indian Express*, 30 Aug. 2014, www.newindianexpress.com/lifestyle/books/2014/aug/30/And-Thereby-Hangs-a-Tale-654309.html. Accessed 26 Sept. 2023.
- Sen, Swagata. "Objectification of Women by Media." *Rights of Equality - Promoting Gender Equality and Women Empowerment*, 30 June 2019, www.rightsofequality.com/objectification-and-exploitation-of-girls-and-women-by-the-mass-media-and-the-social-media. Accessed 18 Jan. 2023.
- Shalini. "The Grip of Change; and Author's Notes." *Aswamegh.net*, 2015-18, ashvamegh.net/book-reviews/the-grip-of-change/. Accessed 12 April 2019.
- Sharma, Ashutosh Dayal. "Education Empowering Women in Rural Areas." *BW Education*, 7 Sept. 2018, bweducation.businessworld.in/article/Education-Empowering-Women-In-Rural-Areas/07-09-2018-159510. Accessed 18 Jan. 2023.
- Sharma, Smriti. "Achieving Gender Equality in India: What Works, and What Doesn't." *United Nations University*, 1 Dec. 2016, unu.edu/publications/articles/achieving-gender-equality-in-india-what-works-and-what-doesnt.html. Accessed 16 Feb. 2023.
- Shetty, Sowjanya S., and V. Basil Hans. "Role of Education in Women Empowerment and Development: Issues and Impact." *SSRN*, 27 Sept. 2015, papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2665898. Accessed 18 Jan. 2023.
- Shibulal, K. "Empowerment of Women Through Education: A Critical Examination." *Times of India Blog*, 17 Apr. 2021, timesofindia.indiatimes.com/readersblog/shibulal-family-philanthropic-initiatives/empowerment-of-women-through-education-a-critical-examination-31111. Accessed 18 Jan. 2023.
- Shree, Geetanjali. "From the Polyphonic World of Hindi Fiction." *The Caravan*, 01 February 2011, caravanmagazine.in/reviews-essays/polyphonic-world-hindi-fiction. Accessed 12 April 2019.

Shree, Geetanjali, and Daisy Rockwell. "Geetanjali Shree and Daisy Rockwell on Translation." *The New York Times*, www.nytimes.com/2023/06/18/special-series/booker-prize-translation-conversation.html. Accessed 19 Sept. 2023.

Sinha, Arunava. "Translations | *The Music of Solitude* and *The Roof Beneath Their Feet*." *Mint*, 29 Nov. 2013, www.livemint.com/Leisure/Z5rgi16rvms5g6M6nwRpXP/Translations--The-Music-of-Solitude--The-Roof-Beneath-Thei.html. Accessed 16 Feb. 2023.

---. "Why Aren't Translations the Big Story of Indian Publishing?" *Scroll.in*, 3 Jan. 2015, scroll.in/article/698475/why-arent-translations-the-big-story-of-indian-publishing. Accessed 12 April 2023.

Soukai, Sandrine. "The Dissenting Voices of Dalit Women Writers: Breaking Away From Narratives of Victimhood." *Archipelies*, 15 Dec. 2020, www.archipelies.org/839. Accessed 27 Jul. 2023.

Spivak, Gayatri Chakravorty. "The Politics of Translation." *Outside in the Teaching Machine*, edited by Pares Chandra Chakravorty, Routledge New York, 1993, pp. 179-200. *Internet Archive*, archive.org/details/outsideinteachin0000spiv. Accessed 28 Feb. 2023.

Sriram, Abhirami. "Abhirami Sriram Reviews Hangwoman: Everybody loves a good hanging by K. R. Meera." *India Today*, 11 Aug. 2014, www.indiatoday.in/magazine/books/story/20140811-abhirami-sriram-kr-meera-hangwoman-review-phanibhushan-mullick-804801-2014-08-01. Accessed 18 Jan. 2023.

Stenza. "Politics of Translation." *Stenza*, 26 Jan. 2014, augustinestenza.wordpress.com/2014/01/26/politics-of-translation. Accessed 15 Jan. 2023.

Sudhagee. "Book Review: *Fence*." *My Favourite Things*, 28 Dec. 2016, sudhagee.com/2016/12/28/book-review-fence. Accessed 12 April 2019.

Sultana, Parvin. "Writing Conflict, Writing Gender: Looking at Two Assamese Novels." *Café Dissensus*, 14 June 2017, cafedissensus.com/2017/06/14/writing-conflict-writing-gender-looking-at-two-assamese-novels. Accessed 11 Jan. 2022.

Thayat, Malavika, and Shilpa S. Nair. "Exploration of Immense Courage and Strength through Chetana: A Feministic Approach to *Hangwoman: Everyone Loves a Good Hanging*." *Ashvamegh*, ashvamegh.net/a-feministic-approach-to-hangwoman-by-k-r-meera/. Accessed 14 Jan. 2023.

Thompson, Karl. "Sylvia Walby: Six Structures of Patriarchy." *ReviseSociology*, 10 Jan. 2017, revisesociology.com/2017/01/10/patriarchy-structure-walby-sylvia. Accessed 18 Jan. 2023.

Trivedi, Harish. "The Success of Translations Has Bridged the Gap Between Writing in Indian Regional Languages and Indian Writing in English." *The Indian Express*, 2 Jan. 2023, indianexpress.com/article/opinion/columns/translation-success-indian-regional-language-english-writing-8355560. Accessed 15 Jan. 2023.

Varghese, Alice. "The Lack of Higher Education of Girls in Rural India." *CUNY Peer Leaders*, 9 Apr. 2021, cunypeerleaders.commons.gc.cuny.edu/2021/04/09/the-lack-of-higher-education-of-girls-in-rural-india. Accessed 13 Feb. 2023.

Wallstrom, Margot. "Culture Is Not an Excuse for Oppressing Women." *the Economist*, www.economist.com/open-future/2018/06/25/culture-is-not-an-excuse-for-oppressing-women. Accessed 12 Mar. 2023.

Warrier, Shobha. "'Has Reservation Served Its Purpose?'" *Rediff*, 23 Dec. 2015, www.rediff.com/news/interview/has-reservation-served-its-purpose/20151223.htm. Accessed 13 Feb. 2023.

Wessler, Heinz-Werner. "Hinduism and Modern Literature." *DiVA*, pp. 659-668, <http://uu.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:381399/FULLTEXT02.pdf>. Accessed 18 Jan. 2023.

White, David. "Reverse Discrimination: Definition, Examples and Cases." *Study.com*, 14 Oct. 2021, study.com/academy/lesson/reverse-discrimination-definition-examples-cases.html. Accessed 18 Jan. 2023.

* MLA 9th Edition has been followed for purpose of the in-text citations and bibliography.

THE PORTRAYAL OF WOMEN BY WOMEN IN INDIAN LITERATURE IN ENGLISH TRANSLATION

Munish Kumar Thakur

PhD Research Scholar, Department of English, Himachal Pradesh University, Shimla (HP).

Abstract:

The true picture of discrimination and marginalization of women in patriarchal societies is depicted mostly by women writers only. As only a woman can understand the real agony faced by women. The patriarchal culture has imposed a feminine identity upon women and accordingly they have to be always submissive to men and have no independent identity of their own. Those restrictions are adverse in the interior parts of India where every single woman has to struggle for the right to education, freedom, and most of all to lead an independent life. The experiences of the women residing in the interior parts of India are much pathetic as compared to the women living in cities. This paper aims at highlighting the adversities faced by the women living in the villages and especially in the economically weaker sections of the societies as depicted by some renowned regional women writers. The role of a good translation is also vital to highlight some extraordinary works written by regional writers in their language. Without translation, such works would have remained confined only to that particular region.

Keywords: Gender equality, Women struggle, Translation, Regional writings, Women writers.

Introduction:

Literature has always been a mirror to society. It always depicts the social norms, cultures and deformities prevailing in the society. Most of the male writers have always depicted women as soft, delicate creatures for the entertainment of men and to be always kept under the control of men. Since the Victorian period, women are associated with household works only. Females could not participate, litigate, or possess estate during the period portrayed by British monarch Queen Victoria's reign. Feminist ideas were popular among learned middle classes, discriminatory policies were repealed, and the female's campaign for voting rights in national elections reached its pinnacle in the Victorian age's last years. "My dear boy, no woman is a genius," Oscar Wilde wrote in *The Picture of Dorian Gray*. He further adds:

Females are sex that is used for decoration. They don't have much to express, yet when they do, they express it in a beautiful manner. Men symbolise the victory of intellect over morality, while females symbolize the victory of substance over intellect. (Riquelme, 2000, pp. 609 – 631)

The societal stereotypes, as represented by various male writers, required women to keep their homes clean for their husbands, put food on the table, or nourish their kids. The women are always placed at the fringes in their respective regions as the centre is occupied by the patriarchal customs and traditions in which only the males have the right to make a decision or have a say about every aspect of life and women have no involvement in it. Therefore, they are always been treated as inferior to men.

Women's struggle against the patriarchal system started in the form of 'Feminism.' For many ages, women are fought against the biased system for equality yet the women residing in most of the interior parts of the world are still facing extreme subjugation. The adversities faced by the women living in the regional parts of India is also not revealed to the world as issues raised by the writers are mostly writing in their own regional languages. Therefore, the role of translation to highlight the literary pieces written by the regional writers to the world is very vital. In the countries like India where a large number of multilingual and multicultural people are residing, the value of translation increases more. One should always keep in mind that translation is not a school exercise or an intermediate one but a literary and cultural activity that may affect the culture of any multilingual/multicultural society. Therefore, translation is the rewriting of an original text in such a manner that it should produce the same effect in the reader's mind as does the original one.

This paper primarily focuses on the struggle of women living in the interior parts of India as depicted by various women writers in their local languages. Following is a brief introduction of the novelists and their works. Palanimuthu Shivakami (born in 1957) is one of the most prominent figures in Dalit literature who writes in Tamil. *The Taming of Women*, the second novel of P. Shivakami taken up for closer scrutiny is named after the main protagonist in Kannada. Geentajali Shree (born in 1957) is the second novelist taken up for closer study. She is a Hindi writer who resides in New Delhi and is the author of three novels and a few short stories. Her novel *Mai* was shortlisted for 2001 Crossword Book Award. Her third novel which

is chosen for study is *Roof Beneath Their Feet* (2002) which is translated into English by Rahul Soni in 2013. Geetanjali Shree's main protagonist Chachcho struggles against social stigmas and suffering from loneliness in the company of a frigid husband.

The third, Arupa Patangia Kalita (born in 1956) is a popular Assamese novelist and an English literature teacher who lives in Darrang, Assam. Her novel *Felanee* was originally written in 2003 and translated by Deepika Pukan in 2011. The story of *Felanee* reveals the awful experiences of a woman, Felanee amid ethnic riots and a frenzied atmosphere in Assam. The fourth, Ila Arab Mehta (born in 1938), is a Gujarati writer born in Mumbai. She has written several novels. Her novel *Vaad* (2011) is translated into English as *Fence* (2015) by Rita Kothari. *Vaad* is the story of a female protagonist, Fateema, who has to face many struggles in her life to live independently and own a house for herself. She struggled with different barriers such as illiteracy, gender, religion and poverty to succeed in her life. She breaks the stereotypes and carves her own identity in the male-dominated society.

Lastly, K. R. Meera (born in 1970) is a well-known feminist and Malayalam writer. She has written five novels, two novellas and about five short-story collections. Her novel *Aarachaar* (2012) is widely regarded as one of the best literary works produced in the Malayalam language. The novel is translated into English by J Devika as *Hangwoman: Everyone Loves a Good Hanging* (2014). It is the story of Chetna, who belongs to a family of executioners in Bengal. It shows the struggles of Chetna while inheriting the position of an executioner. It is also a story of sheer power and defiance of a woman in a man's world.

Women are always being presented as marginalized and victimized at the hand of the patriarchal system. It is not just the female authors but also some of the prominent male writers who have also highlighted the discrimination that every woman has to face in the interior parts of India. Women living in villages and other interior regions have to face much more than the ones residing in cities. Anandhayi has to face a lot of discrimination at the hands of her husband as depicted by Palanimuthu Shivakami in her novel *The Taming of Women*. Periyannan was treating her like an animal to use for sexual pleasure whenever he likes and she has no right to say in any decision which he makes. He can abuse her for anything and even beat her brutally if he feels that she is not obeying his decisions. Sometimes when her mother-in-law tries to take her side even she has to face his egoistic behaviour. He is hungry for the power that money can bring, and tyrannical in his treatment of the women in his life – be it his wife, his old and ailing mother, his daughters or the many women for whom he has an insatiable appetite. Periyannan is the king of all he surveys until he encounters and is enslaved by the beauty of Lakshmi, whom he gets home as his second wife. After a while though, he slips back into his despotic ways and Lakshmi tries to run away and escape his clutches. This does not sit well with Periyannan, who sees it as a blow to his egotism. Therefore, he puts everything at stake in his attempts to gain control over Lakshmi.

Chetna, the main protagonist of KR Meera's *Hangwoman*, has to face a similar sort of discrimination firstly from her father who always wants her to do everything as he dictates and then later by her love interest who wants her absolutely under his control. Being patriarchal mindsets both men treats her as weak sex and believes that she won't be able to perform the task of executing the next official hanging without their active support. As Chetna bitterly observes, "Everyone demanded worship. Not one could prove he deserved it" (Meera, 2014, Chapter 5, para. 28). Meera shows the struggles of Chetna while inheriting the position of an executioner. The next is Fateema, the main female protagonist of Arupa Pathangia Kalita's novel *Vaad*, who has to struggle a lot to fulfil her dream of having an independent house of her own. After completing her education with a lot of struggle she has managed to get a job and was planning to buy a house of her own. But she was facing a lot of difficulties to buy one for herself because of only one reason that she is a single woman. "But how can we allow a flat to a single woman? There's no provision in the society rules" (Mehta, 2011/2015, p. 222). Therefore, a single woman is always been observed with suspicion in the male-dominated society as the patriarchal minds are unable to digest the chastity of a single woman who is staying alone. Such was the gender-based inequalities that Fateema has to face while fulfilling her dream.

Arupa Pathangia Kalita has also depicted a lot of discrimination and marginalization of women in her novel *Felanee*. The main protagonist has to face a lot of problems amidst the ethnic conflicts and violence. Rioters always choose women as an easy target to take revenge upon the other group and the innocent women from both sides have to suffer due to that. *Felanee* depicts such pathetic experiences of discrimination based on gender prevailing in Indian societies. Geetanjali Shree's main protagonist Chachcho struggles against social stigmas and suffering from loneliness in the company of a frigid husband. Chachcho finds Lalna who has been left by her husband. She has a good relationship with her and was able to get out of her lonely world. In Lalna's company, she confronts traditional society. Shree has shown in her novel that how discrimination is done based on gender in societies where women are just seen as objects for the use of men and nothing else. They do not have

any independent identity of their own, they are not allowed to lead a life in which they feel comfortable and happy.

Women of the lower strata of the society have to face more discrimination based on their lower class and cast in the interior parts of the Indian societies. People of the upper class whether a man or woman also exploits the women of the lower class and cast. The women of lower class or cast get discriminated by even the women of the upper class as seen in the case of Fateema, in Ila Arab Mehta's *Fence*, who was always treated inferiorly by her school friend Chandan's family. On one occasion Chandan's mother insulted Fateema by saying, "What will people like you do with education, hanh? Your father will get you married one of these days to a hawker" (Mehta, 2011/2015, p. 20). Once their teacher told them not to eat from one another's lunch box as they belong to different casts/religions by saying, "Chandan check caste and culture first before you.... This Fateema is... never mind. Just be careful from now one" (Mehta, 2011/2015, p. 17). Therefore the women belonging to the lower cast or class of the society have to face multilevel discrimination for being a woman and then for being poor or from a lower class by birth. These women do not even have the power of money to be self-dependant as the women from the upper class can be. A similar difference as we can observe in Geetanjali Shree's *The Roof Beneath Their Feet* where Chachcho was economically strong but Lalna for being from lower class and cast has to face discrimination from everyone in the society. Even sometimes Lalna's character was also questioned many times as, "In Laburnum House, rose a rumour that Lalna had been seen on the roof sneaking up to meet a man! Each time a new lover" (Shree 2001/2013, p. 37) and she was labelled as "a woman with an unspoken but sullied past" (Shree 2001/2013, p. 39).

Likewise, Anandhayi and Luxmi have to suffer at the hands of Periyannan because of poverty and being dependant on him for the money in P. Shivakam's *The Taming of Women*. Periyannan beats them whenever he likes and wants to have them under his full control and do whatever he wants them to do. So because of their helpless of being dependent on him for money they have to bear his brutal animal-like ways. Arupa Pathangia Kalita has also depicted the double discrimination faced by the women belonging to the lower cast and class of the society in her novel *Felanee*. "What awful anguish these women have had to go through!" (Kalita 2011, Chapter 12, para. 18).

Conclusion

Literature has always been a mirror to everything which happens in societies. Many writers have depicted the deformities prevailing in the system which encourages men to discriminate against women. Women are the ones who can truly represent the agony and helplessness of any other woman truly and effectively as every woman must have faced similar sort of experiences in the societies which are dominated by patriarchal customs and especially the interior parts of our country. Therefore, it won't be wrong to say by analysing the experiences faced by many women in the various novels as depicted by women writers. The women residing in the interior regions of India are still facing discrimination despite a lot has been done to empower them. All those efforts will go in vain if we as individuals don't let them implement practically in our societies. Women are half of the population of any part of our country so if we want to develop as a nation then we must give equal chances to all the women of our nation for their empowerment. The role of a good translation is also very much appreciable in this regard because it is only due to translation that the experiences of the women residing in the interior parts of our country can be brought up at the global level.

References

- Riquelme, J. P. (2000). "Oscar Wilde's Aesthetic Gothic: Walter Pater, Dark Enlightenment, and The Picture of Dorian Gray." *MFS Modern Fiction Studies* 46, 609 – 631.
- Meera, K. R. (2014). *Hangwoman: Everyone Loves A Good Hanging* (J. Devika, Trans.). Penguin. (Original work published 2012)
- Sivakami, Palanimuthu. (2014). *The Taming of Women* (Pritham K Chakravarthy, Trans.). Penguin. (Original work published 2012)
- Shree, Geetanjali. (2013). *The Roof Beneath Their Feet* (Rahul Soni, Trans.). Harper Perennial. (Original work published 2001)
- Kalita, Arupa Pathangia. (2011). *Felanee* (Deepika Phukan, Trans.). Zubaan. (Original work published 2003)
- Mehta, Ila Arab. (2015). *Fence* (Rita Kothari, Trans.). Zubaan. (Original work published 2011)

WOMEN SUFFERING WITH IDENTITY CRISIS IN THE ROOF BENEATH THEIR FEET BY SHREE

Munish Kumar Thakur, Assistant Professor of English, IEC University, Himachal Pradesh, India

Sanjay K Gupta, Principal, RLSG Sainik School, Nalagarh, Himachal Pradesh, India

Abstract

In the modern world of technology, the identity of every individual is at risk due to the global intermixing of cultures and borders. In Indian literature, many writers have expressed their concerns over identity crisis, especially in fictional works. Women in any Indian family are always treated secondary as compared to men who enjoy the primary position as per the patriarchal customs. Therefore, women are discriminated against and treated as unimportant in the decision making related to family issues. Due to such treatment of women, in many families especially in the rural parts of India, their identity as an individual is always at stake. Geetanjali Shree, one of the renowned novelists who write in the Hindi language, is one of the exponents of the issues of identity crisis through her shortstories and novels. Her novel *Mai* (originally written in Hindi in 2004), which was later translated into English by Rahul Soni entitled *The Roof Beneath Their Feet*, depicts the story of the main protagonist Chacho who was feeling lonely and suffering from an identity crisis. This paper aims to explore the agony and desires of a woman's lonely heart who has just lost her identity in the patriarchal thinking of society.

Keywords: Women, Identity Crisis, Geetanjali Shree, Chacho.

Introduction

Loss of identity has become quite a point of concern in the modern times when there is no personal space left and all boundaries have been dismantled by the technology. The individual and specific cultural traits are at a great risk due to intermixing of culture and space. Therefore, individual identities are at great risk as there is no specificity of any tribe or society left due to interconnecting space created by the great advancement in technology. The pace of life has also increased a lot which has created a huge amount of pressure on every individual. The competition for success among people has mounted a great pressure on the minds of every human being. This pressure has also contributed adversely to affect the identity crisis in the individuals at the different sections of our society. Due to the competition in every sector, individuals are put under a lot of pressure by their own family and the society around them to do better as a successful person. Everyone wants success in their lives which creates a huge amount of mental burden on human generations from their childhood itself. As every individual is expected to do well in their lives because every day they will be judged for what they have achieved in their life so far. From childhood itself, we start putting pressure on kids to become this or that when they will reach the age of an adolescent. "Personal psychosocial conflict especially in adolescence that involves confusion about one's social role and often a sense of loss of continuity to one's personality" (Merriam-Webster, n.d.). So this demand from the family and society has created a disturbance in the minds of every individual to how to deal with this situation and they got stuck in much of dilemma to choose a path for success in their lives. As to quote an article, "a key aspect of this adolescent dilemma is that of finding a role, which is generally taken to be the outward expression of identity. The emotional upheaval provoked by this mandate is called the identity crisis" (Britannica, n.d.).

As Erikson who coined this term describes it as, "the uncertainty, and even anxiety, that adolescents may feel as they recognize that they are no longer children and become puzzled and confused about their present and future roles in life" (Psychology, 2016). As per Erikson's views, it is really crucial to be aware deeply about most of these concerns and, in the end, to reach a reasonable degree of clarity such that the course you take as an adult seems to be one you've intentionally decided. Vigorous identity evolves from not only the deliberate reflection of one's mission in life, but rather from effectively overcoming the behavioral issues that marked your earlier formative years. Erikson coined the term "identity accomplishment" to describe this psyche (Whitbourne, 2010). Women are always being treated as inferior to men in every sphere of life. They are always treated as weaker individual as compared to men, therefore, their opinions are always less valued as that of

men. From the childhood itself, women are expected to behave as per the patriarchal customs. They are always forced to behave in feminine way and if they do something which are not allowed for a girl then they have to face the wrath of the patriarchal elders of their family. Due to this imposed patriarchal identity upon women by the society, they sometimes suffer from identity crisis as they unable to behave in the manner they like to. The freedom of choice to do this or that is always provided to men in the patriarchal customs whereas women are expected to be quiet and behave as the customary norms.

This article tries to focus on the similar issues faced by women characters in the novel entitled *The Roof Beneath Their Feet* by Geetanjali Shree. The central character, Chacho, is suffering with the problem of identity crisis in this novel. She has been married to a person who mainly focuses on earning more and more money and is totally unaware of the feeling of alienation with which Chacho was struggling with. She was carving for some sort of companion in her mundane and lonely life till Lalna came to live with them. Chacho made a good friendship with Lalna and ultimately in the company of Lalna she was feeling satisfied. Chacho's husband provides her every material thing available in the world for a woman but he was unable to give her what she was always craving for i.e. his time. Chacho could not become mother due to some medical reasons, therefore, she herself brought in Lalna in her house to have a child through her. With the passage of time, their friendship and bonding becomes so strong that they started to spend a lot of time in the company of each other on the roof of their house which was a common roof of many neighboring houses. This paper will try to explore how the friendship of two women was being seen with indifferent eyes by the people of the society. Further, the present article tries to focus of the identity crisis through which Chacho has to gone through in her life and ultimately she dies a premature death due to the same.

Short-lived Friendship of Chachcho and Lalna

There was no purpose left for poor Chachcho to live with her husband. He has provided her with every material thing possible to have for a woman in which Chacho has no interest at all. Her husband could never be able to understand what she wants. She always remains in the house in "Just the room where poor Chachcho slept alone" (Shree 2001/2013, p. 5). Poor Chachcho could not become a mother that is why she herself has to brought in Lalna for having a child for her husband. Although the whole society sees Lalna as a woman of bad character but Chachcho is of the view that her past is due to the ill treatment she had received in her life. She had to left her house because her husband "Lallan was dead and that Lallan's father had tried to force her into prostitution, which was why she ran away" (Shree 2001/2013, p. 7).

Chachcho was living a life of utterly loneliness before Lalna came in her life. After the arrival of Lalna, Chachcho has at least got a reason to live and smile. It was Lalna who gave her the most loveable person in her life i.e. Bitwa, a son. Chachcho was very happy and she really got a reason a live in the company of Lalna and Bitwa. The friendship she was sharing with Lalna has given her the happiness for which her heart was craving for the entire life so far. Now she got someone with whom she can share her feelings and desire of her heart. Lalna was also very happy with having Chachcho as a companion or friend in her life which was earlier full of problems and defame. In Lalna's company "Chachcho's heart started beating madly. Frightened by how her mind and body had started dancing" (Shree 2001/2013, p. 24).

The novel reveals the story of the life of poor Chachcho who has to suffer a lot in her life. She was being imposed with the patriarchal customs by her husband and the society in which she lives. Chachcho has no individual identity of her own. She has to do whatever her husband wants her to, she has to live as he chooses for her. After the friendship with Lalna, Chachcho started to follow her heart and even sometimes "Uncle could never understand. Why the quiet Chachcho, the Chachcho who would shrivel up if he so much as gave her a stern look, would sometimes suddenly sit up" (Shree 2001/2013, p. 11). The story of Chachcho was recalled by Lalna and Bitwa after her death when Lalna left them few years after the birth of Bitwa.

Identity Crisis in the life of Chachcho

Chachcho was always forced to lead a life of a typically ideal woman as per the patriarchal ideology. She was being conditioned from her childhood itself to behave in such a manner which is acceptable as per the patriarchal norms. Throughout her life she has followed this way of living without any question even after her marriage. But as shown through her friendship with Lalna that inside her heart she was always carved for doing the wild things because at her heart she always desired to be

such a person who loved to lead a life of own choice. Despite having the wild desires in her heart of leading a life of her own choice, she was being forced to lead a life as stated by the patriarchal culture. Therefore, this dilemma of leading a wild life and to follow the customs imposed upon her by the society she suffered through the problem of identity crisis. She always has to suppress her desires to respect the customs. “A bit of lost, looking absently outside, her languid eyes searching not for the road to Laburnum House, but for some imaginary one” (Shree 2001/2013, p. 19). Shree further expresses about Chachcho’s desires when she sees Lalna in the beginning when she came there in her neighbourhood, “She started waiting for the girl as if to see how far her own courage would take her – the proof of that courage being the girl who had become her mirror” (Shree 2001/2013, p. 23).

Chachcho started to listen to the hidden desired of her heart and started to live wildly as she always desired to in the company of Lalna who had always live as per her likings without being bothered about what other people may think of her. Therefore, when Lalna came in Chachcho’s life she realized the suppressed desires of her own heart which she has always ignored for the sake of others while following the patriarchal customs. She has always remained as an ideal woman and wife by doing what is being expected from her before and after Lalna was there in her life. It was only in the company of Lalna, Chachcho lived as she always wished to by following the wild feelings of her heart for which she was always carving for throughout her life. “There’s excitement in the air... Whoosh goes the rope through the air... Whoosh we jump... Whoosh our roof!” (Shree 2001/2013, p. 119). It was only Lalna who understood the hidden feelings of Chachcho and she with her ways let her live happily by following her inner desires in her company. As Shree narrates the words of Lalna, “I’m the one who knows Behen-ji, not you! What place do you have in our friendship?” (Shree 2001/2013, p. 118).

Conclusion

Identity Crisis has become a point of serious concern in the present day world as most of the cultures are being intermixed due to the advancement in technology. There is not much privacy left of any individual where he can meditate in aloofness. Every individual is always at the verge of losing their personal or self-identity as all the cultural boundaries have been intermixed. Due to this the individuals remain confused about the way to lead their life as they are always coming under the influence of other cultural norms which may be unacceptable at the place one lives. So this creates a dilemma in the person’s life as Babran (2008) points out, “For a given individual . . . there may be plurality of identities, but these are a source of stress and contradiction in both self-representation and social action.” For women this crisis has become more problematic as they are always expected to behave as per the patriarchal cultural attributes assigned to a woman whether they like it or not. This creates a situation of confusion in the mind of individual with a question to how to react to such societal constraints and create a balance with their own liking and disliking.

In *The Roof Beneath Their Feet*, Chachcho specially has to undergo this trauma of going for her own likings or to behave in a manner which is always demanded from a good woman under the patriarchal customs. Therefore, she has gone through identity crisis which ultimately resulted in her loss of interest in life and she dies due to the meaninglessness of her life. Parenting is also the main point in avoiding this identity crisis in the minds of children as the crisis always results due to the too much expectation from the child to do something in his/her life for which the child may not be capable of. So this burdens the mind of the child with the expectations from the parents, from the family, and the inner desires of the child as per his own interest in life. Therefore, we must always let the children to take their own decisions by telling them what is right and what is not to save the future generations from this dilemma in order to create their own individual identity as per their capabilities.

References

- Britannica, T. Editors of Encyclopaedia (Invalid Date). biological psychology. Encyclopedia Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/science/biological-psychology>
- Merriam-Webster. (n.d.). Identity crisis definition & meaning. Merriam-Webster. Retrieved January 20, 2022, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/identity%20crisis>
- Identity crisis - iresearchnet. Psychology. (2016, January 25). Retrieved January 20, 2022, from <http://psychology.iresearchnet.com/social-psychology/self/identity-crisis/>

Whitbourne, S.K. (2010). *The search for fulfillment*. New York: Ballantine Books

Shree, Geetanjali. (2013). *The Roof Beneath Their Feet* (Rahul Soni, Trans.). Harper Perennial.
(Original work published 2001)

Babran, S. (2008). *Media, Globalization of Culture, and Identity Crisis in Developing Countries*.
Retrieved January 20, 2022, from <https://www-s3-live.kent.edu/s3fs-root/s3fs-public/file/18-Sedigheh-Babran.pdf>

**CHANDIGARH
UNIVERSITY**
Discover. Learn. Empower.

**NAAC
GRADE A+**
ACCREDITED UNIVERSITY

GURU NANAK CHAIR FOR STUDIES IN UNIVERSAL ADVANCEMENT

National Conference

On

SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY: GENDER EQUALITY & WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

Certificate of Participation

This is to certify that Dr./Mr./Ms. Munish Kumar Thakur

from HPU Shimla.

has successfully presented a Paper titled

Chetna Breaking the Patriarchal Myth in K R Meera s Hangwoman

in National Conference on “**Sustainable Society: Gender Equality & Women Empowerment**” under Guru Nanak Chair

For Studies in Universal Advancement organized by Women Cell in collaboration with

University Institute of Teachers Training and Research, Chandigarh University on **19 October 2021.**

Prof.(Dr.) R.S.Bawa
Pro Chancellor

Prof.(Dr.) Mohammad Firoz
ED (Liberal Arts)

Prof. (Dr.) Inderpreet Kaur
Conference Convener

**UGC Sponsored
(Under Autonomy Grant of BSSS)**

ज्ञान-विज्ञान विभुक्तये

University Grants Commission

**Two-Day Virtual International
Conference in English**

on 29 -30 September, 2021

Jointly organized by

The Departments of English, Bhopal School of Social Sciences (BSSS), MP

and

Christ College (Autonomous) Irinjalakuda, Kerala

MUNISH KUMAR THAKUR

presented a paper titled

**A Single Woman's Struggle for Identity against Patriarchy
in Illa Arab Mehta's Fence**

in the UGC Sponsored (Under Autonomy Grant of BSSS) two-day
Virtual International Conference on "Contemporary Trends in World Literatures,
Language and Cultural Studies in English", jointly organised by
the Departments of English, Bhopal School of Social Sciences (BSSS)
and Christ College (Autonomous) Irinjalakuda, Kerala on 29 -30 September, 2021.

Rev. Dr. Jolly Andrews CMI
Principal, Christ College

Dr K J Vargheese
Asso. Professor, Christ College
Convener

Rev Dr John P J
Principal, BSSS

Dr Shibani Basu Dubey
Asso. Professor & HOD, BSSS
Convener